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International Conference on Recent Advances in Communication, VLSI & Embedded Systems

ICRACVES- - 2014

About Conference

The aim of the conference is bring to together Scientists, researchers, educationists and developers to share new ideas and establish cooperation between them and provide a platform for presenting their original work and exchange ideas, information techniques and applications in the field of communication, VLSI & Embedded systems. Participants are encourages to present papers on all topics of listed in the call for papers, which enable inter disciplinary discussion on new ideas, latest research and development.

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INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON
"RECENT ADVANCES IN COMMUNICATION, VLSI & EMBEDDED SYSTEMS"

(19th & 20th December, 2014)

Organised by Department of
Electronics & Communicaton Engineering.

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About the Institution

SR Engineering College, Warangal founded in 2002, is an autonomous and accredited Institution valuing and encouraging creativity and quality in teaching and learning processes for the intellectual growth of its students. The staff and students take on new and interesting activities to acquire ability to think uniquely and independently. The college is in a position to attract and develop outstanding faculty to actively participate and support an open academic climate in the campus. The college adopts innovative approaches for continuous improvement by strategic planning, benchmarking and performance monitoring.

SR Engineering College (SREC) is currently handling number of funded research projects creating research avenues for the faculty and students. Through active industry cooperation, SREC has established centers like Microsoft Innovation Center, CISCO Networking Academy and IBM Center of Excellence for nurturing talent among students. To shape and transform the students to meet challenging and complex engineering tasks globally, the college has systematically built and fostered relationship with reputed US Universities like University of Massachusetts, Saint Louis University, University of Missouri and Wright State University.

About the Department

- The department of ECE was established in the year 2002. The department has well qualified faculties and the state of the art labs to run both UG & PG programs. The department has one UG Program with an intake of 180 and two PG programs - Embedded systems with an intake of 36 and Electronic design technology with an intake of 18.
- Most of the faculty are pursuing their Doctorate besides executing research projects with grants from UGC, DST, AICTE, etc. The students and Staff of ECE are actively involved in publishing papers in various conferences and journals.
- The faculties are encouraged to take up research, attend workshops and conferences. Several faculty development programs are also organized for the benefits of the faculty.
- To cater the needs of the students several technical talks, workshops, personality development programs, soft skills and entrepreneurial activities are regularly conducted under professional societies besides curriculum.

About Warangal

The city of Warangal, located in the north east of Hyderabad in Telangana region of Andhra Pradesh, was accorded World Heritage status by UNESCO. Warangal was the capital of Kakatiya kingdom ruled by the Kakatiya dynasty from the 12th to the 14th centuries. The Kakatiya kings were great builders. Some of the famous examples of this architecture are the Thousand Pillared Temple, Ramappa Temple and Warangal Fort. Warangal is known for its beautiful lakes, temples and wildlife. It is rich in antiques and relics. The best season to visit Warangal is from September to February, when there is little humidity and average temperature is in the range of 22- 23°C.

SR Engineering College is located 15 km away from Warangal City on Warangal-Karimnagar Highway. Warangal is well connected by Rail and Road. The nearest Airport is in Hyderabad, which is 150 km away.

About the Conference

The aim of the conference is to bring together scientists, researchers, educationalists and developers to share new ideas and establish cooperation between them and provide a platform for presenting their original work and exchange ideas, information, techniques and applications in the field of Communication, VLSI & Embedded Systems. Participants are encouraged to present papers on all topics listed in the CALL FOR PAPERS, which enable interdisciplinary discussions on new ideas, latest research and development. Papers are invited from various departments like Aeronautical, Automobile, CSE, ECE, EEE, EIE, Inst. & Control, Mechatronics, and allied branches of Engineering. Selected Papers will be published in the Proceedings of the conference.

Objectives of the conference

- Communication and signal processing have led to unprecedented increase in the number of engineering applications such as Industrial Automation, Computer Communications, Satellite Communications, and Vehicle Control etc. The conference focuses on the recent trends advancement and future trends in the areas of communications, signal processing, VLSI, wireless and mobile communications. The areas of VLSI, Embedded systems and Signal Processing have improved the quality of human life immensely. Innovations in recent years in the areas of mobile computing, biomedical processing, multimedia entertainment devices etc. have contributed towards the same
- A major objective of the conference will be to pursue the progression from the theoretical aspects of innovative communication and signal processing techniques through the implementation, evaluation and performance enhancement of practical communication systems. It is also planned to provide a forum for presenting the latest ideas from academia, industry and the corresponding developments in the domains of signal processing and integrated circuits and systems.
- This Conference aims at bringing together the Researchers, Scientists, Engineers and Scholar students in all areas of VLSI, Communication and provides an international forum for the dissemination of original research results, new ideas and practical development experiences which concentrate on both theory and practices.
- The Conference covers wide range of topics from Communication, VLSI circuits, systems and design methods to system level design and system-on-chip issues in bringing VLSI experience to new areas and technologies like nano and molecular devices, MEMS, Communication and network security. Future design methodologies will also be one of the key topics at the conference.
- Yet another major goal of the conference is to promote academic-industry interaction and foster collaborative research. Apart from these, we expect papers dealing with data, audio, image and video processing for multimedia, biomedical and security applications.

Scope and Topics

Conference Invites original & Unpublished Reserch Papers in the following areas

- Antennas
- Embedded Systems
- VLSI Design
- Audio & Speech Signal Processing
- Wireless Communications
- Bio Medical Signal Processing
- MEMS
- Data communications
- Mixed Signal Processing
- Optical communication & networks
- Digital System Design
- Image & Video Signal Processing
- Neural networks & Fuzzy Logic Applications
- Adaptive Signal Processing
- NEMS

These are suggested areas papers are accepted in related areas also.

Submission of Papers

Authors are invited to submit only full length papers not exceeding 4 pages as per IEEE format which is available on the Conference website. Submission of papers shall be through email: icracves@srecwarangal.ac.in on or before the deadline.

Information about the guidelines to authors, paper format and copyright format are provided on conference website: www.srecwarangal.ac.in/icracves.html Authors and the participants are requested to watch the Conference website for the updates.

Acceptance and Publication

All the papers submitted will be peer reviewed by two experts in a double blinded manner and based on the recommendations of the reviewers, comments will be sent to the authors. The camera-ready manuscripts after incorporating the reviewer comments should be submitted before the deadline. The papers accepted for presentation will be published in the proceedings of the conference and the softcopy of the proceedings will be presented in the form of CD. Papers submitted after deadline may not be included in the conference proceedings.

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Important Dates

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Acceptance of the paper : 27th November 2014
Camera Ready Paper Submission : 08th December 2014
Last date for Registration : 08th December 2014

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Delegates	National	International
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Delegates from Academia & Research	₹ 2500	\$ 150
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Video Quality QOE Estimation and Enhancement

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Abstract: Nowadays, with the continuous rise of Internet-based multimedia services, such as video sharing websites, web radios and IP-based telephony, multimedia communications are gaining more and more popularity. From the service provider's perspective, there is an increasing need for providing high-quality content; at the same time, from the network provider's view, the requirement is to design networks that can effectively support these services with adequate quality-of-service. In both cases, engineers and researchers need suitable planning tools exploitable for providing appropriate designs. For all these reasons, we have focused our work on the design and implementation of a novel open-source tool, named QoE Monitor, which consists of a new module that can be used to perform quality-of-experience (QoE) assessments network. The goal of this paper is to predict the video and/or audio quality perceived by an end user through objective metrics.

Key Words: QOE, MSE, PSNR, Tone Adjustment

I. INTRODUCTION

As wireless networks have been increasingly deployed, the need of quality measurement became essential since network operators want to control their network resources while maintaining user satisfaction. More importantly, measurement of technical parameters fails to give an account of the user experience, what could be named QoE (Quality of Experience). Therefore, many techniques have been developed in order to assess as accurately as possible this perceptual quality. To investigate QoE measurement, this paper presents three approaches namely subjective approach, objective approach, and hybrid approach. It also presents performance evaluation of these approaches for assessing QoE in video streaming application over wireless networks in different network conditions (using variation of loss rate and its distribution).

We focus more specifically on object approach. We demonstrate that this approach provides good

estimations comparing to the well-known objective metric called Peak Signal to Noise Ratio (PSNR). Before the beginning of multimedia communication era, simple parameters such as bandwidth, loss, delay or other network related parameters were enough to evaluate quality of service because the provided services are plain applications such as e-mail or file transfer. These applications do not have complicated definition of quality, for example, with file transfer, bandwidth or delay would probably be sufficient to imply quality of service. However, nowadays real-time multimedia applications are being deployed on IP networks and technical parameters can no longer assess accurately the quality of service as it is perceived by human. Users expect to have good perceptual quality that can be derived from many factors including not only technical parameters but also users experience. Network operators need to control their resource while maintaining user satisfaction, which will result in user fidelity and benefit for the company. Therefore, they need to take into account not only quality of service (QoS) but also quality of experience (QoE). Quality of experience [1] is the overall acceptability of an application or service, as perceived subjectively by end-users. It is basically a subjective measurement of end-to-end performance at the service level, from the point of view of the users. In the following, we give an overview of QoE assessment in three different ways: subjective, objective.

II. VIDEO QUALITY ESTIMATION TECHNIQUES

A. Subjective Assessment

The most accurate approach to assess perceived quality is the subjective assessment because there is no better indicator of video quality than the one given by humans. However, the quality score given by a human also depends on his/her own experience. The assessment consists in building a panel of human observers which will evaluate sequences of video depending on their point of view and their perception. The output of the test is in terms of mean opinion score (MOS) [2], which is given in Table 1 below.

MOS	Quality	Impairment
5	Excellent	Imperceptible
4	Good	Perceptible but annoying
3	Fair	Slightly annoying
2	Poor	Annoying
1	Bad	Very annoying

Table 1 Mean Opinion Score

B. Objective Assessment

Since the subjective approach is not appropriate for implementation, many researchers have been looking for another approach that can be processed automatically using information such as network parameters [3]. Consequently, they are interested in an objective approach that uses algorithms or formulas and quality of service measurements of a stream given by technical parameters that can be collected easily from the network. Many objective metrics exist and we will select one of them to study in this paper. As objective assessment, we choose to evaluate Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) [4] because it is the most common and the most simple objective video quality assessment used by many researchers. PSNR is the ratio between the maximum possible power of a signal and the power of corrupting noise that affects the fidelity of its representation. It is defined via the Mean Squared Error (MSE) between an original frame and the distorted framed as following

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \sum_{j=1}^N (\bar{A}(mn) - A(m,n))^2$$

Where each frame has $M \times N$ pixels, and $\bar{a}(m, n)$ and $d(m, n)$ are the luminance pixels in position (m, n) in the frame. Then, PSNR is the logarithmic ratio between the maximum value of a signal and the background noise (MSE). If the maximum luminance value in the frame is L (when the pixels are represented using 8 bits per sample, $L = 255$) then

$$\text{PSNR} = 10 \cdot \log(1/\text{MSE})$$

It can be noticed that PSNR can be computed only once the image is reconstructed at the receiver, hence, it may not be appropriate to use in real-time mechanisms. This is one disadvantage of such metric. The other would be the reliability to derive MOS from this metric. However, according to [5] there exist heuristic mappings of PSNR to MOS as shown in

PSNR	MOS
> 37	5(Excellent)
31-37	4(Good)
25-31	3(Fair)
20-25	2(Poor)
<20	1(Bad)

Table 2. PSNR and MOS

III. VIDEO ENHANCEMENT

Video enhancement problem can be formulated as follows: given an input low quality video and the output high quality video for specific applications. How can we make video more clearer or subjectively better. Digital video has become an integral part of everyday life[14]. It is well-known that video Enhancement as an active topic in computer vision has received much attention in recent years. The aim is to improve the visual appearance of the video, or to provide a “better” transform representation for future automated video processing, such as analysis, detection, segmentation, and recognition. Moreover, it helps analyses background information that is essential to understand object behavior without requiring expensive human visual inspection [6]. There are numerous applications where digital video is acquired, processed and used, such as surveillance, general identity verification, traffic, criminal justice systems, civilian or military video processing .

In this paper, according to if enhanced video embed high quality background information, the existing techniques of video enhancement can be classified into two broad categories: Self-enhancement and frame-based fusion enhancement. Traditional methods of video enhancement are to enhance the low quality video itself. It doesn't embed any high quality background information. Such as contrast enhancement method, HDR-based video enhancement, compressed-based video enhancement, and wavelet-based transform video enhancement. These approaches are uniformly called self-enhancement of low quality video. It don't enough luminous of low quality video. The reason is that in the dark video, some areas are so dark that all the information is already lost in those regions[7]. No matter how much illumination enhancement you apply, it will not be able to bring back lost information. Frame-based fusion enhancement refers to low quality video, which fuse illumination information in different time video. The approach is that it is by extracting high quality background

information to embed low quality video. How would one combine information from two (or more) background images in a meaningful way [8]. How would one pick high-quality background parts while keeping all the low-quality important Information [13]. To these problems, the previous researchers have abundant research. Fig.1 shows the more detail categories of video enhancement

Fig 1 Video Enhancement

In the frame work show that initially video is first convert into frames and each frame is enhanced by using adaptive histogram equalization process with fusion and red channel processing concept [15]. At the end finally enhanced video we get.

This method is considered a local operator since the operation only affects pixel values in an image individually on a pixel-by-pixel basis and each pixel is mapped in the same way. The global are independent of local spatial context. It performs the same operation on each pixel and don't work well when illumination varies locally [9]. The simplest tone reproduction is a linear mapping which scales the radiances to the range between 0 and 255. The logarithm of the radiances is taken and linearly scaled to [0, 255].

Figure 2 Frame Work of Video Enhancement

Some regions of a video catch human visual attention at first glance more than other regions, and the regions are considered more salient method [10]. The figure 2 is shows actual frame work of the paper

A Framework Overview

Global contrast enhancement is required to reveal hidden details in dark and bright regions [11]. In addition to enhancing regions with extremely high or low luminance, proposed technique is also significantly stretches the contrast in mid-tone regions, which most other curve-based global.

Saliency values can be regarded as complex local information indicating the degree of human interest in each pixel in a video. Saliency maps are most frequently used to extract useful objects in the preprocessing of surveillance systems or recognition problems [12].

IV. EXPERIMENT RESULTS

In this paper we are using MATLAB Software .MATLAB has evolved over a period of years with input from many users. In university environments, it is the standard instructional tool for introductory and advanced courses in mathematics, engineering, and science. In industry, MATLAB is the tool of choice for high-productivity research, development, and analysis. MATLAB features a family of application-specific solutions called toolboxes.

Very important to most users of MATLAB, toolboxes allow you to learn and apply specialized technology. Toolboxes are comprehensive collections of MATLAB functions (M-files) that extend the MATLAB environment to solve particular classes of problems. Areas in which toolboxes are available include signal processing, control systems, neural networks, fuzzy logic, wavelets, simulation, and many others.

To enhance the better quality of a video the tone adjustment technique is used here. In addition, noise estimation is taken into account to quantify the artifacts of noise generation during contrast enhancement process. The Video sequence is separated into frames to yield a single high quality image. Fig 3 is shows the paper proposed technique front panel and it implement using MATLAB 7.11 Version its show the GUI of the paper.

Fig 3.GUI of Video enhancement Technique

Fig 5: separating frames window

GUI is consists of four Push Buttons they are Browse Video, Enhancement, Reconstruction and Validation. When Browse Video button is pressed below window display and selected video is played.

After separating enhancement is done my using AHE with fusion and red channel processing. In figure 5 the process of separating frame is shown

Fig 4: Video Browse push button window

When Enhancement push button is pressed this below window appears. Enhancement process is started first separating frame and enhancement is done.

Fig 6: enhancing frames window

After enhancing again enhanced video is played so that enhancement can be observed. In above figure 6 shows the process of enhancing frames using adaptive histogram process

Fig 7: Enhanced video is playing window

After enhancing for the purpose of video quality estimation calculating PSNR of video. After enhancement process in figure 7 it is shown that the reconstructed video is played

Fig 8: PSNR calculation window

In above figure 8 after reconstructed video played the PSNR and MOS is calculated that is shown above figure 8

V. CONCLUSION

This proposed video enhancement framework consisting of Tone adjustment. This work showed that achieves greater performance using luminance component. To evaluate the enhancement performance, the PSNR value was used to measure the quality of enhancement. This technique will also prove that enhancing the quality of low-grade video surveillance cameras. To objectively judge the quality of a video acquired from some video processing system is not an easy task. The most traditional way of doing this in the literature is by calculating the so called signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) or peak signal-to-

noise ratio (PSNR). The SNR and PSNR are calculated for a processed video by looking at each processed frame and comparing it to a corresponding true frame in a true video.

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A Consolidated Analysis of MANET Routing Protocols

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Abstract — A mobile ad-hoc network (MANET) is an infrastructure-less network, in which nodes communicate with each other without any central administration. Nodes in an ad-hoc network behave simultaneously as host as well as router agreeing to forward data traffic for other nodes. A routing protocol is needed to establish routes for data transmission. Many routing protocols have been proposed and are being studied as a topic of active research. A significant amount of work has already been done on the performance evaluation of these routing protocols. However, in order to compare the results presented in these individual efforts, a level ground is needed. The work presented in this paper is an effort to provide such a level field for three performance metrics viz. Average throughput, End-to-end delay and Packet delivery ratio by applying some heuristics, normalization and other statistical measures. The techniques presented are then applied to the results of some of the leading research works and conclusions are drawn if there was a trend observed. Particularly, three protocols viz. AODV, DSDV and DSR remained the focus of this work.

Keywords— Mobile Ad-Hoc Network, MANET, Routing Protocol, AODV, DSDV, DSR, QoS, Performance Analysis, Average throughput, End-to-end delay and Packet delivery ratio.

I. INTRODUCTION

In a Mobile Ad-Hoc Network [1] nodes are mobile and are connected via wireless link in an arbitrary manner with the neighboring nodes present in their antenna ranges. The overall end to end communications is therefore, multi-hop Routing protocols are used to discover and maintain routed; however in such a highly dynamic environment, routing is a very challenging task [2][3]. Several routing protocols have been proposed and calculated their performance metrics by simulating them under varying scenarios (mobility, size, density, load, etc.). However in order to compare the results of these efforts and to make consolidated inferences one need to normalize these results to a common scale.

This paper discusses three performance metrics (viz. average throughput [4], end-to-end delay [5] delay Packet delivery ratio [6] and present approaches to normalize each of them in order to

establish comparisons between observations made by various researchers.

Rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents a brief review of existing protocols. Section 3 reviews some of the recent literature whose results are then normalized in section 4 to establish the comparison. Finally, section 5 presents the conclusion and indicates some of the possible future research directions

II. ROUTING PROTOCOLS

Routing protocols are used to find a path from source to destination. Essentially these protocols have been classified into three categories. Proactive routing protocols, Reactive routing protocols and Hybrid (Proactive + Reactive) routing protocols. Fig 1 shows a classification of these routing protocols.:

Fig 1: A classification of MANET routing protocol.

A. Proactive Routing Protocols

In proactive (table-driven) [7] [8] protocols all nodes periodically exchange the information about currently known shortest routes with their neighbors. Each node, then, analyzes this information to compute new shortest routes to each possible destination in the network. These types of protocols

are not difficult to implement however due to its resource hungry nature, limited energy of the nodes and slow propagation of routing information it becomes infeasible to be used in larger MANETs. DSDV (Destination Sequenced Distance-Vector), FSR (Fisheye State Routing Protocol), and CGSR (Cluster Head Gateway Switch Routing Protocol) are some examples of proactive routing protocols.

B. Reactive Routing Protocols

In reactive (on-demand) [9] [10] protocols, nodes do not continuously exchange routing information with their neighbors; instead a route is constructed only when it is needed. When a source node needs a route to a destination node it starts a node discovery process, in which route request messages are flooded across the network. The destination node responds to this request hence establishing a route. The Route is maintained until destination become unreachable, or source is no longer interested in destination.

AODV (Ad-Hoc on Demand Distance Vector Routing Protocol) [7], DSR (Dynamic Source Routing Protocol) [8], TORA protocol (Temporary-Ordered Routing Algorithm), CBRP (Cluster Based Routing Protocol) are examples of reactive routing protocols.

C. Hybrid Routing Protocols

Hybrid (proactive + reactive) [11] [12] protocols are simply the combination of two protocols stated above. ZRP (Zone Routing Protocol) being a typical example in which the whole topology is divided into a hierarchy of zones. Proactive routing is used locally within each zone, while reactive routing is used to create routes between the zones.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Following four papers have been carefully selected after a handful of literature review. Observations and results of many papers were unusable because of the insufficient availability of scenario parameters such as number of connections or data rate. Also some papers were dropped from consideration due to the inconsistencies between their input and output parameters.

A. Comparison of DSDV, AODV and DSR by Asma Tuteja et al., [13].

This paper compares DSDV, AODV and DSR routing protocols using network simulator NS2.34. In particular the effects of changing packet size, pause time and mobility on the Throughput, PDR (Packet Delivery Ratio), End to End Delay, and Routing overhead were studied. The scenario consisted of 25 nodes with a single source (node 0) and a single

destination (node 2). The simulation time was 10 seconds with Packet sizes were 1000, 500 and 100 bytes. Packet sending interval was set to 0.015, 0.15 and 1.5 seconds in different scenarios. The paper made the following observations: In AODV and DSR, the number of packets received at destination was found decreasing with the increase in packet sending interval. DSDV was found independent of varying packet sizes. In AODV and DSR Protocols both throughput and packet delivery ratio (PDR) were observed to be decreasing with increase in packet size.

Overall, the performance of DSDV protocol was not good compared to AODV and DSR protocols. In some situations AODV performed better than DSR, however in general DSR performed slightly better than AODV. Performance of all three protocols was found decreasing with increase in node mobility.

B. Comparison of DSDV, AODV, DSR and OLSR. by Deepank Modi et al., [14]

In this paper DSDV, AODV, DSR and OLSR routing protocols are compared using network simulator NS2. It studies the effects of changing network density (number of nodes in unit area) and traffic load (number of connections) on the Throughput, PDR (Packet Delivery Ratio), End to End Delay, and Normalized Routing Load. The scenarios consisted of 30 to 150 nodes in a 1 km x 1 km area. The traffic load in one set of scenarios was 15 connections while it was 25 connections in the other. The paper concluded that AODV protocol produced best results in all network scenarios and traffic conditions with respect to throughput and packet delivery ratio. However the proactive protocol DSDV guarantees lowest values of delay and shows best performance in terms of end-to-end delay. DSR was observed to be having the worst performance in congested networks.

C. Comparison of DSDV, AODV and DSR by G. Lakshmikanth et al., [15]

This paper compares DSDV, AODV and DSR routing protocols using network simulator NS2 and studies the effects of changing network density, pause time and mobility on the PDR (Packet Delivery Ratio), End to End Delay, and Normalized routing load. A total of 123 simulations are presented (41 scenarios for each of the 3 protocols). The scenarios consisted of 10 to 100 nodes, with a maximum pause time of 0 to 900 seconds and mobility speeds varying from 0 to 100 m/s. The simulation time was 15 minutes. The paper made the following observations: At 40 sources, the network was unable to handle all of the traffic generated by the routing protocol and a significant fraction of data packets were dropped. The performance of DSR was very good at all mobility

rates and movement speeds, although its use of source routing increases the number of routing overhead bytes required by the protocol. AODV performs almost as well as DSR at all mobility rates and movement speeds and accomplishes its goal of eliminating source routing overhead, but it still requires the transmission of many routing overhead packets and at high rates of node mobility is actually more expensive than DSR. Finally, AODV and DSR performance is better than DSDV when transmission power is increased. At higher transmission powers AODV routing load is increased.

D. Comparison of DSDV, AODV and DSR by Julia Rahman et al., [16]

This paper analyses the comparative performance of AODV, DSDV and DSR routing protocols in scenarios with varying network density and mobility by observing the Packet Delivery Ratio, Throughput, End to End Delay, and Normalized Routing Load using NS2 simulator. The scenario consisted of a varying number (10 to 120) of nodes in an area of 1 sq. km and a varying pause time of 0 to 200 seconds and node speed of 20 m/s. The traffic type was CBR 2 Kbytes/sec and simulation time was 200 seconds. Simulation results show that different routing protocol performs well in different scenarios and good for specific performance metrics. For example, DSDV perform better in the high density networks or the network with strict requirement on time whereas DSR performs well in smaller network. AODV is more adaptable in the networks with high throughputs and preferable for low loss rate environment.

IV. NORMALIZATION OF QoS PARAMETERS.

Typically, qualities of service (QoS) parameters [17] are used to define the required performance of a connection or a network as described by QoS routing, QoS MAC and resource reservation [18]. However the same parameters may be used as performance metrics to study the effectiveness of a protocol. Following three QoS parameters are analyzed in this study:

A. Throughput:

Throughput is defined as the amount of data delivered in a unit of time by the network [19]. It is measured in bits/sec (or sometimes in bytes/sec). Some authors confuse this quantity with average-throughput which is a different parameter. To compare the throughputs obtained by various studies presented in previous section, and to establish a unifiable pattern, it is very much needed to normalize the throughput values.

Define required-throughput to be the amount of data needed to be transferred in a unit of time and is computed as follows:

$$\text{Required Throughput} = N \times R \times S$$

where, N = No of connections
 R = Packet rate (in packets/sec)
 S = Packet size (in bits)

Now the throughput values can be normalized by dividing them by the corresponding required throughput. This will help one judge the relative merit or de-merit of a protocol over the other.

Table-1 shows the application of this normalization approach on the throughput values observed.

Table-1

THROUGHPUT (K bits /sec)		Asma Tuteja et. al.,			
		Scnr-1	Scnr-2	Scnr-3	Scnr-4
Observed	AODV	163.52	33.6	27.28	178.64
	DSDV	65.76	8	6.56	65.76
	DSR	140.4	27.52	24.8	194.64
Required		480	48	48	240

Normalized	AODV	34%	70%	57%	74%
	DSDV	14%	17%	14%	27%
	DSR	29%	57%	52%	81%

Table-2 shows the average of these normalized values for various studies presented in the previous section.

Table-2

	Julia Rahman et. al.,	Asma Tuteja et. al.,	Guntupalli Lakshmikanth et. al.,	AVG
AODV	59%	42%	54%	52%
DSDV	18%	224%	46%	30%
DSR	55%	32%	34%	40%

From the comparison presented in Table-2, it is deducible that AODV gives 40 to 60% of the required throughput while both DSR and DSDV lag AODV on this.

B. Packet Delivery Ratio:

Packet delivery ratio is calculated by dividing the number of packets received at the destination by the number of packets originated at the source [20]. For the best performance packet delivery ratio of routing protocol should be as high as possible. A ratio of 1 is the best delivery ratio a protocol can ever achieve. To establish a unified result for this parameter and to provide a level playing field, it is suggested to pivot the PDR of one protocol at some standard point and observe the corresponding value of PDR for the other protocols. Specifically, pinpoint AODV around 30% and 70% and observe the corresponding values of other protocols. Table-3 presents the results obtained after applying this approach on the papers presented in the previous section and Figure 2 depicts the same on a graph.

Table-3

	Julia Rahman et. al.,	Asma Tuteja et. al.,	Guntupalli Lakshmikanth et. al.,	AVG 70
AODV	70%	63%	70%	68%
DSDV	42%	15%	65%	41%
DSR	72%	52%	75%	66%

	Julia Rahman et. al.,	Asma Tuteja et. al.,	Guntupalli Lakshmikanth et. al.,	AVG 30
AODV	30%	34%	33%	32%
DSDV	38%	36%	36%	37%
DSR	20%	12%	39%	24%

From this graph it can be concluded that the PDR of DSR protocol remains comparable to the AODV protocol. In scenarios where AODV has a low PDR (30%), DSR also has a low PDR and in scenarios where AODV has a high PDR (70%), DSR also has a high PDR. However, the PDR of DSR remains slightly lower than AODV. The PDR of DSDV protocols maintains its value around 40% for all types of scenarios.

Figure 2: Comparison of Packet Delivery Ratios.

C. Average End-To-End Delay:

Average end-to-end delay is defined as the mean time a data packet takes to reach destination from source [5]. Any retransmission delays at the Media Access Control (MAC) layer are also included. It is measured in the units of time (ms). To establish a uniform comparison between the values of end-to-end delay observed in various papers presented in section 3, the end-to-end delay values for DSR and DSDV protocols were divided by the corresponding value for AODV protocol. Multiple values from each paper are then averaged.

Table-4 summarizes the end-to-end delay values after this normalization:

Table-4

	Julia Rahman et. al.,	Asma Tuteja et. al.,	Guntupalli Lakshmikanth et. al.,	Yin Tan et. al.
AODV	1	1	1	1
DSDV	0.6	0.75	0.85	
DSR	2.1	0.9	0.7	2

From these results it can be concluded that the average end to-end delay in DSDV protocol remains 60 to 85% of the AODV value in the same scenario. The Average end-to-end delay of DSR is fluctuating above and below AODV value in some scenarios it was observed more than 200% of the AODV end-to-end delay value while sometimes it was found around 70% of the AODV value.

V. CONCLUSION

A novel approach to consolidate the results of various studies available in the literature is presented. Methods were defined to compare the throughput, packet delivery ratio and end to end delay from various scenarios and simulations. After applying the approach on the observations of some selected papers, it was concluded that AODV performance remains better than DSDV and DSR protocols with respect to throughput and packet delivery ratio while DSDV performance was found better with respect to the end to end delay. In the future we would like to extend this work to include other available MANET routing protocols and more performance metrics.

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Analysis of Adaptive Bilateral Filtered Images

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Abstract— In this paper, implementation of an image filter algorithm (Adaptive Bilateral Filter) is shown, whose aim is to recover a quality image from a noisy image and calculate the quality of the image. The image quality can be improved by de-nosing. Image noise removal is an important image processing task in digital image processing. This can be implemented on Gray images, colour and text images.

Keywords— Bilateral filter, Noise removal, Image quality, Gray images, Color images, Text images, Psnr.

I. INTRODUCTION

In signal processing, filter is a device which removes unwanted signals like random noise, or to extract some part of signal with in a specific frequency range. Filters are classified into, analog filters and digital filters. An analog filter uses analog electronic circuits made up from components like resistors, capacitors and operational amplifiers to produce the required filtered output. Such filters are widely used in such applications as noise filters, video signal filters, equalizers in high-fidelity systems etc., digital filter performs operations on sampled values of the signal on a processor. The analog signals are sampled and given as input to analog to digital convertor(ADC),which converts the analog signals to digital binary digits, which are given as input to the processor and it performs various operations. If the binary digits are necessary to convert back to analog samples, these can be given to digital to analog convertor(DAC).

Digital Image processing can be implemented by digital filters which include smoothing, improving the edge slope, and sharpening. Filtering can be classified into non linear and linear filtering. Linear filtering is a technique used for enhancing and modifying an image. Linear filtering is based on pixel neighborhood operation with respect to the selected input pixel. Linear filters are capable of removing noise. Non linear filters are extended linear filters which are based on order statistics, and are very faster than linear filters because they only perform comparisons. Image enhancement is a process, which is used to improve noisy or blur images in order to have a better look. The main objective of enhancement is to process an image and obtain a suitable image than the original one. It can be

performed by Spatial Domain(pixel manipulation) and frequency domain (modifying Fourier transform).

Image enhancement techniques can be perform on an image for Brightness adjustment, contrast adjustment, modifying the size, inversion, conversion, correction, color balancing, sharpening, format conversion, and blurring. A process which aims to invert known degradation operations applied to images. Image restoration methods are used to improve the appearance of an image by applications of a restoration process that uses a mathematical model for image degradation.

II. BILATERAL FILTER

Bilateral filtering is a non-linear filtering technique which extends the Gaussian smoothing concept by weighting the filter coefficients with their relative pixel values. The Pixels which have different intensity, when compared from the central pixel are weighted less even though they have very close proximity to the central pixel. The edge-preserving de-noising bilateral filter uses a low pass Gaussian filter for both the domain filter and the range filter. The domain filter gives higher weight to pixels that are spatially close to the center pixel. The range filter gives higher weight to pixels that are similar to the center pixel in gray value. By using the range filter and the domain filter, a bilateral filter ensures that averaging is done mostly along the edge and is greatly reduced in the gradient direction. This makes the bilateral filter perform smoothing the noise while preserving edge structures. The shift-variant filtering operation of the bilateral filter is given by the equation (1).

$$f'(m, n) = \sum_k \sum_l h[m, n; k, l] g[k, l] \quad \dots (1)$$

Where $f^{\wedge}[m, n]$ is the restored image, $h[m, n; k, l]$ is the response at to an impulse at, and $g[m, n]$ is the degraded image. The bilateral filter equation can be as equation (2).

$$I_{filtered}(x) = \frac{1}{W_p} \sum_{x \in \Omega} I(x) f_c(\|I(x) - I(x_i)\|) g_s(\|x_i - x\|) \quad \dots (2)$$

The normalization term can be given by the equation (3) as shown below.

$$W_p = \sum_{x \in \Omega} \text{fr} (||I(x) - I(x)||) \text{gs} (||x_i - x||) \dots (3)$$

Where (I filtered) is the filtered image. (I) is the original input image to be filtered. x is the coordinates of the current pixel to be filtered. Ω is the window centered in x. fr is the range kernel for smoothing differences in intensities. gs is the spatial kernel for smoothing differences in coordinates. As mentioned above in the equation (3), the weight W_p is assigned using the spatial closeness and the intensity difference. Consider a pixel located at (i, j) which needs to be de-noised in image using its neighboring pixels and one of its neighboring pixels is located at (k, l). Then, the weight assigned for pixel (k, l) to de-noise the pixel (i, j) is given by the equation (4).

$$W(i, j, k, l) = e^{-\frac{(i-k)^2 + (j-l)^2}{(2\sigma_r)^2}} - \frac{||I(i,j) - I(k,l)||}{(2\sigma_d)^2} \dots (4)$$

Where σ_d and σ_r are smoothing parameters and I (i, j) and I (k, l) are the intensity of pixels (i, j) and (k, l) respectively. Calculate the weights, normalize them.

$$ID(i, j) = \frac{\sum_{k,l} I(k,l) \cdot W(i,j,k,l)}{\sum_{k,l} W(i,j,k,l)} \dots (5)$$

Where, ID is the de-noised intensity of pixel (i, j).

III. ADAPTIVE BILATERAL FILTER

The adaptive bilateral filter (ABF) uses a new sharpening and smoothing algorithm. The ABF retains the general form of a bilateral filter, but contains two modifications. First, an offset is introduced in the range filter in the ABF and second, both and the width of the range filter in the ABF are locally adaptive and changeable. If it is fixed, the ABF will degenerate into a conventional normal bilateral filter. A fixed domain filters which is adopted in the ABF. The combination of a locally adaptive and transforms the bilateral filter into a much more powerful filter that is capable of both smoothing and sharpening.

The advantage of defining the filter in this manner is that it allows non-linear filtering that allows both spatial and amplitudinal locality at the same time. The amplitude at a point is considered by neighboring points with similar amplitudes more than by those with other different amplitudes. This results in reduced smoothing across signal regions by large but consistence variances in amplitude, thus better

preserving of such signal. It will produce undesirable results in situations where the signal to noise ratio is low. In situations where the signal to noise ratio is low, amplitudinal differences between neighboring points are often large even in the smoother regions of the signal. To achieve noise suppression in smooth regions in such a situation, the spatial spread and amplitudinal spread must be made sufficiently large to accommodate for the increased variation. However, such a large spread can have the adverse effect of over-smoothing the signal in regions of significant signal detail. To alleviate this problem, we propose the adaptation of these constraint parameters based on the perceptual sensitivity of the human perception system to the underlying signal characteristics.

Where $[m_0, n_0]$ and Ω_{m_0, n_0} are defined as before, and the normalization factor is given by the equation (6).

$$m_0, n_0 = \frac{\sum_{m=m_0-N}^{m_0+N} \sum_{n=n_0-N}^{n_0+N} \exp \frac{-(m-m_0)^2 + (n-n_0)^2}{(2\sigma_d)^2}}{(\sum_{m,n} [m,n] - \sum_{m_0, n_0} [m_0, n_0])^2} X \exp - \dots (6)$$

A. Degradation model

Images are the useful information which can be recordable and saved in the storage. Improper capturing of an image results in degraded images. There are many kinds of distortions. The different degradations consider noise, pin cushion distortion, illumination and color imperfections, and blurriness of the image.

General model,

$$G(x, y) = T(f(x, y)) + n(x, y) \dots (7)$$

T(x, y) may not be linear, Modeling T (x, y) by a filtering operation.

$$G(x, y) = f(x, y) * h(x, y) + n(x, y) \dots (8)$$

The degradation operator is linear and shift invariant, h(x, y) is unknown and needs to be estimated which given in the equation (8).

B. Noise types

Noise is any undesired information that contaminates an image. Noise appears in images from a variety of sources. In typical images the noise can be modeled with a Gaussian ("normal"), uniform, or salt-and-pepper ("impulse") distribution. The blurriness is a noise present in an image, can be caused by many factors like Movement during the image capture process or by the camera or when long exposure times are used, Out-focus, by using wide-

angle lens, atmospheric noise, or a short exposure time.

The value of a pixel should be the light intensity at a infinitesimal point in the imaged Scene. Each sensor in a CCD array integrates the light intensity in a small area surrounding a point with possibly non-equal weighting. The point spread function (PSF) is the image captured when there is only one single point with High intensity in the scene. This PSF is the degradation filter. Typically $h(x, y)$ due to sensor PSF is low-pass and is often approximated by a Gaussian filter's equation (9).

$$H(x, y) = e^{-k(x^2 + y^2)} \quad \dots(9)$$

TABLE.I PSNR VALUES

Image type	Adaptive Bilateral Filter(psnr)
Gray image (d)	75.79
Colour image (h)	74.51
Text image (m)	84.40

C. Mean square error

The mean-square-error (MSE) is given by the equation

$$MSE(f, f') = \int f(x)f'(x)^2 \cdot dx \quad \dots (10)$$

Where f is the original image, and f' the restored image. The mean-square-error measures the difference in energy between the compared images. The MSE can be calculated both in the spatial domain and in the frequency domain as given in equation (10).

D. Peak-signal-to-noise-ratio(psnr)

PSNR is used to measure the quality of reconstruction of noisy image. PSNR is an approximation to human perception of reconstruction quality.

IV. RESULTS

The below table (1) shows the experimental results which are obtained for the images filtered by adaptive bilateral filter i.e., the peak-signal- to- noise-ratio(PSNR) obtained by the adaptive bilateral filter for gray image, color image, text image.

Figure.1. (1) Gray Image (2) Noisy image (3) Bilateral filtered Image (4) Adaptive bilateral filtered image (5) Color image (6) Noisy Image (7) Bilateral filtered Image (8) ABF color image (9) Region of Interest (10) selected region (11) Region Degraded (12) BF Region (13) ABF region (14) Text Image (15) Noisy Text (16) Bilateral filtered Text (17) ABF Text

From the above results, we can observe that figure 1.(1) is the original gray image, which is given as input image and figure 1.(2) is the distorted image, after adding noise. When the distorted image is filtered (passed) through bilateral filter, the filter smoothes the image as shown in the figure 1.(3), where as the image passed through the adaptive bilateral filter, it smoothes the image and sharpens the image as shown in the figure 1.(4). Similarly in the case of colour images as shown in figure 1.(5), 1.(6), 1.(7), 1.(8).

In figure 1.(9), a specific region or part of an image is selected and implemented both bilateral and adaptive bilateral filters and obtained the results as shown in figure 1.(10), 1.(11), 1.(12), 1.(13). The outputs of text images are obtained as shown in figure 1.(14), 1.(15), 1.(16), 1.(17).

V. CONCLUSION

The image enhancement and de-noising of gray and colour images using bilateral and adaptive bilateral filter is implemented and achieved better experimental results in perceptual quality. The quality of images are obtained by using peak signal noise ratio (PSNR). The PSNR achieved for gray images is 74.79%, for color images is 73.41%, and for text images 83.3%.

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An Efficient Intra Prediction Architecture for H.264

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Abstract—The paper presents an intra prediction hardware architecture where it exploits parallelism in predicting the pixels and pipelining is implemented during the calculation of the cost function. The parallelism feature includes an optimized data path which calculates only 24 unique pixel values and the former are assigned to the current macro block depending on the equations for different modes as defined in the H.264 standard.

Keywords— *intra prediction, spatial redundancy, mode decision, video frame, macro block, optimized data path* .

I. INTRODUCTION

H.264 audio video coding is the latest standard which is the result of the collaboration between ISO/IEC MPEG and the ITU-T video coding experts group. Intra prediction feature of H.264 reduces the spatial redundancy present in a frame, which adds to the improvement in compression ratio. Current macro block in a video frame is either predicted by the neighboring pixels of the neighboring macro blocks within the same frame (intra prediction to reduce spatial redundancy) or by a macro block in the previous frame (inter prediction to reduce temporal redundancy). The first frame is always intra predicted because it has no reference frame. Intra prediction serves as an alternative when the motion estimator fails to provide a good matching block which results in high residue and low encoding quality.

II. H.264 INTRAFRAME PREDICTION

H.264 intra prediction uses the spatial correlation with neighboring macro blocks i.e. a current macro block is predicted from the neighboring pixels of the previously reconstructed macro blocks. In H.264 intra prediction is performed for two different block sizes (4x4 and 16 x 16) for luma prediction and 8x8 block for chroma prediction. Each 4x4 block is predicted using nine directional prediction modes and the 16x16 and 8x8 blocks are predicted using 4 modes (dc, horizontal , vertical ,plane).

A. Algorithm

For the luma component of the macro block each frame is divided into a number of 16x16 macro blocks and prediction is performed for one 16x16 macro block and sixteen 4x4 macro

M	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
I	a	b	c	d				
J	e	f	g	h				
K	i	j	k	l				
L	m	n	o	p				

Fig 1.A 4x4 luma block and its neighboring pixels

Fig 2.Prediction modes and directions

blocks. A mode decision algorithm is used to compare the predictions of 4x 4 and 16 x16 blocks and select the best luma prediction mode based on the cost function of the macro block.

The pixels A to M in Fig 1. belong to the neighboring blocks and are assumed to be already encoded and reconstructed and thus available for the prediction of the next macro block.

The pixels a to p represented in Fig 1. are the current macro block pixels which are later predicted using the thirteen reconstructed pixels of the neighboring macro blocks. Each 4x4 macro block generates 16 predicted pixels and each 16x16 macro block generates 256 predicted pixels using some or all of the neighboring pixels. The best predicted mode is assigned to the mode with minimum sum of absolute differences(sad).

For a 16 x 16 macro block the best predicted mode is generated as follows:

If the sad value of the 16 x16 macro block is less than the sum of sixteen 4x4 blocks sad values then the best predicted mode is one of the four directional modes for 16x16 macro block.

$$(16 \times 16 \text{ sad}) < \text{sum of } 16(4 \times 4 \text{ sad's})$$

Else the best predicted mode is one of the nine directional modes for each of the sixteen 4x4 macro blocks based on the cost function of each directional mode (considering the minimum sad value). Fig 2. represents the eight directional modes for the 4x4 macro block. Each pixel is assigned values for all the modes depending on the equations as defined in the standard [1].

B. Architecture

Intra prediction process consists of the following steps :

- 1) prediction equation generation for each pixel in the macro block , based on the neighboring samples.
- 2) calculate the cost of each predicted mode and to choose the block with minimum cost based on the sum of absolute differences.[2].

Flow diagram:

Fig 3. Architectural flow diagram of intra prediction process for a 4x4 macro block

a) Neighboring pixel memory:

The first block in the flow diagram is the neighboring pixel memory as shown in Fig 3. The neighboring pixels belong to the previous macro block and are used to predict the current macro block pixel values. All the thirteen pixels are required for the prediction of nine modes. So all the pixels are read from the memory in one clock cycle (4 pixels in one clock cycle). Every time a new macro block is predicted, the left and the top most original samples replace the neighboring pixels memory. The prediction scheme uses original pixels instead of

reconstructed pixels as boundary pixels for next predictions [3].

b) Prediction equations:

The standard formulae for different modes are transformed into pixel processing equations specified in h.264 standard draft [1]. Usually for horizontal and vertical modes the neighboring reconstructed pixel values are directly assigned (Here the neighboring original pixel values are assigned.). DC mode is a simple average of the neighboring reconstructed pixels (Here it is the simple average of the neighboring original pixels). For the remaining six modes all the equations are sorted to find out the unique set of equations which result in 24 equations only [2]. The computational order of these equations is rearranged to achieve an optimized data path [2].

Unique equations:

- D1<=L ; D2<=(K+L+L+L+2); D3<=(K+L+1);
- D4<=(J+K+K+L+2);D5<=(J+K+1);D6<=(I+J+J+K+2);
- D7<=(I+J+1); D8<=(M+I+I+J+2); D9<=(M+I+1);
- D10<=(A+M+M+I+2); D11<=(M+A+1);
- D12<=(M+A+A+B+2); D13<=(A+B+1);
- D14<=(A+B+B+C+2); D15<=(B+C+1);
- D16<=(B+C+C+D+2); D17<=(C+D+1);
- D18<=(C+D+D+E+2); D19<=(D+E+1);
- D20<=(D+E+E+F+2);D21<=(E+F+1);
- D22<=(E+F+F+G+2);D23<=(F+G+G+H);
- D24<=(G+H+H+H+2);

Fig.4. presents our methodology to create an optimized hardware (prediction logic) for Intra Prediction from the formulae specified in H.264 standard draft [1]. First, the standard formulae are transformed into pixel processing equations that are then processed for architecture-independent

Fig 4. optimized hardware for intraprediction from the standard formulae

optimizations under a given set of optimization rules and constraints. A set of unique equations is extracted followed by optimizations at multiple levels (within a prediction mode and across multiple modes) to enhance the level of operation reusability. A set of hardware parameters (e.g. size of register files and memories, number of read/write ports etc.) is considered to perform hardware level optimizations resulting in a fast hardware for Intra Prediction.

c) *Assignment:*

In this block four pixels in a row are assigned the prediction equations in one clock cycle for all the nine prediction modes. The assignment is done in parallel for each row and hence the 4x4 macro block is predicted in one clock cycle for all the nine modes.

d) *Current macro block memory:*

The current macro block memory of Fig 3. stores the 16 original pixels of the 4x4 luma block. These pixels are necessary for the mode decision as the predicted pixels are subtracted from the original pixels to generate the sad based on which the best predicted mode is generated. The neighboring pixels of the current block are updated to the neighboring pixel memory for every block since we are considering the original pixels instead of reconstructed pixels for prediction [3].

e) *SAD calculator:*

There are nine SAD calculators working in parallel for each mode which subtract the four predicted samples from the current block samples and the differences are accumulated to generate the SAD for one predicted 4x4 block line. The SAD calculator works in pipeline with the assignment block, so that after the first predicted line is generated the SAD calculator starts to accumulate during the next 4 clock cycles [2]. As shown in Fig 5 the calculator has an additional adder for accumulation.

Fig. 5. Sad calculations for a 4x4 macro block

In the Fig 5. o1, o2, o3, o4 represent the current macro block original pixels and p1, p2, p3, p4 represent the predicted pixels.

f) *Mode decision:*

The mode decision is the last block. As shown in Fig 3 nine sad values are generated. Mode decision gives the best predicted mode based on the minimum SAD value. The best predicted block is actually reconstructed (transformed, quantized, inverse quantized and inverse transformed) to get the exact predicted block whose boundary pixels are used as neighboring pixels for the next macro block. However an open loop intra prediction scheme is proposed to use original pixels instead of reconstructed pixels as reconstructed pixel values are close to original pixel values [3].

III. IMPLEMENTATION

The architecture is defined in a hardware description language (VHDL) and synthesized by the Compiler with 0.18Mm standard cell library. The design contains a total of 36k gates (The gate count is restricted as such because of the

Table1: Design Specifications

Algorithm	Fast mode algorithm
Memory requirement	(16x8) 16 pixels of each 8bits to store the current macro block and the predicted macro block
Technology	0.18µm
Gate count	36K
Maximum frequency	57MHZ
Throughput(4x4 macro block)	193KMB/s

use of the optimized data path and non implementation of the reconstruction path) and runs at a frequency of 57 MHz . The design specifications are shown in Table 1. The performance analysis after compilation using the Compiler is given in Table 2.

Table 2: Performance Analysis

Critical path	16.87µm
Critical path clk period	17.20ns
Operating conditions	5V
Total dynamic power	440.02µW

IV. EVALUATION AND RESULTS

The proposed architecture supports all baseline /main intra prediction features calculates the SAD cost and decides the best mode for 4x4 MB. This architecture does not implement the reconstruction path (T/Q/IQ/IT). The whole process for 4x4 MB in this architecture takes 9 clock cycles.

Table 3: Comparison with previous designs

Design feature	Our approach	Ref[7]	Ref [8]
Maximum operating frequency	57 MHZ 1280x720@54f ps	125 MHZ 1280x720@30f s	61 MHZ 1280x720@30fps
Maximum throughput	193 KMB/s	115 KMB/s	165 KMB/s
Pixel parallelism	4 pixel	4 pixel	8 pixel

The architecture takes three clock cycles to read the neighboring pixel values from the memory (four pixels in one clock cycle) and one clock cycle for the parallel assignment of each row of pixels (all the nine modes are assigned in one clock cycle for each row of pixels) as discussed in section II. B. 3 and four clock cycles for the SAD calculation as discussed in section II. B. 4 and one clock cycle for the mode decision. So a 4x4 macro block takes 9 clock cycles for its prediction. A 16x16 macro block on a whole takes 300 clock cycles for its prediction without considering the pixel reconstruction.

In each of the previous approaches either a parallel or a pipeline approach with reconstruction is considered. In our approach all the features of the previous works are included without reconstruction and it is observed that use of both parallel and pipeline approaches enhances the speed of processing with a reduction in area.

For full mode intra prediction one macro block takes 300 clock cycles considering 4 pixel parallelism. Therefore at 57 MHz the approach can process 193798 Mb/s i.e. 1920 x 1080 (HD 1080p) at 24 fps (frames per second). The required frequency for 1280 x 720 pixel resolution is 27.6 MHz for 30 fps. So at 57 MHz for 1280x720 resolution 54 frames per second can be processed. This implies that the above design specifications are applicable for (1280x720) application. Table 3 shows the comparison of our approach with other designs. The operating frequency of our approach is 57 MHz which processes 193 K Mb/s using parallelism feature and this approach is observed to be faster (1.6 times faster with respect to [7] and 1.16 times faster with respect to [8]).

V. CONCLUSION

The proposed hardware architecture for H.264/AVC intra prediction supports all the intra modes, calculates the block costs and decides the best intra 4x4 predicted macro block.

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Estimation of Channel Capacity in MIMO System Using Different Fading Channels

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Abstract - This paper focuses on the challenge of reliable communication over a wireless fading channel using multiple transmit and receive antennas. MIMO technology has attracted attention in wireless communications, since it offers significant increases in data throughput and link range without additional bandwidth or transmit power. MIMO models namely Rician and Rayleigh product channels are analyzed. The capacity of a MIMO channel with 'n_t' number of transmitting antennas and 'n_r' number of receiving antennas is analyzed in different fading channels. The channel capacity Vs minimum energy per information bit, (E_b/N_0 min) for different values of interference-to-noise ratio (INR), the Rician K factor and number of numbers transmit and receive antennas in MIMO systems are examined.

Keywords: Antennas, MIMO, Channel Capacity

I. INTRODUCTION

Multiple - Input Multiple - Output (MIMO) antenna systems have established huge concentration in wireless communications. Employing multiple antennas at both ends of the communication link in MIMO systems offers extensive enhancement in capacity and performance over single-antenna systems. So, the analysis of MIMO systems has been extensively analyzed for many different statistical channel models of interest.

The spectral efficiency in the low SNR regime can be analyzed through the minimum E_b/N_0 (with E_b , the average energy per information bit and N_0 , noise spectral density) required for reliable communications.

The low SNR metric has elaborated, where the effect of Rician factor K. Rician fading channel is a more common mode and embraces Rayleigh fading as a special case. Considering this and the significance of understanding the capacity of MIMO channels with interference at low SNRs, work has been done in analyzing the MIMO Rician fading channels with K factor. Based on these results, further analyzed the special cases, namely, the MIMO Rayleigh channels, where the impacts of the number of transmit and receive antennas, the Rician K factor, and the interference-to-noise ratio (INR) on the capacity were illustrated

We also discussed about the low SNR capacity analysis for MIMO Rayleigh-product fading channels.

II. MIMO SYSTEMS

A channel may be affected by fading and this will impact the signal to noise ratio. In turn this will impact the error rate.

The multiple input- multiple output (MIMO), a multi-antenna system, answers the question of how to achieve higher data rates, wider coverage, and increased reliability—all without using additional frequency spectrum.

III. SYSTEM MODEL

Consider a communication link with N_t transmit N_r and receive antennas, corrupted by interference and additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN). The received signals, $y \in C^{N_r \times 1}$ can be expressed as

$$Y = Hx + hs + n, \quad \dots(3.1)$$

In this paper, we discussed the low SNR capacity properties of two important MIMO channel models, namely: 1) Rician fading and 2) Rayleigh-product fading.

MIMO Rician channels: In this, the channel matrix has the form

$$H = \sqrt{\frac{K}{K+1}} H_0 + \sqrt{\frac{K}{K+1}} H_\omega \quad \dots(3.2)$$

Where K denotes the Rician K-factor, and $H_\omega \in C^{N_r \times N_t}$ is the channel matrix containing i.i.d. zero-mean unit-variance complex Gaussian entries. On the other hand, $H_0 \in C^{N_r \times N_t}$ denotes the channel mean matrix, which is normalized to satisfy

$$tr \{H_0 H_0^\dagger\} = N_r N_t \quad \dots\dots\dots(3.3)$$

MIMO Rayleigh-product channels: The channel matrix H can be given as

$$h = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_s}} H_1 H_2 \quad \dots(3.4)$$

Where $H_1 \in \mathbb{C}^{N_r \times N_t}$ and $H_2 \in \mathbb{C}^{N_r \times N_t}$ are statistically independent matrices containing i.i.d zero-mean unit-variance complex Gaussian entries, with N_s , being the number of effective scatters. By varying N_s this model can describe various rank-deficient effects of a MIMO channel.

Based on the definitions, the Ergodic capacity expression can be rewritten as

$$C(\rho) = E \left\{ \log_2 \det \left(I + \frac{N_r \rho H^* (\rho_i h h^\dagger + I)^{-1} H}{E \left\{ \text{tr} \left\{ H^* (\rho_i h h^\dagger + I)^{-1} H \right\} \right\}} \right) \right\} \quad \dots(3.5)$$

This capacity can be well approximated for low E_b/N_0 levels by the following expression

$$C \left(\frac{E_b}{N_0} \right) \approx S_0 \log_2 \left(\frac{\frac{E_b}{N_0}}{N_{0 \min}} \right), \quad \dots(3.6)$$

In which $\frac{E_b}{N_{0 \min}}$ and S_0 is the wideband slope. These are the two key parameters that dictate the capacity behavior in the low SNR regime, and can be obtained from $C(\rho)$.

$$\frac{E_b}{N_{0 \min}} = \frac{N_t N_r}{E \left\{ \text{tr} \left\{ H^* (\rho_i h h^\dagger + I)^{-1} H \right\} \right\}} \frac{1}{\dot{C}(0)} \quad \dots(3.7)$$

Where $\dot{C}(0)$ and $\ddot{C}(0)$ are, respectively, the first- and second-order derivatives taken with respect to ρ . It is worth pointing out that though the low SNR metrics are obtained when $\rho \rightarrow 0$, the capacity approximation by (3.6) is good for SNRs greater than $\frac{E_b}{N_{0 \min}}$.

RICIAN MIMO CHANNELS:

For MIMO Rician fading channels with a single interferer, we have

$$\frac{E_b}{N_{0 \min}} = \frac{\ln 2}{N_r - 1 + A_0}, \quad \dots(3.8)$$

Where $A_0 = D_1(N_r, \rho_I)$, $D_1(m, t)$ and $D_2(m, t)$ are defined as

$$D_1(m, t) \triangleq t^{-m} \psi(m, m, t^{-1}) \quad \dots(3.9)$$

$$D_2(m, t) \triangleq t^{-m} \psi(m, m-1, t^{-1}) \quad \dots(3.10)$$

where $\psi(\cdot, \cdot, \cdot)$ is the confluent hyper geometric function.

The $E_b/N_{0 \min}$ is a decreasing function of N_r and is an increasing function of ρ_I . Moreover, the increase in $E_b/N_{0 \min}$ due to interference is upper bounded by $\frac{\ln 2}{N_r(N_r-1)}$ for $N_r \geq 2$.

When $\rho_I \rightarrow 0$, the above reduces to

$$\frac{E_b}{N_{0 \min}} = \frac{\ln 2}{N_r}, \quad \dots(3.11)$$

Rank-1 Mean MIMO Rician Channels for Large K: In the large K regime, for rank-one mean MIMO Rician channels with a single interferer, it can be derived that

$$\frac{E_b}{N_{0 \min}} = \frac{\ln 2}{N_r - 1 + A_0(1, \rho_I)}, \quad \dots(3.12)$$

This indicates that in the large K regime, for rank-1 mean Rician MIMO fading channels, multiple transmit antennas are irrelevant in terms of $E_b/N_{0 \min}$ and S_0 .

When $\rho_I \rightarrow 0$, equation 3.12 reduces to

$$\frac{E_b}{N_{0 \min}} = \frac{\ln 2}{N_r}, \quad \dots(3.13)$$

When $N_r \rightarrow \infty$, equation 3.12 reduces to

$$\frac{E_b}{N_{0 \min}} = \frac{\ln 2}{N_r - 1}, \quad \dots(3.14)$$

Compared with the interference-free, the above results suggest that interference degrade the capacity by increasing $E_b/N_{0 \min}$ and decreasing S_0 . For sufficiently large N_t , the capacity performance with a single interferer is similar to that of a channel with one less receive antenna operating in an interference-free environment.

When $\rho_I \rightarrow \infty$, and $N_r \geq 2$, equation 3.12 reduces to

$$\frac{E_b}{N_{0 \min}} = \frac{\ln 2}{N_r - 1}, \quad \dots(3.15)$$

Intriguingly, these results coincide with the case $N_r \rightarrow \infty$. One is applicable for large N_r but arbitrary interference power ρ_I , while the other is valid for large ρ_I but arbitrary N_r .

MIMO RAYLEIGH CHANNELS:

For MIMO Rayleigh channels with a single interferer, we have

$$\frac{E_b}{N_{0\min}} = \frac{\ln 2}{N_r - 1 + A_0}, \quad (3.16)$$

This shows that the number of transmit antennas affects the capacity performance through S_0 .

Following corresponds to the case for MIMO Rayleigh channels without interference.

$$\frac{E_b}{N_{0\min}} = \frac{\ln 2}{N_r}, \quad (3.17)$$

When $N_r \rightarrow \infty$, we have

$$\frac{E_b}{N_{0\min}} = \frac{\ln 2}{N_r - 1}, \quad (3.18)$$

When $\rho_I \rightarrow \infty$, and $N_r \geq 2$, we have

$$\frac{E_b}{N_{0\min}} = \frac{\ln 2}{N_r - 1}, \quad (3.19)$$

Similar to the case of rank-one mean MIMO Rician channels with a large K , it is observed that the results for $N_r \rightarrow \infty$ and $\rho_I \rightarrow \infty$ coincide.

MIMO RAYLEIGH PRODUCT CHANNELS:

For MIMO Rayleigh-product channels with a single interferer, we have

$$\frac{E_b}{N_{0\min}} = \frac{\ln 2}{N_r - 1 + A_0}, \quad (3.20)$$

This shows that the $E_b/N_{0\min}$ for MIMO Rayleigh-product channels is the same as that for MIMO Rician fading channels. Moreover, it indicates that the Rayleigh-product channel converges to a Rayleigh fading channel when $N_s \rightarrow \infty$.

The following asymptotic cases are looked at to gain further understanding.

When $\rho_I \rightarrow 0$, we have

$$\frac{E_b}{N_{0\min}} = \frac{\ln 2}{N_r}, \quad (3.21)$$

This scenario corresponds to the interference-free case for Rayleigh-product channels. When $N_r \rightarrow \infty$, we have

$$\frac{E_b}{N_{0\min}} = \frac{\ln 2}{N_r - 1}, \quad (3.22)$$

When $\rho_I \rightarrow 0$ and $N_r \geq 2$, it can be easily shown that $E_b/N_{0\min}$ given by (3.22). In other words, the result for $N_r \rightarrow \infty$, and $\rho \rightarrow \infty$ coincide.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

Fig 1: SNR capacity Vs transmit E_b/N_0 for Rician channel with Rician factor, $K=1$ & $\rho_I=0$ dB

In Fig. 1, SNR capacity is plotted for 2 transmitters and different receivers with $K=1$. It is observed that the capacity is increased as the no. of receivers increased. Here, the dominant path is one and interference to noise ratio is 0dB.

Fig. 2, shows the capacity of 3x2 MIMO Rician channel for different Rician K factor. The graph indicates that as K increases from 1 to 10, the capacity performance increases with different E_b/N_0 values. Here the dominant paths are two and interference to noise ratio is 0dB.

Fig 2: SNR capacity Vs transmit E_b/N_0 for Rician channel with $n_t=2$, $n_r=3$ & $\rho_I=0$ dB

Fig 3: SNR capacity Vs transmit E_b/N_0 for Rician channel with $\rho_I=0$ dB and $k=1$

Fig. 3, is plotted for different combination of transmitters and receivers i.e., (3x2, 4x2, 4x4) MIMO Rician channels with $k=1$ and $\rho_i=0$ dB. It is observed that the capacity performance is good for 4x4 MIMO channel than 3x2 and 4x2 channels by increase in E_b/N_0 . Here the dominant paths are two.

Fig. 4: SNR capacity Vs transmit E_b/N_0 for Rayleigh channel with $\rho_i=0$ dB

In Fig. 4, SNR capacity is plotted for 2 transmitters and different receivers for Rayleigh fading channel. It is observed that the capacity is increased as the no. of receivers increased. Here the interference to noise ratio is 0dB.

Fig 5: SNR capacity Vs transmit E_b/N_0 for Rayleigh product channel with $\rho_i=0$ dB & number of scatterers, $n_s=100$.

In Fig. 5, SNR capacity is plotted for 2 transmitters and different receivers for Rayleigh product channel. It is observed that the capacity is increased as the no. of receivers increased. Here, the interference to noise ratio is 0dB.

V. CONCLUSION

Capacity of MIMO systems operating over Rician fading and Rayleigh product channels in the presence of a single interferer and noise in low SNR system has been discussed. Results of Minimum energy per information for MIMO Rician fading, Rayleigh fading and Rayleigh product channels shown. Rician factor K affects the channel capacity for MIMO Rician channels, and capacity is also increased as the number of receivers increased.

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Lifetime Enhancement Routing Algorithm for Mobile Ad Hoc Networks

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Abstract: Mobile ad hoc networks (MANETs) are formed by mobile nodes without the support of fixed infrastructure. In the MANET, each node performs as a host as well as host to forward the data packets. The nodes are adjustable based on the local environments. MANETs are used in many situations where temporary network connection is needed. In this paper, investigates the problem of lifetime enhancement of mobile nodes in mobile ad hoc networks (MANETs). Here, the MANETs are used in temporary network connections. The MANETs are formed by mobile nodes without the support of fixed infrastructure. Ad Hoc On-Demand Distance Vector (AODV) Routing Protocol is used. The model has been simulated using MATLAB. AODV routing protocol is a reactive routing protocol which enables multi-hop routing between participating mobile nodes in an ad-hoc network. AODV increases the packet delivery ratio with increase in power and decrease in number of hops.

Keywords- AODV, Reactive Routing Protocol, Routing Protocols, True time, Wireless Ad-Hoc Network.

I.INTRODUCTION

Wireless ad hoc networks are self-organized groups of mobile devices that are able to communicate with each other using a wireless physical medium. One of the key design constraints in mobile ad hoc networks (MANETs) is that they are power controlled. A critical issue in *ad hoc* networks is how to maintain network activities in order to achieve maximum lifespan despite energy constraints. Hence, every effort is to be focused towards reducing power. More specifically, network lifetime is a key design metric in MANETs. Since every node has to perform the functions of a router, if some nodes die early due to lack of energy, it will not be possible for other nodes to communicate with each other. Hence, the network will get disconnected and the network lifetime will be adversely affected. The aim of power management of routing protocols is to prolong the lifetime of the entire network and to increase the delivery rate of transactions carried out through the mobile network. Since nodes have limited battery capacity, if a node runs out of battery, this will affect its ability to route the traffic of other nodes and thus affecting negatively the overall network lifetime. For protocols that maximize the overall network lifetime, the main focus is to distribute the energy

consumption among all nodes in a balanced manner. If the route with maximal energy saving is always chosen for delivery, the subset of nodes along this route will be over utilized and therefore drained in a short period of time which may lead to network partitioning. In order to use the energy of nodes in a fairer manner, the traffic must be routed through the nodes that have enough remaining energy, not only by selecting routes simply based on energy consumed. Different approaches were presented to fulfill this target. "Load distribution" and "transmission power control" are two approaches to minimize the communication of energy of the network nodes. The load distribution protocol avoids the choice of exhausted nodes at the route selection phase, thus balances the use of energy among nodes and maximizing the network lifetime. In transmission power control approach, there is a balance between the choice of a high transmission power that lead to increase in the range of signal transmission thus reducing the number of hops and lower power levels that reduces the interference on the expense of network connectivity.

II.AODV (Ad Hoc On-Demand Distance Vector)

AODV activates the multiple hops routing between participating mobile nodes to establish. This AODV is a reactive routing protocol. One of the features is the use of a destination sequence number for each routing table entry. This is based on the distance vector algorithm. AODV deals with routing table. Every node has a routing table. When a node knows the destination route, it sends the route reply to the source node. It enters the

- Destination IP Address
- Prefix Size
- Destination Sequence Number
- Next Hop IP Address
- Lifetime
- Hop Count
- Network Interface
- Routing flags

Other state and routing flags (e.g., valid, invalid)

AODV uses diverse messages to determine and maintain links. When a node wants to try and get a route to another node, it broadcasts a Route Request (RREQ) to all its neighbors. The RREQ propagates through the network until it reaches the destination or a node with a fresh enough route to the destination. When a RREQ reaches a receiving node, the destination route is made available by unicasting a RREP back to the sender route. The path through which the RREQ propagates from source to destination is shown in Figure 1 in given network.

Figure1 Propagation RREQ

A node generates a RREP if it is itself the destination. It has an active route to the destination. As the RREP propagates back to the source node, intermediate nodes update their routing tables (in the direction of the destination node). The RREP propagates from destination to source as shown in Figure 2.

Figure2 Propagation RREP

The algorithm uses hello messages that are broadcasted periodically to the immediate neighbors. These hello messages ensure continued presence of the node and neighbors using routes through the broadcasting node will carry on to mark the routes as valid. If hello messages stop coming from a particular node, the neighbor can assume that the node has moved away and mark that link as broken and sends link failure notification Route Error (RRER) message to all set of nodes.

III.ROUTE DISCOVERY

A node broadcasts a RREQ when it wants a route to a destination and does not have a route to the destination and does not have one existing. This can happen if the route to the destination is unknown. After broadcasting a RREQ. Node waits for RREP, the node may rebroadcast the RREQ or assume that there is no route to the destination If the reply is not acknowledged within a time,. The node also creates a temporary reverse route to the Source IP Address in its routing table with next hop equal to the IP address field of the neighboring node that sent the broadcast RREQ. This is done to keep track of a route back to the original node making the request and can be used for RREP to find its way back to the requesting node. The route is momentary in the sense that if is valid for a much shorter time, than an actual route entry [4-5]. When the RREQ reaches a node that either is the destination or a node with a valid route to the destination, a RREP is generated and unicasted back to the requesting node. While this RREP is forwarded, a route is established to the destination and when the RREP reaches the source node, there present a route from the source to the destination.

A. Forward path setup

When a broadcast RREQ packet arrives at a node having a route to the destination, the reverse path will be used for sending a RREP message. While transmitting this RREP message the forward path is setting up. One can say that this forward path is reverse to the reverse path. The moment the forward path as shown in figure 3 is established the data transmission can be started. Data packets waiting to be transmitted are buffered locally and transmitted in a FIFO queue when a route is set up. After a RREP was forwarded by a node, it can receive another RREP. This new RREP will be either discarded or forwarded, depending on its destination sequence number:

- If the new RREP has a greater destination sequence number, then the route should be restructured, and RREP is forwarded.
- If the destination sequence numbers in old and new RREPs are the same, but the new RREP has a lesser hop count, this new RREP should be chosen and forwarded.
- Otherwise all later incoming RREPs will be discarded.

Figure3 Forward path setup

The path for route request and route reply is as shown in following figure4 from source to destination. S is source for communication with D as destination.

Figure4 Route Discovery Process

IV. ROUTE MAINTENANCE

As the node finds that the neighboring node is invalid to transmit information the routing entry is removed and a link failure message is sent by sending Route Error (RERR) message to the neighboring nodes using the route. The same procedure is repeated by the nodes that received error messages. The affected sources that choose either requesting a new route by sending a new RREQ or stop sending data receive the messages eventually. Each node can know about their neighborhood by local broadcasts called HELLO messages. Each active nodes broadcast them periodically. Nodes neighbors are the nodes where it can communicate directly. AODV uses periodic HELLO messages to inform the neighbors that the link is still alive though it is a reactive protocol. As HELLO messages are broadcasted with TTL=1 these messages will not be forwarded. When a node receives the HELLO message the corresponding lifetime of the neighbor gets refreshed in the routing table. To optimize the ratio of response time and local changes in a network the local connectivity management should be distinguished from the general topology management. The supporting route maintenance by the HELLO messages has limited range. So any overhead is not caused by them in the network. The hello message is broadcasted in the HELLOINTERVAL. If in delete period no hello messages are identified from neighbor nodes then there is a link failure. In such case the

local route repair is initiated in next hop. After sometime the error is propagated to source and destination. Each entry is based on node invalidation. Certain time interval of AODV is given in the following table.

Parameters	Value
Hello interval	0 to 1s
Active Route timeout	3s
Allowed Hello loss	2
Transmission power	-8 to -2db
Threshold	-50 to -48 db

Table1 AODV Parameters

V. TRUETIME

TrueTime is a Matlab/Simulink-based simulator for networked and embedded control systems. The simulator consists of a Simulink block library and a compilation of MEX files, kernel block simulates a real-time kernel executing user-defined tasks and interrupt handlers. The various network kernel blocks permit nodes to communicate over simulated wired or wireless networks. The latest release, TrueTime 1.5, also features a couple of standalone network interface blocks that makes it simpler to develop networked control simulations. A TrueTime simulation is programmed in much the same way as a real embedded system. The application is written in Matlab code or in C++. The main difference from real programming is that the execution/transmission times must be specified by the developer. This approach makes TrueTime a very flexible co-simulation tool. Also, the step from simulation code to production code is not that large.

A. Software requirements for TRUETIME:

1. It currently supports MATLAB 7.x (R14 and later) with SIMULINK 6.x and MATLAB 6.5.1 (R13.1) with SIMULINK 5.1.
2. A C++ compiler is required to run TRUETIME in the C++ version.
3. For the MATLAB version, pre-compiled files are provided in the archive that is downloaded from the TRUETIME web site.
4. The following compilers are currently supported (it may, of course, also work using other compilers):
 - a) Visual Studio C++ 7.0 (for all supported Matlab versions) for Windows
 - b) gcc, g++ - GNU project C and C++ Compiler for LINUX and UNIX

VI. SIMULATION MODEL AODV

The simulation results were carried out using TrueTime toolbox of MATLAB. Wireless Ad-Hoc network with random topology and 7 nodes was simulated. The model structure of AODV was as shown in Fig. 5. The Fig. 6 shows the random topology for wireless Ad-hoc network used for simulation.

Figure5 SIMULINK Model AODV

Figure6 Node Topology

VII. SIMULATION RESULTS

The performance of routing protocol is evaluated using several performance metrics to calculate best path for routing the packet to its destination. These metrics are a standard measurement that could be number of hops, which is used by the routing algorithm to determine the optimal path for the packet to its destination. This performance metrics are

1) *Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR)*: The ratio of the number of data packets received by the receivers verses the Number of data packets supposed to be received. This number presents the effectiveness of a protocol.

2) *End-to-end delay*: End-to-end delay indicates how long it took for a packet to travel from the source to the receiver.

Figure7 AODV Simulation Results

Figure8 Packet Delivery Ratio v/s Power

Figure9 End to End Delay v/s. Power

The Fig. 7 shows MATLAB results which show the path of communication, time at which the various message are sent like data packets, hello messages, node expiry time and status of messages. The performance metrics are evaluated with power varied. The results of performance metrics are as shown in Fig 8 and Fig 9

VIII. CONCLUSION

The packet delivery ratio which is ratio of packets sent to the total packets received increases with increase in power. With increase in amount of power with which the packet is sent, the packet delivery ratio increase with decrease in number of hops. Also the end to end delay which is the delay between the packets sent and received decreases with increase in power. Thus the packet delivery ratio increases and end to end delay decreases with increase in power. The number of hops decreases with increase in power.

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Spectral Subtractive Techniques for Speech Enhancement: A Review

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Abstract— Speech signal enhancement aims to improve quality, intelligibility and sometimes the duo. Spectral subtraction methods are among several existing methods for enhancing speech signals. This paper presents an overview of the commonly used spectral subtraction algorithm which is a quality improvement algorithm and its variants for the enhancement of corrupted speech to reduce noise and speech distortion. Spectral subtractive methods are computationally less intensive and hence can be used in real time applications. The problem of musical noise is an associated artifact and hence various proposed methods to alleviate the problem of musical noise are quoted in this paper. The source of degradation assumed is additive noise.

Keywords—Speech Enhancement, Spectral Subtraction, Oversubtraction, Non-linear Spectral Subtraction, ultriband Spectral Subtraction, Adaptive Gain Averaging, MMSE Spectral Subtraction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Speech is corrupted in real time operating conditions by different kinds of noise affecting the intelligibility and quality which is to compensating by resorting to an appropriate enhancement method. Speech enhancement is a crucial process to be employed to improve the quality while preserving the intelligibility of the speech. Speech enhancement can be a preprocessing stage either for automatic speech recognition, speaker recognition, speech coding and also for human listening purposes. The source of degradation can be background noise, reverberation, competing talker speech. The basic spectral subtraction method [1] being a first of its kind method is being discussed because of its ease of implementation and needs same computation as high-speed convolution [2]. Spectral subtraction methods deal with amplitude spectra only and ignore the phase because ear is less sensitive to changes in phase than amplitude counterparts. Spectral subtraction and several variants of it for enhancement of speech are available in literature, which are presented in this paper. Section 2 deals with basic spectral subtraction method, section 3 deals with variants of spectral subtraction method and section 4 presents the simulation and results of four methods and Section 5 presents a brief summary of the review.

II. BASIC SPECTRAL SUBTRACTION METHOD

The spectral-subtractive algorithm belongs to the initial class of algorithms to reduce noise. Spectral subtraction has been shown to be an effective approach for reducing ambient acoustic noise in order to improve the intelligibility and quality of digitally compressed speech [1]. Spectral subtraction (SS) can be implemented in terms of a non-stationary, multiplicative, frequency domain filter which changes with the time varying spectral characteristics of the speech [1, 2]. An additive noise model is assumed represented by:

$$y(n) = x(n) + d(n) \quad \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

with frequency counterpart as follows:

$$Y(k) = X(k) + D(k) \quad \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

which mathematically represents the speech corrupted by additive noise is represented as sum of clean speech and noise [2]. $y(n)$, $x(n)$, $d(n)$ are noisy speech, clean speech and additive noise respectively. The spectrum of enhanced speech is obtained as [1]:

$$|\hat{X}(k)| = |Y(k)| - |\hat{D}(k)| \quad \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

where $|\hat{D}(k)|$ represents the average magnitude of spectrum of noise. The inverse FFT of the $|\hat{X}(k)|$ using phase of noisy speech is used to get the enhanced signal. If the estimate of the noise spectrum is inaccurate, $|\hat{X}(k)|$ obtained by equation 3 may result in negative values. As the magnitude spectrum should always be positive half-wave rectification is opted as one of the method which sets negative spectral values to zero which can be represented as follows:

$$|\hat{X}(k)| = \begin{cases} |Y(k)| - |\hat{D}(k)| & \text{if } |Y(k)| > |\hat{D}(k)| \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

This nonlinear operation creates isolated spectral peaks at random frequency locations resulting in sounds as tones with frequencies which vary from frame to frame resulting in a noise called musical noise [3]. As autocorrelation function and power spectral density form a Fourier transformable pair, subtraction could be performed in correlation domain [4].

III.VARIANTS OF SPECTRAL SUBTRACTION METHOD

a) Power spectral subtraction:

If $d(n)$ is assumed to be zero mean and uncorrelated with clean speech then it is possible to express power spectral subtraction in terms of short time power spectra as follows:

$$|\hat{X}_i(k)|^2 = |Y_i(k)|^2 - |\hat{D}_i(k)|^2 \quad \dots\dots (5)$$

b) Spectral subtraction using oversubtraction:

To reduce musical noise Boll [1] proposed to set the negative spectral values to a minimum value specified by (6) referred to spectral flooring as follows:

$$|\hat{X}_i(k)| = \begin{cases} |Y(k) - \hat{D}(k)| & \text{if } |Y(k) - \hat{D}(k)| > \beta |\hat{D}(k)| \\ \beta |\hat{D}(k)| & \text{for } j=i-1, i, i+1 \text{ otherwise} \end{cases} \quad \dots(6)$$

(6) needs access to future spectra i.e. for $j = i+1$ this approach may not be suitable for real-time application. Berouti et al. [3] proposed a method of subtracting an overestimate of noise spectrum while spectral flooring as follows:

$$|\hat{X}_i(k)|^2 = \begin{cases} |Y_i(k)|^2 - \alpha |\hat{D}_i(k)|^2 & \text{if } |Y_i(k)|^2 - \alpha |\hat{D}_i(k)|^2 > \beta |\hat{D}_i(k)|^2 \\ \beta |\hat{D}_i(k)|^2 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad \dots(7)$$

where $\alpha(\alpha \geq 1)$ and $\beta (0 \leq \beta \leq 1)$ are over subtraction and spectral floor parameters respectively. α a SNR dependent parameter in frame was suggested to be [3]:

$$\alpha = \alpha_0 - \frac{3}{20} SNR, \quad -5\text{dB} \leq SNR \leq 20 \text{ dB} \quad \dots (8)$$

where α_0 is required value of SNR at 0dB. The residual noise level, the musical noise level and the amount of speech distortion are controlled mainly by the parameters α_0 and β . The larger the value of α more over subtraction of components with smaller SNR occurs and thus the parameter α is to be chosen carefully to reduce the effects of musical noise and speech distortion in the above (SS Berouti) method.

c) Non-linear Spectral Subtraction:

As noise may not affect all the spectral components uniformly, frequency subtraction factor based on frequency dependent SNR in frame proposed in [6]. Larger values are subtracted at frequencies with low SNR levels, and smaller values are subtracted at frequencies with high SNR levels is the idea used in non-linear spectral subtraction method (NSS). The subtraction rule is as follows:

$$|\hat{X}(k)| = \begin{cases} |Y(k) - \alpha(k)N(k)| & \text{if } |Y(k) - \alpha(k)N(k)| > \beta |D(k)| \\ \beta |D(k)| & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad \dots(9)$$

where β is the spectral floor and $|Y(k)|$ and $|D(k)|$ are smoothed estimates of noisy speech and noise

respectively. $\alpha(k)$ is frequency dependent subtraction factor and $N(k)$ is nonlinear function of noise [6]. $N(k)$ is computed over past noise magnitude spectra of 40 frames using the following relation:

$$N(k) = \max(|\hat{D}_j(k)|) \text{ for } i-40 \leq j \leq i \quad \dots (10)$$

$\alpha(k)$ a nonlinear function [22] can be expressed in the following expression:

$$\alpha(k) = \frac{1}{1 + \gamma \rho(k)} \quad \dots(11)$$

γ being the scaling factor and $\rho(k) = \frac{|Y(k)|}{|D(k)|}$ (12)

d) Multiband Spectral Subtraction:

A modification was proposed by Kamath and Louizou [7] who proposed the division of speech into several no overlapping bands, calculate over subtraction factor for each band separately and to apply spectral subtraction independently in each band. Clean speech spectrum is estimated using:

$$|\hat{X}_i(k)|^2 = |Y_i(k)|^2 - \alpha_i \delta_i |D_i(k)|^2 \quad b_i \leq k \leq e_i \quad \dots (13)$$

b_i is beginning frequency bin, e_i is the ending frequency bin of i^{th} frequency band, α_i represents the over subtraction factor to be used in the i^{th} band and δ_i is the tweaking factor in i^{th} band.

$$\alpha_i = \begin{cases} 5 & SNR_i < -5 \\ 4 - \frac{3}{20} SNR_i & -5 < SNR_i < 20 \\ 1 & SNR_i > 20 \end{cases} \quad \dots(14)$$

SNR_i is the segmental SNR of i^{th} frequency band.

Spectral flooring is implemented using the relation:

$$|\hat{X}_i(k)|^2 = \begin{cases} |\hat{X}_i(k)|^2 & \text{if } |\hat{X}_i(k)|^2 > 0 \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad \dots (15)$$

δ_i values provide more control within each band and are empirically determined and set to

$$\delta_i = \begin{cases} 1 & f_i \leq 1\text{kHz} \\ 2.5 & 1\text{kHz} \leq f_i \leq \frac{F_s}{2} - 2\text{kHz} \\ 1.5 & f_i \geq \frac{F_s}{2} - 2\text{kHz} \end{cases} \quad \dots (16)$$

In adverse conditions the performance of the above mentioned method was still low and several perceptual based method were proposed by Virag [8] where the spectral subtraction parameters in (7) are calculated based on masking threshold parameters. These parameters are calculated using a nonlinear function as follows:

$$\alpha(k) = F_\alpha[\alpha_{\min}, \alpha_{\max}, T(k)] \quad \dots (17)$$

$$\beta(k) = F_\beta[\beta_{\min}, \beta_{\max}, T(k)] \quad \dots (18)$$

where $T(k)$ represents masking threshold and $\alpha_{\min} = 1$, $\alpha_{\max} = 6$, $\beta_{\min} = 0$, $\beta_{\max} = 0.02$. This method proposes to reduce noise below the auditory threshold instead of entire noise. Residual noise is minimized but at the cost of added computational complexity.

e) Adaptive Gain Averaging:

The problems of variability in gain function and large variance in spectral estimates are responsible for musical noise in spectral subtractive algorithms. These problems were addressed by Gustafsson et al. [9] by dividing current frame into smaller frames and an average of spectra of sub frames is used to reduce the variance of the spectrum and to smooth the gain function over time using adaptive averaging in adaptive gain averaging spectral subtraction (AGASS) method.

The gain function is given as follows [5]:

$$G_i^{(M)}(k) = 1 - 0.7 \frac{|\hat{D}_i^{(M)}(k)|}{|\bar{Y}_i^{(M)}(k)|} \dots (19)$$

$|\hat{D}_i^{(M)}(k)|$ is the estimated noise spectrum magnitude updated during speech absent segments of speech.

The gain function variability is reduced by averaging $G_i^{(M)}(k)$:

$$\bar{G}_i^{(M)}(k) = a_i \bar{G}_{i-1}^{(M)}(k) + (1 - a_i) G_i^{(M)}(k) \dots (20)$$

a_i is the adaptive averaging parameter computed as:

$$a_i = \begin{cases} 0.8a_{i-1} + (1 - 0.8)(1 - \beta_i) & \text{if } a_{i-1} < (1 - \beta_i) \\ (1 - \beta_i) & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases} \dots (21)$$

Where β_i is measure of spectral discrepancy given as:

$$\beta_i = \min \left\{ \frac{\sum_{k=0}^{M-1} \left| |\bar{Y}_i^{(M)}(k)| - |\hat{D}_i^{(M)}(k)| \right|}{\sum_{k=0}^{M-1} |\hat{D}_i^{(M)}(k)|}, 1 \right\} \dots (22)$$

Spectrum of enhanced speech is expressed as:

$$\hat{X}_i^{(N)}(k) = \bar{G}_i^{(N)}(k) \cdot Y_i^{(N)}(k) \dots (23)$$

f) MMSE spectral subtraction:

The values of parameters used in many tests are empirically Adjusted to the values specified in them based on listening tests and were not optimized in some sense. A method was proposed in [10], where the parameters are derived based on parametric formulation of spectral subtraction.

The optimal estimator has the form [5]:

$$|\hat{X}(k)| = \left\{ \frac{\xi^p(k)}{\delta_p + \xi^p(k)} \left[|Y(k)|^p - |\hat{D}(k)|^p \right] \right\}^{1/p} \dots (24)$$

where $\xi(k) = \frac{E \left[|X_p(k)|^2 \right]}{E \left[|D(k)|^2 \right]} \dots (25)$

and $|X_p(k)|$ is clean speech spectrum.

j) Other Modifications:

An algorithm called Extended Spectral subtraction (ESS) to update the noise characteristics even during speech sequences without the need of VAD was proposed by Pavel Sovka et al. [11,12] which is a combination of spectral subtraction and adaptive Wiener filtering. Noise is estimated using Wiener filtering which is subtracted from noisy speech signal.

A method was proposed in [13,14] to decompose speech into voiced, unvoiced sections and to extract the stochastic content voiced speech was high-pass

filtered. To reduce the spectral variance multi-windowed spectral estimation technique is adapted to estimate the spectrum of unvoiced and voiced speech. Voiced component is low pass filtered to obtain its deterministic component and a single window is used to estimate its spectrum. Standard spectral subtraction was applied to enhance speech. Several other variants of spectral subtraction are available; to quote a few are the following. Kamrul Hasan et al. [15] proposed a method to find a self-adaptive averaging factor to estimate the *a priori* SNR. Yi Hu and Louizou [16] proposed a frequency domain estimator which used wavelet thresholded multi-taper spectra rather than FFT based spectra and proved optimal which included psycho-acoustic model.

Spectral smoothing, comb filtering and formant intensification were used as supplements to spectral subtraction suggested by Hu et al. [17]. Spectral smoothing and comb filtering improved speech quality for speech corrupted by AWGN; formant intensification improved the suppression of musical noise while preserving the formant characteristics. Speech and noise signals are assumed to be uncorrelated in the above mentioned methods which may not be true hence Hu et al. [18] proposed a method called cross correlation spectral subtraction method to take into account the correlation existing between speech and noise. A modified spectral subtraction method with wavelet transform was proposed by in [19] known as wavelet based spectral subtraction

IV. SIMULATION AND RESULTS

Spectral subtraction methods by Boll et al., Berouti et al., Multiband spectral subtraction, Non-Linear Spectral Subtraction and Adaptive gain averaging methods of spectral subtraction are simulated in MATLAB and the objective measures to evaluate speech quality and intelligibility are obtained for a speech signal corrupted by babble noise with 10dB SNR from NOIZEUS data base. The spectrograms and objective measures PESQ, LLR and NCM for the above mentioned algorithms are shown in Figure.1 and Table.1 which follow.

Table I
 Quality and Intelligibility Evaluation Measures

Method	Quality Evaluation Measure			Intelligibility Evaluation Measure
	Raw PESQ	MOS-PESQ	LLR	NCM
SS Boll	2.45	2.08	0.674	0.9299
Power SS	2.38	1.99	0.7034	0.9223
SS Berouti	2.49	2.12	0.686	0.9468
NSS	2.40	2.02	0.8120	0.8971
MBSS	2.63	2.30	0.653	0.9315
AGASS	2.5	2.2	0.711	0.9171
MMSE SS	2.39	2	0.8603	0.8029

Fig.1 Speech signal and Spectrograms

V.CONCLUSION

In this paper a brief review of spectral subtractive algorithms for speech enhancement has been made covering major variants of spectral subtraction technique. Musical noise is one of the artifacts of SS method and various methods quoted have been discussed which addressed this issue. Most of the variations were based on calculation of some over subtraction factor which control the amount of speech spectral distortion introduced by subtraction and to spectrally floor the values less than a specified minimum value. The residual noise and the amount of perceived musical noise are dependent on spectral floor value. The computation of oversubtraction factors are based on linear functions, non-linear functions and psycho-acoustic masking thresholds. Evaluation of spectral subtractive algorithm confirms that they improves quality but not intelligibility, sometimes it even decreases intelligibility. The spectral subtractive algorithm occasionally removes low-energy speech information which is the reason for the inability to improve intelligibility. The better the noise estimation the better would be the performance of the SS algorithm. Simulation results also indicate that there is a trade-off between quality and intelligibility of the enhanced signal.

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Hardware in Loop Simulation ECU Testing In Automotive

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Abstract: Hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) testing has become an essential verification step in the development of vehicle electronics and software systems. If the controller to be tested is implemented in the controller hardware, often denoted the electronic control unit (ECU), and the simulator has to run in real time. The aim of paper to present set up HiL simulation environment which make functional testing and development of ECU's possible, and realized hardware and software integrated with ECU's.

Keywords: Hardware in the Loop simulation, Electronic Control Unit

I. INTRODUCTION

Hardware-in-the-Loop process has existed for no more than 15 to 20 years. Its roots are found in the Aviation industry. The reason the use of a HIL process is becoming more prevalent in all industries is driven by two major factors: time to market and complexity. Hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) simulation is a technique that is used in the development and test of complex process systems. HIL simulation provides an effective platform by adding the complexity of the plant under control to the test platform. The complexity of the plant under control is included in test and development by adding a mathematical representation of all related dynamic systems. These mathematical representations are referred to as the "plant simulation." Another benefit of Hardware-In-the-Loop is that testing can be done without damaging equipment or endangering lives. For instance, potentially damaging conditions in an engine, such as over-temperature, can be simulated to test if the ECU can detect and report it.

II. HARDWARE IN LOOP SIMULATION SYSTEM

The Figure below shows that the plant is simulated and the ECU is real. The purpose of a Hardware-In-the-Loop system is to provide all of the electrical stimuli needed to fully exercise the ECU. In this way you "fool" the ECU into thinking that it is indeed connected to a real plant. The HIL simulation includes a mathematical model of the process and a hardware device/ECU you want to test, e.g. an industrial PID controller in our case.

a) HARDWARE SET UP

In hardware in loop simulation system consist of PXI and its modules and SCB cards and Electronic control unit and interface board.

b) NI PXI AND ITS CARDS

Accepts 3U PXI, PXI Express, Compact PCI ,and Compact PCI Express modules. The National Instruments PXIe-1065 18-slot chassis features a high bandwidth backplane to meet a wide range of high-performance test.NI PXIe-1065 provides a solution for high erchannel density systems.

SPECIFICATIONS:

1. AC Input Voltage range is 100 to 240 VAC
2. DC Output voltage rangeis Maximum combined +3.3 V, +5 V, and +12 V.
3. Maximum total power is 701.5 W.
4. The maximum power dissipated in the system slot should not exceed 140 W.
5. Pollution degree 2For indoor use only.
6. Operating Environment is 0 to 55 °C
7. Storage Environment is -40 to 71 °C.
8. Relative humidity range 5 to 95%.

III. NI PXI MODULES

a). SCB Cards

Serial control bus is used to connect the PXI and Electronic control unit

SPECIFICATIONS

1. Half-pitch DSUB 100-Pin / 0.050 series D-type connector
2. Suitable alternative to National Instruments SCB-100 connector block
3. Connector contains both latch blocks and #2-56 jack screws
4. Screw terminal for each data line plus 1 screw terminal for shield
5. Angled screw terminals provide compact, convenient wiring
6. Screw terminals accommodate wire sizes from 16AWG to 26AWG
7. Approximate dimensions: 3.75" x 4.5"
8. Rubber feet or DIN rail mount

b) INTERFACE BOARD

The 5-6K Interface Board provides a complete system development platform using evaluation

modules from the Data Acquisition Products Group. This board passes signals from TMS320C5000™ and TMS320C6000™ DSK platforms featuring the 80-pin daughter card connectors defined in the TMS320Cross-Platform Daughter card Interface (SPRA711), to a variety of analog-to-digital and digital-to-analog converters. When combined with sensor or amplifier boards, it can provide a complete data acquisition system for a variety of applications.

c) ELECTRONIC CONTROL UNIT

An ECU is basically made up of hardware and software (firmware). The hardware is basically made up of various electronic components on a PCB. The most important of these components is a microcontroller chip along with an EPROM or a Flash memory chip. The software (firmware) is a set of lower-level codes that runs in the microcontroller

The ECU is characterized by

1. many analog and digital I/O lines (low and high power)
2. Power device interface/control.
3. Different communication protocols (CAN, KWP-2000, etc.).
4. Large switching matrices for both low and high power signals.
5. high voltage tests
6. Intelligent communication interface adapters (standard or custom).
7. automatic fixture recognition and software sequence enable
8. Power device simulation.

IV. SOFTWARE SET UP

Developing a Hardware-in-the-Loop, High-Speed Simulation and Data Acquisition System for ECU Testing with the NI PXI Platform and NI LabVIEW Software.

SOFTWARE SYSTEM CONFIGURATION NI Measurement & Automation Explorer

1. Import CAN database files for testing.
2. Create and edit CAN channels easily.

NI LAB View Software:

3. FRONT PANEL

V. BLOCKDIAGRAM

1. LabVIEW is a graphical programming language that uses icons instead of lines of text to create applications.
2. NI LABVIEW program consist of front panel and block diagram.
3. Front panel consist of controls as inputs and indicators as outputs.
4. Block diagram consist logic of the program.

MATLAB State flow model

1. MATLAB State Flow models are used for analysis of internal signal analysis.

CANdb++:

1. In Candb++ consist the CAN signals and LIN signals for testing
2. CANdb++ files consist of vehicles nodes and messages and signal list.

VI. HILS TESTING AND SIMULATIONS

1. Analysis of specification files:CANdb++,MATLABfiles and Specification documents
2. Generation of Vector Canoe configuration file (.cfg) using CAN Database (.dbc)
3. GUI & Logic development for testing by using LabView Software.
4. Study of PXI and its modules for Hardware connection
5. Test case generation and Verification

VII. SIMULATION & RESULTS

VIII. CONCLUSION

After the ECU functions have been developed and implemented on the production ECU, they have to be tested thoroughly. With hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) simulation, you can easily cover all the different motor varieties and their ECUs. The ECU's environment (interacting components or even a whole system), is simulated.

This has several advantages:

1. Function tests are possible at an early development stage, even before all parts are available in reality.
2. Laboratory tests reduce time and cost and take place under controlled conditions.
3. Failures, and the ECU's behavior in what are normally dangerous situations, can be tested with no risk for the driver or the controlled machine.
4. The tests are reproducible and can be automated.

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A Low Power Analog Front end CMOS Circuitry for Acquiring Multichannel Signals

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Abstract — The design of an ultra low voltage, low power high speed 8 channel Analog multiplexer in 180nm CMOS technology is presented. A modified transmission gate using a dynamic threshold voltage MOSFET (DTMOS) is employed in the design. Sub threshold source coupled logic gate circuits were designed and implemented for achieving low power. The design is optimized with respect to critical requirements like short switching time, low power dissipation, good linearity and high dynamic range with an operating voltage of 0.4V. The ON and OFF resistances achieved are 27 ohms and 10Mohms respectively. The power dissipation obtained is around 165nW for a dynamic range of 1 μ V to 0.4V.

Keywords—Analog multiplexer; low power; high speed; body-bias;

I. INTRODUCTION

Advances in CMOS technology have led to a renewed interest in the design of basic functional units for digital systems. The use of integrated circuits in high performance computing, telecommunications, and consumer electronics has been growing at a very fast pace. This trend is expected to continue, with very important implications for power-efficient VLSI system designs[8]. Low power has emerged as a principal theme in today's electronics industry. The need for low power has caused a major paradigm shift where power dissipation has become as important consideration as performance and area.

The increasing demands on portable devices have motivated the development of CMOS Analog Multiplexer Integrated circuits. These portable devices require low power dissipation to maximize battery lifetime. Some low power applications, such as multichannel recorders, require the portable devices to operate at a low supply voltage with a small battery or environment energy, so the power and supply voltage constriction is a key issue for these designs [9]. However, due to standby power consideration, the threshold voltage of a metal oxide semiconductor

field effect transistor (MOSFET), which doesn't scale down with supply voltage of future standard CMOS technologies [10], makes a limitation for the CMOS low voltage designs.

An analog multiplexer is a key part in bio-medical applications MEAs (multi electrode arrays) are widely used for recording signals from human body. For analog multiplexer design, low voltage applications make the trade-off between switching frequency, signal losses and power consumption very challenging. Many efforts, have been made to develop low power Analog Multiplexer, but little research has been reported for ultra low voltage applications. In this work a 0.4 V fully integrated Analog Multiplexer is presented, meeting the requirement of both ultra low power applications and ultra low voltage applications. By using a modified transmission gate and forward body bias technology, the supply voltage is successfully reduced to 0.4 V. At such a low supply voltage, a good trade-off is made between power and other performances.

High-density arrays, comprising tens of electrodes driven for the development of multi-channel integrated circuits for selective recording of signals from the human body [1]. One of the important building blocks of such integrated circuits are analog multiplexers. A multiplexer is required to reduce the number of output data links as for a system comprising several tens of recording channels. It is not feasible technically and it would be expensive to transfer signals from each individual electrode to a data acquisition system via a separate cable.

In a typical measurement sequence the signals from all the channels are read out at very high speed to avoid any loss of signals through a multiplexer and routed to single output. The multiplexer in our design essentially built into a decoder and switches. Analog systems carry the signals in the form of physical variables such as voltage, currents which are continuing functions of time. The manipulation of these variables must often be carried out with high accuracy. Analog circuits continue to be used for

direct signal processing in some very high frequency or specialized applications. The development of VLSI technology has led to computers being pervasive in telecommunications, bio-medicine, robotics etc. since analog circuits are needed together with digital once in almost any complex chip most of the current analog circuits are CMOS circuits. CMOS switches have an excellent combination of attributes. In its most basic form, the MOSFET transistor is a voltage-controlled resistor. In the "on" state, its resistance can be less than 100 Ω, while in the "off" state, the resistance increases to several hundreds of mega ohms, with Pico-ampere leakage currents. CMOS technology is compatible with logic circuitry and can be densely packed in an IC [2]. Its fast switching characteristics are well controlled with minimum circuit parasitic. MOSFET transistors are bilateral, that is they can switch positive and negative voltages and conduct positive and negative currents with equal ease.

A transmission gate is used as an analog switch, it is defined as an electronic element that will selectively block or pass a signal level from the input to the output. This analog switch is comprised of a PMOS transistor and NMOS transistor shown in fig:1

Fig:1. Transmission gate

The control gates are biased in a complementary manner so that both transistors are either ON or OFF. When a signal is passed through this transmission gate there will drop in amplitude of the signal at the output. To overcome this problem and getting the original signal without any loss the transmission gate is modified as shown in Fig-2.

Fig: 2. Modified Transmission gate

II. BODY BIASING

Body effect refers to the change in the transistor threshold voltage (V_T) resulting from a voltage difference between the transistor source and body. Because the voltage difference between the source and body affects the V_T , the body can be thought of as a second gate that helps determine how the transistor turns on and off. The strength of the body effect is usually quantified by the body coefficient γ_B (gamma). The threshold voltage of MOSFET is well known as,

$$V_{Th} = V_{Th0} + \gamma_B(\sqrt{|2\phi_F + V_{SB}|} - (\sqrt{|2\phi_F|})) \dots (1)$$

where V_{Th0} is the threshold voltage when $V_{SB} = 0$, γ_B is the body-effect coefficient, ϕ_F is the bulk Fermi-potential, V_{SB} is the voltage between source and body. Thus, changing V_{SB} can modify V_{Th} , which can achieve a dynamic threshold voltage MOSFET (DTMOS). Usually, the junction between source and body is zero-biased or reverse-biased. To further improve performance with lower V_{Th} , forward-body-biased MOSFETs are also used in some circuits [12]. Here, we introduce this concept into low power Analog Multiplexer design. A 0.4 V forward body bias is used to make the transistors in strong inversion region. The MOSFETs with W/L of 30μm/0.18μm for P1, P2 and 15μm/0.18μm for N1, N2 are used in the Modified transmission gate is shown in Fig-3.

FIG 3: Transmission gate with dynamic body bias.

Strong body effect enables a variety of effective body biasing techniques, and these techniques were used effectively in older process generations. The body bias can be supplied from an external (off-chip) source or an internal (on-chip) source. In the on-chip approach, the design usually includes a charge pump circuit to generate a reverse body bias voltage and/or a voltage divider to generate a forward body bias voltage. Reverse body bias, which involves applying a negative body-to-source voltage to an n-channel transistor, raises the threshold voltage and thereby makes the transistor both slower and less leaky. Forward body bias, on the other hand, lowers the threshold voltage by applying a positive body-to-source voltage to an n-channel transistor and thereby makes the transistor both faster and leakier. The polarities of the applied bias described above are the opposite for a p-channel transistor.

III. SUB THRESHLOD SOURCE – COUPLED LOGIC CIRCUITS

The speed of operation in an SCL gate is inherently high as the logic operation mainly takes place in current domain. An NMOS source coupled differential pair transistors acts as a switch to steer the tail current I_{SS} to one of the output depending on the input logic. The Load resistor R_L converts this current to output voltage to drive the other SCL gates. In order to switch the input differential pair of the next stage the output voltage swing ($R_L I_{SS}$) should be adequately high. Based on this the drain source over drive voltage input pair should be larger than $\sqrt{2} n V_{dssat}$ when $V_{in} = 0$.

A source coupled logic based inverter/ buffer circuit is shown in FIG 4. More complex logic functions can be implemented by using a complex network of NMOS source coupled pairs as switching part [3,8]. The load resistance R_L is implemented by biasing the PMOS device in triode region and also NMOS switching network should be arranged in a proper way to achieve desired logic operation. The input logic level steers the tail bias current into one of the branch of the source coupled pair and this current is converted to voltage by the load resistance. The DC response of the SCL circuit is given in FIG 5.

Fig. 4. Source Coupled Logic-based inverter/buffer circuit.

FIG 5. DC response of the SCL circuit.

Operating In sub threshold region, the device trans conductance does not depend upon the device size but strongly depends on the temperature through

U_T . Hence by changing the design parameters it is not possible to change the transfer curve [7].

The voltage swing and the current required for charging and discharging the parasitic capacitances is less in SCL topology, when compared to the CMOS topology where the signal swing is equal to V_{DD} . The major advantage in SCL topology is reduction in signal swing. In order to make the tail bias current completely switch to one of the two output branches, the voltage swing at the input and output of a logic circuit should be high enough. The voltage swing at the output node is given as

$$V_{sw} = R_L \cdot I_{SS} \quad \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

should be adequately high to switch completely the input differential pair of the next stage. In other words SCL circuit can be used as a logic circuit with allowable noise margin if its gain is sufficiently high. The region of operation of the NMOS devices [12] gives the minimum allowable voltage swing at the output of each SCL gate.

$$= \begin{cases} \sqrt{2} \cdot n \cdot V_{D_{ssat}} & \text{in strong inveri} \\ 4 \cdot n \cdot U_T & \text{in subthresho} \end{cases} \quad \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

Where n is the sub threshold slope factor of NMOS devices. In the sub threshold region the required voltage swing can be as low as 150 mV at room temperature (assuming). This swing in the sub threshold region depends on the sub threshold slope factor and is independent of the threshold voltage of the NMOS switching devices.

A PMOS device is used as a load device when SCL gate is biased in sub threshold region as shown in FIG 4. Since all the devices are operated in sub threshold region the tail bias current can be reduced till comparable with leakage currents in the circuit.

The trans conductance of the input differential pair is given as

$$G_m = \frac{\partial I_{OUT}}{\partial V_{IN}} = \left(\frac{I_{SS}}{2n_n U_T} \right) \cdot \frac{1}{\cosh^2(V_{IN}/(2n_n U_T))} \quad \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

PMOS and NMOS Transistors can be combined as transmission gate for implementing analog switch which selectively allows or blocks the signal from input to output. The transistors are turned ON or OFF by applying control signals to the gates in complimentary manner and at the output a drop in signal amplitude is observed. This problem is eliminated by modifying the transmission gate by stacking transistors and the signal is passed to the output without any loss.

IV. MULTIPLEXER DESIGN

Using the concept of a shift register large number of multiplexers designed in the past. Synchronously triggered D-latches using external clock connected serially are used to build shift register. Each D-latch

enables one S & H circuit. The clock feed-through to the output line is the major disadvantage of this circuit. With each clock cycle glitches occur synchronously for every positive and negative clock edge. The proposed multiplexer design minimizes this problem.

Instead of setting the body bias just once either during design or at production test, the Dynamic body bias changes the body bias many times when the chip is operating. The temperature and aging effects are minimized by Dynamic body bias and also the power management modes for optimizing very low power operation are effectively utilized [3], [4].

A logic '1' on SEL signal at the gate of NMOS transistors will turn them ON and a complimentary SELBR connected to the gate of PMOS transistors will turn them ON and the applied signal is allowed to pass from IN to OUT. On the other hand when the SEL is at logic '0' and its complimentary SELBR will turn all the transistors OFF thereby blocking the signal from IN to OUT. The output will be forced into a high-impedance state during the transition period from ON to OFF where the junction capacitance will be charged to few millivolts.

A PMOS transistor connected as a pass transistor between the ground and the output node minimizes this problem. Whenever all the transistors are in OFF state then the PMOS transistor will be turned ON, forcing the output capacitor to discharge to ground.

The widths of the transistors are maintained in a ratio of 1:2 for NMOS to PMOS. The ON resistance R_{on} of the switch is

$$R_{on} = \frac{1}{\frac{q\mu C_{ox} W}{L}(V_{GS} - V_{TH})} \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

The value of the ON-resistance depends on the overdrive voltage, $V_{ov} = V_{gs} - V_{th}$ and on the aspect ratio, W/L through the transconductance parameter μC_{ox} .

An analog loss less multiplexer with eight channels has been designed using the modified circuit shown in FIG-3 for each channel. The channels are selected by three binary control inputs. The inhibit input is used to Enable or Disable the multiplexer. A low ON resistance of 27 ohms, high OFF resistance of 10Mohms, with very low leakage current in the order of Pico amperes were obtained with the analog transmission gate.

V. STSCL GATES & DECODER DESIGN.

The logic gate designed using STSCL is AND gate and the schematic is given in the FIG 6 below. The circuit is simulated and analyzed so that nominal

parameters of the STSCL can be used which will produce an optimum level output for the system.

Fig 6: Source coupled logic AND gate

This AND gate is modified into SCL NAND gate and a 3 to 8 decoder is implemented using this SCL AND gate. This is used to generate the select signals for each channel from three binary control inputs. The block diagram and the circuit diagram of the system is shown in FIGs 6(a) & (b).

Fig: 6(a). Block diagram of 8:1 MUX with Decoder

Fig 6(b) circuit diagram of 8:1MUX

VI. RESULTS

The dynamic body bias is provided by means of potential divider using poly resistors for both NMOS and PMOS devices. A capacitor of 100pf is used to reduce the leakage at the output. The Inverter and Buffer output of the SCL gate drives the NMOS and PMOS devices. The circuit is verified with input signals with different amplitudes and frequency. When the SCL output signal is a Logic 0 PMOS transistors are turned ON and the complementary Logic 1 is applied to NMOS transistors to turn ON which allows the signal to pass from IN to OUT. When the signal goes to Logic 1, all transistors are turned OFF blocking the input signal. During the transition period from ON to OFF the output will be forced into a high-impedance state where the junction capacitance will be charged to few millivolts. The Transmission gate response is given in Fig7 .

FIG 7. Response of Transmission gate.

To avoid this drawback, a PMOS transistor is used between the output node and ground as a pass transistor. When all the transistors are in OFF state, the PMOS transistor turns ON forcing the output capacitor to discharge to ground. The system is simulated by applying sinusoidal input of $1\mu\text{V}$ amplitude and the frequency is varied from 1Hz onwards up to 1kHz. The total current drawn by the circuit is around $0.413\mu\text{A}$ resulting in the total power consumption of 165 nW. The transient response of the 3to 8 Decoder and the eight channel multiplexer is shown in the figures 8(a) & 8(b). As the frequency of the input signal is increased the power dissipation increased.

FIG 8(a) 3 to 8 Decoder Response

The circuit is simulated by applying sinusoidal signals with an amplitude ranging from $1\mu\text{V}$ to maximum of 0.4V to each channel. The channels are selected by changing the input control signals of the decoder and the desired input is selected as shown in table-1

Table-1 (MUX channel selection)

INHIBIT	INPUTS	C	B	A	OUTPUT
L	X	X	X	X	L
H	10	L	L	L	10
H	11	L	L	H	11
H	12	L	H	L	12
H	13	L	H	H	13
H	14	H	L	L	14
H	15	H	L	H	15
H	16	H	H	L	16
H	17	H	H	H	17

The channel selection frequency is varied from DC to 10KHz. The output voltage is obtained without any distortion and the simulated results are shown in the figures 8(b).

FIG 8(b): Response of 8 channel Multiplexer.

VII. CONCLUSION

A low power wide range source coupled logic circuits operated in sub threshold region for switching analog signals is implemented in 180nm technology using CADENCE TOOLS. The required output voltage swing for proper logic operation is provided by using high resistance PMOS load devices. Transmission gate circuit was used to switch analog signals with amplitude ranging from $1\mu\text{V}$ onwards. The On and OFF resistance of the gate achieved was 27 ohms and 10M ohms respectively. The total power dissipated at a switching frequency of up to 10 KHz is around 165 nW. The STSCL circuit was used to implement 8 channel multiplexer for acquiring biomedical signals and the number of channels to be multiplexed can be increased further with suitable additional circuitry.

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Intelligent Gesture Controlled Wireless Robot

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Abstract– Today human machine interaction is moving away from mouse and pen and is becoming pervasive and much more compatible with the physical world. With each passing day the gap between machines and humans is being reduced with the introduction of new technologies to ease the standard of living. Gestures have played a vital role in diminishing this abyss Robots of the future should communicate with humans in a natural way. Hence, we are especially interested in hand motion based gesture interfaces. The purpose of this study was to present a reliable means for human-computer interfacing based on hand gestures made in three dimensions, which could be interpreted and adequately used in controlling a remote robot's movement. In this paper we discuss the development of a novel architecture of an intelligent robot working on wireless hand gesture control and not by the usual method of keypad. The locomotion of the robot is controlled by a MCU (Microcontroller Unit).

Keywords—Gesture control, Accelerometer

I. INTRODUCTION

Humans are anxiously working on finding new ways of interacting with machines. However, a major breakthrough was observed when gestures were used for this interaction. A gesture is a form of non verbal communication in which visible bodily actions communicate particular messages [1]. It comprises of sound, light variation or any type of body movement. Based upon the type of gestures, they have been captured via Acoustic (sound), Tactile (touch), Optical (light), Bionic and Motion Technologies through still camera, data glove, Bluetooth, infrared beams etc. Motion Technology has succeeded in drawing the attention of researchers from different parts of the world. The accelerometer circuit can be freely rotated in space, temporarily varying 3-dimensional signal data obtained from the 3-axis acceleration sensor [2]. Gestures control robots are extensively employed in human non-verbal communication which works with our hand gestures. This project enhances the work with the development of the wireless mechanism for control of the locomotion. This robot is mainly divided into two practical parts: 1. Transmitter – The gesture device. 2. Receiver – The Robot. They allow to express orders (eg. “stop”), mood state (eg. “victory” gesture), or to transmit some basic cardinal information (eg. “two”). Thus, it seems convenient that human-robot interfaces incorporate hand gesture recognition capabilities [6]. For instance, we would like to have

the possibility of transmitting simple orders to personal robots using hand gestures. The recognition of hand gestures requires both hand's detection and gesture's recognition. Both tasks are very challenging, mainly due to the variability of the possible hand gestures (signs), and because hands are complex, deformable objects (a hand has more than 25 degrees of freedom, considering fingers, wrist and elbow joints) that are very difficult to detect in dynamic environments with cluttered backgrounds and variable illumination. Several hand detection and hand gesture recognition systems have been proposed. This data is transmitted to a robot via Im324 Module. Further, it is processed by a microcontroller embedded on the robot for its desirable motions. In this context, a robot is an analogy for any machine that is controlled by man varying from a simple toy to heavy machinery. Robots have even replaced humans in performing various tasks that they are unable to perform due to physical disability, size limitation or extreme environments. Other than that the robot also has edge avoider modules on the front which helps to detect any sudden edge or stair when in the forward motion [4]. On detection the robot will automatically move backward and on two such consecutive edge detections the robot will be protected from accidents.

II. BLOCK DIAGRAM

The present structure of the project involves the method of controlling the wireless robot using hand gestures as commands. The control of the locomotion of the robot is presently done by microcontroller (MCU-8 Prototyping Platform). The following block diagram shows how the entire system works using the hand gesture method.

Fig. 1 Block diagram for the hand gesture method of control

As we can see from the above Fig. 1 the wireless robot works on the hand gestures. The MCU-8 prototyping platform is an open source prototyping platform which runs on embedded C structure. The platform is extremely powerful and easy to use with several inbuilt functions and a powerful microcontroller. Atmel 89s52 which is an 8-bit CISC-based microcontroller. It combines 8 KB of ISP flash memory with read-while-write capabilities, 32 general purpose I/O lines, 32 general purpose working registers, serial programmable USART, three timer/counters, internal and external interrupts, SPI serial port, programmable timer with internal oscillator, and five software selectable power saving modes.

HAND GESTURE MODULE

The hand gesture module has been prepared by using a triple axis accelerometer sensor (ADXL 335).

Fig. 2 Block diagram of Accelerometer sensor to Microcontroller module

The relatively low cost sensor provides the data for the orientation of the hand and therefore helps in recognizing the gestures. The accelerometer sensor senses the accelerating force (acceleration due to gravity) and thus gives a particular voltage for the x, y and z coordinate orientation. The data can be observed in integer format through the serial port of MCU on the computer's serial monitor and accordingly the orientations of the hand can be sorted out. The basic working block diagram of the accelerometer sensor is as shown in Fig. 2

Hand Position	Direction of Motion	Threshold values of ADXL335
	Forward	$x \geq 280 \ \& \ y \leq 280$ $\& \ z \leq 1230 \ \& \ z \geq 1295$
	Right	$x \leq 280 \ \& \ y \leq 280$ $\& \ z \leq 1230 \ \& \ z \geq 1295$
	Left	$x \leq 280 \ \& \ y \geq 280$ $\& \ z \leq 1230 \ \& \ z \geq 1295$
	Back	$x \leq 280 \ \& \ y \leq 280$ $\& \ z \leq 230$
	Stop	$x \leq 280 \ \& \ y \leq 280$ $\& \ z \geq 295$

Table 1 Accelerometer threshold values for different hand orientations.

The accelerometer sensor has specific values which are read as analog inputs by the microcontroller. The data obtained from the accelerometer for the various orientations of the hand gave us the readings to decide the threshold value for each x, y and z coordinate reading:

Fig. 3 Hand Gesture Module

RF TRANSMITTER & RECEIVER MODULE

The RF transmitter module has been used as per the purpose of making the gesture module completely wireless as in Fig. 3. We are using a 434 MHz WS-TX-01 module for the transmission. For a specific orientation of the hand the microcontroller unit on the hand decides the condition and a particular character are sent to the receiver module. For the receiver we are using a 434 MHz WS-RX-02 module which is a low cost receiver module as in Fig. 4. The receiver upon receiving the string sends the data to the microcontroller on the robot which in turn decides the case of the locomotion for the robot. The entire module is very effective for long distances as shown in the Table 2

Condition of test	Minimum range tested for efficient communication
Outdoor (without obstruction)	>60 (meters)
Indoors (with two wall obstruction)	>10 (meters)

Table 2 Range for hand gesture module

Fig. 4 RF Transmitter and Receiver Module

LOCOMOTION

For the locomotion of the robot we have used general DC motors as part of the model for the project. The motors are controlled by the bidirectional motor driver IC – L293D. The motor driver is connected through the microcontroller on the robot which sends the signal to the driver for the various conditions. For smooth turning during the motion of the robot we have used the method of PWM. The Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) allows the microcontroller to send the power to the motor driver in small packets over high frequency. The constant ON and OFF states actually helps to conduct smooth turning motion. The Fig. 5 shows an example graph of the PWM duty cycles for varying efficiency output supplies.

Fig. 5 PWM Duty Cycle

PROXIMITY DETECTION MODULE

As part of the proximity detection module for measuring closeness to the objects or the walls when the robot is in motion we have used ultrasonic sensors (HC-SR04). The ultrasonic module sends the analog voltage data to the microcontroller which effectively converts it into centimeters and hence the

distances are measured. Thus the microcontroller can command the motor driver to successfully avert the obstacles or walls during motion.

Fig. 6 IR Object Detection Module

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

All the components after integration give us the working skeleton model for the robot as in Fig. 7. The robot model works perfectly according to the hand gestures. The various gestures were tested and the outputs were studied to check if the right codes were transmitted. Therefore the project is seen to be working successfully with an artificial human-machine interaction system.

Fig. 7 Intelligent wireless gesture controlled robot

IV. APPLICATIONS

- Through the use of gesture recognition, remote control with the wave of a hand of various devices is possible.
- Gesture controlling is very helpful for handicapped and physically disabled people to achieve certain tasks, such as driving a vehicle.
- Gestures can be used to control interactions for entertainment purposes such as gaming to make the game player's experience more interactive or immersive.

V. CONCLUSION

Enormous amount of work has been done on gesture controlling of robots. In this paper, various methodologies have been analyzed and reviewed with their merits and demerits under

various operational and functional strategies. Thus, it can be concluded that features like user friendly interface, light weight and portability has overtaken the sophistication of technologies like programmable glove etc., making them obsolete. Although recent researches in this field have made wireless gesture controlling a ubiquitous phenomenon, it needs to acquire more focus in relevant areas of applications like home appliances, wheelchairs, artificial nurses, table top screens etc. in a collaborative manner.

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Comparative Study of Broadband RF Subharmonic Mixers in Submicron Technology

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Abstract—With the advancements in wireless technologies a lot of concern has been given for designing RF circuits and the designers are trying to introduce new topologies to achieve better outputs whether be at transmitter or receiver section of a communication system and this in-turn has led to the development of individual components of these systems. In this paper, a review of various broadband configurations of the mixer component of receiver/transmitter is given. In general first the fundamental mixers (diode-based and FET-based) are reviewed and later on subharmonic mixer configuration are discussed in detail.

Keywords— Gilbert cell mixer, subharmonic mixers, direct conversion receiver, CMOS technology, DSB noise figure, isolation, anti parallel diode pair (APDP).

I. INTRODUCTION

With the advent of Wireless LAN and Wireless Internet the operating radio frequency (RF) for data transfer has been further pushed from 2.4 GHz, 3.5GHz and now around 20 GHz. This has directly led to the demands of more sophisticated system level designs of RF circuit and the designers are evolving novel high frequency chip architecture and designs. In order to accommodate higher data-rate systems and to avoid the increasingly cluttered frequency spectrum in the low-GHz area, many new systems will need to move to higher frequencies where new challenges in circuit design are encountered [1]. To address this issue, new circuit topologies need to be demonstrated that become increasingly advantageous as the frequency of operation is increased. We know that RF down-conversion mixer is one of the most important part of the system because its performance directly impacts on the overall performance of the whole front end receiver. For the down conversion of the input RF signal at the mixer circuit with LO frequency operating at a fraction of input signal subharmonic mixers are widely used. Due to the absence of dc offsets in subharmonic mixers they have gained a greater interests in direct conversion receivers. Initially in direct conversion receivers the subharmonic mixers were diode based and

implemented in millimeter-wave technology but due to the recent advancements silicon bipolar technology they have found their applications at low frequencies also[12,13].

In this Paper, a review of various configuration of broadband mixer circuits are discussed with their topologies and performance matrices. First the fundamental mixers circuits i.e. diode-based and FET-based are discussed and then the subharmonic mixer with order 2 and 4 are discussed in detail.

II. FUNDAMENTAL MIXERS

A. Diode-based Mixers

Diodes are used extensively for designing mixer circuits. In the recent time, the diode-based mixers are generally designed for very-high frequencies applications where the use of complex transistor designs are difficult to implement due to their limited high-frequency performance.

B. FET-Based Mixers

There has been a lot of advancement in the field of mixer circuits with the introduction of field effect transistors. The most popular configuration of FET-based mixer circuit is the Gilbert-cell, shown in Fig 1 [2]. This mixer can be realised by using either bipolar transistors or field-effect transistors. Due to its double-balanced structure, the Gilbert cell results in several important advantages like excellent high port to port isolation, a reasonably high conversion gain.

Depending on how the current source is employed and due to the two stacked transistors, the Gilbert cell circuit is difficult to implement for low-supply and low- power applications. The noise figure of this configuration will be obviously high because of the increased number of active devices and resistors. If the mixer is to be implemented as a discrete component then a matching network will be required for obtaining a reasonable good input impedance. The matching network required can be

implemented using on-chip or off-chip capacitors or inductors or structures like transmission lines.

Fig 1: Gilbert cell mixer [2]

A recent example of Gilbert-cell using CMOS 0.13 μm technology is presented in [3]. In this work, a down-convert mixer operating in a wideband of 9 GHz to 50 GHz was designed. This circuit is the typical modification of Gilbert-cell as shown in Fig 1. Since the differential configuration of mixer was implemented here so on-chip transformers were used to convert the single ended RF and LO signals into differential signals. The source follower buffers at the output were used to drive 50 Ohm of load which can be either the measuring device or next part of receiver section. Now in this paper, the g_m of the RF transistors was increased by using current injection technique to improve the overall noise performance. This mixer resulted in conversion gain of >5 dB, RF-IF port to port isolation of over 40 dB, DSB noise figure of 16.4 dB and IIP3 was 1.2 dBm@20GHz in the said frequency range. The mixer circuit consumed 97 mW of power and had a relatively compact size at $0.5 \times 0.5 \text{ mm}^2$.

Another wideband CMOS Gilbert-cell mixer was presented in [4] which operated from 0.3 GHz to 25 GHz. In this paper, wideband input impedance matching was achieved using LC ladder matching networks. This circuit resulted in achieving a conversion gain of 10 dB from 10 GHz to 25 GHz, return loss was better than 7 dB from 3 GHz to 25 GHz. The power consumption of the mixer core circuit was 71 mW and port to port isolation was better than 25 dB. The area of the circuit was a bit larger i.e. $0.8 \times 1.0 \text{ mm}^2$ because inductors were integrated on-chip.

Although Gilbert cell configuration is the most common type of FET mixers but a large number of other configuration has also been introduced to realize a fundamental mixer. Consider the example of resistive FET mixer as shown in Fig 2. Resistive mixers are passive mixers that employ the nonlinearity of FET resistance for mixing process. In mixers FETs are generally biased in resistive or triode

region of operation and filters are used for RF and IF ports. This topology of mixer results in low DC power consumption and are comparatively simpler but they have significant conversion losses as compared to Gilbert cell mixers. In [5], an example of resistive FET mixer implemented on 90 nm CMOS silicon-on-insulator technology with an operating range of 26.5 GHz to 30 GHz is given. In this work, a parallel combination of LC filters was used for matching for both RF and IF ports as shown in Fig 2. The design resulted in a range of conversion gain between 9 dB @26.5 GHz to 13 dB @30 GHz with a LO power of 5 dBm. The SSB noise figure was 11.4 dB, port to port isolations were between 22 dB and 33 dB and an IIP3 of 12.7 dBm.

Fig 2: Resistive FET mixer[5]

III. SUBHARMONIC MIXERS

The major advantage of using direct conversion receivers is because there are no image frequency produced while frequency translation hence they eliminate the use of complex and expensive filtering techniques. Besides this in order to take advantage from lower LO frequency subharmonic mixer were introduced.

A. 2x Subharmonic Mixers

A large number of 2x SHM has been proposed (e.g. [6-11]). Majority of the SHM designs [6,7,9,10] have been implemented by the modification of the Gilbert-cell mixer to obtain a double frequency LO component for mixing with RF signal. The most common modification to Gilbert cell to subharmonic mixing is achieved by using the quadrature LO signal instead of differential signal. This is achieved by addition of another LO switching transistor stage [6-8]. Consider the example of circuit shown in Fig 3 where three level of transistors with the 0° and 180° LO signals are given to the middle LO-transistor level and 90° and 270° LO signals are given to gates of top LO-transistor. This topology doubles the LO frequency signal. Due to the use of three levels of transistors in this technique, a higher DC supply voltage is required than that of Gilbert cell and hence it may not be suitable for low-voltage applications.

The circuit shown in Fig 3 was introduced by [6]. In [6] the mixer was implemented in Si/SiGe HBT technology and a passive on-chip RC phase shifters for the generation of LO signals. The circuit operated from 1 GHz to 2 GHz with LO frequency ranging from 500 MHz to 1 GHz, with a DC supply voltage of 2.5V. This mixer circuit resulted in a conversion gain of 13.5 dB having a LO power of 10 dBm, a DSB noise figure of 10.4 dB and an IIP3 of 3.5 dBm.

Fig 3: Basic 2x subharmonic mixer circuit used in [6-9]

[7] also used the circuit shown in Fig 3 with a SiGe BiCMOS process. Here the circuit was designed for a frequency range of 5 GHz to 6 GHz with an IF of 50 MHz. In this work, polyphase filters were used to generate quadrature LO signal. The circuit resulted in voltage conversion gain of 6 db, IIP2 of 29 dBm, LO-RF isolation >50 dB. The chip area was 2.3x1.8mm² and a power consumption of 16.5 mW.

A circuit similar to Fig 3 was also used in [8] but it was implemented in CMOS 0.13 μm technology and was adjusted for passive operation. In this paper, RF pre-amp as well as LO and IF buffers are used and the circuit was designed for 24 GHz direct-conversion applications. The quadrature LO signals were generated by an off-chip 90° hybrid. The measured overall conversion gain was 3.2 dB, DSB noise figure of 10 dB, 2LO-RF isolation was 57 dB. The chip area was 0.9mm x0.65mm with a power consumption of 13.6 mW.

In [9], another implementation of same circuit shown in Fig 3 was done in CMOS 0.18 μm technology where an RC-CR phase shift network generates the required Lo signals. The circuit operates in 5GHz band resulting in a conversion gain of 9.5 dB, LO-RF of 48 dB, IIP3 of 7.5 dBm and the power consumption was 17.5 mW.

A typical modification of the Gilbert cell to enable 2x subharmonic mixing was introduced by [10] using a 0.35 μm BiCMOS technology. The circuit

shown in Fig 4 employs only two transistor levels but interchanges the positions of the LO and RF transistor (i.e. the RF transistors are on the top and the LO are on the bottom). As shown in Fig 4 here a quadrature LO signal is also required. In [10], circuit with an RF signal at 1.9 GHz and an LO signal at 900 MHz was designed. It resulted in a conversion gain of 7.5 dB, SSB noise figure of 10 dB, input 1-dB compression point was 8 dBm, IIP3 was 3 dBm and a power consumption of 24 mW.

[11] presents a comparison between three most common transistor-based 2x subharmonic mixer topologies. (1) Circuit shown in Fig 3 (three level), (2) LO transistors on the bottom and RF transistors on the top (Fig 4), and (3) LO transistors on the top used in [12]. Through this comparison it was found that as in Fig 3 circuit operates with the lowest LO power levels, but at the same time requires a higher DC supply voltage when compared with other two topologies. Also the circuit in Fig 3 has the lowest maximum operating frequencies out of all three topologies. The bottom LO subharmonic mixer shown in Fig 3 results in higher linearity, RF-IF isolation and noise figure. The third topology [12] results in a higher 2LO-RF isolation and a higher conversion gain.

One thing got clear here that the requirement of quadrature LO signal in 2x subharmonic mixer is very common (e.g. [9, 10, 12]).

There are several other circuits which are not based on Gilbert cell and are used to realize 2x subharmonic mixers using FETs. Consider the example of [13], here the RF signal was applied to the gate of FET and the LO signal was given to the bulk connection of FET (using CMOS 0.18 μm technology). The injecting of LO signal into the bulk of the transistor results in modulation of threshold voltage and exploits the non-linearity resulting in subharmonic mixing. The measured conversion gain was 10.5 dB, 1db compression point was 12 dBm and the IIP3 was 3.5 dBm. The circuit operated with RF frequency 2.1 GHz and LO frequency 1.025 GHz and produced a DSB noise figure of 17.7 dB and power consumption was 2.5 mW.

In [14] a 31 GHz 2x subharmonic mixer was demonstrated in 90 nm CMOS technology. As shown in Fig 5 it operates either with RF signal applied to gate and LO applied to the source. The capacitor Cg acts as a DC block whereas Ls and Cs act a high pass filter. Vg provides FET's gate bias through a large resistor Rg. The important feature of this circuit is that it can operate with either a $\frac{1}{2}f_{LO}$ or $\frac{1}{4}f_{LO}$ or in other words it can be used both as 2x subharmonic mixer or 3x subharmonic mixer. The conversion loss for the 2x SHM was between 8 dB to 11 dB and for 3x SHM it was 12 dB to 15 dB. An IIP3 of 3 dBm for the 2x

SHM and 7 dBm for 3x SHM. The dimensions of fabricated chip were 0.9mm x 1.0mm.

Fig 4: Subharmonic mixer circuit proposed in [10]

B. 4x Subharmonic Mixers

A large number of 4x SHMs have been demonstrated [15-20]. In these diodes were used to perform mixing operation which reduced the conversion gain. In order to obtain a greater conversion gain an anti parallel diode pair (APDP) configuration was used for mixing purposes, and infact majority of 4x SHMs use this configuration for their operation. The simple model of APDP is shown in Fig 6.

In [15], an APDP was used for a direct up converter using the basic circuit as shown on Fig 6. In this paper, RF and IF filters were implemented by an RF/baseband duplexer. In order to minimize the LO input reflection coefficient a transmission line matching network was used. A baseband signal was used with a 10 GHz LO signal to produce 40 GHz RF output signal. The measured conversion gain was quite high (21 dB to 15dB as we increased LO power from 6 dBm to 11 dBm), isolation between RF and IF ports were >30 dB.

In [16], a MMIC implementation of the APDP circuit of 94 GHz quadruple subharmonic mixer (4x SHM) was designed and measured using GaAs MESFET technology, as shown in Fig 6. In this work, stub filters were used at the IF and LO ports and a coupled line bandpass filters was used at the input RF port. Here the 94 GHz RF signal was mixer with 23.5 GHz LO input signal to obtain an IF of 100 KHz. The measured conversion gain of this circuit was 11.4 dB and the input 1-dB compression point was a 6dBm. The chip had an area of 0.9mm x 1.4mm.

In [17], a 4x SHM was presented again using the same APDP configuration but in a hybrid implementation with two packaged diodes and a 10 mil duroid substrate. In this work, an RF signal of 38.5 GHz to 40 GHz (upper Ka-band) and the LO frequency was in X-band to produce an IF output at 2.5 GHz. Transmission line stub filters were used for

matching and filtering purposes. The measured conversion loss of this circuit was 9 dB and the return loss for the RF, IF, and LO ports was approximately -20 dB, -20 dB and -15 dB respectively.

Fig 5: Passive FET subharmonic mixer [14]

In [18] a GaAs-based MMIC APDP 4x SHM was presented which uses a number of anti parallel diodes along with transmission line stub filters to extract the IF signal at $(\omega_{RF} - 4\omega_{LO})$. In this design the single APDP is replaced by a triple APDP implementation. (Six diodes in total). The purpose of this topology was to reduce the conversion loss of the mixer by minimizing the diode series resistance. The simulated circuit operated in a frequency range of 50 GHz to 65 GHz with a LO input frequency range of 12 GHz to 16 GHz. The minimum conversion loss for the circuit is 11 dB with a 7 dBm LO input signal. The LO-IF, LO-RF isolation was 17 dB and 33 dB. Linearity measurements were not given in this work.

In [19], a V-band MMIC based on APDP circuit was presented. This work used GaAs PHEMT technology along with CPW transmission lines, stub filters for RF and LO signals, lumped element inductor and capacitors for IF matching and low pass filtering and FETs for amplification. The RF signal was 60.4 GHz with LO frequency of 14.5 GHz producing an IF of 2.4 GHz. The measured conversion gain was 0.8 dB for an input LO power of 12 dBm. The LO-RF and LO-IF isolations were > 40 dB and the area was 1.9mm x 2.6mm.

Now, there are only few cases where 4x Subharmonic mixers are designed without using any diodes as demonstrated in [20]. In this work, several stubs for RF and LO filtering are used in a cascade configuration with GaAs MESFETS. The FET used here generates and enhances the fourth harmonic of the LO input signal and then mixes it with the RF signal.

Fig 6: Subharmonic mixer using an anti-parallel diode-pair [12, 15]

The circuit operates with an RF range of 59.4 GHz to 60.9 GHz with LO input frequency of 14.5 GHz. For matching and low-pass filtering lumped inductors and capacitors were used. The circuit resulted in a conversion gain of 2.5 dB to 3.4 dB for LO input power of 13 dBm. The LO-RF and LO-IF isolation were 46.2 dBm and 53.6 dBm respectively and chip area was 1.9 mm x 1.8mm.

IV. CONCLUSION

Gilbert cell mixer is the most common configuration used in designing fundamental FET based mixer though other designs have also been demonstrated. Now, due to the concept of direct receivers the Subharmonic mixers have become of much importance which can be of different orders based on their LO signal. One thing got obvious here that SHM most commonly need quadrature LO signal for frequency translation of input RF signal. Generally, and as expected, 4x SHMs have more loss than 2x SHMs, which in turn generally have more conversion loss than fundamental mixers. In most cases, 4x subharmonic mixers do not exhibit a conversion gain.

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Robotic Hand with Base Rotation Implementation Using Arm

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Abstract—This paper presents a robotic hand to pick and place appliances. Automation is playing an important role to save human efforts in most of the regular and frequently carried works such as industrial jobs like welding, painting, assembly, container filling etc. One of the major and most commonly performed work is picking and placing of jobs from source to destination. The pick and place robot is a mechatronic system that detects the object, picks that object from source location and places at desired location. For detection of object, infrared sensors are used which detect presence of object. Once the object is detected, it moves towards object, picks it with end effectors, and places it on destination. If there is any interrupt the robot changes its path and completes the same job.

Keywords: Mechatronics , ZIGBEE, ARM processor, RF transmitter, RF Reciever.

I. INTRODUCTION

An embedded system is a special-purpose computer system designed to perform one or a few dedicated functions, sometimes with real-time computing constraints. It is usually embedded as part of a complete device including hardware and mechanical parts. In [3] controlling the robot using the wireless communication (ZIGBEE) is carried out. It describe a specification for a suite of high level communication protocols used to create personal area networks built from small, low-power digital radios. In [7] Motion planning for a whole –sensitive robot arm maniuator is described, in which robot hand would allow it to maneuver and move around in a cluttered and unknown environment. In [1] quad trees representation of 2-dimensional objects is performed with a tree that describes the recursive subdivision of the more complex parts of a picture until the desired resolution is reached. Once the object is detected, it moves towards object, picks it with end effectors, and places it on destination. In [6] a hierarchical data structure for representing the spatial decomposition of 3-D object is described. In the present work the robot can detect the 3 dimensional object which finds its use in various industrial applications such as terrestrial, underground and space explorations, navigation in hazardous environments and in military

operations. Enhancements can be done by adding a series of modules on this robot for other specific purposes. At industrial level these automated robots are very expensive. This robot can pick and place any object. Regular maintenance needs a financial toll as well. Robots may protect workers from some hazards, but in the mean time, there very presence can create some other safety problems.

II. BASIC BUILDING BLOCKS FOR MODEL IMPLEMENTATION

(A).power supply section.

Fig. 1 shows the power supply section which generates 5v DC

Fig. 1 shows the power supply section which generates 5v DC for the module implementation.

(B) Arm based LPC 2148 Microcontrollers:

The microcontroller incorporates all the features that are found in microprocessor. The microcontroller has built in ROM, RAM, Input Output ports, Serial Port, timers, interrupts and clock circuit. A microcontroller is an entire computer manufactured on a single chip. Microcontrollers are usually dedicated devices embedded within an application. The LPC2148 microcontrollers are based on a 32/16 bit ARM7TDMI-S CPU with real-time emulation and embedded trace support, that combines the microcontroller with embedded high speed flash memory ranging from 32 kB to 512 kB. A 128-bit wide memory interface and a unique accelerator architecture enable 32-bit code execution at the maximum clock rate.

(C) Dc motors:

DC-motors are very easy to use, but like most other motors their usefulness for robotics is very dependent on the gearing available. DC-motors are made much more effective if they have an efficient gear ratio for a particular task. The control of a DC motor can be split into two parts: speed and direction.

(D) RF transmitters and receivers:

An RF module (radio frequency module) is a (usually) small electronic device used to transmit and/or receive radio signals between two devices. In an embedded system it is often desirable to communicate with another device wirelessly.

(E) Driver IC'S:

A driver is an electrical circuit or other electronic component used to control another circuit or other component, such as a high-power transistor. They are usually used to regulate current flowing through a circuit or is used to control the other factors such as other components, some devices in the circuit. High-brightness LED drivers are integrated circuits that are optimized to efficiently drive strings of high-brightness LEDs.

(F) Keypad:

A keypad is a set of buttons arranged in a block which usually bear digits and other symbols but not a complete set of alphabetical letters. The technique is called multiplexed matrix keypad. In this technique keys are connected in a matrix (row or column)

(G) KEIL Microvision IDE:

The μ Vision development platform is easy-to-use and helping you quickly create embedded programs that work. The μ Vision editor and debugger are integrated in a single application that provides a seamless embedded project development environment.

(H) Embedded C:

Embedded C is a set of language extensions for the C Programming language by the C Standards committee to address commonality issues that exist between C extensions for different embedded systems. Historically, embedded C programming requires nonstandard extensions.

III. BLOCK DIAGRAM OF IMPLEMENTATION

Fig.2 shows the transmitter part which is used for controlling of the robot. The pressing of the keypad inputs the control which inturn is transmitted through RF transmitter.

Fig. 2 Transmitter section

Fig. 3 is the receiver section which receives the commands from the transmitter, and accordingly actuates the motors of the robot to rotate.

Fig. 3 Receiver section

IV. ROBOT HARDWARE IMPLEMENTATION AND OPERATION

The main operation in constructing a robot lies in the control of its motors. Here a microcontroller is used to control the DC motors which are connected as wheels of robot. The robot is mounted on a three motorized spherical wheels [4] arranged to make omni directional movement possible. When the key is pressed on the keypad it is transmitted through RF transmitter. In the receiver section, RF receiver will receive the commands, and accordingly the motors will rotate. The five motors operate the grab, release, lift and lower. This robotic arm performs base rotation, elbow and wrist motion with a functional gripper for pick and place [2] applications using zigbee. In [5] collision detection by four- dimensional intersection testing is described.

Fig. 4 Hardware implementation of robot

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

The hardware implementation of robot is shown in fig. (4) The code is implemented by using keil software .The simulation steps are shown in fig.(4), fig.(5) and fig.(6).

The flashing LED are configured to Port 1. Fig.(5) displays the configuration of LED.

Fig.5 connection of LED

To ensure that the port activity is visible, there is a need to start the 'periodic window update' flag. Fig.(6) shows the visibility of port active.

Fig.6 visibility of port active

Fig. (7) shows the inclusion of delay in programming loop. This is implemented by double click on delay loop waiting function.

Fig.7 Inclusion of delay

After delay programming, perform the execution operation then dump that program code into the ARM controller.

VI. CONCLUSION

The present paper gives an implementation of a pick and place robot which detects the object, picks that object from the source locations and places at desired location. The main operation in constructing a robot lies in the control of its motors. Here ARM controller is used at the transmitter and receiver. The signal from the RF transmitter is received by the receiver section which then controls the motors. The motor performs grab, release, lift and lower operations. Thus, the robotic arm performs base rotation, elbow and wrist motion with a functional gripper for pick and place applications using zigbee.

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Smart Phone Android Operated Robot for Home Security System

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Abstract—This paper presents an implementation to make a home secured system which controls a robot to perform the home needs. Security of one's belongings when a person leaves his/her house is always a concern with increasing number of incidents of theft, robbery etc. Many automated systems has been developed which informs the owner in a remote location about any intrusion or attempt to intrude in the house. Intel micro controller has been extensively used in the past implementations. However, this paper looks into the development of an ANDROID application which sends a message to mobile device receives on possible intrusion and subsequently a reply (Short Message Service) SMS which triggers an alarm/buzzer in the remote house making others aware of the possible intrusion. The single ANDROID is making a home completely secured and a robot controlling element which is easy to code and implement.

Keywords—*ANDROID, Short Message Service (SMS), Microcontroller, LED, Embedded C,WIFI, LAN, Global Communication for mobile system (GSM).*

I. INTRODUCTION

Controlling home appliances remotely with mobile applications have started becoming quite popular due to the exponential rise in use of mobile devices. There have been so many applications that exploit the use of GSM/GPRS facility of the handset [5]. Mobile handsets today are essentially handheld computers with integrated mobile radio communication capabilities. With increasing usage of GSM, network services are expanded beyond speech communication to incorporate many other custom applications, machine automation and machine to machine communication. This paper discusses an approach where an authorized remote mobile user receives an SMS when a third party tries to enter his house in a remote location. The minimum requirement at the user end is that the mobile device should have an ANDROID OS. ANDROID is a java based operating system which runs on the Linux 2.6 kernel. It's lightweight and full featured. ANDROID applications are developed using Java and can be ported to new platform easily thereby fostering huge number of useful mobile applications [6]. A hardware circuit with a switch and a GSM modem embedded is

installed and connected to the door of the house. When the intruder tries to open the door, the switch triggers an interrupt and subsequently sends a signal into the microcontroller which subsequently triggers the GSM modem to transmit a warning SMS into already registered number in the modem. The SMS on the users end is interpreted by the ANDROID Application and if it finds that the SMS is from the designated number; the application immediately informs the person with a frequent pop-up menu. If the user positive acknowledge the pop-up in 1 minute, an acknowledgement is send back to the remote GSM modem. The modem outputs an interrupt to the microcontroller and the microcontroller subsequently triggers an alarm. If the user fails to acknowledge in the defined time interval, an automatic positive acknowledgement is send by the application to the modem and the activities follow. Additional to this we are controlling a robot for our own needs we can make the to control a robot with interfacing by an ANDROID mobile.

II. EXISTING METHODOLOGY

A lot many Home automation systems are available in the market. Different approach has been proposed at different times. However, Home automation system using ANDROID is still ongoing research project field. Google is trying to join home control arena with ANDROID application. Two of the approaches relevant to the topic are listed below.

a) *Design and Implementation of Home Automation System* [4].

In this paper presented by A. Alheraish, Member, IEEE, a design and implementation of remote control system by means of GSM cellular communication network is described. This design integrates the device to be controlled, the microcontroller, and GSM Module so that it can be used for a wide range of applications. The proposed M2M design a design, GSM dialup and communication protocol is embedded in the PC. The M2M microcontroller interacts with the M2M engine, embedded with the SIM card. The information that will be sent to the network has to be taken to a microcontroller to make the interface between the

machine and M2M engine. They had used different modules such as check and read message module, which check any received message from the M2M module using AT commands, a decode module which decodes the text message and excludes all other details such as date, time and sender's name.

b) A mobile-based home automation system [3].

In paper [3] a system consisting of java-enabled mobile phone, a cellular modem, and a controller board incorporating a microcontroller. The mobile phone serves as a remote control through which a user can interact with the home automation system.

III. PROPOSED METHOD

The Proposed project aims in designing a Robot that can be operated using Android mobile phone. The controlling of the Robot is done wirelessly through Android smart phone using the Bluetooth feature present in it. Here in the project the Android smart phone is used as a remote control for operating the Robot. Android is a software stack for mobile devices that includes an operating system, middleware and key applications. Android boasts a healthy array of connectivity options, including Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, and wireless data over a cellular connection (for example, GPRS, EDGE (Enhanced Data rates for GSM Evolution), and 3G).

Android provides access to a wide range of useful libraries and tools that can be used to build rich applications. In addition, Android includes a full set of tools that have been built from the ground up alongside the platform providing developers with high productivity and deep insight into their applications. Bluetooth is an open standard specification for a radio frequency (RF)-based, short-range connectivity technology that promises to change the face of computing and wireless communication. It is designed to be an inexpensive, wireless networking system for all classes of portable devices, such as laptops, PDAs (personal digital assistants), and mobile phones. It also will enable wireless connections for desktop computers, making connections between monitors, printers, keyboards, and the CPU cable-free. The controlling device of the whole system is a Microcontroller[1]. Bluetooth module, DC motors are interfaced to the Microcontroller. The data received by the Bluetooth module from Android smart phone is fed as input to the controller. The controller acts accordingly on the DC motors of the Robot. The robot in the project can be made to move in all the four directions using the Android phone. The direction of the robot is indicated using LED indicators of the Robot system. In achieving the task the controller is loaded with a program written using Embedded 'C' language.

IV. BLOCK DIAGRAM IMPLEMENTATION OF PROPOSEDSYSTEM

Fig 1.POWER SUPPLY SECTION

Fig. 1 shows the power supply section which generates 5v DC for the module implementation of fig 2.

Fig 2.Set Up of Smart Phone Android Robot

figure 2 illustrate the set up of the smart phone android robot which is used for home security system. The system consists of an android phone which functions as robot and an micro controller which is used for controlling the appliances. Their is an motor supply to drive the motor driver.

V. PROBLEM DEFINITION AND SYSTEM REQUIREMENT

A. Problem definition

Home automation systems face four main challenges [3], these are high cost of ownership, inflexibility, poor manageability, and difficulty achieving security. The main objectives of that research is to design and to implement a cheap and open source home automation system that is capable of controlling and automating most of the house appliance through an easy manageable web interface to run and maintain the home automation system. The proposed system has a great flexibility by using WiFi technology to interconnect its distributed modules to home automation server[2]. That will decrease deployment cost and will increase the ability of upgrading, and system reconfiguration. System will make use of secure wireless LAN connections between distributed hardware modules and server, and secure communication protocols between users and serve.

B. System requirements

The following list gives an overview of the most important requirements of the proposed system.

- 1) User friendly interface: User can easily manage system locally or remotely home automation system, through easy web based interface.
- 2) Security and authentication: Only authorized user can login to the system (locally, or remotely) in order to manage, control, & monitor. If system detects intruder sit should immediately alert the system owner and lock login capability for a while.
- 3) Low cost per node / High node count: Thinking of building automation, hundreds of nodes may be needed to provide automation. However, the market requires competitive performance (compared to wired networks) to be delivered at this low system cost. Additionally, also protocols need to scale to high node count e.g., ensuring message delivery.
- 4) Large area coverage: Another challenge lies in the fact that devices of a building automation system are dispersed over large areas. Since transceivers must not consume so much power, they cannot be built with a transmission range sufficient for sensors to reach associated controllers or actuators directly. Also, they may rely on an infrastructure of access points and a wired backbone network (or particularly sensitive receivers).
- 5) System Scalability: Scalability is the ability of a system, network, or process, to handle growing amount of work in a capable manner or its ability to be enlarged to accommodate that growth. For example, system upgrade/downgrade by adding/removing hardware interface module should be easy and systematic task.

VI. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Fig. 3 Experimental Set up of ANDROID based home security system

Fig 3 shows the experimental set up of the homes security system implemented using ANDROID software. The set up consists of an android phone which acts as a robot. The micro controller is used for controlling the various appliances from the signals obtained from the ANDROID phone. Here ARM 7 is used as a processor. There are two LED which acts as an indicators. The green LED is used for ON and the red LED is used for OFF of the system.

Fig .4 Set up in ANDROID phone

Fig. 4 shows the ANDROID phone display setup for controlling the various appliances.

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper presents an implementation of low cost, secure, ubiquitously accessible, auto-configurable, remotely controlled solution using ARM Processor. The approach discussed in this paper, has achieved the target to control home appliances remotely using the WiFi technology to connects system parts, satisfying user needs and requirements. WiFi technology capable solution has proved to be controlled remotely, provide home security and is cost-effective as compared to the previously existing systems. Thus, the proposed system is better from the scalability and flexibility point of view than the commercially available home automation systems.

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An Advanced Method for Detecting Cracks in Railway Tracks with The Help of LDR and LED System with Efficient Robot

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Abstract— This paper presents the problem about a railway analysis is detection of cracks in the structure. If these deficiencies are not controlled at early stages they might lead to a number of the railments resulting in a heavy loss of life and property. In this paper, the proposed broken rail detection system automatically detects the faulty rail track without any human intervention. There are many advantages with the proposed system when compared with the traditional detection techniques. The advantages include less cost, low power consumption and less analysis time. By this proposed system the exact location of the faulty rail track can easily be located which will recommended immediately so that many lives can be saved. The proposed system uses to identify the traditional and the faulty part to overcome the limitations of the existing system and we did not get the exact location of the defective part. We receive only the latitude and longitude location. We get the exact location of the broken rail track so we GPRS module using the proposed system. In this proposed system, we also consume low power and cost less than using ARM7 controller. Analysis using the ARM controller recommended lifetime significantly robot has been programmed before the start of scan line Light Emitting Diode (LED) embodiment calibrating Light Dependent Resistor (LDR). It is necessary because the LDR has a natural tendency to show a drifting effect because of which, its resistance under the same lighting condition may vary with time. After calibration, the robot waits for a predetermined period of time so that the onboard Global Positioning System (GPS) module starts reading the correct geographic coordinate. This is necessary because any GPS module will take some time to synchronize with the satellites.

Keywords— Railway Cracks, crack detection, GPRS, Microcontroller, LED, LDR, GSM, GPS.

I.INTRODUCTION

In India most of the commercial transport is being carried out by the railway network and therefore as any problem occurred during transportation the major damage is getting occurred to the economy-non withstanding a social life. The Indian railway network today has a track length of 113,617 kilometers (70,598m) over a route of 63,974 kilometers (39,752 m) and 7,083 stations [11]. It is the fourth largest railway networking the world exceeded only by those of the United States, Russia and China. The rail network traverses every length and breadth of India and is known carry over 30 million passengers and

2.8 million tons of freight daily. Despite boasting of such impressive statistics, the Indian rail network is still on the growth trajectory trying to fuel the economic needs of our nation. In terms of the reliability and safety parameters, we have not yet reached truly global standards. Though rail transport in India growing at a rapid pace, the associated safety infrastructure facilities have not kept up with the aforementioned proliferation. Our facilities are inadequate compared to the international standards and as a result, there have been frequent derailments that have resulted in severe loss of valuable human lives and property as well [6]. The principal problem has been the lack of cheap and efficient technology to detect problems in the rail tracks and of course, the lack of proper maintenance of rails which have resulted in the formation of cracks in the rail sand other similar problems caused by anti-social elements which jeopardize the security of operation of rail transport [4].

In general, there exist three main categories of techniques excitingly used for damage identification and condition monitoring of Railway tracks. These include:

- Graphical inspections
- Non-destructive testing technologies such as acoustic emissions or ultrasonic methods, magnetic field methods, radio graphic, eddy Existing techniques, thermal field methods, dye penetrate, fiber optic sensors of various kinds
- Shuddering-based global methods

Graphical inspection is the primary technique used for defect identification in tracks, and is effectively used in specialized disciplines. The successful implementation of this method generally requires the regions of the suspected damage to be known as a first step, and be readily accessible for physical inspection. As a result, this method can be costly, time consuming and ineffective for large and complex structural systems such as the rail track [3]. NDT techniques have resulted in a number of tools for us to choose from. Among the inspection methods used to ensure rail integrity, the common ones are ultrasonic inspection and eddy Existing inspection. Ultrasonic Inspections are common place in the rail industry in many foreign countries. It is a relatively well understood technique and was thought to be the

best solution to crack detection [6]. The below figure.1 Ultrasonic Broken Rail Detector system is the first and only alternative broken rail detection system developed, produced and implemented on a large scale. By using ultrasonic Broken Rail Detector system railway operators will have the benefit of monitoring rails continuously for broken rails without human intervention. This will contribute to ensure that the people do not suffer losses as a result of train derailments [10]. Ultrasonic can only inspect the core of materials; that is, the method cannot check for surface and near-surface cracking where many of the faults are located [6].

Another method for detection of cracks on tracks is by using wireless sensor networks. In this method the detection of Cracks can be identified using IR rays with the IR transmitter & receiver. IR receiver is connected to the Signal Lamp or Electrified lamp is shown in figure.2 with the IR sensor [7]. CAN controller is connected to the main node and it send the information via GSM and transmit the message to engine and to the nearest station. The detection of Cracks can be identified using IR rays and IR sensor. IR receiver is connected to the signal lamp and to the CAN controller.

Fig.1 Ultrasonic Broken Rail Detector

The electrified lamp is nothing but it sides of the tracks the electric lamp which is existing flowing for the engines transportation [2], [9]. But this type of system doesn't locate small cracks and the system is also costly.

Fig.2 Model Figure to Fix the IR Sensor on the Wheel

This paper proposes a cost-effective solution to the problem of railway track crack detection utilizing LED-LDR assembly which tracks the exact location

of faulty track which then mended immediately so that many lives will be saved [12].

The rest of the paper is organized As follows: section II gives the complete details about the Existing system developed to perform the crack detection. The complete illustration of the proposed system is given in section III. It also gives the details about the components used in the developing of this system. Section IV concludes the paper.

II. EXISTING SYSTEM

In the Existing System uses the concept of LDR (Light Dependent Resistor) to detect the cracks. The LED will be attached to one side of the rails and the LDR to the opposite side in the existing approach. When cracks during normal operation, and hence the LED does not fall LDR, LDR resistance is high. After falling of the LED light after LDR, LDR resistance is reduced and the reduction of the amount of light intensity will be nearly proportional. As a consequence, when light from the LED deviates from its path due to the presence of a crack or a break, a sudden decrease in the resistance value of the LDR ensues [1]. This change in resistance indicates the presence of a crack or some other similar structural defect in the rails. In order to detect the Existing location of the device in case of detection of a crack, a GPS receiver whose function is to receive the Existing latitude and longitude data is used. To communicate the received information, a GSM modem has been utilized. The function of the GSM module being used is to send the Existing latitude and longitude data to the relevant authority as an SMS .The robot is driven by four DC motors. With this Existing system only latitudes and longitudes of the broken track will only be received so that the exact location cannot be known [6].

III. DESIGN APPROACH

The proposed system use so identify the traditional and the faulty part to overcome the limitations of the existing system and we did not get the exact location of the defective part. We receive only the latitude and longitude location. We get the exact location of the broken rail track so we GPRS module using the proposed system. In this proposed system, we also consume low power and cost less than using ARM7controller. Analysis using the ARM microcontroller commended life time significantly robot has been programmed before the start of scan line LED embodiment calibrating LDR. It is necessary because the LDR has a natural tendency to show a drifting effect because of which, its resistance under the same lighting condition may vary with time [5]. After calibration, the robot waits for a predetermined period of time so that the onboard GPS module starts reading the correct geographic coordinate. This is necessary because any GPS module will take some time to synchronize with the

satellites. The principle involved in crack detection is the concept of LDR. In the proposed design, the LED will be attached to one side of the rail sand the LDR to the opposite side. During normal operation, when there are no cracks, the LED light does not fall on the LDR and hence the LDR resistance is high. Subsequently, when the LED light falls on the LDR, the resistance of the LDR gets reduced and the amount of reduction will beep proximately proportional to the intensity of the incident light. As a consequence, when light from the LED deviates from its path due to the presence of a crack or a break, a sudden decrease in the resistance value of the LDR ensues [1]. This change in resistance indicates the presence of a crack or some other similar structural defect in the rails. In order to detect the Existing location of the device in case of detection of a crack, a GPS receiver whose function is to receive the Existing latitude and longitude data is used. To communicate the received information, a GSM modem has been utilized [7]. The GSM modem transfers the received information to the GPRS which then shows the exact location of the faulty rail track in the mobile. This can be observed by using the automatic broken rail detection scheme in figure.3.

Fig.3 Automatic Broken Rail Detection Scheme using LED-LDR Assembly

A. System Architecture:

The proposed rail track detection system architecture consists of ARM7 controller, GPS, GSM, LED-LDR Assembly, and GPRS, DC Motor.

B. Operation:

This section explains the operation of modules present in the faulty rail track detection system architecture

i) *Microcontroller:* The microcontroller used in this system is LPC2148 microcontroller that is based on a 32/16 bit ARM7TDMI-S CPU with real-time emulation and embedded trace support, that combines the microcontroller with embedded high speed flash memory ranging from 32 KB to 512 KB. Due to their tiny size and low power consumption, LPC2148 are

ideal for applications where miniaturization is a key requirement, such as access control and point-of-sale. A blend of serial communications interfaces ranging from a USB 2.0 Full Speed device, multiple UARTs, SPI, SSP to I2Cs, and on chip SRAM of 8 KB up to 40 KB, make these devices very well suited for communication gateways and protocol converters, soft modems, voice recognition and low end imaging, providing both large buffer size and high processing power [14].

ii) *GPS Module:* SR-92 GPS receiver has been used as the GPS module. SR-92 is a low-power, ultra-high performance, easy to use GPS smart antenna module based on Si RF'S third generation single chip. The 5-pin I/O interface is then connected to the main board with either connector or wire soldering.

The main features of GPS module includes

- High tracking sensitivity of -159dBm
- Low power consumption of 40mA at full tracking
- Built-in backup battery allowing hot/warm starts and better performance
- Hardware power saving control pin allowing power off GPS via GPIO [8].

iii) *GSM Module:* The SIM 300 GSM module has been chosen to achieve the SMS functionality. The leading features of SIM300make it deal fir virtually unlimited application, such as Will applications, M2M application, hand held devices and much more [13]. Featuring an industry standard interface, the SIM 300 delivers GSM / GPRS900 / 1800 /1900 Mhz performance for voice, SMS, data and Fax in a small form factor and with low power consumption.

iv) *LED - LDR Assembly:* The common 5V LED and cadmium sulphide LDR was found to be sufficient. The LED is powered using one of the digital pin of the ARM microcontroller. The LDR and a 45kΩ resistor form a potential divider arrangement. The output of the potential divider is given to one of the analog input channel of the ARM. The LDR is calibrated every time the robot is used. The light dependant resistor or cadmium sulfide (CDS) cell is a resistor whose resistance decreases with increasing incident light intensity.

v) *GPRS Module:* In this system the GPRS module is used to know the exact location of the broken rail track. The GSM modem sends the coordinates of the faulty rail track to the GPRS which then sends the exact location to the mobile

vi) *DC Motor:* The proposed design uses 4 DC motors (Torque Rating: 10Kg and Speed Rating: 500 rpm) interfaced with the ARM With a wheel diameter of 5.2 cm and the total mass of around 5 Kg [6]. The approximate speed of the robot is around 0.5 m/sec

IV. CONCLUSION

The proposed broken rail detection system automatically detects the faulty rail track without any human intervention. There are many advantages with the proposed system when compared with the traditional detection techniques. The advantages include less cost, low power consumption and less analysis time. By this proposed system the exact location of the faulty rail track can easily be located which will mended immediately so that many lives can be saved.

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Reversible ALU Implementation using Kogge-Stone Adder

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Abstract— In this paper, implementing a novel programmable reversible Kogge-Stone adder is presented, verified and its implementation in the design of a reversible Arithmetic Logic Unit is demonstrated. Then, reversible implementations of ripple-carry, Kogge-Stone carry look-ahead adders are analyzed and compared in terms of delay. The proposed design consists of the reversible Fredkin, Feynman, MG, HNG, PG and RKSC gates. The performance characteristics analysis is carried out in Xilinx environment

Keywords- Arithmetic Logic Unit; Carry Look-Ahead Adder; Emerging Technologies; Low Power; Nanotechnology; Reversible Logic; Ripple-Carry Adder.

I. INTRODUCTION

Logical computing devices without a bijection between input and output states were demonstrated by Landauer to require a minimal heat generation of $kT \ln(2)$ joules of energy per computing cycle [1]. This resulting dissipated heat also causes noise in the remaining circuitry, which results in computing errors. Bennett showed that the dissipated energy directly correlated to the number of lost bits, and that computers can be logically reversible, maintain their simplicity and provide accurate calculations at practical speeds [2]. Resultantly, a new paradigm in computer design arose with the goal of reducing the entropy increase and subsequent energy dissipation. Such a logical structure must possess the same number of inputs and outputs and a one-to one mapping between the input and output states. Any device designed to these constraints is known as a reversible logic device.

Section II, the goals of programmable reversible logic design and some fundamental logic gates. In Section III, a novel 5*5 programmable MG gate is proposed that may be utilized in an arithmetic logic unit requiring the calculation of AND, NAND, OR, NOR, XOR and XNOR results. In Section IV, previous work in programmable reversible arithmetic logic units is reviewed, and the proposed MG gate is implemented in the design of a novel programmable arithmetic logic unit. In Section V, basic adder designs are presented for ripple carry adder and kogge-stone adder. In Section VI, a reversible implementation of the carry logic presented in the Kogge-Stone is proposed and verified. In section VII, a 4-bit ALU is implemented with ripple carry and

kogge-stone adders and these designs are functionally verified and compared in terms of delay.

II. REVERSIBLE LOGIC

A. Programmable Reversible Design Goals. The three major design goals of reversible logic are as follows. First, minimization of the quantum cost – the number of 1*1 and 2*2 reversible calculations necessary to generate the logical output [6] will reduce the device's computational complexity. Second, minimization of the delay - the logical depth of the device [7] will improve the throughput of the device. Third, reduction of the ancillary inputs and garbage outputs - inputs and outputs not implemented in the design of the gate and only serve to maintain reversibility of the device will improve the design space require to implement the logic.

A programmable reversible logic gate is defined in [8] as a logic structure which possesses a bijection between input and output states and an equal number of inputs and outputs wherein a subset of the inputs are fixed select lines, and a fixed subset of the outputs produce guaranteed logical calculations. An ideal programmable reversible logic gate with j inputs and outputs has a quantity of fixed select inputs m , fixed select outputs n , data inputs d and propagated outputs p such that $|d-p|=|m-n|$ [8]. In addition, an ideal programmable reversible logic gate with m select inputs may produce at maximum $n \cdot 2^m$ logical calculations on the n logical outputs .

B. Fundamental Logic Gates

There are three types of fundamental 2*2 reversible logic gates. First, the square-root-of-not gates utilize the unitary operators to produce reversible logic calculations. The Controlled-V and the Controlled-V+ gates are the two types of square-root-of-not gates. In both of these gates, when the control input is 0, the second input is propagated to the output. The same holds for two Controlled-V+ gates in series. When a Controlled-V and Controlled-V+ gate are activated in series, they act as an identity.

The second type of fundamental 2*2 reversible logic gate is the Feynman gate, or the Controlled-Not gate. Proposed in [9] by Feynman, it is configured such that its outputs states correlate to the input states

in the following manner: $P=A$ and $Q=A \oplus B$. The resulting value of the second output corresponds to the result of a conventional XOR gate. Since fanout is expressively forbidden in reversible logic, since a fanout has one input and two outputs, the Feynman gate may be used to duplicate a signal when B is equal to 0. Its quantum configuration is shown in Fig 2.

Fig 1: Quantum Representation of Feynman gate

The third type of fundamental 2×2 reversible logic gate is the integrated qubit gate. This gate is implemented with a Feynman gate with either a Controlled-V or Controlled V+ gate. The XOR output of the Feynman gate is used as the control signal for the Controlled-V or V+ gate it is coupled with. The quantum cost of the integrated qubit gate is 1 and its worst-case delay is 1. The quantum configuration of these gates are shown below in Fig. 3.

Fig 2: Quantum Representations of Integrated Qubit Gates

There are three 3×3 fundamental reversible logic gates. The first was proposed in [10] by Fredkin and Toffoli. The Fredkin gate's outputs states map to the inputs as follows:

$P=A$, $Q=A \oplus B \oplus AC$ and $R=AB \oplus A \oplus C$. Therefore, the outputs serve as a multiplexed output of the two data inputs based on the control input. It is realized using 2 Feynman gates, a Controlled-V gate and two integrated qubit gates.

Fig 3: Quantum Representation of Fredkin gate

Toffoli proposed the second fundamental 3×3 reversible logic gate in [11]. The output states of the Toffoli gate map to the inputs in this manner: $P=A$, $Q=B$ and $R=AB \oplus C$. The quantum cost is 5 and the worst-case delay is 5. The quantum representation is shown below in Fig. 5.

Fig 4: Quantum Representation of Toffoli gate

The 3×3 Peres gate was proposed by Peres in [12]. The Peres gate has a quantum cost of 4 and a worst-case delay of

3. The quantum representation is shown in Fig. 6. The output states map to the inputs in this manner: $P=A$, $Q=A \oplus B$ and $R=AB \oplus C$.

Fig 5: Quantum Representation of Peres gate

The HNG gate, also designed by Hagparast and Navi and proposed in [13], is a full adder with inputs A, B, C, D producing outputs $P=A$, $Q=B$, $R=(A \oplus B) \oplus C$ and $S=(A \oplus B)C \oplus (AB \oplus D)$ and is shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6: Hagparast-Navi (HNG) Gate

The Peres And-Or (PAOG) gate, proposed in [8], produces the outputs $P = A$, $Q = A \oplus B$, $R=AB \oplus C$ and $S=(AB \oplus C) \oplus ((A \oplus B) \oplus D)$. Fig. 7 shows the quantum representation of the PAOG gate. This gate is an extension of the Peres gate for ALU realization. When the PAOG is utilized as a programmable reversible logic gate with two select inputs, it will calculate four logical calculations on those two logical outputs: AND, NAND, NOR and OR.

Fig. 7: Quantum Representation of the PAOG

The Morrison-Ranganathan (MRG) gate, proposed in [8], has a quantum cost of 6, since it consists of three XOR gates, 2 Controller-V and one Controller-V+ gate. The worst-case delay of the MRG gate is 6. The quantum representation of the MRG gate is shown in Fig. 8 below. When the MRG is utilized as a programmable reversible logic gate with two select inputs, it will calculate four logical calculations on those two logical outputs: OR, NOR, XOR and XNOR.

Fig. 8: Quantum Representation of the MRG Gate

III. PROPOSED 5*5 PROGRAMMABLE REVERSIBLE MG GATE

Next, propose the design of a 5*5 programmable reversible logic gate structure utilized in the implementation of an ALU. Fig. 9 shows the block diagram of the MG, and the logical calculations based on the programmable inputs are presented in Table 2. The cost of the MG is 7, and the worst-case delay is 7. The design for the programmable MG was verified and simulated using VHDL in Xilinx.

Fig 9: Quantum Representation of Proposed MG.

TABLE II
 MG PROGRAMMABLE INPUTS AND LOGICAL OUTPUTS

C	D	E	R	S	T
0	0	0	$A \oplus B$	AB	$A + B$
0	0	1	$A \oplus B$	AB	$(A + B)'$
0	1	0	$A \oplus B$	$(AB)'$	$(A + B)'$
0	1	1	$A \oplus B$	$(AB)'$	$A + B$
1	0	0	$A = B$	AB	$A + B$
1	0	1	$A = B$	AB	$(A + B)'$
1	1	0	$A = B$	$(AB)'$	$(A + B)'$
1	1	1	$A = B$	$(AB)'$	$A + B$

IV. MODIFIED ALU DESIGN WITH MG GATE

Two 1-bit ALUs were proposed in [8]. The first utilizes the MRG gate and HNG gate to produce six logical calculations: ADD, SUB, XOR, XNOR, OR and NOR. The ALU has 8 inputs and 8 outputs. The inputs consist of three data inputs (A, B and Cin) and five fixed input select lines. The eight outputs are: A, S0, S3 and S4 propagated to the output, A, B, SUM, Cout, Overflow and Result. The cost of this 1-bit ALU is 24, and the worst-case delay is 16. For n-bit ALU devices, an addition cost of 2 is incurred per bit in order to propagate S1 and S2 to other bits. Therefore, the total cost for an n-bit ALU is $26n-2$.

The MG gate is utilized in the implementation of a novel arithmetic logic unit based on those proposed in [8]. The ALU, in addition to producing the same logical calculations as the MG, is able to perform addition and subtraction by utilizing the HNG gate and store less-than operation. The cost of an n-bit ALU is $37n-3$ and had a worst case delay of $4n+13$. The proposed ALU is shown in Fig. 10 and the logical results based on the input opcodes are presented in Table 3. The design for the novel one-bit ALU was verified and simulated using VHDL in Xilinx.

Fig. 10: Reversible ALU with MG and HNG gates

TABLE III

ALU OPCODES AND LOGICAL RESULT FOR FIG. 9

S6	S5	S4	S3	S2	S1	S0	Result
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	ADD
0	0	0	0	0	0	1	SUB
0	0	1	0	0	0	0	$A + B$
0	0	1	1	0	0	0	$(A + B)'$
0	1	0	0	0	0	0	$A \oplus B$
0	1	0	0	0	1	0	$A = B$
0	1	1	0	0	0	0	AB
0	1	1	0	1	0	0	$(AB)'$
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	SLT

V. BASIC ADDER DESIGNS

The adders implemented are the ripple carry adder and Kogge-Stone adder. The ripple carry adder is one of the simplest adders. It consists of a cascaded series of full adders. The 4-bit ALU implemented by cascading four 1-bit ALUs. The delay for an N-bit adder is given by

$$t_{\text{adder}} = (N-1)t_{\text{carry}} + t_{\text{sum}}$$

where, t_{carry} is the carry propagation delay for one stage and t_{sum} is the time required to compute the sum bit for one stage.

The Kogge-Stone adder is classified as a parallel prefix adder since the generate and the propagate signals are precomputed. In a tree-based adder, carries are generated in tree and fast computation is obtained at the expense of increased area and power. The parallel-prefix adder becomes more favorable in terms of speed due to the $O(\log_2 n)$ delay through the carry path compared to $O(n)$ for the RCA.

Fig.11. 4-bit Kogge-Stone Adder

The 4-bit Kogge-Stone adder is built from generate and propagate (GP) blocks, black cell (BC) blocks, and buffer blocks as shown in the Figure 11. The expressions for the output signals g,p generated by the black cell are given by $g = g_i + p_i \cdot g_j$ and $p = p_i \cdot p_j$. The expressions for the output signals g, p obtained by the buffer block are given as $g = g_i$ and $p = p_i$. The expressions for the output signals g, p obtained by the GP block are given as $g = a \cdot b$ and $p = a \text{ xor } b$. Reversible Kogge-Stone Cumulate Logic

A reversible carry look-ahead adder based on the Kogge-Stone adder is presented [9]. First, a RKS Cumulate utilized in the calculation of the carry out signal is designed and verified. The logical structure of the RKSC is shown in Fig. 12. The cost of the RKSC is 14 and it has a worst-case delay of 4.

Fig. 12: Reversible Kogge-Stone Cumulate (RKSC) Logical Layout

VI. IMPLEMENTATION OF REVERSIBLE KOGGE-STONE ADDER

A reversible Kogge-Stone adder is implemented by using Peres gate as GP block, Feynman gate as Buffer block and RKSC gate as BC block as shown in Fig.13. The design was verified and simulated using VHDL in Xilinx 9.2i.

Fig. 13. 4-bit Reversible Kogge-Stone adder ALU Design with Reversible Kogge-Stone adder

The 4-bit ALU was implemented using reversible Kogge-Stone adder as shown in Fig.14. This design was verified and simulated using VHDL in Xilinx9.2i.

Fig.14. 4-bit reversible ALU with kogge-stone adder

VII. COMPARISON AND RESULTS

The comparison is carried out in between the reversible Ripple Carry and Kogge-Stone adders with respect to 4-bit ALU design and for those the code was written in VHDL and that was verified and simulated using Xilinx 9.2i. and also corresponding simulating waveforms are shown in fig 15-18.

TABLE IV

Comparison of ALUs of ripple carry and kogge-stone adders

Parameter	4-bit ALU with ripple carry adder	4-bit ALU with kogge-stone adder
Delay(ns)	16.856	15.536
LUT's	37	31

Fig.15. 1-bit reversible ALU

Fig.16. 4-bit reversible kogge-stone adder

Fig.17. 4-bit reversible ALU with ripple carry adder

Fig.18. 4-bit reversible ALU with kogge-stone adder

VIII. CONCLUSION

A novel 5*5 programmable MG gate was proposed and verified that may calculate of AND, NAND, OR, NOR, XOR and XNOR depending on the inputs from the programmer. The proposed MG gate was implemented in the design of a novel programmable arithmetic logic unit. The novel 1-bit ALU required only minimal increase in quantum cost and delay due to the MG design, which also allowed for increased functionality for the programmer.

Next, presented reversible implementations of ripple carry adder(RCA) and kogge-stone adder. A reversible implementation of the carry logic presented in the Kogge-Stone was presented and verified. The proposed design of 4-bit ALU with RCA and Kogge-Stone adder were compared in terms of delay.

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A Novel 3 Transistor XOR Gate Based Full Adder Design for VLSI Applications

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Abstract--This paper deals with a new way of designing XOR gate using 3 transistors. A full adder circuit has been designed using proposed 3T XOR circuit and a transmission gate is used extensively in very large-scale integration (VLSI) application. The power consumption of the circuit is in range of 421.7256uW to 581.542uW in 0.35 um technology with a voltage supply range of 1.8V to 3.3V. The simulation process has performed by the SPICE and DSCH tool based on TSMC 0.35um CMOS technology. The power consumed by the 3T XOR gate as well as single bit full adder has been compared with previous reported circuits, the proposed circuit shows good performance in terms of the factors power consumption, speed and area optimization(transistor count).

Keywords: CMOS, transmission gate, full adder, exclusive-OR (XOR).

I. INTRODUCTION

Now a days electronic devices like laptops, portable systems, and cellular networks with increasing demand of low power consumption, less area occupation, less delay, high speed and high degree of sophistication. Attentions towards Research in low power VLSI (very large-scale integration) have increased. With increase in the number of transistors integrated on a chip, power consumption of the integrated circuit is also increasing leads to cause reliability and packaging hazards [1]. In Complementary Metal Oxide Semiconductor VLSI circuits power consumption can be categorized into three different ways: Dynamic, static and short circuit power consumption [2].

$$P_{total} = P_{dynamic} + P_{static} + P_{short\ circuit} \dots(1)$$

Static power is because of unwanted leakage current when transistor is in off state. The dynamic power dissipation is due to switching action of parasitic components, also called switching power. Short circuit power consumption is because of current flowing from V_{dd} to V_{ss} . [2].

Binary addition is a fundamental arithmetic operation which is used extensively in many very

large-scale integration (VLSI) systems such as application-specific digital signal processing (DSP) and microprocessors. In recent years several variations of different logic styles have been proposed to implement 1-bit adder cells [1-12]. The basic CMOS 28T full adder design with good load driving capability and high noise margin [3]. In [4] a full adder design with XOR pass transistor logic (PTL) is reported. CMOS adder based on transmission gate using 20 transistors is reported in [5]. Design of full adder using 10 transistors with low power and high delay presented in [6].

II. FULL ADDER CIRCUIT DESCRIPTION

The full adder performance can be explained as follows: the addition of two 1-bit inputs A and B with carry C_{in} gives the two 1-bit outputs Sum and C_{out} , where

$$Sum = (A \oplus B) \oplus C_{in} \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

$$C_{out} = A.B + C_{in}(A \oplus B) \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

In our design, we rewrite the Boolean function as

$$Sum = X \oplus C_{in} = XC_{in}' + X'C_{in} \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

$$C_{out} = A.B + A'.B.C_{in} + A.B'.C_{in} \dots\dots\dots(5)$$

$$C_{out} = (A'.B' + A.B).A + (A'.B + A.B').C_{in} \dots\dots\dots(6)$$

$$C_{out} = A \oplus X = A.X' + A'X \dots\dots\dots(7)$$

Fig. 1: Block diagram of full adder

Table.1. Truth table for full adder

A	B	Cin	SUM	Cout
0	0	0	0	0
0	0	1	1	0
0	1	0	1	0
0	1	1	0	1
1	0	0	1	0
1	0	1	0	1
1	1	0	0	1
1	1	1	1	1

The standard way of designing full adder using XOR gate and multiplexer is as shown in figure (1) of [7]. The XOR gate and multiplexer are basic building blocks in full adder design. Arithmetic operation of full adder circuit is depends on performance of XOR and multiplexer blocks. The design should have less number of transistors to implement XOR circuits for low power dissipation.

The multiplexer circuit MUX is adopted in our proposed design to generate Cout. Transmission gate is used as a 2 to 1 multiplexer. The transmission gate has advantage for the circuit: firstly, it speeds up the carry propagation as a buffer along the carry chain. Secondly, it provides, the transmission gate can improve the output voltage swing as a level restoring circuit. The proposed full adder circuit, which uses two XOR gates and one multiplexer, requires eight transistors. Choosing appropriate width to length ratios of transistors,

Fig.2: Design of proposed XOR cell

Fig.3: Input and output patterns for proposed XOR circuit

A novel xor circuit with 3 transistors shown in fig(2). When A and B both the inputs are Low the circuit producing Logic Low as output, when inputs A is low and B is high then transistor s Q1 is on, Q2 and Q3 are off and provide logic high at output terminal. When input combinations A are high and B is low, Q1 is off, Q2 is on and Q3 is on leads to provide the output as high, when A is high and B is high then circuit provides Low as output. So the proposed circuit functioning as XOR circuit. Output wave forms shown in fig(3).

The proposed 8 transistor full adder circuits designed by joining the 2 XOR circuits and a single 2 to 1 multiplexer. In this circuit the sum output is generated by two XOR gates and carry out is generated by two transistor multiplexer block or transmission gate. It provide the better performance than the previous full adder circuits and obtain less area due to less number of transistor count. A novel design of full adder using proposed XOR gate with 8 transistors has been implemented as shown in fig (4).

Fig.4: Full adder using two XOR gates and multiplexer

Fig.5: Input and output patterns for proposed full adder

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 2 shows power consumption, delay and output voltage levels with variable supply voltage ranging from [3.3-1.8]V for proposed xor gate, power consumed by this circuit is changes from[500.727-89.93] entire simulation done with supply voltage ranging from(1.8-3.3)V is suitable to compare the power consumption and delay.

TABLE.2: Power consumption, delay and output levels of proposed XOR gate.

Supply voltage(V)	Power consumption (μ w)	Output delay(ps)	Minimum level for high output (V)	Maximum level for high output(V)
3.3	500.727	14.466	2.05	0.084
3.0	395.378	15.846	1.84	0.072
2.5	218.996	18.165	1.41	0.054
2.0	127.452	21.099	1.13	0.041
1.8	89.931	23.050	0.92	0.034

Fig.6: Power consumption of XOR gate with supply voltage

Fig.7: Delay of XNOR gate with supply voltage

Fig.6 shows the power consumption versus supply voltage, with this, it has been observed that power consumption of XOR circuit is decreasing with decreasing the supply voltage. Fig.7 shows the output delay versus supply voltage, delay increasing with decrease in supply voltage.

The entire simulation done with supply voltage ranging from(1.8-3.3)V is suitable to compare the power consumption, delay of single bit full adder circuit and also the simulation result of the proposed full adder circuit is compared with existed CMOS full adder circuits. Power consumption has been reduced due to reduced transistor count and reduced capacitance in the XOR circuit. The shorting of terminals from power supply to ground is completely eliminated. So that short circuit current is also low in the circuit.

TABLE 3: Comparison between different types of full adder designs

Full adder type	Power consumption(μ w)	Number of transistors for design
conventional	946.116	28
22T adder	546.289	22
TG adder	371.632	20
10SERF	263.038	10
Present work	197.104	8

Power efficient adders have been designed with different combination of XOR gates and transmission gate transistor multiplexer concept Power consumption has been reduced From the above table

3, It is clear that even though proposed circuit has 8 transistors, still it consuming less power.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this present work a low power and area efficient design of full adder with 8 transistors using proposed 3 transistors XOR gate has been presented. The characteristics of the proposed full adder circuit are compared against earlier reported full adder circuits based on power consumption. Full adder shows the power consumption of 197.104 μw and better output signal levels with reduced transistor count.

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Modeling of Closed Loop PID Controller for an Auto-Pilot Aircraft Roll Control

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Abstract---An aircraft contains three rotational motions like pitch, yaw and roll. The roll motion is controlled by the ailerons that are present on either side of an aircraft. In this paper, ailerons are considered as plant and its transfer function is used in modeling of the controller. The PID controller modeled performs better roll motion with good stability. From the MATLAB simulation results it is shown that the PID controller has the ability to minimize error between input and output with more stability and less response time with considerable overshoot.

Keywords----Ailerons, PID controller, Roll motion, MATLAB.

I. INTRODUCTION

After the successful development of man-carrying airplane by Wright brothers, the development of auto-pilots emerged. The first auto-pilot (or) automatic flight controller in the world is designed by the Sperry brothers in 1912. Currently, the auto-pilot design relies heavily on automatic control systems to monitor and control the aircraft subsystems [1]. Generally, an aircraft is controlled by three main control surfaces. They are elevator, rudder, and ailerons. These three control surfaces are used to control pitch, yaw and roll actions of an aircraft respectively.

Elevator, rudder and ailerons are depicted in fig. 1. Pitch control is achieved by changing lift. Yaw control is achieved by deflecting a flap on vertical tail called rudder and roll control can be achieved by deflecting small flaps present toward the wing tips in differential manner and these are called ailerons. The two ailerons are typically

interconnected and both ailerons move in opposite direction to each other. The roll motion achieved by these ailerons is used to bank the aircraft.

Fig. 1: Controls of an aircraft [Showing elevators, rudder, ailerons]

The rolling motion of an aircraft is controlled by adjusting the roll angle with the use of ailerons. Roll angle control is a lateral problem and this work is developed to control the roll angle of an aircraft for roll control in order to stabilize the system, when an aircraft performs the rolling action.

II. MODELING OF ROLL CONTROL SYSTEM

Consider the following state and output matrix equations describing the lateral directional equations of motion of an aircraft.

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}(t) &= A x(t) + B u(t) \\ y(t) &= C x(t) + D u(t) \end{aligned} \quad \text{-----(1)}$$

All the four states of 'x' are available for the controller. When the parameters in the plant have non-linearities and time-varying dynamics, the control system should possess a mechanism for automatically adjusting them. By using a fixed

controller we cannot achieve a satisfactory compromise between robust stability and performance. Then we have to use adaptive control. The adaptive control use is justified on complex and mission critical systems exhibiting time-varying dynamics.

The roll angle motion of an aircraft is controlled by adjusting roll angle signal. In this study, an auto-pilot controller is modeled to control the roll angle of an aircraft. The roll motion depends upon many parameters like side slip angle, rolling rate, yawing rate, aileron deflection and so on. The roll control system is shown in fig.2

Fig. 2: Description of roll control system [Figure adapted from [2]]

From the fig.2, Yb and Zb represent the aerodynamics force components, phi and delta represent the orientation of the aircraft i.e.; roll angle in the earth-axis system and aileron deflection angle respectively. Referring to fig. 2 the different forces, moments and velocity components of an aircraft system are shown in fig.3. From the figure 3 we analyze that L,M,N represent the aerodynamic moment components, the terms p, q, r represent the angular rate components of roll, pitch, yaw axis and the terms u, v, w represent the velocity components of roll, pitch and yaw axis.

Fig.3: Definition of forces, moments and velocity components

$$u = u + \otimes u \quad v = v + \otimes v \quad w = w + \otimes w$$

$$p = p + \otimes p \quad q = q + \otimes q \quad r = r + \otimes r$$

$$Y = Y + \otimes Y \quad L = L + \otimes L \quad M = M + \otimes M$$

By applying Newton's law and making relevant assumptions for simplification and finding the transfer function, the transfer function from aileron deflection angle to roll angle is given by the following equation [3].

$$\frac{\Delta\phi(s)}{\Delta\delta(s)} = \frac{-28.92s^2 - 29.81s - 140.8}{s^2 + 9.409s^2 + 14.02s^2 + 48.5s + 0.3979}$$

All these parameters are time dependent and time-varying dynamics.

III. PID CONTROLLER

In most of the research literature, different control algorithms and methods are discussed for reconfigurable control [4]. A discussed in [4] there are different control approaches. Among them adaptive control is widely used because the controller has the ability to analyze nonlinearities and time-varying dynamics that are found in most of the processes. Several control strategies have been proposed in the literature, such as PID [5][6], fuzzy logic [3][7], neural networks [8], LQR [5][6]. Among all, PID is the very simple and easy to control nonlinearities and time-varying parameters. A fixed controller cannot be implemented to achieve satisfactory results. So, continuous adaption to these parameters is required for controlling of roll motion. An adaptive control is modelled for the roll motion i.e., dependent on different dynamic parameters[11].

For the design of PID (proportional-Integral-Derivative) controller, we require the specification of three parameters: proportional gain, integral time constant and derivative time constant. The following transfer function from [9] describes the PID controller.

$$G_c(s) = K_p + K_p/T_i \cdot s + K_p \cdot T_d \cdot s \quad \text{----- (2)}$$

It can also be re-written as

$$G_c(s) = K_p + K_i/s + K_d \cdot s \quad \text{----- (3)}$$

Where Kp is the proportional gain

$K_i = K_p/T_i$ is the integral gain

$K_d = K_p /T_d$ is the derivative gain of the controller.

The discrete time equivalent expression can be given as

$$u(k) = K_p e(k) + K_i T_s \sum e(i) + K_d /T_s \Delta e(k) \text{ ----- (4)}$$

Where $u(k)$ is the control signal

'i' is considered from 1 to n.

$e(k)$ is the error signal between reference input and the plant output.

T_s is the sampling period and

$$\Delta e(k) = e(k) - e(k-1).$$

The PID parameters K_p , K_i , K_d are manipulated to produce various response curves for a given plant. The parameters of PID controller can be changed in two types. Firstly, by using Zeigler-Nichols tuning formula [10]. In second way, adaptively the parameters are estimated and hence they are called adaptive controllers.

IV. MODELLING OF PID CONTROLLER

The general structure of a auto-pilot control system will be as shown in [4]. Specifically, the aileron deflection is controlled by the roll control loop. The roll control block diagram is as shown in fig. 4. The deflection of ailerons is achieved from the force initiated by actuators. The amount of force, direction and angle how much the deflection must be, all these parameters are obtained by the control system. The input to the control system is the data from different sensors. The data obtained from the sensors is mixed in data fusion and filtering unit and if any error occurs it is minimized by the controller.

Fig 4: Block diagram of roll control

In this study, the controller here in the block diagram is PID controller i.e., implemented by MATLAB simulink. The MATLAB simulink diagram of PID controller is as shown in fig. 5.

Fig. 5: Simulink model of PID Controller

The input to the PID controller is the error signal i.e., obtained by the difference between input and feedback from the plant. In this study, as we are considering the roll angle motion of an aircraft, we limit ourselves for acceptable stability and medium fastness. We modeled a MATLAB simulink model as shown in fig. 5 considering the plant as roll motion control.

After extensive simulation study on various values for parameters of PID controller for roll transfer function implementation, we determined values for K_p , K_i , K_d as a good compromise between stability and performance.

The K_u value is tuned and chosen, the point of sustained oscillations. By using K_u and relationship equations [11], K_p , K_i , K_d values are determined and the response for the particular values are shown in the results. The K_p , K_i , K_d values are manipulated for different values and final appropriate response is considered for the better error reduction of the sensed input data. The resultant signal with minimum error will be given to analog to ARINC 429 converter and then to actuators followed by ailerons for the smooth and stable aileron deflection of an aircraft for roll. Always roll motion should be performed in cruise state only.

V. RESULTS

The open loop response of the system is not considered because of its exponentially rising output, as it does not use feedback for necessary corrective measure. The closed loop structure with feedback mechanism provides a better response

with ringing and longer settling time. To achieve a better response, a PID controller has been modelled with the plant. The response of the system with the plant is more stable with less ringing and settling time, with some considerable overshoot. The transient characteristics of the PID controller are shown in fig.6.

Fig 6: Simulation waveform of PID Controller

From fig. 6 it is evident that $T_r=0.1$ msec, $T_p=0.3$ msec, $T_s=0.9$ msec, Overshoot=16% with $K_p=4.2$, $K_i=1$, $K_d=0.12$. After multiple trials these K_p , K_i , K_d values are selected as optimum values.

V. CONCLUSION

Due to the limitations of the open loop system we introduce a closed loop system with efficient characteristics using PID controller. The PID controller has dynamic response compared to other normal controllers. The designed controller possesses response time in milliseconds with very good settling time but with considerable overshoot. The modeled PID controller has the capability of controlling roll motion effectively making it suitable for auto-pilot roll control.

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Reduction of PAPR using Modified SLM Technique-Application to OFDM Systems

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Abstract – Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM) is an efficient method of data transmission. It is a base for high speed communication systems. The main drawback of OFDM system is that it suffers from high Peak – to – Average Power Ratio (PAPR). Due to high PAPR there is inefficient use of high power amplifier and this could limit transmission efficiency. OFDM consist of large number of independent subcarriers, as a result of which the amplitude of such a signal can have high peak values. In this paper, we introduce a modified SLM technique to reduce PAPR. The simulation results show PAPR can be reduced by applying the proposed scheme. The complexity is also reduced in proposed scheme. The PAPR of original OFDM is near about 10.4dB. By using SLM technique with original OFDM PAPR is reduced nearly about 3.5dB. And by using the modified SLM technique PAPR is reduced nearly about 3.8dB in comparison to original OFDM.

Keywords – OFDM, SLM, BER, QPSK, PAPR

I. INTRODUCTION

By the turn of the nineteenth century, a great leap in communication system was observed when wireless communication was introduced. After the advent of wireless communication huge change has been observed in the lifestyle of people. Wireless communication which was initially implemented analog domain for transfer has is now-a-days mostly done in digital domain. Instead of a single carrier in the system multiple sub-carriers are implemented to make the process easier.

The performance of wireless communication systems is mainly governed by the wireless channel environment. As opposed to the typically static and predictable characteristics of a wired channel, the wireless channel is rather dynamic and unpredictable, which makes an exact analysis of the wireless communication system often difficult. In recent years, optimization of the wireless communication system has become critical with the rapid growth of mobile communication services and emerging broadband mobile Internet access services. In fact, the understanding of wireless channels will lay the

foundation for the development of high performance and bandwidth-efficient wireless transmission technology.

OFDM has several advantages like high spectral efficiency, robustness to channel fading, immunity to impulse interference, uniform average spectral density, capacity to handle very strong echoes and less non-linear distortion. OFDM is the modulation technique used in many new broadband communication systems. In recent years OFDM has emerged as the standard of choice in a number of important high data applications. OFDM is so popular for new broadband systems due to the reason that most broadband system contains multipath transmission and it gives a simple way of dealing with multipath.

Though OFDM has many advantages there are disadvantages also. One of the major disadvantages of OFDM is the high Peak-to-Average power ratio of OFDM signal[1]. These multi – carrier systems have a problem that Peak – to – Average power ratio increases with the increase of number of subcarrier, which causes poor efficiency or serious performance degradation to transmit power amplifier. Many PAPR reduction techniques have been proposed [2-3]. These techniques can be mainly categorized into signal scrambling techniques and signal distortion techniques.

II. ORTHOGONAL FREQUENCY DIVISION MULTIPLEXING

With the ever growing demand of this generation, need for high speed communication has become an utmost priority. Various multicarrier modulation techniques have evolved in order to meet these demands, few notable among them being Code Division Multiple Access (CDMA) and Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM)[4]. Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing is a frequency – division multiplexing (FDM) scheme utilized as a digital multi – carrier modulation method. A large number of closely spaced orthogonal sub – carriers is used to carry data. The data is

divided into several parallel streams of channels, one for each sub – carriers. Each sub – carrier is modulated with a conventional modulation scheme (such as QPSK) at a low symbol rate, maintaining total data rates similar to the conventional single carrier modulation schemes in the same bandwidth.

The OFDM has many advantage such as high bandwidth efficiency, robustness to the selective fading problem, use of small guard interval, and its ability to combat the ISI problem. The main disadvantages of the OFDM systems is that it exhibits a high peak to average power ratio, namely the peak value of some of the transmitted signals could be much larger than the typical values[5]. PAPR (Peak Average Power Ratio) makes the amplifiers to work in non-linear regions. This will cause inter modulation between the different sub carriers and introduce additional interference to the system. Additional interference leads to an increase in Bit Error Rate (BER). Large PAPR leads to in band distortion and spectral spreading.

Figure 1. FFT Based OFDM Model

Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing is a special form of multicarrier modulation which is particularly suited for transmission over a dispersive channel. Here the different carriers are orthogonal to each other, that is, they are totally independent of one another.

Two periodic signals are orthogonal when the integral of their product over one period is equal to zero.

For the case of continuous time:

$$\int_0^T \cos(2\pi nft) \cos(2\pi mft) dt = 0$$

For the case of discrete time:

$$\sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \cos\left(\frac{2\pi kn}{N}\right) \cos\left(\frac{2\pi km}{N}\right) dt = 0$$

Where $m \neq n$ in both cases.

III. PROBLEM OF PEAK TO AVERAGE POWER RATIO IN OFDM

An OFDM signal consists of a number of independently modulated sub carriers, which can give a large peak-to-average power (PAP) ratio when added up coherently. When N signals are added with the same phase, they produce a peak power that is N times the average power[6-8]. High PAPR of the transmitted signals results in clipping noise, non-linear distortions of power amplifiers, BER performance degradation, energy spilling into adjacent channels, inter modulation effects on the sub carriers, warping of the signal constellation in each sub channel, increased complexity in the analog to digital and digital to analog converter.

Let the data block of length N be represented by a vector $X=[X_0, X_1, X_2 \dots X_{N-1}]^T$. Duration of any symbol X_k in the set 'X' is 'T' and represents one of the subcarriers $\{f_n, n=0,1,\dots,N-1\}$ set. As the N sub-carriers chosen to transmit the signal are orthogonal to each other, so we can have $f_n = n\Delta f$, where $n\Delta f = 1/NT$ and NT is the duration of the OFDM data block 'X'.

The PAPR of the transmitted signal is defined as

$$PAPR = \frac{\max_{0 \leq t \leq NT} |x(t)|^2}{\frac{1}{NT} \int_0^{NT} |x(t)|^2 dt}$$

PAPR is defined as a ratio of peak instantaneous power to the average power. Reducing the max $|x(t)|$ is the principle goal of PAPR technique.

IV. PAPR REDUCTION TECHNIQUES

There are several techniques to reduce PAPR of the OFDM system [9]. These techniques are classified into two i.e. Signal Scrambling Techniques and Signal Distortion Techniques. In signal scrambling techniques we basically scramble the codes to reduce PAPR. Coding techniques can be used for signal scrambling.

Signal scrambling technique can be further classified into:-

1. With explicit side information.
2. Without explicit side information.

Signal scrambling technique with explicit side information is of two types i.e. coding based and probabilistic schemes. Selective level mapping comes under probabilistic schemes. Hence selective mapping can be said to be a part of signal scrambling technique with explicit side information.

V. THE SELECTIVE MAPPING TECHNIQUE & PROPOSED SCHEME

Selective mapping scheme is a technique in which multiple phase rotations are applied to the constellation points, and the one that minimizes the time signal peak is used. Selective mapping involves generating a large set of data vectors all representing the same information. The data vector with the lowest resulting PAPR is selected. Information about the selected and transmitted data vectors is coded and these codes are by an additional sub carriers [10-11].

Figure 2. Block Diagram of SLM Technique

In this technique the actual transmit signal lowest PAPR is selected from a set of sufficiently different signals which all represents the same information. SLM Technique is very flexible as they do not impose any restriction on modulation applied in the subcarriers or on their number. In proposed scheme we have modified the SLM technique. Earlier in SLM technique we have used phase sequences $[B(1), B(2), B(3), B(4)] = [1, -1, j, -j]$.

In the proposed scheme we have used phase sequences $[B(1), B(2), B(3), \dots, B(u)] = [1, -1, -1, -1, -1, 2, -1, -1, 3, -1, 3, -1, -1, -1, 4]$. First the data source is partitioned into blocks and then serial to parallel conversion of data is done. The transformed data is processed by the modified SLM unit. Then IFFT of data is done. After that one with lowest PAPR is selected [12-14].

VI. SIMULATION RESULT

We carried out extensive simulation using MATLAB to evaluate the PAPR reduction performance of the modified SLM technique. OFDM systems with $N=256$ subcarriers was used for the simulation with QPSK modulation. The parameters used for simulation are given in table below

Modulation	QPSK
Number of data subcarriers(N)	256
Total number of data symbols	1000
Size of the phase sequence	256

We implemented the proposed algorithm of modified SLM to obtain a design in MATLAB. The result is shown in figure 5. We compared the result with earlier SLM technique and it is found that

proposed method worked efficiently.

Figure 3. Block Diagram of Modified SLM Technique

Figure 4. CCDF Plot of PAPR using SLM Technique

Figure 5. CCDF Plot of PAPR for PROPOSED Method

The PAPR obtained by using SLM technique with

phase sequence $[1, -1, j, -j]$ is nearly about 6.9dB. The PAPR obtained by using modified SLM technique is nearly 6.6dB. So we are able to reduce PAPR effectively by nearly 0.3dB by modified SLM technique.

VII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, technique for reducing PAPR has been proposed. By modifying the sequence used in original PAPR, new technique improved the PAPR value near about 6.6dB. The PAPR reduction performances were evaluated using MATLAB simulation tool. Experimental result clearly proves that there is a significant reduction in PAPR. The proposed scheme reduced the PAPR by about 3.8dB.

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Performance Analysis of Multi Stage Fault-Tolerant Adaptive Filter for Noisy ECG Signals

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Abstract: Power-line interference (PLI) may be the most popular interference in electro-cardiogram (ECG). Many studies have been published regarding adaptive PLI filter design for ECG signal processing. The adaptive filter essentially minimizes the mean-squared error between a primary input, which is the noisy ECG, and a reference input, which is either noise that is correlated in some way with the noise in the primary input or a signal that is correlated only with ECG in the primary input. Different filter structures are presented to eliminate the diverse forms of noise: baseline wander, 60 Hz power line interference, muscle noise, and motion artifact. To achieve reliability, the real-time computing systems must be fault-tolerant. This paper proposed a multi stage fault-tolerant adaptive filter for noise cancellation of ECG signals. Comparison of the performance and reliability of non-fault-tolerant and multi stage fault-tolerant adaptive filters are performed. Experimental results showed that the multi stage fault-tolerant adaptive filter not only successfully extract the ECG signals, but also is very reliable.

Keywords: ECG, adaptive filter, noise cancellation, multi stage fault tolerant.

I. INTRODUCTION

Electrocardiogram is the body-surface manifestation of the electrical potentials produced by the heart. The ECG is acquired by placing electrodes on the patient's skin. In a resting setting, the principal technical issue in interpreting ECG waveforms arise from the existence of ambient or background "noise" emanating from other electromagnetic sources, including (1) signals generated by the other organs, muscles and systems of the body, whether from movement or the performance by those organs of their bodily functions, and (2) signals generated by sources external to the body, such as electronic equipment, lights or engines. Cardiologists can identify irregularities in the heart's rate and rhythm, known as arrhythmia, by examining changes in the 0.67 to 40 Hz frequency range. Because of the relatively large amplitudes of these waveforms in this range, cardiologists can easily identify arrhythmia notwithstanding the existence of electromagnetic ambient noise from other sources. However, it is

very difficult for cardiologists to distinguish physiological signals from ambient noise in the broader frequency ranges used to identify different types of heart disease, including cardiac ischemia, hypertrophy and the existence of past or presently occurring heart attacks. The reason for this difficulty is that the physiological signals associated with these other heart diseases are of a much lower amplitude or strength in the lower 0.05 to 0.67 Hz and upper 40 to 150 Hz portions of the frequency range, meaning that they do not stand-out from the ambient noise in these portions and therefore cannot be easily discriminated from that ambient noise. In order to minimize ambient noise in the clinical setting, ECGs are normally taken in the hospital or physician offices. Cardiologists instruct the patient to lie in the supine position, being as still as possible while a reading is taken to reduce ambient noise caused by physical movement. Another method to reduce ambient noise is to reduce the sensitivity of the monitoring equipment, although this alternative results in a loss of signal quality and the ability to read certain signal intricacies.

Subsequently advances in filtering techniques will also improve ambulatory ECG recording routinely used to detect infrequent, and asymptomatic arrhythmias [4], [5] and to trace heart activities in fetals [6], [7]. Furthermore, it will enhance ECG editing [8] used to supplement advances in other technologies such as computer tomography used for cardiology [9]. Microprocessor-based even recorders have been commonly developed and used that carry out online signal processing, data reduction, and arrhythmia detection [10]. Computational power of the microprocessor makes them feasible to implement digital filters for noise cancellation and arrhythmia detection [11].

Adaptive filtering technique using neural networks has been shown to be useful in many biomedical applications [3]. The basic idea behind adaptive filtering has been summarized by Widrow et al. [12]. It reduces the mean-squared error between a primary input, which is the noisy ECG, and a reference input, which is either noise that is primary input [13]. Adaptive filters permit to detect time-varying potentials and to track the dynamic variations of the signal. These

types of filters learn the deterministic signal and remove the noise. Besides, they modify their behavior according to the input signal. Therefore, they can detect shape variations in the ensemble and thus can obtain a better signal estimation.

The first aim of this paper is to construct non-fault tolerant adaptive filter and demonstrate its application in noise cancellation. The adaptive filter weights are updated by using the least mean square algorithm. The constructed filter is proved and demonstrated with a single frequency noise source. The second aim is to introduce a multi state fault-tolerant adaptive filter and demonstrate its improved reliability. A parallel construction is adapted for the two stage fault-tolerant adaptive filter and three stage fault-tolerant adaptive filter whose reliability is compared with that of the non fault-tolerant adaptive filter.

II. NON-FAULT TOLERANT ADAPTIVE FILTER

a) Non-Fault Tolerant Adaptive Filter and its Noise Cancellation System

The adaptive filter without fault tolerance is designed to remove the contaminating signal, as shown in Fig. 1. The ECG signal, s is the original uncontaminated input signal to the network. The desired output is the contaminated ECG signal t . The adaptive filter will do its best to reproduce this contaminated signal, but it only knows about the original 60 Hz noise source, v . Thus, it can only reproduce the part of t that is linearly correlated with v , which is m . In effect, the adaptive filter will attempt to mimic the noise path filter, so that the output of the filter a will be close to the contaminating noise m . In this way the error e will be close to the original uncontaminated ECG signal s . We call $(s+m)$ the primary input, and a the reference signal.

Fig.1 Non-Fault Tolerant Adaptive Filter Noise Cancellation System

Since the adaptive filter output is a and the error is $e = (s+m) - a$, then the mean square error (MSE) is

$$e^2 = ((s+m) - a)^2 = (s+m)^2 - 2(s+m).a + a^2 = (m-a)^2 + s^2 + 2.s.m - 2.s.a \quad \dots (1)$$

Since signal and noise are uncorrelated, the MSE is

$$E[e^2] = E[(m-a)^2] + E[s^2] \quad \dots\dots (2)$$

Minimizing the MSE results in a filter error that is the best least squares estimate of the signal s . The adaptive filter extracts the signal or eliminates noise, by iteratively minimizing the MSE between the primary and the reference inputs.

b) The Least Mean Square (LMS) Algorithm

The LMS algorithm is an iterative technique for minimizing the mean square error (MSE) between the primary input and the reference signal [8]. The adaptive filter weights are updated by using the LMS algorithm. The LMS algorithm can be written in matrix notation:

$$W(k+1) = W(k) + 2\alpha.e(k).p^T(k) \quad \dots\dots (3)$$

and $b(k+1) = b(k) + 2\alpha.e(k) \quad \dots\dots (4)$

where $W(k) = [w_1(k) w_2(k) \dots w_i(k)]^T \quad \dots\dots(5)$

is a set of filter weights at time k , and $w(k)$ is the i th row of the weight matrix.

$$p^T(k) = [p_1(k) p_2(k) \dots p_i(k)]^T \quad \dots\dots(6)$$

is the input vector at time k of the samples from the reference signal. The error is

$$e(k) = r(k) - (s(k) + m(k)) = a(k) \quad \dots\dots(7)$$

where t is the desired primary input from the ECG to be filtered, and $a(k)$ is the filter output that is the best least-squared estimate of $t(k)$.

III. MULTI STAGE FAULT-TOLERANT ADAPTIVE FILTER

a) Two Stage Fault-Tolerant Adaptive Filter

Real-time computing systems must be fault-tolerant: they must be able to continue operating despite the failure of a limited subset of their hardware or software. A fault is a physical defect, imperfection or flaw that occurs within some hardware or software component. A fault can be caused by specification mistakes, implementation mistakes, component defects or external disturbance. The two stage fault-tolerant adaptive filter is shown in Fig.2. The three stage fault-tolerant adaptive filter is shown in Fig.3.

Fig.2 Two stage fault-tolerant adaptive filter Noise Cancellation System

b) Three Stage Fault-Tolerant Adaptive Filter

Fig.3 Three stage fault-tolerant adaptive filter Noise Cancellation System

c) Reliability Analysis of Multi Stage Fault-Tolerant Adaptive Filter

The reliability at time t , $R(t)$, is the conditional probability that the system performs correctly during the period $[0, t]$, given that the system was performing correctly at time 0. The unreliability, $F(t)$, is equal to $1-R(t)$. Often referred to as the probability of failure. Now we compare the reliability of a non-fault-tolerant adaptive filter and that of a two stage fault-tolerant adaptive filter.

For a parallel construction, as shown in Fig.2, two parts are considered to be operating in parallel if the combination is considered failed when both parts fail. The combined system is operational if either is available. From this it follows that the combined availability is $1-(\text{both parts are unavailable})$. The combined availability is shown by the equation below.

$$R = 1 - F_1. F_2 = 1 - (1 - R_1)(1 - R_2)(1 - R_3) \dots (8)$$

When the redundancy of a parallel construction is N , the reliability is

$$R = 1 - F_1. F_2. \dots F_N$$

$$= 1 - \prod_{i=1}^N F_i = 1 - \prod_{i=1}^N (1 - R_i)$$

The reliability of two stage fault-tolerant adaptive filter is

$$R = 1 - (1 - R_1)(1 - R_2)$$

where R_1 is the reliability of adaptive filter 1, and R_2 is the reliability of adaptive filter 2.

Assume the reliability of the two filters are equal, the reliability of the two stage fault-tolerant adaptive filter is simplified as

$$R = 1 - (1 - R_1)^2 = (1 + (1 - R_1)).(1 - (1 - R_1)) \dots (9)$$

$$= R_1 (2 - R_1)$$

$$\frac{R}{R_1} = 2 - R_1$$

Since $0 \leq R_1 \leq 1$, so $1 \leq 2 - R_1 \leq 2$.

In other word, the reliability of two stage fault-tolerant adaptive filter is greater than or equal to that of the non-fault-tolerant adaptive filter. In similar manner we can conclude that the reliability of three stage fault-tolerant adaptive filter is greater than equal to two stage fault-tolerant adaptive filter and greater than non-fault-tolerant adaptive filter.

d) Time-domain measures

In time-domain operation, three different RMS values, root mean square deviation (RMSD), root mean square error (RMSE) and root mean square variation (RMSV) are used to assess the filtering efficacy and the degree of distortion of the signal after running the algorithms.

RMSD is the RMS value obtained from the pure ECG signal minus the restored ECG signal that has been processed by the adaptive filter. A smaller RMSD value indicates a better efficacy of the adaptive filter in eliminating PLI and less distortion of signal after the filtering process.

RMSE is the RMS value of the difference between the restored ECG and the filter output for clean ECG. A smaller

RMSE value indicates a lesser distortion of ECG morphology after the filtering operation. RMSE looks similar to RMSD, yet RMSE takes more considerations on the possibility of the ECG morphology distortion after filtering.

RMSV is the RMS value of the tiny variation from the original input ECG after it has been blindly processed by the algorithms. The RMSV indicates the degree of variation of the ECG signal processed by the adaptive filter. The flow chart for the three RMS values is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 Flow chart for time-domain measures.

IV. EXPERIMENT AND RESULTS

Fig. 5 shows original ECG signal. Fig. 6 shows ECG signal corrupted with 50 Hz noise signal. Fig. 7 shows output of non-fault-tolerant adaptive filter. Fig. 8 & 9 shows the output of multi stage fault-tolerant adaptive filter. Fig. 10 shows mean square error of non-fault-tolerant adaptive filter. Fig. 11 & 12 shows mean square error of multi stage fault-tolerant adaptive filter. So we can conclude that multi stage fault-tolerant adaptive filter removes power line noise effectively with that of non-fault-tolerant adaptive filter.

Fig. 5 Original ECG signal

Fig.6 Noise + ECG signal.

Fig. 7 Output of the non-fault-tolerant adaptive filter.

a) Outputs of the Multi stage fault-tolerant Adaptive filter

Fig. 8 Output of the two stage fault-tolerant adaptive filter.

Fig. 9 Output of the three stage fault-tolerant adaptive filter.

Fig. 10 Output error of the non-fault-tolerant adaptive filter.

b) Outputs errors of the Multi stage fault-tolerant adaptive filter:

Fig. 11 Output error of the two stage fault-tolerant adaptive filter.

Fig. 12 Output error of the three stage fault-tolerant adaptive filter.

The results of filtering 3 kinds of ECG are shown in Table-1. As seen in Table-1 the multi stage fault-tolerant adaptive filter showed better performance in minimizing the distortion of the ECG signal than the non- fault-tolerant adaptive filter.

Table-1: Comparison of multistage adaptive filter RMSD values

Filter	RMSD
NFTADF	0.0214
2FTADF	0.0157
3FTADF	0.0131

V. CONCLUSION

A reliable neural network based fault-tolerant adaptive filter was designed. The filter does not need computation for voting and error detection. As a result, it requires very little computational power or memory while still maintaining the ability to handle complex signal processing. We analyzed the reliability of the non-fault-tolerant and multi stage fault-tolerant adaptive filters. The experimental results showed that the multi stage fault-tolerant adaptive filter is highly reliable after a permanent fault occurs. Thus the adaptive filter approach as described herein can be applied to readily remove 60Hz artifact noise while minimally distorting the true ECG signals.

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Efficiency of Video Coding Standards using PSNR

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Abstract — This paper mainly deals with the performance comparison of several video coding standards by means of peak signal-to-noise ratio and subjective testing like RD curves and average bit-rate savings. A particular procedure is applied for the video coding standards H.264/MPEG4-Advanced Video Coding (AVC), MPEG4V2, MPEG4 at different bit-rates and peak signal-to-noise ratios are estimated. The bit-rate reduction on average is achieved about 50% for comparable to earlier video coding standards. The results obtained illustrate the H.264/MPEG4-AVC achieving high peak signal-to-noise at low bitrates this resembles high coding efficiency, comparing with lower versions of video coding standards.

Keyword- H.264/MPEG4-AVC, MPEG4V2, MPEG4, video coding standards, peak signal-to-noise, RD-curves, bit-rate.

I. INTRODUCTION

The video coding standards MPEG4V2 [1], MPEG4 [2] and H.264/MPEG4 Advanced Video Coding (AVC) [3]-[5] developments coordinated by ITU-T Video Coding Experts Group (VCEG) and ISO/IEC Moving Pictures Expert Group (MPEG). The main principle of video coding standards is coding efficiency optimization. The ability to reduce the bit rate for a given video to achieve high quality of a video is known as coding efficiency. In designing video coding standard for multi use, the coding is done to give much freedom to the encoder and decoder developers for their various implementations. This results in adaptation of wide range of architectures, applications and resources.

Like earlier standards, such as MPEG-4V2[1], MPEG-4 [2] and H.264/MPEG-4 Advanced Video Coding (AVC)[3]-[5] is a lossy compression standard and also based on the motion compensation approach. In many ways these standards are very similar, but each consecutive standard offered a higher compression, while maintaining a similar quality. This has been achieved by improving the steps in the compression algorithm, often at the cost of a higher complexity. In general it is said that H.264/MPEG-4 AVC gives double the compression rate, at the same quality, when compared to MPEG-4V2, MPEG-4 was developed by the Moving Picture Experts Group

(MPEG), together with the ITU-T Video Coding Experts Group (VCEG)[7]. Since both groups have their own way of naming new compression standards, MPEG-4 AVC is also called H.264, which is the name given by VCEG. Both groups have competed in creating better video compression standards since the early nineties.

The H.264/MPEG-4 Advanced Video Coding (AVC) standard was created to offer a higher compression rate, but often at the cost of a higher complexity. This compression gain is achieved by many small improvements, when compared to earlier standards. Some of these changes are better motion compensation, image segmentation into finer blocks, improved entropy encoding schemes and a mandatory de blocking filter. It is however not a single standard, but rather a family of standards. It defines a set of compression tools, which are then used or not used, based on a selected profile. There are several profiles, designed to match the standard to the user's needs. For example the baseline profile offers a low compression rate and some error resilience, while maintaining a low complexity. The main profile, on the other hand, offers high compression gain, at the cost of a high complexity. Based on these profiles the standard can be used in many fields. For example it is used to store videos on Blu-ray discs, but it is also used to stream videos on websites such as Youtube or Vimeo.

II. METHODOLOGY

In determining the PSNR (YUV) values mainly Bjøntegaard measurement [9] methodology is used. It is used to find objective differences of Rate-Distortion (RD) curves calculation [6]. In the used method, the luma and chroma components used together of rate-distortion curves are used. PSNR (YUV) [8] is calculated as the weighted sum $PSNR_Y$, $PSNR_U$, and $PSNR_V$

$PSNR_{(YUV)} = (6 \cdot PSNR_Y + PSNR_U + PSNR_V) / 8$
Y represents → Luma Components which means Brightness.

U & V represents → Chroma Components.

$PSNR = 10 \cdot \log_{10} ((2B - 1)^2 / MSE)$

Where $B = 8$ is the number of bits per sample of the video signal to be coded and the MSE is the SSD divided by the number of samples in the signal. The PSNR measurements per video sequence are computed by averaging the per-picture measurements. Using the bit rate and the combined $PSNR_{YUV}$ as the input to the Bjøntegaard measurement method gives a single average difference in bit rate that (at least partially) takes into account the tradeoffs between luma and chroma component fidelity.

The PSNR (YUV) values of different video sequence at different bitrates are estimated for video coding standards. The methodology used in this paper is represented by a process flow as shown below.

Fig-1 Efficiency Estimation of video Standards

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The test sequence 'park view' is taken for different coding standards such as H.264/MPEG4-AVC, MPEG4v2, and MPEG4 at different bit-rates and the PSNR (YUV) values are determined and tabulated in Table-I.

Table-I PSNR (YUV) values for video coding standards

PSNR(YUV) values for video coding standards			
BIT-RATE(kb)	H.264	MPEG4	MPEG4V2
1000	36.0805	35.8340	35.8123
3000	36.1066	35.8627	35.8196
5000	36.1477	35.8621	35.8321
7000	36.6013	36.4783	36.3831

The PSNR (YUV) values are responsible for drawing RD-curves with respect to different bit-rates for different video coding standards shown in figure-2.

Fig-2 PSNR (YUV) v/s Bit-Rate

The above graph mainly deals with the PSNR v/s bit-rate for different video codings namely MPEG4V2, MPEG4, H.264/MPEG4 Advanced Video Coding (AVC) developments coordinated by ISO/IEC Moving Pictures Expert Group (MPEG) this gives the difference in PSNR of different video codec's with respect to different bit-rates. Thus this graph mainly gives the quality measure of different video codec's of a test video sequence.

These RD-curves determined above are responsible for estimating the bit-rate saving for different video coding standards shown in figure-3.

Fig-3 PSNR (YUV) v/s Bit-Rate Saving

The above graph gives the Bit-rate saving's of different video codec's with respect to the PSNR. This gives the best video codec which is responsible for high PSNR or best video quality at low bit rates.

The average bit-rate savings are tabulated shown in Table-II

Table-II Bit-Rate saving Results

Average Bit-Rate Savings		
Coding Standards	Mpeg4	Mpeg4v2
H.264/Mpeg4-Avc	49.3%	50.6%
Mpeg4	-	45.03%

IV. CONCLUSION

The coding efficiency of H.264/MPEG4 AVC compared to the MPEG4v2 and MPEG4 for the testing sequence park scene are determined through RD-curves drawn from the results in the earlier section. The bit-rate saving of the H.264/MPEG4 Advanced Video Coding (AVC) compared to MPEG4v2, MPEG4 respectively 50.6% and 49.3% with the same video quality. This result in high coding efficiency for H.264/MPEG4 AVC compare to earlier video coding standards.

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Skin Segmentation using Face Color Mapping Technique

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Abstract- A new face detection technique is proposed in this paper, which uses mixed Gaussian color model, adaptive threshold, and template matching techniques. Face detection provides a content-based representation of the image where it can be used for encoding, manipulation, enhancement, indexing, modeling, pattern recognition and object tracking purposes. The face detection algorithm involves three stages: Applying mixed Gaussian color model, adaptive threshold algorithm, and template matching. Experimental results show that this algorithm is quite practical and faster in comparison to the techniques such as neural networks and other techniques.

Keywords - Face detection, Mixed Gaussian color model, Adaptive threshold, Morphological operations, Template matching.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human face detection has drawn considerable attention in the past decades as it is one of the fundamental problems in computer vision. Given a single image, the ideal face detection should identify and locate all faces regardless of its three-dimensional position, orientation, and lighting conditions. The existing face detection techniques can be classified into four categories, namely, knowledge-based methods, feature invariant approaches, template matching methods, appearance based methods. Detailed descriptions of algorithms and representative works for face detection in a single image within the above four categories can be found in [3], [5]. This paper proposes a novel face detection algorithm with color based technique for detecting frontal human face images using the mixed Gaussian color models and template matching techniques.

Although face detection has been investigated using various approaches, there is still much to explore. Firstly, face detection has been regarded as a challenging problem in the field of computer vision, due to the inherent variability arising from face characteristics (age, gender and race), geometry (distance and viewpoint) and image content

(background, illumination, occlusion and disguise). However, many existing methods only work well on simple input images with a benign background and frontal view of the person's face. To cope with more complicated images and conditions, many more assumptions will have to be made. In fact, there is generally little or no constraint on the number, location, size, and orientation of human faces in image and video databases. And the background of these images and video scenes is usually complex. Secondly, most existing face detection methods are mainly based on gray-level images. Color images and video sequences are seldom addressed.

The proposed face detection system mainly consists of four stages: mixed Gaussian color model, adaptive threshold algorithm, and template matching. First, skin model is created based on YCbCr and YIQ space respectively. By applying the skin models based on the statistical distribution of skin tone colors in YIQ and YCbCr space, image is segmented into skin region and non-skin region. The face image is segmented from the skin region. The template matching technique is used to mark the face region in the given image. A moderate level of false alarms is tolerable in this stage

II. FACE DETECTION ALGORITHM

The use of color information has been introduced to the face-locating problem in recent years. Most publications [1, 2, 3,5] have shown that color is a powerful descriptor that has practical use in the extraction of the face detection. Modeling skin color requires choosing an appropriate color space and identifying a cluster associated with skin color in this space. YIQ color space is used in commercial color television broadcasting. YCbCr space is a hardware orientated model and is used in most video standards like H.263, MPEG-1, MPEG-2, and MPEG-4. HSV space is another commonly used for image analysis. However, in this paper, the YCbCr and YIQ color spaces are used for creating skins. Color model, and the reasons are twofold. First, the chrominance

components such as Cb, Cr are separated from the luminance Y. So an effective use of the chrominance information for modeling human skin color can be achieved in these color space. Second, this format is typically used in video coding, and therefore the use of the same format for segmentation will avoid the extra computation required in conversation. Many research studies [7, 8] assume that chrominance components of skin-tone color are independent of the luminance component. In fact, the skin-tone color is non-linearly dependent on luminance. In [1], Rein-Lien Hsu found that although skin colors of different people appear to vary over a wide range, they differ less in chrominance than brightness, specially the skin colors from a compact area in the YCbCr plane and they nonlinearly transform the YCbCr space to make skin cluster luma independent.

However, clothes cannot be segmented from face areas, because skin- colors and clothes colors locate at the same range in the YCbCr, plane. Based on the color areas in the YCbCr color space and YIQ color space, two Gaussian models are utilized for representing the skin color model with mean and covariance

Among all the stages, this first stage is the most important. Based on the proposed model of skin color, the color segmentation has to remove as many pixels as possible that are unlikely to belong to the skin region. However, the result of color segmentation is the detection of pixels in a skin area and may also include other areas where the distribution of pixels coincides with the proposed model of skin color areas.

A. Skin Segmentation

The skin regions can be segmented from the rest of the image through a thresholding process. To process different images of different people with different skin color, a fixed threshold value is not good. So an adaptive thresholding process is required to find the optimal threshold value. The adaptive thresholding is based on the observation that the stepping the threshold value down may increase the segmented regions. The threshold value at which the minimum increase is observed while stepping down the stepping down the threshold value will be the optimal threshold. The following stages are used to remove those pixels, which do not belong to the facial regions.

B. Detection of Skin regions

In order to determine the frontal human face it is necessary to determine the number of skin regions in the image. A skin region is defined as a closed region in the image. The process of determining the number of skin regions in a binary image is by labeling such

regions. An 8-bit connected neighborhood is used to label the skin regions.

i) Number of holes inside a region

If a skin region has one or more holes, it is assumed to be a face region. Otherwise the skin region is assumed to non- face region and it is ignored It is necessary to find which regions have at least one hole inside it.

Fig. 1. The skin color model face detection algorithm.

ii) Width and height of the region

First, the regions with holes are filled out. This is to avoid problems when holes are encountered. Now it is necessary to determine the height and width by moving 4 pointers: one from the left, right, top and bottom of the image. If a pixel is found with a value other than 0, the pointer is stopped and this is the coordinate of a boundary. With the help of the 4 values, the height of the facial region is computed by subtracting the bottom and top values and the width is computed by subtracting the right and the left values.

iii) Region ratio

The width and the height of the region are used to improve the decision process. The height to width ratio of the human faces is around 1. In order to have less misses however, it is found that a minimum good value is 0.8. Ratio values below 0.8 do not suggest a face since human faces are oriented vertically. The ratio should also have an upper limit.

This is determined by analyzing the results in our experiments that a good upper limit should be around 1.6 while the above-mentioned information improves the classification, it can also be a drawback for cases such as the arms that are very long. If the skin region for the arms has holes near the top, this might yield into a false classification.

C. Template matching

One of the most important characteristics of this method is that it uses a human face template to take the final decision of determining if a skin region

represents a face. The template is chosen by averaging 16 frontal view faces of males and females wearing no glasses and having no facial hair. The template used is shown in figure 2. Template face (model) is used to verify the existence of faces in skin regions. The template face has to be positioned and rotated in the same coordinates as the skin regions image. The template face is resized according to the height and the width of the region of the region computed. The resized template face is rotated to $-\theta$, so that it is aligned in the same direction as the skin region. The center of the rotated template face is computed. Then the cross-correlation between the part of the image corresponding to the skin region and the template face is computed. The coordinates of the frontal face image are determined and a rectangle is drawn in the gray scale image.

d) Skin Color Classification

The aim of skin color pixel classification is to determine if a color pixel is a skin color or non skin color. Good skin color pixel classification should provide coverage of all different skin types (blackish, yellowish, brownish, whitish, etc.) and cater for as many different lighting conditions as possible. This section describes the color spaces and the classification algorithms that will be investigated in this study.

e) Color Representations

In some cases, color classification is done using only pixel chrominance because it is expected that skin segmentation may become more robust to lighting variations if pixel luminance is discarded. In this paper, we investigate how the choice of color space and the use of chrominance channels affect skin segmentation. We should note that there exist numerous color spaces but many of them share similar characteristics. Hence, in this study, we focus on four representative color spaces which are commonly used in the image processing field [8]:

- **RGB:** Colors are specified in terms of the three primary colors: red (R), green (G), and blue (B).
- **HSV:** Colors are specified in terms of hue (H), saturation (S), and intensity value (V) which are the three attributes that are perceived about color. The transformation between HSV and RGB is nonlinear. Other similar color spaces are HIS, HLS, and HCL.
- **YCbCr:** Colors are specified in terms of luminance (the Y channel) and chrominance (Cb and Cr channels). The transformation between YCbCr and RGB is linear. Other similar color spaces include YIQ and YUV.

- **CIE-Lab:** Designed to approximate perceptually uniform color spaces (UCSs), the CIE-L ab color space is related to the RGB color space through a highly nonlinear transformation. Examples of similar color spaces are CIE-Luv and Farnsworth UCS.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this paper a frontal face detection algorithm using mixed Gaussian color model is implemented according to the skin color information in color images. A variety of images with different illumination condition, with complicated backgrounds were used. The photo images taken under controlled lighting condition like in a studio or inside a building have best results. The photo images taken under uncontrolled lighting conditions such as effect of sun on the open environment have better results. The images with more than one facial images used have good results. Best results are obtained from the photos which have good resolution and fixed lighting conditions.

Fig 2: Input template image

Fig3. The process of determining the number of stages in skin regions of color image

Fig4. Face detected with color image results

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a novel frontal face detection based on mixed Gaussian color model technique is developed and implemented using face images with different pose, illumination conditions. This algorithm gives very good results for images with controlled lighting conditions. Experiments with variety of images prove that this technique of detecting face images is more efficient and useful. The method is good because it reduces much of the computational work.

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Next Generation Wireless Communication-5G

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Abstract—5G is an incremental advance on 4G. The previous four generations of cellular technology have each been a major paradigm shift that has broken backward compatibility. However, unlike the previous four generations, it will also be highly integrative providing universal high-rate coverage and a seamless user experience. To support this, the core network will also have to reach new levels of flexibility and intelligence, spectrum regulation will need to be rethought and improved, and energy and cost efficiencies will become even more critical considerations. In this paper the key challenges for future research and 5G standardization activities are discussed, providing overview of the current literature.

Keywords—Cellular systems, energy efficiency, HetNets, massive MIMO, millimeter wave, small cells.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. The Road to 5G

IN just the past year, preliminary interest and discussions about a possible 5G standard have evolved into a fullfledged conversation that has captured the attention and imagination of researchers and engineers around the world. As the long-term evolution (LTE) system embodying 4G has now been deployed and is reaching maturity, where only incremental improvements and small amounts of new spectrum can be expected, it is natural for researchers to forecast the next stage [1].

B. Engineering Requirements for 5G

1) **Data Rate**: The need to support the mobile data traffic explosion is unquestionably the main driver behind 5G. Data rate can be measured in several different ways, and there will be a 5G goal target for each such metric:

- a) **Aggregate data rate** or **area capacity** refers to the total amount of data the network can serve, characterized in bits/s per unit area. The general consensus is that this quantity will need to increase by roughly 1000× from 4G to 5G.
- b) **Edge rate** or **5% rate** is the worst data rate that a user can reasonably expect to receive when in range of the network, and so is an important metric and has a concrete engineering meaning. Goals for the 5G edge rate range from 100 Mbps (easily enough to support high-definition streaming) to as much as 1 Gbps. Meeting 100 Mbps for 95% of users will be extraordinarily challenging, even with major technological advances. This requires about a 100× advance

since current 4G systems have a typical 5% rate of about 1 Mbps, although the precise number varies quite widely depending on the load, the cell size, and other factors.

- c) **Peak rate** is the best-case data rate that a user can hope to achieve under any conceivable network configuration. The peak rate is a marketing number, devoid of much meaning to engineers and likely to be in the range of tens of Gbps.

Meeting the requirements in (a)-(b), which are several times higher than current 4G technology, respectively, are the main focus of this paper.

2) **Energy and Cost**: As we move to 5G, costs and energy consumption will, ideally, decrease, but at least they should not increase on a per-link basis. Since the per-link data rates being offered will be increasing by about 100×, this means that the Joules per bit and cost per bit will need to fall by at least 100×. In this article, we address technological solutions that promise reasonable cost and power scaling.

C. Device Types and Quantities

5G will need to be able to efficiently support a much larger and more diverse set of devices. With the expected rise of machine-to-machine communication, a single macrocell may need to support 10 000 or more low-rate devices along with its traditional high-rate mobile users. This will require changes to the control plane and network management relative to 4G.

II. KEY TECHNOLOGIES HIGH DATA RATES

Of the requirements outlined in Section I-B, certainly the one that gets the most attention is the need for radically higher data rates across the board.

The combination of more nodes per unit area and Hz, more Hz, and more bits/s/Hz per node, will compound into many more bits/s per unit area. Other ideas not in the above categories, e.g., interference management through BS cooperation [10] may also contribute improvements, but the lion's share of the surge in capacity should come from ideas in the above categories.

1) **Base Station Densification Gains**: We define the BS densification gain $\rho(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) > 0$ as the effective increase in data rate relative to the increase in network density, which is a proxy here for cost. Specifically, if we achieve a data rate R_1 (could be any measure

thereof, e.g., edge rate or aggregate) when the BS density is λ_1 BSs/km² and then we consider a higher BS density λ_2 , with corresponding rate R_2 , then the densification gain is the slope of the rate increase over that density range.

$$\rho(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) = \frac{(R_2 - R_1)/R_1}{(\lambda_2 - \lambda_1)/\lambda_1} \quad (1)$$

For example, if the network density is doubled, and the edge data rate increases by 50% (for example since some of the added BSs were lightly loaded), then the densification gain is $\rho = 0.5$. In some applications with channel access protocols like CSMA that are inefficient in high density, it is possible that $\rho < 0$, which is colloquially referred to as “the tragedy of the commons”, but for cellular network with a centralized MAC we can safely assume $\rho > 0$.

In general, quantifying and optimizing the densification gains in a wide variety of deployment scenarios and network models is a key area for continued small-cell research.

2) *Multi-RAT Association*: Networks will continue to become increasingly heterogeneous as we move toward 5G. A key feature therein will be increased integration between different RATs, with a typical 5G-enabled device having radios capable of supporting not only a potentially new 5G standard (e.g., at mmWave frequencies), but also 3G, numerous releases of 4 G LTE including possibly LTE-Unlicensed, several types of WiFi, and perhaps direct device-to-device (D2D) communication, all across a great many spectral bands. Hence, determining which standard(s) and spectrum to utilize and which BS(s) or users to associate with will be a truly complex task for the network (see Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. User association in a multi-RAT network over many frequency bands is complex. In this simplified scenario, a mobile user in turn associates with different BSs based on a tradeoff between the gain to that BS and the traffic load (congestion) that it is experiencing.

3) *Mobility Support*: Clearly, the continued network densification and increased heterogeneity poses challenges for the support of mobility. Although a hefty share of data is served to stationary indoor users, the support of mobility and always-on connectivity is arguably the single most important feature of cellular networks relative to WiFi. Because modeling and analyzing the effect of mobility on network performance is difficult, we expect to see somewhat *ad hoc* solutions such as in LTE Rel-11

where user-specific virtual cells are defined to distinguish the physical cell from a broader area where the user can roam without the need for handoff, communicating with any BS or subset of BSs in that area.

4) *Cost*: Evolving to ever-smaller cells requires ever-smaller, lower-power and cheaper BSs, and there is no fundamental reason a BS needs to be more expensive than a user device or a WiFi node. Nevertheless, obtaining permits, ensuring fast and reliable backhaul connections, and paying large monthly site rental fees for operator-controlled smallcell placements have proven a major hindrance to the growth of picocell, distributed antennas, and other enterprise-quality small cell deployments.

B. Millimeter Wave

Terrestrial wireless systems have largely restricted their operation to the relatively slim range of microwave frequencies that extends from several hundred MHz to a few GHz and corresponds to wavelengths in the range of a few centimeters up to about a meter. By now though, this spectral band—often called “beachfront spectrum”—has become nearly fully occupied, in particular at peak times and in peak markets. Regardless of the efficacy of densification and offloading, much more bandwidth is needed.

1) *Propagation Issues*: Concerning mmWave propagation for 5G, the main issues under investigation are:

Pathloss: If the electrical size of the antennas (i.e., their size measured by the wavelength $\lambda = c/f_c$ where f_c is the carrier frequency) is kept constant, as the frequency increases the antennas shrink and their effective aperture scales with $\lambda^2/4\pi$; then, the free-space pathloss between a transmit and a receive antenna grows with f_c^2 . Thus, increasing f_c by an order of magnitude, say from 3 to 30 GHz, adds 20 dB of power loss regardless of the transmit-receive distance. However, if the antenna aperture at one end of the link is kept constant as the frequency increases, then the free-space pathloss remains unchanged. Further, if both the transmit and receive antenna apertures are held constant, then the free-space pathloss actually *diminishes* with f_c^2 : a power gain that would help counter the higher noise floor associated with broader signal bandwidths.

Blocking: MmWave signals exhibit reduced diffraction and a more specular propagation than their microwave counterparts, and hence they are much more susceptible to blockages. This results in a nearly bimodal channel depending on the presence or absence of Line-of-Sight (LoS). According to recent measurements, as the transmit-receive distance grows the pathloss accrues close to the free-space value of 20 dB/decade under LoS propagation, but drops to 40 dB/decade plus an additional blocking loss of 15–40 dB otherwise.

Atmospheric and Rain Absorption: The absorption due to air and rain is noticeable, especially the 15 dB/km oxygen absorption within the 60-GHz band (which is in fact why this band is unlicensed), but it is inconsequential for the urban cellular deployments currently envisioned where BS spacings might be on the order of 200 m. In fact, such absorption is beneficial since it further attenuates interference from more distant BSs, effectively increasing the isolation of each cell.

Fig. 2. MmWave-enabled network with phantom cells.

where a narrow beam could possibly be found, or deploy extremely large coding/spreading gains over a wider beam that is successively narrowed in a multistage acquisition procedure. Developing solutions to this problem, particularly in the context of high mobility, is an important research challenge.

Leveraging the Legacy 4G Network: A concurrent utilization of microwave and mmWave frequencies could go a long way toward overcoming some of the above hurdles. An interesting proposal in that respect is the notion of “phantom cells” (relabelled “soft cells” within 3GPP), where mmWave frequencies would be employed for payload data transmission from small-cell BSs while the control plane would operate at microwave frequencies from macro BSs (cf. Fig. 2).

C. Massive MIMO

Stemming from research that blossomed in the late 1990 s, MIMO communication was introduced into WiFi systems around 2006 and into 3G cellular shortly thereafter. In essence, MIMO embodies the spatial dimension of the communication that arises once a multiplicity of antennas are available at BSs and mobile devices.

1) *Pilot Contamination and Overhead Reduction:* Pilot transmissions can be made orthogonal among same-cell users, to facilitate cleaner channel estimates, but must be reused across cells—for otherwise all available resources would end up consumed by pilots. This inevitably causes interference among pilots in different cells and hence puts a floor on the quality of the channel estimates. This interference, so-called “pilot contamination,” does not vanish as the number of BS antennas grows large, and so is the one impairment that remains asymptotically.

2) *Architectural Challenges:* A more serious challenge to the realization of the massive MIMO vision has to do with its architecture. The vision requires radically different BS structures where, in lieu of a few high-power amplifiers feeding a handful of

sector antennas, we would have a myriad of tiny antennas fed by correspondingly low-power amplifiers; most likely each antenna would have to be integrated with its own amplifier.

3) *Full-Dimension MIMO and Elevation Beamforming:* Existing BSs mostly feature linear horizontal arrays, which in tower structures can only accommodate a limited number of antennas, due to form factors, and which only exploit the azimuth angle dimension. By adopting planar 2D arrays as in Fig. 3 and further exploiting the elevation angle, the so-called full-dimension MIMO (FD-MIMO) can house many more antennas with the same form factor. As a side benefit, tailored vertical beams increase the signal power and reduce interference to users in neighboring cells.

4) *Channel Models:* Parallel to the architectural issues run those related to channel models, which to be sound require extensive field measurements. Antenna correlations and couplings for massive arrays with relevant topologies must be determined, and a proper modeling of their impact must be established; in particular, the degree of actual channel orthogonalization in the face of such nonidealities must be verified. And, for FD-MIMO, besides azimuth, the modeling needs to incorporate elevation, which is a dimension on which far less data exists concerning power spectra and angle spreads.

III. DESIGN ISSUES FOR 5 G

In addition to supporting 1000× higher data rates, 5G networks must decrease latencies, lower energy consumption, lower costs, and support many low-rate connections. In this section, we discuss important ongoing research areas that support these requirements. We begin with the most fundamental aspect of the physical layer—the waveform—and then consider the evolution of cloud-based and virtualized network architectures, latency and control signaling, and energy efficiency.

A. The Waveform: Signaling and Multiple Access

In light of this history, it is natural to ponder the possibility that the transition to 5G could involve yet another major change in the signaling and multiple access formats.

1) *OFDM and OFDMA: The Default Approach:* OFDM has become the dominant signaling format for high-speed wireless communication, forming the basis of all current WiFi standards and of LTE, and further of wireline technologies such as digital subscriber lines, digital TV, and commercial radio. Its qualities include:

- A natural way to cope with frequency selectivity.
- Computationally efficient implementation via FFT/IFFT blocks and simple frequency-domain equalizers.
- An excellent pairing for MIMO, since OFDM allows for the spatial interference from multiantenna transmission to be dealt with at a

subcarrier level, without the added complication of intersymbol interference.

2) *Drawbacks of OFDM:* Given this impressive list of qualities, and the large amount of inertia in its favor, OFDM is the unquestionable frontrunner for 5G. However, some weak points do exist that could possibly become more pronounced in 5 G networks.

First, the peak-to-average-power ratio (PAPR) is higher in OFDM than in other formats since the envelope samples are nearly Gaussian due to the summation of uncorrelated inputs in the IFFT. Although a Gaussian signal distribution is capacity-achieving under an average power constraint, in the face of an actual power amplifier a high PAPR sets up an unattractive tradeoff between the linearity of the transmitted signal and the cost of the amplifier. This problem can be largely overcome by precoding the OFDM signals at the cost of a slightly more involved equalization process at the receiver and a slight power penalty; indeed, this is already being done in the LTE uplink.

Second, OFDM's spectral efficiency is satisfactory, but could perhaps be further improved upon if the requirements of strict orthogonality were relaxed and if the cyclic prefixes (CPs) that prevent interblock interference were smaller or discarded.

Potential Alternatives to OFDM: To address OFDM's weaknesses, we now overview some alternative approaches being actively investigated. Most of these, however, can be considered incremental departures from OFDM rather than the step-function changes that took place in previous cellular generations. Further tutorial treatment can be found in a recent tutorial.

Time-Frequency Packing: Time-frequency packing and faster-than-Nyquist signaling have been recently proposed to circumvent the limitations of strict orthogonality and CP. In contrast to OFDM, where the product of the symbol interval and the subcarrier spacing equals 1, in faster-than-Nyquist signaling products smaller than 1 can be accommodated and spectral efficiency improvements on the order of 25% have been claimed.

Nonorthogonal Signals: There is a growing interest in multicarrier formats, such as filterbank multicarrier, that are natively nonorthogonal and thus do not require prior synchronization of distributed transmitters. A new format termed universal filtered multicarrier (UFMC) has been proposed whereby, starting with an OFDM signal, filtering is performed on groups of adjacent subcarriers with the aim of reducing sidelobe levels and intercarrier interference resulting from poor time/frequency synchronization (see Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Frequency-domain magnitude responses of some adjacent waveforms for OFDM, frequency-packed OFDM, and filtered OFDM. The two signaling formats alternative to OFDM trade subcarrier orthogonality for either better spectral efficiency (frequency-packed OFDM) or lower out-of-band emissions (filtered OFDM).

Generalized Frequency Division Multiplexing: GFDM is a multicarrier technique that adopts a shortened CP through the tail biting technique and is particularly well suited for noncontiguous frequency bands, which makes it attractive for spectrum sharing where frequency-domain holes may have to be adaptively filled.

Single Carrier: Single-carrier transmission has also been attracting renewed interest, chiefly due to the development of low-complexity nonlinear equalizers implemented in the frequency domain.

C) Energy Efficiency: As specified in our stated requirements for 5G, the energy efficiency of the communication chain—typically measured in either Joules/bit or bits/Joule—will need to improve by about the same amount as the data rate just to maintain the power consumption. And by more if such consumption is to be reduced.

IV. SPECTRUM REGULATION AND STANDARDIZATION FOR 5G

A. Spectrum Policy and Allocation

As discussed in Section II-B, the beachfront microwave spectrum is already saturated in peak markets at peak times while large amounts of idle spectrum do exist in the mmWave realm. Due to the different propagation characteristics, and recalling the concept of phantom cells, future systems will need to integrate a broad range of frequencies: low frequencies for wide coverage, mobility support, and control, and high frequencies for small cells. This will require new approaches to spectrum policy and allocation methods. Topics such as massive MIMO and small cells, which address the efficient use of spectrum, must also be considered important issues in spectrum policy.

B. Regulation and Standardization

5G Spectrum Standardization Status: Several regional forums and projects have been established to shape the 5G vision and to study its key enabling technologies [6]. 5G has been increasingly referred to as “IMT2020” in many industry forums and international telecommunications union (ITU) working groups with the goal, as the name suggests, of beginning commercial deployments around 2020.

V. CONCLUSION

It is an interesting time to look in wireless industry and for wireless research at large. Demanding new requirements for 5G are already unveiling a flurry of creative thinking and a sense of urgency in bringing innovative new technologies into reality. Even couple of years ago, a mmWave cellular system was considered something of imaginative; now it is almost considered an inevitability. As this article has presented, it is a long way ahead to truly disruptive 5G networks. Many technical challenges remain spanning all layers of the protocol stack and their implementation, as well as many intersections with regulatory, policy, and business considerations.

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PAPR Reduction in MIMO-OFDM Downlink Wireless Systems

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Abstract-Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM) is a multi-carrier transmission method which is most broadly used in the field of communication. One of the main draw-back of this scheme is Peak to Average Power Ratio (PAPR). There are various methods introduced for the reduction of PAPR in OFDM. However these techniques have major disadvantage that they reason non-linear in-band deformation and out-of-band emission, this reduces the scheme throughput. Thus, Multi-Input and Multi output, which is the proposed technique discussed in this paper overcomes this problem. In this method, some of the broadcast data symbols are replaced by nulls, i.e. errors are introduced in the transmitted signal. At the receiver, an iterative decoder is used to correct the channel errors. Particularly, MU pre-coding is carried, OFDM, and PAR lessening by solving a convex optimization trouble. A fast iterative algorithm is used and show mathematical results to PAR-reduction competence.

Keywords: OFDM, PAPR, Switching and Shifting of Null Sub-Carriers

I. INTRODUCTION

After more than thirty years of research and growth carried out in the field of communication OFDM has been widely implemented in high speed digital communication [1].OFDM has its major benefits of higher data rates and better presentation. The higher data rates are achieved by use of multiple carriers and presentation improved by use of guard interval which leads to removal of put in the ground Symbol intrusion(ISI) [2]. OFDM has several features which makes it more advantageous for high speed data transmission. These features include High Spectral competence, strength to Channel Fading, and protection to Impulse Interference, litness and Easy Equalization. In spite of these benefits there are some drawback such as PAPR, Offset occurrence and Inter Carrier meddling (ICI) between sub-carriers [3]. Practical wireless channels typically exhibit frequency selective fading and a low-PAR pre-coding

solution suitable for such channels would be desirable. rather, the explanation should be such that the complexity required in each (mobile)terminal is small (due to stringent area and authority constraints),whereas heavier allowance could be afforded at the BS. Orthogonal frequency-division multiplexing (OFDM) [8] is an efficient and well-established way of commerce with regularity selective channels. In addition to simplify the equalization at the receiver, OFDM also facilitate per-tone authority and bit allocation, development in the occurrence domain, and band influential. However, OFDM is known to suffer from a high PAR [9], which necessitates the use of linear RF mechanism(e.g., power amplifiers) to avoid out-of-band emission and signal distortions. regrettably, linear RF workings are, in general, more costly and less power efficient than their non-linear counterparts, which would sooner or later result in exorbitant costs for large-scale BS implementations having hundreds of antennas. Therefore, it is of paramount end result to reduce the PAR of OFDM-based large-scale MU-MIMOs to facilitate parallel low-cost and low-power BS implementations.

II. PEAK TO AVERAGE POWER RATIO

PAPR Problem

One of the new problems emerging in OFDM is the so-called Peak to Average Power Ratio (PAPR) problem. The input symbol watercourse of the IFFT should have a uniform power spectrum, but the output of the IFFT may result in a non-uniform or spiky power spectrum. Most of transmission energy would be allocated for a few instead of the majority subcarriers. This problem can be quantified as the PAPR measure. It causes many problems in the OFDM at the transmitting end.

Effect of PAPR

There are some obstacles in using OFDM in transmission in contrast to its advantages [3]:

- (i) A major obstacle is that the OFDM signal exhibits a very high Peak to Average Power Ratio (PAPR).
- (ii) Therefore, RF power amplifier should be operated in a very large linear region. Otherwise, the signal peaks get into non-linear region of the power amplifier causing signal distortion. This signal deformation introduces intermodulation among the subcarriers and out of band radiation. Thus, the power amplifiers should be operated with large authority back offs. On the other hand, this leads to very inefficient intensification and expensive transmitters. Thus, it is highly desirable to decrease the PAPR
- (iii) These large peaks cause saturation in power amplifiers, leading to inter modulation products among the subcarriers and disturbing out of band energy. Therefore, it is desirable to reduce the PAPR.

Fig. 1. Large-scale MU-MIMO-OFDM system (left: BS with N transmit antennas; right: M independent single-antenna terminals).

III. PROPOSED TECHNIQUES

PAPR Reduction Techniques

The PAPR is painstaking as one of the major disadvantage in the multicarrier communication s. In order to reduce and eliminate these problems many different methods are future. These methods are classified into various categories. All the proposed method mainly aim at reducing the PAPR as much as possible and along with it they take care not to interrupt and perturb the other parts of the . The algorithms considered while diminution should not be intricate and easily implementable. Following are the category of PAPR reduction.

Clipping

The technique with the lowest complication is the article technique. In the excerpt system, simply clip the high amplitude peaks. Some of these techniques use digital clipping ,i.e. the signal is brusque at the output of the inverse discrete Fourier transform without any oversampling. This causes re

growth of the signal peaks after the subsequent interpolation. To avoid the signal re-growth some techniques clip the indicator after interpolation and subsequently use a filter to reduce the consequential out-of-band spectral leakage. In addition they cause peak re-growth and result in significant distortion of the wanted signal.

Tone Reservation

In the tone reservation method [5] the orthogonality between the different subcarrier is exploited to generate the peak lessening signal. In the OFDM not all subcarriers are used for data transmission. Some of them are reserved for the reduction signal. Due to the fact that all subcarrier are orthogonal the signal generate by the reserved tones does not concern the data carrying tones. In the tone reservation method both transmitter and receiver know the set of data carry in subcarriers. The creation of the reduction signal can be done in different ways with different complexities. The PAPR decrease method using tone stipulation method can be transformed into a convex optimization problem. Advantages of tone stipulation include among other no side in sequence and low complexity.

Shifting Null sub-carriers

For 16-QAM, the total number of sub-carriers is 64. According to the IEEE 802.11a standard among the 64 subcarriers-the first 6 sub-carriers, the last 5 sub-carriers and the sub-carrier at position '33' should all be null carriers. Apart from the null sub-carriers the remaining sub-carriers contain modulate data before introducing it to inputs of IFFT. The fundamental concept of the Shifting algorithm is that the null sub-carriers are essentially shifted to the positions of data sub-carriers. Now, all the null sub-carriers from furthermore of the two sides – low frequency edge or high frequency border shouldn't be shifted since they also serve as guard band. Thus it is advisable to use only one null subcarrier from each side of low frequency and high occurrence edge. The null sub-carrier at position below should be left unaltered since it serves to avoid DC energy. According to the future Shifting method, the 6th null sub-carrier, from the low frequency edge is switched with ever other data sub-carrier in positions and null sub-carrier from the high occurrence edge is switch through every other data sub-carrier in positions.

Implemented version of Shifting Null sub-carriers According to the proposed method, the 6th null sub-carrier from the low frequency edge is

switched with the 7th position which is a data subcarrier. Then from the higher frequency edge the 60th unacceptable sub carrier is switched with the 59th position data sub-carrier. IFFT operation is performed. PAPR is then calculated for this arrangement of data and null sub-carriers. This PAPR value is stored in a variable where only the minimum value is stored. This variable can be assumed as “min PAPR”.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, we demonstrate the efficacy of the future joint pre-coding, modulation, and PAR drop approach, and provide a comparison to conventional MU pre-coding schemes.

Simulation Parameters

Unless explicitly stated otherwise, all simulation results are for a MU-MIMO-OFDM having $N = 100$ antenna at the BS and serving $M = 10$ single-antenna terminals. We employ OFDM with $W = 128$ tones and use a spectral map T as specified in the 40MHz-mode of IEEE 802.11n. We consider coded transmission, i.e., for each user, we independently encode 216 information bits using a convolution code (rate-1/2, generator polynomials [1330 1710], and constraint length 7), apply random interleaving (across OFDM tones), and map the coded bits to a 16-QAM constellation (using Gray labeling). To implement (PMP-L), In addition to LS and MF pre-coding, we also consider the performance of a baseline pre-coding and PAR-reduction method. To this end, we make use of LS pre-coding followed by truncation (clipping) of the entries of the time-domain

Fig. 2. Time/frequency representation for different precoding schemes (a) Time-domain signals (b) Frequency-domain signals

samples n . We use a clipping strategy where one can state a target PAR, which is then used to compute a clipping level for which the PAR in [4] of the resulting time-domain samples is no more than the chosen target PAR.

Performance Measures

CCDF computes the complementary cumulative distribution (CCDF) function from a time area signal. The CCDF curve shows the amount of time a signal spends above the average control level of the deliberate signal, or equivalently, the probability that the signal power will be above the average power level. To compare the PAR characteristics of different pre-coding schemes, we use the complementary cumulative distribution function (CCDF) defined as

$$CCDF(PAR) = P\{PAR_n > PAR\}$$

We furthermore define the “PAR performance” as the maximum PAR level, that is met for 99% of all transmitted OFDM symbols, i.e., given by $CCDF(PAR) = 1\%$. The error-rate performance is measured by the average (a cross users) symbol-error rate (SER); a symbol is said to be in error if at least one of the information bits per received OFDM symbol is decoded in error. The “SNR operating point” corresponds to the minimum SNR required to achieve 1% SER. In order to characterize the amount of signal power that is transmitted outside the active tones.

Fig. 3. PAR and SER performance for various precoding schemes. (a) PAR performance (the curves of LS and MF overlap). Note that PMP effectively reduces the PAR compared to LS and MF precoding. (b) Symbol error-rate (SER) performance. Note that the signal normalization causes 1 dB SNR-performance loss for PMP compared to LS precoding

Fig.4. PAR performance of PMP and LS precoding depending on the number of transmit antennas N and the number of non-zero channel taps T

Conclusion:

In this paper, a novel downlink transmission scheme for MIMO-OFDM is proposed. The major blocks in the system are pre-coding, modulation and PAPR reduction. This yields constant envelope OFDM signals in the antennas reaching the large number. This is considered as an optimum technique called fast iterative algorithm. The results obtained shows that there is more than 10dB reduction in PAPR when compared to conventional pre-coding methods. This suppresses the linearity requirements of radio frequency components. As the method affects only signal processing at base station, it can be deployed in MIMO-OFDM wireless communications systems.

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Multilevel Boost Converter Implementation for Photo Voltaic Applications

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Abstract: This paper presents the implementation of a Maximum Power Point Tracker (MPPT) for photovoltaic (PV) applications by using Multi-level boost converter and FPGA Board. The control algorithm for extracting maximum power from the cell is proposed by means of the VHDL code and implemented using Xilinx XC3S400 FPGA Board. In this work, a practical implementation of the real-time Estimate Perturb and Absorb algorithm for maximum power point tracking (MPPT) control in a PV system has been developed. The Developed implementation has the advantage of simple programming with high performance even with low resolution ADC and low cost current sensor. The proposed technique has been validated through detailed experimental work.

Keywords: Photovoltaic (PV), FPGA, multilevel boost converter, maximum power point tracking, simple sensor.

I. INTRODUCTION

Renewable energy sources such as solar energy are acquiring more significance, due to shortage and environmental impacts of conventional fuels. The photovoltaic (PV) system for converting solar energy into electricity is in general costly and is a vital way of electricity generation only if it can produce the maximum possible output for all weather conditions. The PV array has a highly non-linear current-voltage characteristic varying with the irradiance and temperature that substantially affects the array power output. The maximum power point tracking (MPPT) control of the PV system is therefore critical for the success of a PV system. P&O MPPT algorithm which implemented by XILINX FPGA have been considered extensively in the literature. Field programmable gate arrays (FPGA's) are standard integrated circuits that can be programmed by a user to perform a variety of complex logic functions. The high level of integration available with these devices (currently up to 500,000 gates) means that they can be used to implement complex electronic system. Furthermore, there are many advantages due to the rapid design process and reprogrammable function. XILINX FPGA enables to produce prototype logic designs right in a short period. It is possible to create, implement, and verify a new design. A configuration program stored in

internal static memory cells of the XILINX FPGA is written by VHDL programming language that has been designed and optimized for describing the behavior of digital systems; VHDL has many features appropriate for describing the behavior of electronic components ranging from simple logic gates to complete microprocessors and custom chips. Features of VHDL allow electrical aspects of circuit behavior (such as rise and fall times of signals, delays through gates, and functional operation) to be precisely described. The utilization of FPGAs instead of other architectures was mainly based on four factors: the acceleration of the design or parts of it, the flexibility of reconfiguration hardware, the reduction of costs, and the energy consumption. These factors had a different impact on each application area [1]. Several MPPT techniques have been proposed, during the last decades. They range from conventional methods, from simple hill-climbing algorithms (P&O, MP&O and EPP), to fuzzy logic and neural network algorithms. The hill climbing algorithm [2-4] is widely used in practical PV systems because of its simplicity and because it does not require prior study or modeling of the source characteristics and can account for characteristics drift resulting from ageing, shadowing, or other operating irregularities, but its performance is poor compared to Artificial Intelligent methods. Recently, the increasing performance and cost reduction of digital circuits have made possible their applications for power converter control. Comparison with other digital signal processors, Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) based systems could provide a number of run-time advantages over the sequential machines such as a microcontroller. Moreover, with concurrent operation, it is executed continuously and simultaneously which faster than DSP. Thus the FPGA has been applied for high speed switching circuit to reduce equipment-sizing [5] specially in the implementation of MPP, FPGA features are utilized [6, 7]. The paper is organized as follows:

Section.2 shows the system configuration of the proposed system. In section.3 a multilevel boost converter is analyzed. The MPPT control is discussed in section.4. Section.5 shows the experimental results. Finally conclusions are presented in section.6.

II. PV CELL MODEL AND SIMULATION

The simplest equivalent circuit of a solar cell is a current source in parallel with a diode. The output of the current source is directly proportional to the light falling on the cell. The diode determines the characteristics of the cell. Increasing sophistication, accuracy and complexity can be introduced to the model by adding in turn:

- Temperature dependence of the diode saturation current I_0
- Temperature dependence of the photo current I_L
- Series resistance R_S , which gives a more accurate shape between the maximum power point and the open circuit voltage.
- Shunt resistance R_P in parallel with the diode.
- Either allowing the diode quality factor n to become a variable parameter (instead of being fixed at either 1 or 2) or introducing two parallel diodes (one with $A = 1$, one with $A = 2$) with independently set saturation currents [8]. For this research work, a model of moderate complexity was used. The model includes temperature dependence of the photo current I_L and the saturation current of the diode I_0 . A series resistance R_S was included, but not a shunt resistance. A single shunt diode was used with the diode quality factor set to achieve the best curve match. The circuit diagram for the solar cell is shown in Fig. 1. The studied system configuration is shown in Fig. 2. This system consists of a solar array type of the solar cell that is used is SP85P Electrical Characteristics is shown in Table. 1.

Fig.2 Configuration of the controlled MPPT

III. MULTILEVEL BOOST CONVERTER DESIGN

Fig.3 illustrates a multilevel boost converter which combines the boost converter and the switched capacitor function to provide an output of several capacitors in series with the same voltage and self balanced voltage, The major advantages of this topology are: (i) continuous input current, (ii) a large conversion ratio with low duty cycle and without a transformer. It can be built in a modular way and more levels can be added without changing the main circuit; it provides several self balanced voltage

levels and only one switch is necessary [9]. Here, a multilevel boost converter is designed based on the specification shown in Table. 2.

The transfer function of the conventional boost converter is

$$V_{out} = \frac{v_g}{1-D}$$

But in the multilevel converter the transfer function of it is

$$V_{out} = \frac{N + v_g}{1-D}$$

It can be noted from the above equations 1 and 2 the MLBC has a higher conversion ratio with the conventional converter based on the number of level used.

IV. MAXIMUM POWER POINT TRACKING ALGORITHM

Fig.4 indicates that the characteristic output power curve for the solar cell from make the solar cell to work at its maximum power under a given temperature and irradiance, a MPPT control algorithm is employed to harvest this maximum power from the cell. As mentioned it was said there are many MPPT control algorithms have been proposed so far in the literature. The well known algorithm is called perturb and observe (P&O) has been employed in this work. Figure 5 depicts a flow chart explaining the main steps of it. It operates by perturbing the PV array voltage (i.e. incrementing or decreasing) and comparing the PV output power with that of the previous perturbation cycle. If the perturbation leads to an increase (decrease) in array power, the subsequent perturbation is made in the same (opposite) direction. In this manner, the peak power tracker continuously seeks the peak power condition. The output power of the solar cell in this algorithm is not constant but it oscillates around the maximum power point because there is no reference point in this algorithm. The algorithm is programmed using VHDL code, the inputs of the program are the PV current and voltage driven from two ADC converters and the program output is the duty cycle which drives the gate of the boost converter switch.

According to the flow chart the program read the input signals (V, I), then calculate the PV module power by multiplying the two signals. The current values for the power, current, and voltage are compared with their counterparts of the previous values to execute the conditions. The duty cycle increment or decrement according to the change in the reference value which is compared with the saw tooth carrier signal. The process repeat itself the system oscillate at a certain point this point is the maximum power point.

Fig. 3 A dc-dc MLBC for 3-levels.

Fig. 5 Flowchart of the P&O algorithm.

V. THE PROPOSED FPGA SYSTEM

A. The circuit configuration

Generally the design of a digital controller impact is always the implementation of a suitable data acquisition path, so that digital control requires particular care in signal conditioning and analog to digital conversion implementation [10]. A low power prototype is built for experimental. Figure 6 shows the overall hardware implementation circuit of the proposed system, that is containing solar cell, multilevel boost converter that boosting output voltage of the solar cell and in the same time extract maximum power from it. There is one switch in the multilevel boost converter (MOSFET-16N60) and the fast recovery diodes are FR605. All capacitor are 220µF- 400V aluminum electrolytic and inductor has a value of 8mH. MLBC extract maximum power by using (Xilinx XC3S400 FPGA Board) that is containing the program of perturb and observe, FPGA Board read the PV output voltage and current by using low cost 8-bits analog to digital converter chip ADC0804ICN to converter the analog signal to digital signal.

Fig. 6 The overall hardware implementation

Fig. 7: The experimental setup

B. Voltage and current sensing

The P&O method which used to implement MPPT requires two sensors. Simple series and shunt resistances are used to measure the PV cell current and voltage respectively. However special care should be taken for the current sensor of this type. Where most of the time, it is easier and more reliable to measure voltage than current. Series sense resistor [11] is the conventional technique of sensing the current, it simply inserts a sense resistor in series with the return line of the PV, and the output current of the PV is determined by sensing the voltage across it. This method obviously acquires a power loss in R sense. In this paper low resistance with high power rating resistance has been used (0.25ohm, 5W). The voltage across it equal 1.25V when the maximum current (5A) flow through it. But the full scale range (FSR) of the ADC depends on the amplitude of the voltage reference of the ADC0804ICN (5V) so if the maximum value input to the ADC equal 1.25 V this means the FSR not utilized. To boost this value to near the FSR, an amplifier circuit consist from operational amplifier is used as a gain equal 3, to utilize the FSR as shown in Fig. 8. The designed values for R1 and R2 can be chosen from equation 3. The performance of the implementation by FPGA is high even if using low resolution ADC 8 bits.

$$V_{out} = V_{in} \left(1 + \frac{R_2}{R_1} \right) \quad (3)$$

Where: R1=1kΩ and R2=2kΩ

Fig. 9 The duty cycle, output voltage, output current, and output maximum power respectively at time T1 during the day.

P=77.84W.

C. Experimental results:

The algorithm has been tested at different time during the day to ensure the testing is done for different environmental operation conditions. Figures 9 - 12 show the performance results obtained from the algorithm for different time during the day. These figures show different results for the variables due to the change of the environmental temperature. Figure 9 is done for maximum power at 77.84W and then with small time difference Fig.10 has been captured to show the capability of the control with tracking MPPT. For other different time with smaller insulation, Fig. 11 and 12 are done where the maximum extracted power is 75.89W and 66W, respectively. Figure 13 shows the PV voltage and current waveforms and how they reach the steady state point for tracking the maximum power point. Figure 14 shows the output voltage from MLBC and the pulses generated from FPGA Board that is used to switching the gate of MLBC at frequency 100 kHz. These experimental set up has proves the control algorithm and its function to track the maximum power point.

Fig. 10 The duty cycle, output voltage, output current, and output maximum power respectively at time T2 during the day. P=77.44W

Fig. 11 The duty cycle, output voltage, output current, and output maximum power respectively at time T3 during the day. P=75.89W

Fig. 12 The duty cycle, output voltage, output current, and output maximum power respectively at time T4 during the day. P=66W.

Fig. 13 The oscillation of the voltage and current waveform

Fig. 14 Recorded waveforms from Prototype II, 220µF- 400V, L=8mH, Vin=16 V, Vout=110 V.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the implementation of the FPGA system to control the high-performance multi level boost converter has been introduced. The implemented control has worked in the direction to track the maximum power from the PV source by using only one switch and implemented by XILINX FPGA which is considered as an efficient hardware for rapid prototyping. XILINX FPGA Web Pack software is used to generate PWM pattern by means of VHDL program. XILINX FPGA enables to make easy, fast and flexible design and implementation. Also a simple method of current sensing is used depending on the high performance of the FPGA with low resolution. Both simulation and experimental results are presented as confirmation of the approach presented.

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Dual Tree-Complex Wavelet Transform and Multi Wavelet Transform For Content-Based Retinal Image Retrieval

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Abstract: The paper presents the dual tree complex wavelet transform (DT-CWT) and multi wavelet transforms for content based retinal image retrieval (CBRIR). The multi wavelet transform is more retrieval accuracy compare to DT-CWT. It is less complexity and less retrieval time. In this work, the proposed method follows two steps. The firstly, apply the wavelet transform (either DT-CWT or multi wavelet) and energy is used for feature extraction. Energy function is the most suitable for texture characterization of the image. Secondly, calculate the similarity measures between query and database image feature vectors using Euclidian distance. The experimental data base diabetic retinopathy database (DRD) contains 1261 images. The experimental results shows that the retrieval efficiency and retrieval time of multi wavelet is less compare to DT-CWT.

Keywords- Dual-tree complex wavelet (DT-CWT) and multi wavelet transform, Diabetic retinopathy, content based retinal image retrieval (CBRIR),

I.INTRODUCTION

Now a days computer imaging and database techniques play an important role in medical field, which leads to the huge amount of digital images with a wide variety of image modalities, such as Computed Tomography(CT), Magnetic Resonance (MR), X-ray and ultrasound, generated in hospitals every day[1]. Developing efficient medical image indexing system is an urgent work. Recently Picture Archiving and Communication System (PACS) system is widely used in hospitals, but PACS provides only simple text-based retrieval capabilities using patient names or patient ID numbers. Content-Based Image Retrieval (CBIR) systems can greatly help to retrieve useful information within enormous amount of medical images. Presently the demand of multimedia information such as digital images and video rapidly increase [2]. Image Retrieval plays a vital role in many application areas, such as education, entertainment, art history, digital library, diagnostic medical image databases, journalism data management and general consumer use.

In [3], 1261 images are indexed in a generic fashion and adapted the wavelet basis within a lifting scheme framework. Wavelets like LeGall 5/3, Daubechies 9/7, Haar, cubic B-spline, Daubechies 4-tap, Daubechies 6-tap and adapted wavelets were evaluated. The wavelet coefficient distribution was mode lied using histogram and generalized Gaussian functions, out of which generalized Gaussian functions gave better results. In [4], the performance of the adapted non-separable wavelet filter bank and the separable wavelet filter bank was analyzed for Diabetic Retinopathy Database (DRD) consisting of 1045 photographs. Adapted wavelet using weighted distance between signatures is used for retrieving 1045 photographs from DRD in [5]. It has been proved that wavelet-based image features enable fast retrieval and increased retrieval performance [3]. The enhancement to the discrete wavelet transform (DWT) is the dual-tree complex wavelet transform (DT -CWT) due to its nearly shift invariant and directionally selective properties [6]. From the literatures related to existing methods, it is found that different wavelets along with probability distribution model Euclidian distance measure have been used for content-based retinal image retrieval. In [7], the DT - CWT has been successfully used for general texture retrieval purpose yielding better retrieval results and the same is adopted in this work. In this paper is organized as follows. The DT-CWT is explained in II. Proposed method in section III. Retrieval measure in section IV. The simulation results are presented in Section V. Concluding remarks are made in Section VI.

II.DT-COMPLEX WAVELET TRANSFORM

The images in its original form may lead to computational complexity and burden as reported in the literature. Therefore, the first step in pre-processing is to separate the green component which has comparatively better contrast and energy than other components [2]. Hence, the green component of the retinal images is used in the subsequent stages of

the retrieval process. Next, the region of interest (ROI), i.e., the retina portion is cropped based on the locations of the extreme edge pixels obtained by applying the Sobel edge operator. Finally, the contrast of the ROI is enhanced further through contrast-limited adaptive histogram equalization (CLAHE) method. It is a simply a non-decimated wavelet transform. The drawback in DT-CWT is more expansive wavelet transform in place of a critically-sampled one. The DT-CWT is separating the positive and negative frequencies thus differentiating and splitting the sub bands of a dyadic decomposition into sub bands orientated at $\pm 15^\circ$, $\pm 45^\circ$, $\pm 75^\circ$ as shown in figure 1.

Fig 1: Frequency plane showing 6 orientated sub bands of the complex wavelet transform

The block diagram of decomposition of DT-CWT in two level is shown in fig.2.

Fig 2 : block diagram of 2- dimensional DT –CWT

At each level contain two stages. The first one is generating the six sub bands of branch a and b in which satisfy the Hilbert pairs requirement. The Hilbert pairs are HLa, HLb, LHa, LHb, HHa and

HHb. The two stages involved in getting the sub-band coefficients are: (i) generation of the initial six sub-bands of branch a and b through filters satisfying the Hilbert pair requirement resulting in HLa, HLb, LHa, LHb, HHa and HHb and (ii) linear combination, either by averaging or differencing the real and imaginary part of the sub-band outputs as $(HLa + HLb)/2$, $(HLa-HLb)/2$, $(LHa+ LHb)/2$, $(LHa-LHb)/2$, $(HHa + HHb)/2$, $(HHa - HHb)/2$ [16] The second one is find the average and difference the real and imaginary of Hilbert pairs. It is called linear combination. After that calculate the feature extraction of each sub band of DT-CWT GGD function will implemented. The main advantages are Better directionality, Anti- aliasing effect, Good shift-invariant, Geometry of the image features retained from phase, Better robustness for smooth varying and Low computation compared with discrete wavelet transform. It is less retrieval accuracy, high computation and storage. So, to solve such a problem using multi wavelet transform as explain in next section.

III. PROPOSED METHOD

The block diagram of content-based retinal image retrieval technique is given in Fig.3 , which consists of three important stages namely wavelet transform, feature selection and similarity measurement as explain in sub section A, B, and C

Fig 3: block diagram of proposed method

A. Multi wavelet

It is also called two level transform. Multi wavelet is high retrieval accuracy, less complexity and storage. The discrete wavelet framework for image decomposition. The prefilter is first applied to all the rows of the image, before the first level decomposition is applied to each of the resultant rows. The first half of each row of the decomposition results contains coefficients corresponding to the first scaling function and the second half contains coefficients corresponding to the second scaling function. Then the prefilter and decomposition

operations are repeated to the columns, such that the first half of each column contains coefficients corresponding to the first scaling function and the second half of each column corresponding to the second scaling function. At the end of the first of 2-D discrete wavelet decomposition, we have a 16-subband intermediate image as follows

Here a typical block 1 2L H contains low pass coefficients corresponding to the first scaling function in the horizontal direction and high pass coefficients corresponding to the second scaling function in the vertical direction. The next step of the cascade will decompose the "low-low pass" sub matrix. The L1L1 sub band resolution is high compare to other sub bands. In this fashion, an L-level decomposition of a 2-D image will produce $4(3L+1)$ sub bands. After this calculate energy of each sub band i.e to get the 12 feature values in a single image.

Fig 4: One level of 2-D multiwavelet decomposition of a 2-D image

B. Feature extraction

In order to have features that requires less computation and storage using energy. The energy calculation of each sub-image and defined as

$$E = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i,j} X_{i,j}^2 \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where X is the sub-band and N is the total number pixel in X sub-band. The wavelet energy features reflect the distribution of energy along the frequency axis over scale and orientation and have

proven to be very powerful for texture characterization. Since most relevant texture information has eliminated the low pass filtering, we didn't consider the energy of the low resolution sub-images. The results shows showed that the performance of the energy feature was statistically better than the existing feature extraction methods.

C. Similarity measure

To compute the similarity measurement between the query feature vector and the ones in the feature dataset using Euclidian distance in which is based on square-root of feature vectors of query image and dataset images.

$$d = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - y_i)^2} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where x is the query feature vector and y is the dataset feature vector. N is the total number of feature vectors.

IV. RETRIEVAL MEASURE

Precision and recall are the two widely used metrics for evaluating the performance of a content-based retinal retrieval method. Precision describes the amount of relevancy achieved by the system,

$$Precision = \frac{No.of\ relevant\ images\ retrieved}{Total\ No.of\ images\ retrieved}$$

Whereas, recall defines how fast the relevant images are retrieved.

$$Recall = \frac{No.of\ relevant\ images\ retrieved}{No.of\ relevant\ images\ in\ the\ database}$$

V. THE EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The experimental dataset of this work consists of the retinal images available in the MESSIDOR database. In this work implemented using MATLAB tool. The results of different retinal test images are shown below.

Original image

Fig 5: original image

Fig 6: image retrieval using multi wavelet

Fig 7 : original image

Fig 8: image retrieval using dual tree wavelet

The graph between precision and recall for the multi wavelets and DT-CWT as shown in figure9. Where as precision taken on Y-axis and recall on X-axis. By comparing this we can say that multi wavelets can give better results.

Fig 9: graph between precision and recall

VI. CONCLUSION

The paper presents the retinal image retrieval based on multi wavelet and DT-CWT. The performance of retrieval efficiency in multi wavelet is better compare to DT-CWT as shown in experimental results. The multi wavelet system gives good results on the tests conducted. It is more powerful and efficient retrieval system for image and multimedia databases, content based queries must be combined with text, keyword predicate and it has shown that best in the sense of time and accuracy.

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Implementation of Digital IIR Filter Using VHDL on VIRTEX-6 (XC6V SX475T) FPGA

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Abstract— The development of digital IIR (Infinite Impulse Response) filter is done on VIRTEX-6 FPGA using VHDL (Very High Speed Integrated Circuit Hardware Description Language) in XILINX Integrated Software Environment. IIR filter is analytically simulated by simulink environment in MATLAB. The digital data output of A/D converter is sent through IIR module in FPGA. Testing and debugging IIR module is done in custom made VIRTEX-6 data acquisition hardware. The results obtained are cross checked with MATLAB results. Speed of computation greatly increased by developing digital filter in FPGA. Advantages of FPGA approach to develop IIR filter include higher sampling rates than traditional DSP chips, lower cost than ASICs for moderate applications.

Key words: DAQ, IIR filter, MATLAB, XILINX, VHDL, FPGA (VIRTEX-6).

I. INTRODUCTION

A filter is used to remove the undesirable signals or the noise of the signal. In naval there is requirement to remove the unwanted portion of the underwater acoustic signals. We know there are two types of digital filters. 1) FIR (Finite Impulse Response) filter and 2) IIR (Infinite Impulse Response) filter. Impulse response of an LTI system which donot reach zero past a certain point and continues[8]. Such a response is called as Infinite Impulse Response. IIR filters [1] are better to implement than FIR filters to meet the specifications like passband, stopband etc... Computational time is saved by using digital IIR filters [2] which is a large factor. IIR filters gives the output such that the input is deformed without filter frequency which by means called as non linear phase characteristic. These filters are not believed to be stable when the output is mainly dependent on frequency domain rather than time domain. IIR filters are computationally more efficient than FIR filters as they require as they require fewer coefficients due to the usage of poles and feedback [5], [7].

Generalized equation of IIR filter is

$$y[n] = \sum_{k=0}^N b[k]x[n-k] + \sum_{k=1}^M a[k]y[n-k] \quad \dots (1)$$

$$H(z) = \frac{b_0 + b_1 z^{-1} + \dots + b_N z^{-N}}{1 + a_1 z^{-1} + \dots + a_M z^{-M}} \quad \dots (2)$$

$$= \frac{\sum_{k=0}^N b_k z^{-k}}{1 + \sum_{k=1}^M a_k z^{-k}} \quad \dots (3)$$

Transfer function of the filter

Where a_k and b_k are the filter coefficients. z_1, z_2, \dots, z_N are the zeros, p_1, p_2, \dots, p_N are the poles.

II. DATA ACQUISITION HARDWARE SYSTEM

DAQ system works on the basis to measure a physical phenomenon such as light, temperature, sound and pressure. It includes transducer, signal conditioning, data acquisition software. It captures a signal and converts the physical signal into electrical signal, analog signal is converted to digital by an A to D converter. The obtained signal is filtered by FPGA using VHDL. Ultimately physical phenomenon is measured and analyzed through computer.

Fig1. DAQ system

a) Transducer

Transducer converts a physical signal into an electrical signal. These transducers generate the electrical signal to measure temperature, sound, light etc., All the signals are not computed in unique pattern. So these electrical signals are classified as

analog and digital signals. The maximum possible information you get from a signal are state, rate, level, frequency, shape.

b) Signal Conditioning :

A signal cannot directly connected to a DAQ device. So that the signal is to be altered. To connect a signal suitably to a DAQ device the Signal conditioning is used. Signal Conditioning is the significant technology in computing any signal. It is important to convert a signal into the acceptable format of DAQ device. Amplification strengthens the transducer signals so that they match the input range of the A/D converter [10].

c) Data Acquisition Software :

The data acquisition software transforms the PC and DAQ hardware into a complete DAQ, analysis, and display system. It can be the most critical factor in obtaining reliable, high performance operation. The main advantage of it is flexibility.

III. IMPLEMENTATION OF IIR FILTER IN MATLAB

Digital IIR filters are partitioned into some of the solutions like chebyshev filters(type I and type II), Butterworth filters, elliptical filters. Chebyshev type II filter is also known as inverse chebyshev type I. For the implementation of IIR filter we need the difference equation. Chebyshev filters are having steeper roll off. Chebyshev type I filter has more passband ripple [6].

- a) Filter specification.
- b) Order calculation
- c) Coefficient calculation.
- d) Structure selection.
- e) Simulation (optional).
- f) Implementation.

a) Filter specification

Using FDA (Filter Design Analysis) Tool we can select the specifications of the filter. The required specifications are passband (ripple), stopband (attenuation) [3].

Fig 2. Filter Specifications

- Rp = 1; % amax[db]
- Rs = 50; % amin[db]
- Fs = 44; % sampling frequency
- fp = 5; % passband frequency
- fs = 8; % stopband attenuation
- wp = 2*fp/Fs; %normalized passband
- ws = 2*fs/Fs; % normalized attenuation

b) Order calculation:

By default it shows the order of such filter in an FDA tool . While given some particular specifications the calculation is [N,Wn] = cheb1ord(wp,ws,Rp,Rs); This chebyshev type I filter order is obtained as 7.

c) Coefficient calculation:

The coefficients are calculated as
 [b,a] = cheby1 (N,Rp,Wn)(4)

The filter transfer function coefficients are obtained as b = 10⁻³*[0.0176 0.1232 0.3696 0.6160 0.6160 0.3696 0.1232 0.0176]; and a= [1.0000 - 5.5152 13.7614 -20.0229 18.2902 -10.4726 3.4791 - 0.5178].

d) Structure selection : There are three types of structures used in IIR filters.

- 1) Direct form
- 2) Cascade form
- 3) Parallel form.

The generalized transfer function of IIR filter is

$$H(z) = \frac{\sum_{k=0}^N b_k z^{-k}}{1 + \sum_{k=1}^M a_k z^{-k}} \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

This transfer function is decomposed as the product of number of transfer functions in the cascade form.

$$H(z) = \frac{P(z)}{D(z)} = \frac{P_1(z)P_2(z)P_3(z)}{D_1(z)D_2(z)D_3(z)} \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

Such that each transfer function is the first order or the second order function. Hence the error is greatly minimized at each stage using cascade structures.

$$H(z) = p_0 \prod_k \left(\frac{1 + \beta_{1k}z^{-1} + \beta_{2k}z^{-2}}{1 + \alpha_{1k}z^{-1} + \alpha_{2k}z^{-2}} \right) \dots\dots (7)$$

The second order filter is usually called as the bi quadratic filter or biquad filter. A biquad filter is as follows. According to given specifications the order of the filter obtained is 7. We use the cascade form structure IIR filters such that the function results in three biquad filters (second order filters) and one first order filter.

Fig 3. Second order (Biquad) filter

Matlab code to modify b,a values into second order sections is [sos,g]=tf2sos(b,a); Constant “g” is distributed among the sections as $g_4=g^{0.25}$. Where g is

$$g = 1.7600 \times 10^{-5}$$

b and a values are obtained as follows

```

b1 = [1.000 1.0090 0];
a1 = [1.0000 -0.8577
0];
b2 = [1.0000 2.0113
1.0113];
a2 = [1.0000 -1.6545
0.7642];
b3 = [1.0000 1.9960
0.9961];
a3 = [1.0000 -1.5320
0.8396];
b4 = [1.0000 1.9837
0.9838];
    
```

```

a4 = [1.0000 -1.4707
0.9420];
    
```

e) Simulation: let us take an input signal. Input signal code in MATLAB

INPUT

```

t=0:1/44000:0.0015;
f1 = 2000;
f2 = 9000;
y = 2*sin (2*pi*f1*t) +2*sin
(2*pi*f2*t);
    
```

Input signal is the sum of two individual signals with different frequencies 2 KHz and 9 KHz. Output code of MATLAB is as follows [9].

OUTPUT

```

yy1 = filter (b1, a1*g4, y);
yy2 = filter (b2, a2*g4, yy1);
yy3 = filter (b3, a3*g4, yy2);
yy4 = filter (b4, a4*g4, yy3);
    
```

f) Implementation : Depending on these calculations IIR filter program is developed in VHDL [4] language and is dumped into an FPGA(Field Programmable Gate Array) using VHDL (Very High Speed Integrated Circuit Hardware Description Language) on Xilinx ISE(Integrated Software Environment) platform.

IV. APPLICATION OF IIR FILTER USING VIRTEX-6

The underwater acoustic signals are to be filtered. A real time signal is captured and is converted into an electrical signal. The filtering is to be done in VIRTEX-6 FPGA using VHDL language [11], [12]. The input signal is converted in a 32 bit data. The hexadecimal multiplication addition and subtraction are done in VHDL using CORE GENERATORS. These reduce the precision while multiplication, addition and subtraction. The captured real time signal is observed and is between 21 to 25 kHz frequency. A this particular band of frequencies 21 kHz to 25khz a band-pass chebyshev filter is used to filter the input acoustic signal. Order of the filter is measured by FDA tool in MATLAB. At these particular ranges order of the filter obtained is 14.

Fig 4. Filter order calculation in MATLAB

According to these specifications the filter coefficients are measured in MATLAB and the same are used in VHDL for simulation.

V. ADVANTAGES OF VIRTEX-6 FPGA

Virtex-6 FPGA meets the target easily. It stays within power budget without sacrificing the performance. It optimizes the power, bandwidth and cost. Virtex-6 family FPGAs are easy to use relatively is operated on high speed connectivity technologies.

VI. RESULTS

a) Sum of two sinusoidal signals is given as input of IIR chebyshev type I filter. The output obtained is a pure sine wave.

Fig 6. Chebyshev filter result in MATLAB

b) Simulation results in VHDL using XILINX ISE platform.

Fig 7. VHDL Simulation results

c) Virtex-6 FPGA Input and Output

Fig 8. Virtex-6 FPGA result

d) Resource utilization in Spartan-6 and Virtex-6 FPGAs

Device Utilization Summary (estimated values)				
Logic Utilization	Used	Available	Utilization	
Number of Slice Registers		4135	4930	86%
Number of Slice LUTs	4932	2400	201%	
Number of fully used LUTFF pairs	4016	4951	81%	
Number of bonded IOBs	179	302	179%	
Number of BUFGs/BUFGCTRLs	1	16	6%	

Spartan-6

Device Utilization Summary (estimated values)				
Logic Utilization	Used	Available	Utilization	
Number of Slice Registers	4135	4930	86%	
Number of Slice LUTs	4932	2400	201%	
Number of fully used LUTFF pairs	4016	4951	81%	
Number of bonded IOBs	179	302	179%	
Number of BUFGs/BUFGCTRLs	1	16	6%	

Virtex-6

e) Matlab and Virtex-6 FPGA output comparison

The same real time signal is filtered in both MATLAB and in VIRTEX-6 FPGA. The results are observed.

VII. CONCLUSION

The IIR filter is implemented on VIRTEX-6 FPGA to reduce the noise of underwater acoustic signal. From the results we observed that the IIR filter greatly reduces the noise of the signal and is efficiently implemented in FPGAs. Utilization of resources in virtex-6 board are less compared to Spartan-6 board. So the computational time is less. Chebyshev type-I band-pass filter eliminates the unwanted signal. FPGA results are cross checked with MATLAB results. By using digital filters in FPGAs the computational speed increases.

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Online Power Management System for Smart Home using RF Technology

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Abstract— RF Technology is advanced communication system where we can make reliable communication here we are interfacing the RF communication with cloud computing, connecting to the Internet at any time and any place has been made easy and possible. On the other hand, as our world is suffering energy crisis on oil and natural resources shortages, how to make efficient use of limited power energy has remained a major problem to be conquered so far. Aimed to facilitate the life of human being as well as to use the limited power energy more efficiently, we propose in this paper a technology that can perform remote control and monitoring of electrical appliances on the Internet. To do this, an Advanced intelligent power socket (AIPS) module that is able to control and monitoring the power of electricity is realized in this research. The IPS modules are placed in conjunction with the electrical appliances that are to be controlled from a far-end place. In addition, an embedded system based home gateway that can be connected with the Internet is set up in which the electrical appliances are located. Moreover, the acquired power consumption information or the status of the appliances is stored in a database server in the Cloud. With the proposed structure, authorized users or system managers can log into the web server which is connected with the database, monitoring the power status and take actions on the appliances remotely. The control command from the far-end place, i.e., from the web server on the Internet, is first sent to the home gateway and then transmitted to the AIPS modules through the RF wireless communication protocol so that the remote control of appliances can be achieved. The proposed architecture can be easily applied to any kind of room space. Moreover, only a browser is needed for the client to communicate with the web server, no other application program is required. As the browser is now available almost on every information technology products, e.g., a notebook or a smart phone, the proposed architecture has been shown to be very convenient and useful for remote control and monitoring of electrical appliances, and hence can facilitate the life of human beings.

Keywords—RF, Cloud computing, IR, Embedded Systems

I. INTRODUCTION

Our world is now suffering energy crisis on oil and natural resources shortages. What's worse is that most of the scientific industries all over the world

rely heavily on these resources, especially the power energy. The high demands on power energy do have a great impact on the economy of the world. From the catastrophe of Japanese Tsunami in March 2011, we are aware of the risks of nuclear power. Therefore, we realize that the termination of nuclear power delivery is just a matter of time. However, nuclear power cannot be replaced by Green power in the near future yet. Therefore, while discovering a substitution for nuclear power, we can now embark on energy saving. Considering our living environment, almost every place, e.g., office, school, and dwelling house, are all equipped with computers, air conditioners, lights and other high-power consumption devices. People usually forgot turning off the power devices after they are not in use. Therefore, how to make efficient use of the limited energy resources so that wasting of power energy can be avoided has become a major problem to be conquered. Recently, the idea of central power management system is proposed. However most of the central power management system just perform on and off operation on the power switch in a room space, control on every single or individual appliance is hard to attained. In [1], a client/server based architecture in conjunction with bluetooth signal for the remote control of home appliances is proposed. They also propose the use of a Hall current transducer for the monitoring of the status of electrical appliances. However, only on and off control can be attained, and a specific application program should be installed on both the client host and the server so that the control command can be transmitted via the Internet [1]. A smart home energy management system (SHEM) based on personal area networks is proposed in [2] [3]. The SHEM system, which provided with the context-aware ability and applies the use of RF signal for indoor wireless transmission of commands, is a well designed architecture for smart home systems. However, the SHEM system cannot be controlled remotely, and the power measurement ability is also not implemented [2] [3]. To monitoring the power consumption, some of the researches propose measuring the power consumption in digital manners [4][5] or reading the power consumption remotely [6] so that the human resources of the power company originally arranged for recording the power meter of individual customer

can be saved. On the other hand, the user can also know the status of individual electrical appliance remotely. Aimed to facilitate the life of human being as well as to use the limited power energy more efficiently, we propose in this paper a technology that can perform remote control and monitoring of electrical appliances on the Internet. To do this, a module that is able to control the power of electricity is realized. We call this module intelligent power socket (IPS) in the proposed system. The IPS modules are placed in conjunction with the electrical appliances that are to be controlled from a far-end place on the Internet. To do this, an embedded system-based home gateway that can be connected with the Internet is set up in which the electrical appliances are located. Besides, we also set up a web server and a database server in the cloud. The database server is used to record the status and power consumption of individual appliances. With the proposed architecture, authorized users or the system manager can log into the web server which is connected with the database, monitoring the status and take actions on the home appliances remotely.

The user command from the far-end place, i.e., from the web server in the cloud, is first sent to the home gateway and then transmitted to the IPS modules through RF wireless communication so that the remote control of the appliances can be achieved. The proposed architecture can be easily applied to any kind of room space. Moreover, no application program should be installed in the proposed architecture; only a browser for the client is needed. As the browser is now available almost in any devices, e.g., a note book or a smart phone. The proposed system architecture is hence very friendly and convenient to users that also facilitates the life of mankind. As can be seen the proposed architecture is mainly composed of three blocks, the client, the cloud web server and database server, and the room space in which the electrical appliances are located. Any devices equipped with a browser can be used as the client device. The database server here is used to record the status or power consumption of individual electrical appliances. Here, we use My SQL, powerful and free software, as our database server. To bridge the user, i.e., the browser, and the database server, a web server is required. We apply a cache, widely used, free, and stable software, as our web server. The client can now communicate with the web server through HTTP protocol, an application layer protocol which is based on TCP/IP protocol in the Internet hierarchy, monitoring the status and take actions on individual appliance. The control commands from the server in the Cloud are first sent to the home gateway through TCP/IP protocol and then transmitted to the appliance with RF wireless communication. The home gateway is a server which is used to receive the user command from the far-end place on the Internet, and to transmit the status as

well as the power consumption information of appliances back to the database server. To make the gateway compact, the RDK-S2e, a Cortex-M3-based module developed by Texas Instruments incorporation (TI), is chosen for this purpose which is shown in figure1. Moreover, the RDK-S2e module which transforms between UART and TCP/IP protocol is very useful for industrial applications for its compact dimension and robustness.

Fig.1. (a) The Cortex-M3-based RDK-S2e module (b) The CC2530 Zigbee transceiver

The gateway will then transmit the received commands to a RF transceiver through the universal asynchronous transmitter and receiver (UART) interface. The RF protocol, which is based on the standard of *IEEE 802.15.4*, has been widely applied in a variety of fields for its characteristics of low-power consumption and supporting variable topologies [2]-[13]. With these advantages, the RF is also selected for the short distance transmission of signals in the proposed architecture. We choose in this research the chip CC2530, a chip also developed by TI, as the RF transceiver. The command is then sent to another RF receiver which is connected to the appliance to be controlled in a wireless manner. To summarize, the architecture of remote control process can be best observed through, an architecture for smart home systems. The appliances are all integrated with the proposed IPS module so that the power of individual appliances can be controlled remotely. The IPS is also equipped with a RF transceiver, which is used to accept the command from the far-end as well as to transmit the status of the appliance back to the server in the cloud.

II. POWER CONTROL AND MEASUREMENT

The mechanism for power control and measurement will be addressed in this section. We first give a short introduction on the basis of proposed power control mechanism as shown in figure 2. After that, the IR remote control circuit as well as the power measurement mechanism will be introduced.

A. The Power Control Unit

The basis of the power control mechanism is the zero crossing detection circuit, which is shown in Fig. 3. Point **A** in Fig. 3 is a fully rectified waveform, where point **B** is just an attenuated signal of **A**. After the inverter, the zero-crossing signals can be detected at point **C**, and the zero-crossing signals can then be used for the control of power electricity. In the

proposed architecture, the point **D** is used to control the duty cycle between on and off state of the solid State relay (SSR), which is indeed a pulse width modulation system. The circuit in Fig. 3 constitutes the main portion of the A IPS module. *B. The IR Remote Control Unit* It is noted that some of the appliances, e.g., the air conditioner, TV, etc, cannot be controlled by varying the power directly.

Fig.2. Proposed power control mechanism

For this, we design an IR transmission circuit. That just acts what an IR remoter performs. The circuit inside the dashed block in Fig. 4 is the sub-carrier generation circuit (usually 38KHz) as well as the IR transmitter. As can be seen the transmission of IR signal is controlled by the CC2530 module. *C. The Power Measurement Unit* The block as can be seen in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5, a small resistor is used in series with the load diagram of the power and measurement circuit as well as the detailed schematic diagram between the power measurement module and the CC2530 RF transmission module are shown in Fig. 5 and to measure the current flow of the electrical appliance. The sensed current and voltage signal are then amplified and processed through the chip ADE7753, a single phase multifunction metering IC. Besides, the instantaneous current, voltage signal, the instantaneous power consumption, active power, reactive power as well as the power factor information (in Fig. 6) can all be calculated and kept in the registers of ADE7753. We can then read all the values out by connecting the serial SPI interface between the ADE7753 the CC2530 controller. The CC2530 controller can calculate the

Fig. 3. IR transmission circuits, Fig.4. Block diagram of power measurement module, Fig.5. Schematic diagram of power measurement module, Fig.6 Measurement of power factor

Power energy used by summing up the acquired instantaneous power consumption. These power energy information will be transmitted to the home gateway via the wireless RF signal, and then sent back to the database in the cloud.

III. DATABASE LAYOUT AND COMMUNICATION PROTOCOLS

In this section, the layout of the database server as well as the command format i.e., the communication protocol, are to be introduced.

A. Database Layout

In the proposed architecture, we use My SQL, a very popular and free database software, as our database server. In the database, we have a main table that records the authorized users and their password. Every registered user has an individual table that records the status of every electrical appliances, which is the main page of PHP My Admin, a web-based interface that can manipulate the database server in a graphical manner. After connected and logged into the database server, the authorized user will see the status of each electrical appliances. The user can then change to the command mode. Which is actually a *FORM* component in HTML document for interactive page design. The user can then select the command or adjust the power of selected appliance. After selecting the button next, the control command will be sent out to the home gateway through the TCP/IP protocol on the Internet. The dynamic page on the web server is realized by using the PHP language, a kind of script language embedded in the HTML document. We thus transfer the control commands to the home gateway by using the PHP socket after the user has pressed the command button.

The web server now acts just like a client for the connection is initiated by the PHP socket. The TCP/IP connection flow is shown in Fig. 7. The function *socket write()* in Fig. 7 is to transmit the command to the home gateway, while the function *socket read()* is to *read* the status as well as the power consumption information of the appliance. The read procedure is necessary because we have to make sure that the commands or actions have been carried out on the appliances to be controlled.

Fig.7. Connection process to the home gateway

B. Communication Protocols

In this subsection, we introduce three kinds of command format used in the proposed architecture, i.e., the command format for wired devices, the command format for devices controlled by IR remoter, and that of the acknowledgement from devices. The third byte is due to that we have three power sockets in each A IPS module. Therefore, we have to indicate which number of the power socket is to be controlled. Indeed, we have already registered the name of the device connected to each power socket on the database before the control process. In addition, the *Module ID 0X00* in the second byte is reserved for devices that have to be controlled by IR remoter.

IV. CONCLUSION

Aimed to facilitate the life of human beings as well as to use the limited power energy more efficiently, we propose in this paper a technology that can perform remote control and monitoring of electrical appliances on the Internet. To do this, an intelligent power socket (AIPS) module that is able to control and monitoring the power of electricity has been realized successfully in this research. The IPS modules are placed in conjunction with the electrical appliances that are to be controlled from a far-end place. In addition, an embedded system-based home gateway that can be connected with the Internet is set

up in which the electrical appliances are located. Moreover, the acquired power consumption information or the status of the appliances are all stored in a database server in the Cloud. With the proposed structure, authorized users or the system manager can log into the web server which connected with the database, monitoring the power status and take actions on the appliances remotely. The control command from the far-end place, i.e., from the web server on the Internet, is first sent to the home gateway and then transmitted to the AIPS respectively. Modules through the RF wireless communication protocol so that the remote control of appliances can be achieved. The proposed architecture can be easily applied to any kind of room space. Moreover, only a browser is needed for the client to communicate with the web server, no other application program is required. As the browser is now available almost on every information technology products, e.g., a notebook or a smart phone, the proposed architecture has been shown to be very convenient and useful, and hence can facilitate the life of human being.

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Pedestrian Detection for Vehicle Autonomous Navigation System by Using CMOS Camera

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Abstract – Wireless sensor network based architecture is designed for the purpose of image transmission between two controlling units through CMOS camera. It is used to increase the data transmission speed. This project can be applied to any surveillance purpose. The protocol serial communication is used to transmit image accurately to the monitoring section. Image transmission with a combined robotic application is presented in this paper. For vehicle purpose, the path of the vehicle has to feed initially. This robotic section runs with LPC2148 with CMOS camera with RF transmitter and the other section with 8051 and RF receiver and monitoring section runs with MATLAB platform. Communications between two sections are accomplished through RF.

Keywords- ARM, RF, CMOS Camera

I. INTRODUCTION

A self powered object tracking is been discussed in this project. A CMOS camera and ARM can do on-board image transmission, and these images are processed on MATLAB to localize vehicle and alert pedestrians. CMOS image sensors are rapidly becoming the technology of choice for digital imaging in mobile phones and other digital consumer portable products as they offer advantages in size, power consumption and system cost.

In this project, image transmission will be done with object tracking. The image transmission time is increased with the protocol standard. The Traffic signal section runs with CMOS Cam module and LPC2148 and monitoring unit runs on MATLAB platform. Communications between two units (hardware and PC) are accomplished through serial communication.

A. Block Diagram

Fig.1. ARM Processor of Signal section.

Fig.2. Monitoring section.

Fig.3. 8051 section.

II. HARDWARE AND DESIGN

The ARM7TDMI core is the industry's most widely used 32-bit embedded RISC microprocessor solution. Optimized for cost and power-sensitive applications, the ARM7TDMI solution provides the low power consumption, small size, and high performance needed in portable, embedded applications.

The ARM7EJ-S processor is a synthesizable core that provides all the benefits of the ARM7TDMI – low power consumption, small size, and the thumb instruction set while also incorporating ARM's latest DSP extensions and Jazelle technology, enabling acceleration of java-based applications.

Compatible with the ARM9, ARM9, and ARM10 families, and Strong-Arm architecture software written for the ARM7TDMI processor is 100% binary-compatible with other members of the ARM7 family and forwards-compatible with the ARM9, ARM9E, and ARM10 families, as well as products in Intel's Strong ARM and x-scale architectures.

A. Features

The features of AT89C51 is,

- Compatible with MCS-51TH products.
- 4 Kbytes of in-system reprogram able flash memory.
- Fully static operation: 0 Hz to 24 MHz.
- Three-level program Memory Lock.
- 128*8-Bit Internal RAM.
- 32 Programmable I/O Lines.
- Two 16-Bit Timer/Counters.
- Six Interrupt sources.
- Programmable serial channel.
- Low Power Idle and Power Down Modes

B. RF Module

The XBee/XBee-PRO RF Modules are Radio Frequency, any frequency within the electromagnetic spectrum associated with radio wave propagation. When an RF current is supplied to an antenna, an electromagnetic field is created that then is able to propagate through space. Many wireless technologies are based on RF field propagation.

The range of Radio Frequency is 10 kHz to 300 GHz. It can be used for wireless communication and also used generally to refer to the radio signal generated by the system transmitter, or to energy present from other sources that may be picked up by a wireless receiver.

- Wireless mouse, keyboard
- Wireless data communication
- Alarm and security systems
- Home Automation, Remote control
- Automotive Telemetry
- Intelligent sports equipment
- Handheld terminals, Data loggers
- High-end security and fire alarms

The TWS-434 extremely small, and are excellent for applications requiring short-range RF remote controls. The transmitter module is only 1/3 the size of a standard postage stamp, and can easily be placed inside a small plastic enclosure.

TWS-434: The transmitter output is up to 8mW at 433.92MHz with a range of approximately 400 foot (open area) outdoors. Indoors, the range is approximately 200 foot, and will go through most walls.

The TWS-434 transmitter accepts both linear and digital inputs can operate from 1.5 to 12 Volts-DC, and makes building a miniature hand-held RF transmitter very easy. The TWS-434 is approximately 1/3 the size of a standard postage stamp.

RWS-434: The receiver also operates at 433.92MHz, and has a sensitivity of 3uV. The WS-434 receiver operates from 4.5 to 5.5 volts-DC, and has both linear and digital outputs.

Fig.5. RF Receiver and Transmitter.

IV. INTRODUCTION TO MATLAB

MATLAB is a high-performance language for technical computing. It integrates computation, visualization, and programming in an easy-to-use environment where problems and solutions are expressed in familiar mathematical notation. Typical uses include

- Math and computation
- Algorithm development
- Data acquisition
- Modeling, simulation, and prototyping
- Data analysis, exploration, and visualization
- Scientific and engineering graphics

Application development, including graphical user interface building

MATLAB is an interactive system whose basic data element is an array that does not require dimensioning. This allows you to solve many technical computing problems, especially those with matrix and vector formulations, in a fraction of the time it would take to write a program in a scalar non interactive language such as C or FORTRAN. The name MATLAB stands for matrix laboratory. MATLAB was originally written to provide easy access to matrix software developed by the LINPACK and EISPACK projects. Today, MATLAB engines incorporate the LAPACK and BLAS libraries, embedding the state of the art in software for matrix computation. MATLAB has evolved over a period of years with input from many users.

In university environments, it is the standard instructional tool for introductory and advanced courses in mathematics, engineering, and science. In industry, MATLAB is the tool of choice for high-productivity research, development, and analysis. MATLAB features a family of add-on application-specific solutions called toolboxes. Very important to most uses of MATLAB, toolboxes allow you to learn and apply specialized technology. Toolboxes are

comprehensive collections of MATLAB functions (M-files) that extend the MATLAB environment to solve particular classes of problems. Areas in which toolboxes are available include signal processing, control systems, neural networks, fuzzy logic, wavelets, simulation, and many others.

A. MATLAB system

The MATLAB system consists of five main parts are,

1. Development Environment

This is the set of tools and facilities that help you use MATLAB functions and files. Many of these tools are graphical user interfaces. It includes the MATLAB desktop and command window, a command history, an editor and debugger, and browsers for viewing help, the workspace, files, and the search path.

2. The MATLAB Mathematical Function Library

This is a vast collection of computational algorithms ranging from elementary functions, like sum, sine, cosine, and complex arithmetic, to more sophisticated functions like matrix inverse, matrix Eigen values, Bessel functions, and fast Fourier transforms.

3. The MATLAB Language

This is a high-level matrix/array language with control flow statements, functions, data structures, input/output, and object-oriented programming features. It allows both "programming in the small" to rapidly create quick and dirty throw-away programs, and "programming in the large" to create large and complex application programs.

4. Graphics

MATLAB has extensive facilities for displaying vectors and matrices as graphs, as well as annotating and printing these graphs. It includes high-level functions for two-dimensional and three-dimensional data visualization, image processing, animation, and presentation graphics. It also includes low-level functions that allow you to fully customize the appearance of graphics as well as to build complete graphical user interfaces on your MATLAB applications.

5. The MATLAB Application Program Interface (API)

This is a library that allows you to write C and FORTRAN programs that interact with MATLAB. It includes facilities for calling routines from MATLAB

(dynamic linking), calling MATLAB as a computational engine, and for reading and writing MAT-files.

Various toolboxes are there in MATLAB for computing recognition techniques, but we are using IMAGE PROCESSING toolbox.

V. CMOS CAMERA

The μ CAM (micro CAM) is a highly integrated serial camera module which can be attached to any host system that requires a video camera or a JPEG compressed still camera for embedded imaging applications.

Fig.6. CMOS Camera.

The module uses an Omni Vision CMOS VGA colour sensor along with a JPEG compression chip that provides a low cost and low powered camera system. The module has an on-board serial interface (TTL or RS232) that is suitable for a direct connection to any host micro-controller UART or a PC system COM port.

User commands are sent using a simple serial protocol that can instruct the camera to send low resolution (160x120 or 80x60) single frame raw images for a quick viewing or high resolution (640x480 or 320x240) JPEG images for storage or viewing. The μ CAM comes in a compact form factor with a built in lens and a 4-wire connector that provides easy access to both power and serial data. Small size, low cost and low powered camera module for embedded imaging applications.

The features are,

- μ CAM-TTL: 3.3V DC Supply
- μ CAM-232: 5.0V DC Supply
- On-board EEPROM provides a command-based interface to external host via TTL or RS-232 serial link.
- UART: up to 1.2Mbps for transferring JPEG still pictures or raw images.
- On board Omni Vision OV7640/8 VGA colour sensor and JPEG CODEC for different resolutions.
- Built-in down sampling, clamping and
- Windowing circuits for VGA, QVGA, 160x120 or 80x60 image resolutions.

- Built-in colour conversion circuits for 2-bit gray, 4-bit gray, 8-bit gray, 12-bit RGB, 16-bit RGB or standard JPEG preview images.
- No external DRAM required.
- Weight is 11g.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this project, image transmission will be done with object tracking. The image transmission time is increased with the protocol standard. The Traffic signal section runs with CMOS Cam module and LPC2148 and monitoring unit runs on Matlab platform. Communications between two units hardware and PC are accomplished through serial communication. Camera attached to the Processor will continuously track the vehicle and pedestrians on the X-road region. If any vehicle and pedestrians are detected then automatically interrupt handling technique in the processor will receive the image and it will convert the image in to packets and transmit through serial communication. The monitoring section receives the image and converts the pixel values into image by using Matlab platform. Using an RF transmitter module the alert signal will be send to the vehicle. Similarly the buzzer on street will also blow to alert pedestrians.

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Medical Image Segmentation Of A New Metric Distribution Using GAC and Level Set Approach

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Abstract— In this paper, present a new distribution metric for image segmentation that arises as a result in prediction Theory using level set method. We incorporate an energy model based on the metric into the Geometric Active Contour framework. We demonstrate the Kaposi Sarcoma algorithm on several challenging medical images, which further ensure the viability of the metric in the context of image segmentation. In particular, it implements active contours utilizing an energy derived from prediction theory. This implementation is not very fast! It should only be used as a proof of concept of the new distribution metric. Please see other implementation methods for active contours for a big speed up (i.e., the same functional and energy can be utilized in other faster frameworks).

Keywords-Geometric Active Contours, Distributions, Metrics Segmentation, Level set Evolution.

I.INTRODUCTION

A well-studied problem in computer vision is the fundamental task of segmenting or partitioning an image into disjoint regions with applications ranging from medical image analysis, quality control, or military surveillance and tracking. Although the general segmentation problem involves separating N distinct partitions, a piecewise assumption of two sets is generally made. That is, the image is assumed to be comprised of two homogeneous regions, often referred to as "Object" and "Background". The goal of segmentation is to accurately capture these regions. Specifically, the use of active contours has been proven to be quite successful in accomplishing this task. [1-6]

Employing the methodology of geometric active contours (GAC), a curve is represented as the zero levelset of a higher dimensional surface [7, 8] a common choice is the signed distance function. Although this implicit representation of a curve is computationally more expensive than parametric approaches, it allows for the contour to naturally undergo topological changes. In the GAC framework, a curve is evolved to minimize image based energy functional, typically via gradient descent. Several energy functionals have been proposed in literature:

Some models use local information and features such as edges, 3 while other methods use regional information by discriminating on a photometric variable of interest (e.g., gray-scale intensity, color, tensors). Recently, hybrid models, which incorporate regional statistics in a localized fashion, have been proposed [9]. It should also be Noted that one can constrain the evolution of a curve by incorporating shape information, and we refer the interested reader for more details to the following references.

Region based approaches have been popularized due to a higher level of robustness to noise and initialization when compared to models based on local information. In region-based segmentation, energy models employ the use of image statistics dependent on the segmenting curve using parametric [10] and non-parametric methods. In this work, we will restrict most of our discussion to approaches that generalize the statistical inference beyond first and second moments to entire probability density functions (pdf). From this, segmentation can be reinterpreted as measuring the "distance" between two distributions via a similarity metric.

There are many advantages of region-based approaches when compared to edge-based methods including robustness against initial curve placement and insensitivity to image noise. However, techniques that attempt to model regions using global statistics are usually not ideal for segmenting heterogeneous objects. In cases where the object to be segmented cannot be easily distinguished in terms of global statistics, region-based active contours may lead to erroneous segmentations. The construction of this image causes it to be segmented improperly by a standard region-based algorithm [, but correctly by an edge-based algorithm. Heterogeneous objects frequently occur in natural and medical imagery. To accurately segment these objects, a new class of active contour energies should be considered which utilizes local information, but also incorporates the benefits of region-based techniques.

Segmentation is to Partition an image into disjoint, connected components that are homogeneous w.r.t. intensity, texture or certain probabilistic

measures. Active contour method is evolving contours towards boundaries of interest by designed forces (e.g. edge, region information or prior knowledge). Active contour models have a consistent mathematical description; their solutions satisfy certain minimum principles.

Edge based Rely on edge information (high magnitude of image gradient) Limitation – sensitive to noise, artifacts, may leak through gaps on boundary Region based: Make use of information on regional statistics from image intensities. Limitation – high noise level, intensity homogeneity, complex intensity distribution Combination of edge based and region based.

II. MERTIC BASED ON PREDICTION THEORY

Typically, we seek to maximize the distance of two distributions defined by a certain photometric variable so as to identify the distribution that best characterizes an object or the foreground. To this end we motivate our metric that quantifies (dis)similarity between spectral distributions using basic concepts of prediction theory[11-12]. So let $f_1(\theta)$ and $f_2(\theta)$, with $\theta \in [0, \pi]$, denote the power spectral densities of two discrete-time, zero-mean, random processes $u_k^{f_i}$ with $i \in [1, 2]$ and $k \in \mathbb{Z}$. The variance of the optimal, linear, one-step-ahead prediction error for the process corresponding the density $f_i(\theta)$ is

$$\varepsilon \left\{ \left| u_0^{f_i} - \hat{u}_{0|past}^{f_i} \right|^2 \right\} = \varepsilon \left\{ \left| u_0^{f_i} - \sum \alpha_k^{f_i} u_{-k}^{f_i} \right|^2 \right\} \quad \dots\dots(1)$$

With $K > 0$. Hence, $\alpha_k^{f_i}$ denote the coefficients that minimize the linear prediction error variance for the specific $f_i(\theta)$.

Since we want to quantify dissimilarity between $f_1(\theta)$ and $f_2(\theta)$, we use $f_2(\theta)$ to design a linear predictor (i.e., coefficients $\alpha_k^{f_2}, k \geq 0$), and then compare how well this predictor performs when used to predict a random process with spectral density $f_1(\theta)$ against the optimal predictor for the corresponding process, i.e., the optimal one that is based on $f_1(\theta)$ instead of $f_2(\theta)$. That is, we quantify the degradation of predictive error variance for the case where the predictor is optimal for one process and then applied to the other. The degradation of predictive error variance turns out to

be equal to the ratio between the arithmetic over the geometric means of the fraction f_1/f_2 , namely

$$\rho(f_1, f_2) = \frac{\varepsilon \left\{ \left| u_0^{f_1} - \sum_{k=1}^{k=\infty} \alpha_k^{f_2} u_{-k}^{f_2} \right|^2 \right\}}{\varepsilon \left\{ \left| u_0^{f_1} - \sum_{k=1}^{k=\infty} \alpha_k^{f_1} u_{-k}^{f_1} \right|^2 \right\}} = \frac{\int \frac{f_1(\theta)}{f_2(\theta)} d\theta}{\exp \int \log \frac{f_1(\theta)}{f_2(\theta)} d\theta} \quad \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

The quantity $\rho(f_1, f_2)$ can be viewed as analogous to “divergences” such as the Kullback-Leibler relative entropy used in Information Theory. The differential form $\rho(f, f + \Delta)$, for Δ a “small” perturbation (i.e., neglecting third order terms and above), gives rise to the following Riemannian metric on the cone of spectral density functions

$$g_f(\nabla) := \int_x \left(\frac{\nabla(x)}{f(x)} \right)^2 dx - \left(\int_x \frac{\nabla(x)}{f(x)} dx \right)^2 \quad \dots\dots(3)$$

Geodesics turn out to be exponential families of distributions and geodesic distances can be computed in closed form. [13]. In fact, the geodesic distance provides the sought metric between distributions and tailored for the level set framework of the present paper. It is interesting to note that geodesic distances are insensitive to scaling and can be seen as giving rise to a “shape” comparator (and hence, actually, a pseudo-metric).

III. NEW VERSION OF SNAKE MODEL– GEOMETRIC ACTIVE CONTOURS (GAC)

Based on the classical snakes, Caselles *et al* in [14] and Kichenassy *et al* in proposed a new model of snake- Geometric Active Contour (GAC). The model is defined by the following minimization problem

$$\min_c \left\{ E_{GAC}(c) = \int_0^{L(c)} g(|\nabla I(c(s))|) ds \right\} \quad \dots\dots(4)$$

Where ds is the length of the Euclidean element and $L(C)$ is the length of the curve C defined:

So, the energy function in (6) is actually a new length obtained by dl -Euclidean element of length and function g which contains information concerning the boundaries of object. The function g is an edge indicator function. It has values close to zero in the regions where the gradient of image is high. For example in [16], authors choose

$$g = \frac{1}{1 + |\nabla I|^2} \quad \dots\dots\dots(5)$$

Where \tilde{I} is a smoothed version of image I .

Although it has many good properties when using GAC model in segmentation but the snake/GAC model is highly sensitive to the initial contour. In other words an improper initial contour can give inaccurate result. The problem with the initial contour relates to the non-convexity of the energy function, $EGAC$, to be minimized and then the existence of the local minimum. It prevents the segmentation of the objects (parts) lying in images. So, choosing an image segmentation model, which gives correct results but is independent of initial contour, is necessary. Such method is to find a global minimum of the energy function of GAC model.[15]

IV. PROPOSED SEGMENTATION OF KAPOSI SARCOMA

Although various metrics and distributional functional have been proposed for segmentation in the GAC framework, a qualitative comparison to demonstrate the varying behavior has not been done (to the best of our knowledge). The goal of this experiment is not to claim the ideal energy model for distinguishing between two distributions, but to add our metric with differing properties to a general class of models discriminating on probability densities. Hence, we would like show that with the same distribution, two different metrics can provide drastically different results. Note, no smoothing or regularizing term is used in these comparisons, and the results are obtained strictly on the energy describing the respective similarity measure

We demonstrate segmentation of the similarity metric proposed in this paper. Note, the same initialization is used, and hence, the same initial pdf's. Moreover, it favors to segment an entirely different region. However, an acceptable segmentation result is obtained by evolving the curve.

On a different case of the Kaposi Sarcoma, in this paper results in a successful segmentation. From these experiments, we believe (without proof) the metric proposed and the ability to capture objects under low contrast. As present in both of the Kaposi Sarcoma images, the infected portion's gray-scale intensity is not entirely different from the region surrounding it, when compared to region exterior of the initial curve. This will be a subject of future work. Several stages of the segmentation are given.[16-17]

V. PROPOSED SIMILARITY METRIC WITH LEVEL SET FORMULATION

We consider the problem of segmenting an image I . That is, we first assume the image is composed of two homogeneous regions referred to as "Object" and "Background". From this, the goal of segmentation is to capture these two regions. To do so, we enclose a curve C , represented as the zero-

level set of a signed distance function $\phi : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, such that $\phi < 0$ represents the inside of C and $\phi > 0$ represents the outside of C . Our goal is to evolve the curve C , or equivalently ϕ , so that the interior matches the Object and the exterior matches the Background. As a result, the curve C would then match the boundary of the curve $\partial\Omega$ separating the Object and Background. The general minimization is performed by evolving C according to the flow:

$$\frac{\partial\phi}{\partial t} = \nabla_{\phi} E_{image} + \lambda \cdot \delta(\phi) \cdot \text{div} \left(\frac{\nabla(\phi)}{|\nabla(\phi)|} \right) \dots (6)$$

Where a regularization term is added to the image based energy. We now propose energy functional based on our metric discussed previously, and derive the corresponding partial differential equation (PDE) that describes its curve evolution in the level set framework. Moreover, because our metric measures similarity or "distance" as the standard deviation between the log-likelihood of two distributions, pin and $pout$, we seek to maximize the following energy functional

$$E_{img}(z, \phi) = \sqrt{\mathcal{E} \left\{ \log \frac{p_m(z, \phi)}{p_{ur}(z, \phi)} \right\}^2} - \sqrt{\mathcal{E} \left\{ \log \frac{p_m(z, \phi)}{p_{ur}(z, \phi)} \right\}^2} \dots (7)$$

Where $\mathcal{E}\{f(z)\}$ is the expected value of the functional $f(z)$ with respect to the random photometric variable $z \in Z$, and pin and $pout$ are the pdf's defined on the random variable z . In the present work, we restrict the variable z to set of gray level values $\{1, 2, \dots, 256\}$. Moreover, let $I: \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow Z$ be a mapping of the image defined over the domain Ω , to the photometric variable z , and $x \in \mathbb{R}^2$ be the image coordinates. Then the pdf inside the curve C can be formulated as such

$$p_{in}(z, \phi) = \int_{\Omega} \frac{K(z - I(x)) H_{\epsilon}(-\phi)}{H_{\epsilon}(-\phi)} dx \dots (8)$$

$$p_{out}(z, \phi) = \int_{\Omega} \frac{K(z - I(x)) H_{\epsilon}(\phi)}{H_{\epsilon}(\phi)} dx \dots (9)$$

Where $K(z - I(x))$ is a specified kernel. For numerical experiments, we have used $K(z - I(x)) = \delta_{\epsilon}(z - I(x))$. Also $H_{\epsilon}: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ denotes the smoothed Heaviside step function with the corresponding derivative δ_{ϵ} .

The gradient $\nabla_{\phi} T$ can be computed using the calculus of variations. Taking the first variation with respect to ϕ , we arrive at the following PDE

$$\nabla_{\phi} E_{image} = - \frac{\delta_{\epsilon}(\phi)}{E_{image}} \cdot [\mathcal{E}\{B.G\} - \mathcal{E}\{B\} \cdot \mathcal{E}\{G\}] \dots (10)$$

With B and G given as

$$B = \log \frac{p_{in}(z, \phi)}{p_{out}(z, \phi)} \quad \dots (11)$$

$$G = \left[\frac{1}{A_h} + \frac{1}{A_u} \right] K(z - I(x)) \left(\frac{1}{A_h p_n(z, \phi)} + \frac{1}{A_u p_u(z, \phi)} \right) \quad \dots (12)$$

Also noting that A_{in} is given by, $\int_{\Omega} H_{\epsilon}(\phi) dx$

Equation (10) is a PDE that describes the evolution of the curve C that optimally maximizes the “distance” between the distributions which correspond to the exterior and interior regions of segmenting curve [18-20]

VI. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS OF PERFECT SEGMENTATION

We present experimental results obtained from evolving a curve C according to Equation (6). Moreover, we compute segmenting the Kaposi Sarcoma, a pathology that infects the skin. We also demonstrate our algorithm on segmenting medical structures and the classic image of a zebra figure1&2.

Figure 1. Case one of the Kaposi Sarcoma. Top Row: shows the evolution of a curve according to the Bhattacharyya distance resulting in an unsuccessful segmentation. Bottom Row: Successful segmentation when using the proposed similarity metric

Figure 2: The Classic Zebra. Top Row: Several stages of the segmentation in which we capture the bimodal object Bottom Row: Corresponding distribution plots of both interior (red) and exterior (blue) regions if segmenting curve

VII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, proposed an efficient medical image segmentation using a new similarity metric method with geometry active contours (GAC) and

level set formulation. The method has advantage of perfect locked segmentation with level set evolution. We introduce a new metric for image segmentation that quantifies the “distance” between two distributions as the standard deviation of the difference between logarithms of those densities. While several metrics and measures have been proposed for image segmentation, results often vary drastically. Specifically, although separating distributions using the Bhattacharyya distance as a measure has resulted in the successful segmentation on some challenging imagery, in other cases such as the Kaposi Sarcoma, the Bhattacharyya - based algorithm fails to capture the infected portion of the skin while the energy model proposed in this paper results in a successful segmentation.

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A Mean Shift Clustering Based Segmentation of HR Satellite Imagery using Level set Approach

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Abstract: In this paper, a novel Fast Mean shift clustering for High Resolution (HR) satellite images with level set method. First we selectively penalize the level set function to be binary and then use a Gaussian smoothing kernel to regularize it. The advantages of our method is a new region based signed pressure force (SPF) function is proposed, which can step effectively the contour at weak or blurred edges and automatically detect the interior and exterior boundaries with the initial contour being any where in the images effected with noise. The proposed method allows a low dimensional image clustering with significant reduction of the complexity experimental results with High resolution satellite images show that the proposed algorithm is superior to the typical MS algorithm, producing high precision and requiring less operation time.

Keywords- Active contours, Image segmentation, Chan-vase model, Level set method.

I. INTRODUCTION

Image Segmentation refers to the process of partitioning a digital image into multiple segments. It subdivides an image into its constitute regions or object. The goal of segmentation is to simplify and change the representation of an image into something that is more meaningful and easier to analyze. Segmentation should stop when the object of interest in an application have been isolated. Image segmentation is typically used to locate objects and boundaries (lines, curves, etc.) in images. More precisely, image segmentation is the process of assigning a label to every pixel in an image such that pixels with the same label share certain visual characteristics. Segmentation of nontrivial images is one of the most difficult tasks in image processing. The result of image segmentation is a set of segments that collectively cover the entire image, or a set of contours extracted from the image. Each of the pixels in a region is similar with respect to some characteristic or computed property, such as color, intensity or texture. Adjacent regions are significantly different with respect to the same characteristics [1-5].

Image segmentation plays an important role in the field of image understanding, image analysis and

pattern identification. The foremost essential goal of the segmentation process is to partition an image into regions that are homogeneous (uniform) with respect to one or more

Self-characteristics and features. Active contour methods are applied in a wide range of problems including visual tracking and image segmentation. The basic idea is to allow a contour to deform so as to minimize a given energy functional in order to produce the desired segmentation. Two main categories exist for active contours: edge-based and region-based. Edge-based active contour models utilize image gradients in order to identify object boundaries, e.g., [6], [7]. Region-based ACMs have many advantages over edge-based ones. Initially, region-based models utilize the statistical information inside and outside the contour to control the evolution, which are less sensitive to noise; give better performance for images with weak edges or without edges and they are significantly less sensitive to the location of initial contour, further more they can efficiently detect the exterior and interior boundaries simultaneously.

In this paper, a novel mean shift clustering with level set method, i.e. Selective Binary and Gaussian Filtering Regularized Level Set Evolution (SBGFRLS), to implement our model. Unlike in Traditional Level Set methods, this method avoids the calculation of SDF and costly re-initialization [8-11]. Firstly the Level Set Evolution will be penalized by using a selective step and then we use a Gaussian filter to regularize it. The Gaussian filter can make the level set function smooth and the evolution more stable. Furthermore, computational complexity analysis shows that the SBGFRLS method is more efficient than the traditional level set methods. In addition, the proposed model implemented with SBGFRLS has a property of selective global segmentation, which can not only extract the desired objects, but also accurately extract all the objects with interior and exterior boundaries[12-14].

This paper is organized as follows: In section II described the Mean shift clustering algorithm. In section III we describe our method with level set approach and show how to construct the region-based SPF function. Section IV validates our method by extensive experiments on HR satellite images.

II. MEAN SHIFT CLUSTERING APPROACH

A. Intuitive Idea of Mean Shift:

This section provides an intuitive idea of Mean shift and the later sections will expand the idea. Mean shift considers feature space as a empirical probability density function. If the input is a set of points then Mean shift considers them as sampled from the underlying probability density function. If dense regions (or clusters) are present in the feature space, then they correspond to the mode (or local maxima) of the probability density function. We can also identify clusters associated with the given mode using Mean Shift.

For each data point, Mean shift associates it with the nearby peak of the dataset's probability density function. For each data point, Mean shift defines a window around it and computes the mean of the data point. Then it shifts the center of the window to the mean and repeats the algorithm till it converges. After each iteration, we can consider that the window shifts to a denser region of the dataset.

At the high level, we can specify Mean Shift as follows:

1. Fix a window around each data point.
2. Compute the mean of data within the window.
3. Shift the window to the mean and repeat till convergence

Fig.1: mean shift process

B. Preliminaries:

i. Kernel Density Estimation

Kernel density estimation is a non parametric way to estimate the density function of a random variable. This is usually called as the Parzen window technique. Given a kernel K , bandwidth parameter h , Kernel density estimator for a given set of d -dimensional points is

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{nh^d} \sum_{i=1}^n K\left(\frac{x-x_i}{h}\right) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

C. Mean shift procedure:

At density maxima $\nabla f(x) = 0$

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla f(x) &= \frac{2c_k}{nh^{(d+2)}} \sum_{i=1}^n (x-x_i) k\left(\left\|\frac{x-x_i}{h}\right\|^2\right) \\ &= \\ &= \frac{2c_k}{nh^{(d+2)}} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n g_i \right) \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i g_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n g_i} - x \right) \dots \dots \dots (2) \end{aligned}$$

For

$$g(r) = k^2(r), g_i = g(\|(x-x_i)/h\|^2) \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

As explained above, Mean shift treats the points the feature space as an probability density function. Dense regions in feature space corresponds to local maxima or modes. So for each data point, we perform gradient ascent on the local estimated density until convergence. The stationary points obtained via gradient ascent represent the modes of the density function. All points associated with the same stationary point belong to the same cluster

Mean Shift Vector:

$$m(x) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i g_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n g_i} - x \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

Successive locations of the kernel:

$$y_{j+1} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i g\left(\left\|\frac{y_j - x_i}{h}\right\|^2\right)}{\sum_{i=1}^n g\left(\left\|\frac{y_j - x_i}{h}\right\|^2\right)} \dots \dots \dots (5)$$

D. Algorithm Procedure for Mean Shift Clustering:

Input: A positive integer k , n data points, x_j , where $i=1,2,\dots,n$, one of the data points, and a total number N of iterations.

Output: An appropriate local maximum (mode) of the density

1. $h=0.2$
2. $j=1$
3. while $j < N$
4.
$$y_2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{h^{d+2}} x_i g\left(\left\|\frac{y_1 - x_i}{h}\right\|^2\right)}{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{h^{d+2}} g\left(\left\|\frac{y_1 - x_i}{h}\right\|^2\right)}$$
5. $y_1 = y_2$
6. $j=j+1$
7. End while

III. LEVEL SET SEGMENTATION APPROACH

A. The Chan-Vese (Cv) Model:

Chan and Vese [15] proposed an ACM which can be seen as a special case of the Mumford-Shah problem [11]. For a given image I in domain X , the C-V model is formulated by minimizing the following energy functional:

$$E^{cv} = \lambda_1 \int_{\text{inside}(c)} |I(x) - C_1|^2 dx + \lambda_2 \int_{\text{outside}(c)} |I(x) - C_2|^2 dx, x \in \Omega \quad \dots\dots (6)$$

Where C_1 and C_2 are two constants which are the average intensities inside and outside the contour, respectively. With the level set method, we assume

$$C = \{x \in \Omega: \phi(x) = 0\}$$

$$\text{Inside}(C) = \{x \in \Omega: \phi(x) > 0\}$$

$$\text{Outside}(C) = \{x \in \Omega: \phi(x) < 0\}$$

By minimizing eq.: (1), we solve C_1 and C_2 as follows

$$C_1 = \frac{\int_{\Omega} I(x) \cdot H(\phi) dx}{\int_{\Omega} H(\phi) dx} \quad \dots\dots\dots(7)$$

$$C_2 = \frac{\int_{\Omega} I(x) \cdot (1 - H(\phi)) dx}{\int_{\Omega} (1 - H(\phi)) dx} \quad \dots\dots\dots(8)$$

By incorporating the length and area energy terms into Eq. (1) and minimizing them, we obtain the corresponding variational level set formulation as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} = \delta(\phi) \left[\mu \nabla \left(\frac{\nabla \phi}{|\nabla \phi|} - \nu - \lambda_1 (I - C_1)^2 + \lambda_2 (I - C_2)^2 \right) \right] \quad \dots\dots (9)$$

Where $\mu \geq 0, \nu \geq 0, \lambda_1 > 0, \lambda_2 > 0$ are fixed parameters, μ controls the smoothness of zero level set, ν increases the propagation speed, λ_1 and λ_2 control the image data driven force inside and outside the contour, respectively. ∇ Is the gradient operator. $H(\phi)$ Is the Heaviside function and $\delta(\phi)$ is the Dirac function. Generally, the regularized versions are selected as follows:

$$H_{\varepsilon}(z) = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \frac{2}{\pi} \arctan \left(\frac{z}{\varepsilon} \right) \right), \quad \dots\dots\dots(10)$$

$$\delta_{\varepsilon}(z) = \frac{1}{\pi} \cdot \frac{\varepsilon}{\varepsilon^2 + z^2}, z \in R$$

B. SPF function design:

The SPF function defined in [16] has values in the range $[-1, 1]$. It changes the signs of the pressure forces inside and outside the region of interest so that the contour shrinks when outside the object, or expands when inside the object. Based on the analysis in Section 2, we construct the SPF function as follows:

$$spf(I(x)) = \frac{I(x) - \frac{c_1 + c_2}{2}}{\max \left(\left| I(x) - \frac{c_1 + c_2}{2} \right| \right)}, x \in R \quad \dots\dots\dots(11)$$

where C_1 and C_2 are defined in Eq. (7) and (8), respectively.

The significance of Eq. (11) is that, we assume the intensities inside and outside the object are homogeneous. It is intuitive that $\min(I(x)) \leq c_1, c_2 \leq \max(I(x))$, and the equal signs cannot be obtained simultaneously wherever the contour is. Hence, there is

$$m \min(I(x)) \leq \frac{c_1 + c_2}{2} \leq \max(I(x)), x \in \Omega \quad \dots\dots\dots(12)$$

Obviously, the signs of the SPF function in Eq. (10) are identical; it can serve as an SPF function. Substituting the SPF function in Eq. (10) for GAC model, the level set formulation of the proposed model is as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} = spf(I(x)) \cdot \left(\text{div} \left(\frac{\nabla \phi}{|\nabla \phi|} \right) + \alpha \right) |\nabla \phi| + \nabla spf(I(x)) \cdot \nabla \phi, x \in R \quad \dots\dots\dots(13)$$

C. Implementation to level set:

In the traditional level set methods, the level set function is initialized to be an SDF to its interface in order to prevent it from being too steep or flat near its interface, and re-initialization is required in the evolution. The undesirable side effect in many existing re-initialization methods is moving the zero level set away from its interface. Furthermore, it is difficult to decide when and how to apply the re-initialization. In addition, re-initialization is a very expensive operation. To solve these problems, we propose a novel level set method, which utilizes a Gaussian filter to regularize the selective binary level set function after each iteration. The procedure of penalizing level set function to be binary is optional according to the desired property of evolution. If we want local segmentation property, the procedure is necessary; otherwise, it is unnecessary.

In our method, the level set function can be initialized to constants, which have different signs inside and outside the contour. This is very simple to implement in practice. In the traditional level set methods, the curvature-based term $div\left(\frac{\nabla\phi}{|\nabla\phi|}\right)|\nabla\phi|$ is usually used to regularize the level set function ϕ . Since ϕ is an SDF that satisfies $|\nabla\phi|=1$ [17], the regularized term can be rewritten as $\Delta\phi$, which is the Laplacian of the level set function ϕ . As pointed out in [18-20] and based on the theory of scale-space the evolution of a function with its Laplacian is equivalent to a Gaussian kernel filtering the initial condition of the function. Thus we can use a Gaussian filtering process to further regularize the level set function. The standard deviation of the Gaussian filter can control the regularization strength, just as the parameter μ in Eq. (4) does. Since we utilize a Gaussian filter to smooth the level set function to keep the interface regular, the regular term $div\left(\frac{\nabla\phi}{|\nabla\phi|}\right)|\nabla\phi|$ is unnecessary. In addition, the term $\nabla spf \cdot \nabla\phi$ in Eq. (12) can also be removed, because our model utilizes the statistical information of regions, which has a larger capture range and capacity of anti-edge leakage. Finally, the level set formulation of the proposed model can be written as follows:

$$\frac{\partial\phi}{\partial t} = spf(I(x)) \cdot \alpha |\nabla\phi|, x \in \Omega \quad \dots\dots\dots (13)$$

The main procedures of the proposed algorithm are summarized as follows: Initialize the level set function ϕ as

$$\phi(x, t = 0) = \begin{cases} -\rho & x \in \Omega_0 - \delta\Omega_0 \\ 0 & x \in \delta\Omega_0 \\ \rho & x \in \Omega - \Omega_0 \end{cases} \quad \dots\dots\dots (14)$$

1. Where $\rho > 0$ is a constant, Ω_0 is a subset in the image domain Ω and is the boundary of $\delta\Omega_0$ is the boundary of Ω_0 .
2. Compute $c_1(\phi)$ and $c_2(\phi)$ using Eqs. (7) and (8),
3. Evolve the level set function according to Eq. (13).
4. Let $\phi = 1$ if $\phi > 0$; otherwise, $\phi = -1$;

This step has the local segmentation property. If we want to selectively segment the desired objects, this step is necessary; otherwise, it is unnecessary.

5. Regularize the level set function with a Gaussian filter, i.e. $\phi = \phi * G_\sigma$

6. Check whether the evolution of the level set function has converged. If not, return to step 2.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Implementation of this model is done on two images of high resolution satellite images. The results are compared and analyzed with the previous work done. Original images are shown in first row and the second, third rows give the results of mean shift clustering segmentation image and the proposed MS clustering with level set method.

Fig 1: Results obtained with proposed method: column (a) is the original image, (b) is the mean shift clustered segmented image and the below column (c) represents the segmented image with MS clustered based level set method

Fig 2: Results obtained with proposed method: column (a) is the original HR Satellite image, (b) is the mean shift clustered segmented image and the below column (c) represents the segmented image with MS clustered based level set method

Analysis Table:

Images	Proposed method			
	Iterations	evolution time	Parameter (mu)	Image Size
Image1	120	11.2934 sec	$\mu=55$	340x400
Image2	120	12.6974sec	$\mu=60$	375x500

V.CONCLUSION

In this paper, proposed a novel approach for Mean shift clustering with Level Set Evolution in satellite images. This image segmentation model has been successfully implemented on the high resolution satellite images and results reveal the speed, accuracy of high convergence and less number of iterations.

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A Mesochronous Pipeline Scheme Implemented for an 8x8-Bit Multiplier

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Abstract—A mesochronous pipeline scheme is described in this paper. In a conventional pipeline scheme each pipeline stage operates on only one data set at a time. In the mesochronous scheme, pipeline stages operate on multiple data sets simultaneously. The clock period in conventional pipeline scheme is proportional to the maximum pipeline stage delay while in mesochronous pipelining, it is proportional to the maximum pipeline stage delay difference, which means higher clock speeds are possible and number of pipeline stages is significantly less. In mesochronous approach the clock distribution network is simple and load on it is less resulting in significant power savings. Also, the variations in supply current drawn by clock network is significantly less in mesochronous scheme, thus power supply noise (IR drop and Ldi/dt noise) is less. An 8×8-bit multiplier using carry-save adder technique has been implemented in conventional and mesochronous pipeline approach using TSMC 180nm (drawn length 200nm). The overall power dissipation in mesochronous approach is less than 50% of the power dissipation in conventional approach. In conventional approach, the power dissipation in clock network and pipeline registers is close to 80% of total power dissipation, while in mesochronous approach logic dissipates more power.

Keywords—pipelined systems, high performance, mesochronous pipelining, multipliers, low power.

I. INTRODUCTION

Clocking is an essential component in digital system design. Switching events in a pipelined system occur in well defined order and at precise moments with reference to a globally distributed clock signal. Today's high frequency clocks have to be generated on chip and distributed throughout the chip. In any digital system, of all data and control signals, clock signal is the one with the largest fan-out, and fastest switching rate. To achieve higher operational (clock) frequencies digital designers are

using ultra-thin super-pipelines, as a result of which the load on the clock distribution is increasing and it is becoming extremely difficult to distribute a clean giga-hertz frequency clock signal [1], [2]. Increasing portion of clock period is also being spent in countering clock uncertainties like uncontrolled transmission line effects, clock skew and clock jitter [3], [4]. Thus, the useful portion of clock period available for computation is decreasing. With shrinking feature sizes, interconnects are becoming thin, long, and their resistance is increasing. With high speed signals (with fast rise and fall times) running on thin long wires, the inductive component of wire parasitic is gaining significance [5]. The increase in clock frequency, system size, and wire parasitic values are introducing power supply noise [6], [7]. In conventional pipeline schemes, huge currents drawn by the clock network and large number of pipeline registers is increasing the power consumption. The clock network's power consumption has increased to 50% of the total chip power consumption [8]. These huge currents are also causing higher IR drops in the power supply network, which is essentially a huge RLC network. Also, the large current slew rates (di/dt) coupled with on-chip inductance are generating significant amount of Ldi/dt noise on power supply. These power supply noise affect the power supply integrity and this is worsened due to decreasing supply voltage levels.

Architecture modifications can eliminate complex clock distribution to reduce power consumption, power supply noise and improve system performance. Alternate architectures like wave-pipelining, asynchronous pipelining and package wiring [8] have been proposed. While asynchronous pipelining may be appealing since it completely eliminates the need to distribute clock, it is complex compared to synchronous schemes [8], [9]. Our Mesochronous pipeline (MPP) scheme [10], [11], [12] modifies the pipeline architecture to address the power issues and also achieve higher performance.

In this paper we present the power performance gains from our MPP scheme and compare it with the conventional pipeline scheme. The organization of

this paper is as follows. In Section II, the MPP concept is discussed. In Section III, we discuss the implementation of an 8-bit multiplier in conventional and mesochronous pipeline architecture. Performance analysis of the multiplier is presented in Section IV. Finally in Section V, some concluding remarks are presented.

II. MESOCHRONOUS PIPELINE ARCHITECTURE

In a conventional pipeline (CPP) scheme, a digital system is divided into small sub-systems called pipeline stages separated by pipeline registers. The schematic of an N-stage pipelined system is shown in Fig. 1. In a pipelined system, at any given time each stage operates on only one data set. When the computation is complete in a stage, data is passed onto the next stage in the pipeline. Pipeline registers synchronize this data movement from one stage to the next with the help of globally distributed clock signal. This clock signal must trigger all the pipeline registers in the system simultaneously. New data is admitted into a stage only after data in that stage has been cleared and latched by the register following it. In a pipelined system, pipeline stage with the longest computation time dictates clock-cycle time for the entire system. The delay incurred in the registers also influences the clock period.

Fig. 1. Conventional pipeline scheme.

Equation (1) defines the clock cycle time for a CPP scheme.

$$T_{clk_cpp} \geq D_{max} + D_R + t_s + \Delta_{clk} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

where D_{max} is the computation time of stage with the longest propagation delay, D_R is the pipeline register delay, t_s is the pipeline register setup time and Δ_{clk} is clock uncertainty. From (1), it is clear that small clock periods are possible by reducing the delays: D_{max} , D_R , t_s and/or Δ_{clk} . Scaling can help decrease these delays and achieve smaller clock periods i.e. higher clock frequencies. However, in a given technology, to shrink the clock period further, the only delay which can be reduced is D_{max} . By partitioning each pipeline stage into more stages, stage delays can be reduced, in turn reducing D_{max} and T_{clk_cpp} . The result of such a partition is super-pipelines where there are more pipeline stages

and registers. Increase in the number of registers complicates the clock distribution and also significantly increases the power consumption.

The mesochronous pipeline scheme (MPP) [10], [11], [12] modifies CPP scheme to gain higher performance, simplify the clock distribution and reduce power consumption. In the MPP scheme, like in the CPP scheme, a digital system is partitioned into pipeline stages. However it is clocked such that a pipeline stage is operating on more than one data set simultaneously. At any given time, multiple data sets can be present in a stage and these data sets are separated based on physical properties of internal nodes. This eliminates the need for some pipeline registers. The number of registers that can be eliminated depends on how many simultaneous data sets can be sustained in a stage without synchronization. This concept has some similarities to the wave-pipeline scheme [13], [14]. Unlike the CPP scheme, clock signal in MPP scheme travels along with the data and it is possible that different pipeline registers are triggered at different times. The schematic of this scheme is shown in Fig. 2. Clock signal path includes delay elements (Δ_{si}) which emulate the delay experienced by data in pipeline stages. The clock period of the MPP scheme is defined by (2). A complete derivation of (2) is presented in [11], [12].

$$T_{clk_mpp} \geq d_{max(j)} - d_{min(j)} + t_s + t_h + 2\Delta_{clk} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

In (2), j is the stage with the maximum delay difference. Delay difference of a stage i is the difference between its maximum and minimum propagation delays ($d_{max(i)} - d_{min(i)}$). The delay difference of any stage, gives the amount of time the values generated at d_{min} have to be held until the computation is complete in that stage.

Fig. 2. Mesochronous pipeline scheme.

The clock period in this pipeline scheme is determined by stage with the largest delay difference and safe time required before a new data set is admitted into this stage. From (2) it is easy to see that for any stage i , $d_{max(i)} \geq T_{clk_mpp}$ is always true. This means that new data is admitted into a stage before computation on previously admitted data set is complete. Depending on the $d_{max(i)}$ value of a stage, at any given time two or more data sets can be present in a stage. From (2) it is clear that a smaller

delay difference would result in higher clock frequency. It is not difficult to show that for any system the following expression is valid. $D_{max} \geq (d_{max(j)} - d_{min(j)})$, which implies that $T_{clk_mpp} \leq T_{clk_cpp}$. Thus MPP delivers higher performance compared to conventional scheme. Also, complexity of clock distribution is greatly reduced as shown in Fig. 2 and so significant power savings are possible. This scheme also eliminates long interconnects in clock network, so the line parasitic values are lower and simpler delay models can be used for delay estimation. The number of registers required in MPP is significantly less compared to CPP, reducing the load and power dissipation of the clock network.

III. 8×8-BIT MULTIPLIER

In this section we present a multiplier simulated in CPP and MPP schemes, to illustrate how the MPP clocking technique impacts power and performance of a pipelined system. Carry-Save Adder (CSA) technique [15] is a well known technique often used to realize fast multipliers. Using this technique, in an M -bit multiplier, M layers with 1-bit Full Adders (FA) reduce M -partial products to two partial products. Until this point the data flow is from one layer of adders to the next. In the last layer of the multiplier, the two M -bit partial products have to be merged to form the final product. The adder used for the final merging involves propagation of the carry signal and this would make it the bottleneck stage. Fast adder implementations like carry-look ahead or carry-select structure can be used to reduce delay in the last layer; however these structures increase in complexity for large word lengths and produce diminishing returns. Instead of this, we added M -layers of 1-bit Half Adders (HA) to merge the final two partial products. This improves throughput, however there is increase in latency.

To achieve a fast multiplier the CSA architecture must be pipelined. In CPP scheme according to (1) minimum clock period is achieved by making each of the $2M$ layers into stages of a pipeline, separated by pipeline registers. Effectively, the CPP multiplier would have $2M$ stages with $2M+1$ pipeline registers. An 8×8 -bit pipelined multiplier implemented has 16 pipeline stages and 17 sets of inter-stage registers. The schematic of this multiplier is shown in Fig. 3. Fig. 4 shows the schematic of the same 8×8 -bit multiplier implemented in MPP scheme. The logic enveloped between any two adjacent register stages supports multiple data sets simultaneously. In this implementation there are only 3 pipeline stages and 4 register stages. The placement of the registers is based on the maximum delay difference that can be handled for a target clock frequency. This will be

elaborated in Section IV.

Fig. 3. 8×8-bit conventional pipelined multiplier.

A fast multiplier can be implemented if its basic cells have small propagation delay. The basic cells in the multiplier schematic shown in Fig. 3 are FA, HA, flip-flop, two input AND gate, two input OR gate, and buffers. The critical cells in the multiplier are the FA and HA. A differential transmission-gate implementation [12] has been used to realize the FA, HA, and all other basic cells. The registers in the multiplier have been realized using a dynamic two-phase D flip-flop [15].

In the CPP implementation of multiplier, a tree network has been used to distribute the clock signal to all the register stages of the pipeline. This is identical to the distribution shown in Fig. 1. Inverters have been used in place of buffers, and a fan-out of four has been used. The inverters in the tree network have sizes 50, 40, 25, 10 times the minimum sized inverter. Each register stage has another small tree network to deliver the clock to all the flip-flops in that stage without any vertical skew. The path taken by clock signal in MPP implementation is clear from Fig. 4. The clock travels close to the data path and includes delay elements realized using simple inverters. The periodic nature of clock signal has been used to achieve most of the delay, while small delay elements have been used to align the clock edge at the register stages [12].

IV. PERFORMANCE

Simulations have been performed on multiplier layout in TSMC 180nm (drawn length 200nm, 1.8V supply voltage) CMOS technology. A number of simulations have been performed on the full adder to precisely characterize performance of this cell. The propagation delay for the full adder varied from 210ps (d_{min}) to 280ps (d_{max}), resulting in a maximum delay variation of 70ps [10], [11]. From simulations of the D flip-flop, the clock-to-output delay is approximately 130ps, set-up time is 65ps, and hold time is 5ps. From (1), the minimum achievable clock period in conventional scheme is 475ps. A fair compare between the two schemes is

terms of power consumption is when they are operating at the same clock period. For this purpose a clock period of 500ps (2GHz)

Fig. 4. 8x8-bit mesochronous pipelined multiplier.

has been chosen. From (2) it is clear that for a clock period of 500ps, the maximum delay variation of any stage can be 400ps. The placement of registers as shown in Fig. 4 is based on this calculated limit on delay difference. The delay variation of the FA is 70ps, and maximum calculated delay variation is 400ps, and so maximum number of FA layers in a stage is five. This placement also accommodates additional variations that can occur in a stage. From Fig. 4 it can be seen that stage 2 is the critical stage as it has five FA/HA layers combined into a single stage. The logic enclosed between any two adjacent register stages supports two or more data sets simultaneously and the stage delay difference is less than 400ps.

Simulations have been performed to calculate the average current drawn by the clock network, registers, and logic in both the pipeline schemes. The current consumption in the clock network and flip-flops should be relatively constant. In logic stages, current drawn is data dependent. The average current drawn by the clock network, registers, and logic stages, is shown in Table I [16]. The current drawn by the logic stages has been calculated for a significant activity in these stages. From simulations it has been observed that the CPP scheme consumes less current (power) than MPP scheme only if operated at one-third the speed of MPP [16].

Table I. Clock Network, Registers, and Logic Current at 2GHz

Scheme	Current (mA)			Total
	Clock network	Registers	Logic	
CPP	86.9	66.6	38.2	191.7
MPP	24.2	12.8	45.3	82.3

A graphical comparison of the current results is shown in Fig. 5 [16]. In CPP scheme, the amount of current drawn by the clock network and registers is greater than in MPP implementation. This is due to the complex clock distribution and higher number of

register stages in CPP. The overall current drawn is higher in CPP scheme.

Figure 6 shows a bar-graph of current drawn by clock network, registers and logic for both the schemes. On an average, the current drawn by the logic stages in MPP scheme is higher than CPP scheme, which represents useful current drawn, as it is used for computation.

Fig. 5. Clock network, registers, and logic current at 2GHz.

Fig. 6. Percentage of total current drawn by clock network, registers, and logic.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the power performance gains from mesochronous pipeline (MPP) scheme over conventional pipeline (CPP) scheme have been presented. Following are features of the MPP scheme.

Smaller number of pipeline registers. The performance achieved in CPP scheme can be easily achieved using MPP scheme with fewer pipeline stages and registers.

Simpler clock distribution. The clock signal in the proposed scheme travels along with data, greatly reducing the complexity of clock distribution.

Low power dissipation. A MPP implementation of an 8x8-bit carry-save adder multiplier using modest TSMC180nm CMOS technology is dissipating less power compared to a CPP implementation. The average power dissipation in MPP implementation is 148.05mW, while in CPP implementation is 345.6mW.

Lower power supply noise. In MPP scheme the variation in current drawn by clock network is significantly less, which means less power supply noise.

Shorter clock period (Tclk). The clock period in MPP architecture is determined by the pipeline stage with the largest difference between its minimum and maximum propagation delay. So, smaller clock periods are possible.

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VLSI Implementation of Efficient Fixed-Point LMS Adaptive Filter with Low Adaptation Delay

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Abstract- The Least Mean Square (LMS) adaptive filter is the most popular and widely used adaptive filter, because of its simplicity and its satisfactory convergence performance. Here an efficient approach for the implementation of Delayed Least Mean Square (DLMS) adaptive filter is presented to have satisfactory convergence performance of DLMS algorithm, which reduced both adaptation delay and critical path to support high input-sampling rate. For achieving lower adaptation-delay and to have area-delay-power efficient implementation, error computation block and weight update block with Partial Product Generator is proposed to achieve a lower adaptation delay and efficient area, power. Here, the pipelining structure is proposed across the time consuming combinational blocks of the structure to reduce the critical path. From the simulation results, we find that the proposed design offers large efficient output comprising the existing output with large complexities. An efficient fixed-point implementation scheme of the proposed architecture for $N=8$ is designed. This design is synthesized and simulated on Xilinx ISE14.4 targeted to Spartan 3E.

Keywords- Adaptive filters, circuit optimization, fixed-point arithmetic, Least Mean Square (LMS) algorithms.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Least Mean Square (LMS) adaptive filter is the widely used filter because of its simplicity and performance. LMS algorithms are a class of adaptive filter used to mimic a desired filter by finding the filter coefficients that relate to producing the least mean squares of the error signal (difference between the desired and the actual signal). It is stochastic gradient method in that the filter is only adapted based on the error at the current time. The LMS algorithm is the most popular method for adapting a filter, which have made it widely adopted in many applications. Applications include adaptive channel equalization, adaptive predictive speech coding, Noise Suppression and on-line system identification. Recently, because of the progress of digital signal processors, a variety of selective coefficient update of gradient-based adaptive algorithms could be implemented in practice. The Least Mean Square adaptive filter is used here because it differs from a traditional digital filter in the following ways: A traditional digital filter has only one input signal $x(n)$

and one output signal $y(n)$. An adaptive filter requires an additional input signal $d(n)$ and returns an additional output signal $e(n)$. The filter coefficients of a traditional digital filter do not change over time. The coefficients of an adaptive filter change over time. Therefore, adaptive filters have a self-learning ability that traditional digital filters do not have. The filter is an important component in the communication world. It can eliminate unwanted signals from useful information. However, to obtain an optimal filtering performance, it requires a priori knowledge of both the signal and its embedded noise statistical information. The classical approach to this problem is to design frequency selective filters, which approximate the frequency band of the signal of interest and reject those signals outside this frequency band.

Fig 1.1 Adaptive filter system

The direct form LMS adaptive filter involves a long critical path due to an inner product computation to obtain the filter output. The critical path is required to be reduced by pipeline implementation when it exceeds the desired sample period. Since the conventional LMS algorithm does not support pipelined implementation because of its recursive behavior, it is modified to a form called Delayed LMS (DLMS) algorithm [3]-[5], which allows pipelined implementation of the filter. Since the convergence performance degrades considerably for a large adaptation delay, Visvanathan,[8] have

proposed a modified systolic architecture to reduce the adaptation delay. A transpose form LMS adaptive filter is suggested in [9], where the filter output at any instant depends on the delayed version of weights and the number of weights varies from I to N. The existing work of DLMS adaptive filter does not discuss the fixed-point implementation issues, e.g., location of radix point, choice of word length, and quantization of various stages of computation. Therefore fixed-point implementation issues are given adequate emphasis in this paper.

II. DELAYED LMS ADAPTIVE FILTER

For every input sample the LMS algorithm calculates the filter output and finds the difference between the computed output and desired response. The weights are given as:

$$W_{n+1} = W_n + \mu \cdot e_n \quad \dots\dots\dots(1a)$$

$$\text{where } e_n = d_n - y_n, y_n = W_n^T \cdot X_n \quad \dots\dots\dots(1b)$$

where

the input vector x_n , and the weight vector w_n at n th iteration are, respectively, given by

$$X_n = [x_n, x_{n-1}, \dots, x_{n-N+1}]^T$$

$$W_n = [W_n(0), W_n(1), \dots, W_n(N-1)]^T$$

Fig 2.1 Structure of the conventional DLMS adaptive filter

d_n is the desired response, y_n is the filter output, and e_n denotes the error computed during the n th iteration. μ is the step-size, and N is the number of weights used in the LMS adaptive filter. The DLMS algorithm therefore uses the delayed error e_{n-m} , i.e., the error corresponding to $(n - m)$ th iteration for updating the current weight instead of the recent most error. The weight-update equation of DLMS adaptive filter is given by

$$W_{n+1} = W_n + \mu e_{n-m} \cdot X_{n-m} \quad \dots\dots\dots(2a)$$

Fig 2.2. Structure of modified DLMS adaptive filter

Adaptation delay of conventional LMS can be decomposed into two parts: one part is the delay introduced by the pipeline stages in FIR filtering, and the other part is due to the delay involved in

pipelining the weight update process. This type of structure is shown in Fig.2.1.

The weight update equation of the modified DLMS algorithm is given by

$$W_{n+1} = W_n + \mu \cdot e_{n-1} \cdot X_{n-1} \quad (3a)$$

$$\text{where } e_{n-1} = d_{n-1} - y_{n-1} \quad (3b)$$

$$\text{and } y_n = W_n^T \cdot X_n \quad (3c)$$

We notice that, during the weight update, the error with n_1 delays is used, while the filtering unit uses the weights delayed by n_2 cycles.

III. PROPOSED ARCHITECTURE

Adaptive filter architecture consists of two main computing blocks, the error computation block and the weight update block.

A. Pipelined structure of the Error-Computation Block

The proposed structure of error-computation unit is shown in Fig 3.1. It consists of N number of 2-bit Partial Product Generators (PPG) corresponding to N multipliers and a cluster of $L/2$ binary adder trees, followed by a single shift-add tree. Each subblock is described in detail.

Fig 3.1 Proposed structure of the error-computation block

Fig 3.2 Proposed structure of PPG, AOC stands for AND/OR cell

1) Structure of PPG: The structure of PPG is shown in Fig.3.2. The structure of each PPG is shown in Fig.3.1. It consists of $L/2$ number of 2-to-3 decoders and the same number of AND/OR cells. (u_1, u_0) are 2-b inputs given to each of the 2 to 3 decoders and produces three outputs $b_0 = u_0 \cdot u_1$, $b_1 = u_0 \cdot \bar{u}_1$, and $b_2 = \bar{u}_0 \cdot u_1$, such that $b_0 = 1$ for $(u_1 u_0) = 1$, $b_1 = 1$ for $(u_1 u_0) = 2$, and $b_2 = 1$ for $(u_1 u_0) = 3$. AOC gets an

input from the decoder output b_0, b_1 and b_2 along with w , $2w$, and $3w$, where w , $2w$ and $3w$ are in 2's complement representation and sign-extended to have $(W+2)$ bits each.

2) Structure of AOC's: Each AOC consists of three AND cells and two OR cells. A single bit input b and n -bit input D is given to AND cell and consists of n AND gates. Each OR cell similarly takes a pair of n -bit input words. It has n OR gates. w , $2w$ and $3w$ are the output of an AOC. The decoder along with the AOC performs a multiplication of input operand w with a 2-b digit (u_1, u_0) such that the PPG of Fig.3.1 performs $L/2$ parallel multiplications of input word w with a 2-b digit to produce $L/2$ partial products of the product word wu .

TABLE I
 LOCATION OF PIPELINE LATCHES FOR L=8 AND N=8,16,32

N	Error-Computation-Block		Weight-Update Block
	Adder Tree	Shift-add Tree	Shift-add Tree
8	Stage-2	Stage-1 and 2	Stage-1
16	Stage-3	Stage-1 and 2	Stage-1
32	Stage-3	Stage-1 and 2	Stage-2

3) Structure of Adder Tree: To obtain product value, shift and add operations has to be performed on the partial products of each PPG separately and then all the N product values are added to compute the desired inner product. The adder size of $N-1$ additions of product values increases due to the shift-add operation which also increases word length. To avoid such increase in word size of the adders, the N partial products of the same place value are added from all the N PPGs by one adder tree.

Fig 3.3. Adder structure of the filtering unit for N=4 and L=8.

All the $L/2$ partial products of generated by each of the N PPGs are thus added by $(L/2)$ binary adder trees. The outputs of $L/2$ adder trees are added by shift-add tree according to the place values. The addition scheme for the error computation is shown in Fig 3.3. Four binary adder trees of two stages each and a two stage shift-add tree for $N=4$ and $L=8$ are required in the adder network. The dotted line shows all the possible locations of pipeline latches. If for

every addition pipeline latches are introduced, it would require $L(N-1)/2 + L/2$ latches in $\log_2 N + \log_2 L - 1$ stages, which may lead to high adaptation delay and introduce a large overhead of area and power consumption for large values of N and L . The maximum delay to the critical path is contributed by final adder in the shift-add tree. The pipelining is performed by error-computation block.

B. Pipelined structure of Weight-Update Block

The proposed structure is shown in Fig. 3.4. To update N filter weights, N multiply and accumulate operations are performed of the form $(\mu \times e) \times x_i + w_i$. The step size μ is taken as negative power of 2 to realize the multiplication with recently available error only by a shift operation. The MAC unit performs the multiplication of the shifted value of error with the delayed input samples x_i followed by the additions with the corresponding old weight values w_i . N PPGs perform all the multiplications for the MAC operations, followed by N shift-add trees. The desired updated weights to be used as inputs to the error-computation block as well as the weight-update block for the next iteration are constituted by the final outputs of MAC units.

Fig 3.4 Proposed structure of weight-update block

IV. FIXED-POINT IMPLEMENTATION, OPTIMIZATION, SIMULATION AND ANALYSIS

The fixed-point implementation and optimization of the proposed DLMS adaptive filter is discussed here.

Fig 4.1 Fixed-point representation of a binary number (X : integer word length; X f: fractional word-length)

TABLE II
 Fixed-Point Representation Of The Signals Of The Proposed Dlms
 Adaptive Filter ($M=2^{-(L_i+\log_2 n)}$)

Signal Name	Fixed-Point Representation
X	(L, L _i)
W	(W, W _i)
P	(W+2, W _i +2)
Q	(W+2+log ₂ N, W _i +2+log ₂ N)
y,d,e	(W, W _i +L _i +log ₂ N)
μe	(W, W _i)
R	(W+2, W _i +2)
S	(W,W _i)

x, w, p, q, y, d, and e can be found in the error-computation block of Fig. 2.3. μe, r, and s are defined in the weight-update block in Fig.3.3.

A. Fixed-Point Design Considerations

Fig.4.1 shows the fixed-point representation of binary number. Let (X, X_i) be a fixed-point representation of a binary number where X is the word length and X_i is the integer length. The word length and location of radix point of x_n and w_n in Fig.2.3 need to be predetermined by the hardware designer. All signals in Figs.2.3 and 4.1 can be decided as shown in Table II except (L, L_i) and (W, W_i), which are assumed to be the representations of input signals and filter weights. The output of PPG block, P_{ij} has at most three times the value of input coefficients. Thus, two more bits can be added to the word length and to the integer length of the coefficients to avoid overflow. The output of each stage in the adder tree in Fig.3.2 is one bit more than the size of input signals, so that the fixed-point representation of the output of the adder tree with log₂ N stages becomes (W+log₂N+2, W_i +log₂N+2). And the output of the shift-add tree would be of the form (W+L+log₂ N, W_i+L_i+ log₂ N), assuming that no truncation of any least significant bits (LSB) is performed in the adder tree or the shift-add tree. However, the number of bits of the output of the shift-add tree is designed to have W bits.

The most significant W bits need to be retained out of (W+L+log₂ N) bits, which results in the fixed-point representation (W,W_i +L_i+log₂ N) for y, as shown in Table II. Let the representation of the desired signal d be the same as y. The error signal e is set to have the same representation as y, since the LMS algorithm performs learning so that y has the same sign as d, without overflow after the subtraction. The multiplication with μ is equivalent to the change of location of the radix point. Since the multiplication with μ does not need any arithmetic operation, it does not introduce any truncation error.

To use a smaller step size, i.e., $n > W_i + L_i + \log_2 N$, some of the LSBs of en need to be truncated. The weight increment term s which is equivalent to $\mu e_n x_n$, is required to have fixed-point representation (W+L, W_i+L_i). W_i MSBs in the computation of the shift-add tree of the weight-update circuit are only retained and the rest of the MSBs are discarded. This is carried out when the assumption is, as the weights converge towards the optimal value, the weight increment terms become smaller, and the MSB end of error term contains more number of zeros. To have the same fixed-point representation as the weight values, (L-L_i) LSBs of weight increment terms are truncated. We also assume that no overflow occurs during the addition for the weight update. The updated weight can be computed in truncated form (W,W_i) and fed to the error computation block.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The Synthesis and Simulations are carried out for Fixed - point LMS adaptive filter. The synthesis is carried out on Xilinx 14.4. Simulation is carried out by the ISIM simulator tool. The performance of the delay block is simulated by giving various inputs to the weight update block with various weights.

TABLE III
 DEVICE UTILIZATION SUMMARY

Logic Utilization	Used	Available	Utilization
Number of Slices	585	4656	12%
Number of Slice FlipFlops	112	9312	1%
Number of 4 input LUTs	1071	9312	11%
Number of Bonded IOBs	67	232	28%
Number of GCLKs	1	24	4%

Device utilization summary is shown in above table. Usage of different logics, there utilization and available number is shown in this table. Utilization is expressed in percentages.

Fig 5.1 LMS adaptive filter flow chart

These are the steps involved in adaptive filter design

1. Input samples are given to the proposed error-computation block.
2. Result is given as input to 2 to 3 decoder.
3. 3 bit output obtained from decoder is given to AOC.
4. The partial products generated are given to adder tree block.
5. Output obtained is given to shift-add-tree of weight update block.
6. Finally desired output is obtained. Device utilization summary of the LMS adaptive filter is shown below.

Fig 5.2 Schematic of LMS filter

Fig 5.3 Schematic of Weight update block

Fig 5.4 Schematic of Error Computation block

Fig 5.5 Simulation waveforms of LMS filter with input 11010101

Fig 5.6 Simulation waveforms of Error correction block

Fig 5.7 Simulation waveforms of Adder tree block

VI. CONCLUSION

By using an Error computation block and novel PPG for efficient implementation of general multiplications and inner-product computation by common sub expression, the proposed LMS filter with low adaptation-delay architecture for fixed-point implementation of DLMS adaptive filter is achieved. From this, proposed strategy an optimized balanced pipelining across the time consuming blocks is to reduce the adaptation delay and power consumption. For a fixed-point implementation, when the adaptive filter is required to be operated at a lower sampling rate, one can use the proposed design with a clock slower than the maximum Usable frequency and a lower operating voltage to reduce the power consumption.

VII. FUTURE SCOPE

The future work involves that to reduce the adder complexity by replacing the various adders in adder blocks to achieve the better performance of area and power. The fixed-point implementation of the proposed architecture derives the expression for steady-state error.

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Channel Estimation of MIMO OFDM System

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Abstract— Wireless Communication Technology has developed many folds over the past few years. One of the techniques to enhance the data rates is called Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO) in which multiple antennas are employed both at the transmitter and the receiver. Multiple signals are transmitted from different antennas at the transmitter using the same frequency and separated in space. Various channel estimation techniques are employed in order to judge the physical effects of the medium present. In this project, we analyze and implement various estimation techniques for MIMO OFDM Systems such as Least Squares (LS), Minimum Mean Square Error (MMSE), Constant Modulus Algorithm (CMA) and linear Pre-coding. These techniques are therefore compared to effectively estimate the channel in MIMO OFDM Systems

Keyword: Multiple Signal, MIMO, Channel,

I. INTRODUCTION

The major challenges in feature wireless communication system design are increased spectral efficiency and improved link reliability. The wireless channel constitutes a hostile propagation medium, which suffers from interference from other users. Diversity provides the receiver with several replicas of the transmitted signal and is therefore a powerful means to combat fading and interference and there by improve link reliability. Common forms of diversity are time diversity (due to Doppler spread) and frequency diversity (due to delay spread). This design is motivated by the growing demand for broadband Internet access. The challenge for wireless broadband access lies in providing a com-parable quality of service (QoS) for similar cost as competing wireline technologies. The target frequency band for this system is 2–5 GHz due to favorable propagation characteristics and low radio frequency (RF) equipment cost. The broad-band channel is typically non-LOS channel and includes impairments such as time-selective fading and frequency-selective fading. This article describes the physical layer design of a fourth-generation (4G) wireless broadband system that is, motivated from technical requirements of the broadband cellular channel, and from practical requirements of hardware and RF. The key objectives of the system are to provide good coverage in a non-line-of-sight (LOS) environment (>90 percent of the users within a cell), reliable transmission (>99.9 percent reliability), high peak data rates (>1 Mb/s), and high spectrum efficiency (>4 b/s/Hz/sector).

These system requirements can be met by the combination of two powerful technologies in the physical layer design: multi-input and multi-output (MIMO) antennas and orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) modulation. Henceforth, the system is referred to as Airburst. Multiple antennas at the transmitter and receiver provide diversity in a fading environment. By employing multiple antennas, multiple spatial channels are created, and it is unlikely all the channels will fade simultaneously. In addition, the two base transceiver station (BTS) antennas are used to double the data rate for users with certain channel characteristics by transmitting independent data streams from the two antennas. This technique, known as spatial multiplexing, can significantly increase system capacity [1, 2]. At the receiver, multiple antennas are used to separate spatial multiplexing streams and for interference mitigation, which makes aggressive frequency reuse a reality.

Generally, there are three categories of MIMO techniques. The first aims to improve the power efficiency by maximizing spatial diversity. Such techniques include delay diversity, space–time block codes (STBC) and space–time trellis codes (STTC). The second class uses a layered approach to increase capacity. One popular example of such a system is V-BLAST suggested by Foschini where full spatial diversity is usually not achieved. Finally, the third type exploits the knowledge of channel at the transmitter. The IEEE802.11a LAN standard operates at raw data rates up to 54 Mbps (channel conditions permitting) with a 20-MHz channel spacing, thus yielding a bandwidth efficiency of 2.7 bps/pHz. The actual throughput is highly dependent on the medium access control (MAC) protocol. Likewise, IEEE802.16a operates in many modes depending on channel conditions with a data rate ranging from 4.20 to 22.91 Mbps in a typical bandwidth of 6 MHz, translating into a bandwidth efficiency of 0.7 to 3.82 bps/pHz. Recent developments in MIMO techniques promise a significant boost in performance for OFDM systems. OFDM has been adopted in several wireless standards such as digital audio broadcasting (DAB), digital video broadcasting (DVB-T), the IEEE 802.11a [1] local area network (LAN) standard and the IEEE 802.16a [2] metropolitan area network (MAN) standard. OFDM is also being pursued for dedicated short-range communications (DSRC) for road side to vehicle communications and as a potential

candidate for fourth-generation (4G) mobile wireless systems OFDM converts a frequency-selective channel into a parallel collection of frequency flat sub channels.

II. GENERAL MIMO SYSTEM

As a key building block of next-generation wireless communication systems, MIMOs are capable of supporting significantly higher data rates than the Universal Mobile Telecommunications System (UMTS) and the High Speed Downlink Packet Access (HSDPA) based 3G networks. As indicated by the terminology, a MIMO system employs multiple transmitter and receiver antennas for delivering parallel data streams, as illustrated in Figure 1.1. Since the information is transmitted through different paths, a MIMO system is capable of exploiting transmitter and receiver diversity, hence maintaining reliable communications. Furthermore, with the advent of multiple antennas, it becomes possible to jointly process/combine the multi-antenna signals and thus improves the system's integrity and/or throughput. Briefly, compared to Single-Input Single-Output (SISO) systems, the two most significant advantages of MIMO systems are: A significant increase of both the system's capacity and spectral efficiency. The capacity of a wireless link increases linearly with the minimum of the number of transmitter or the receiver antennas.

Fig.1. Schematic of the generic MIMO system employing M transmitter antennas and N receiver antennas.

MIMO wireless communication refers to the transmissions over wireless links formed by multiple antennas equipped at both the transmitter and receiver. The key advantages of employing multiple antennas lay in the more reliable performance obtained through *diversity* and the achievable higher data rate through *spatial multiplexing*.

1. Spatial multiplexing: It is widely recognized that the capacity of a MIMO system is much higher than a single-antenna system. For a rich scattering environment, in a MIMO system with M_t transmit antennas and M_r receive antennas, the capacity will grow proportionally with $\min(M_t, M_r)$. MIMO

systems provide more spatial freedoms or spatial multiplexing, so that different information can be transmitted simultaneously over multiple antennas, thereby boosting the system throughput.

2. Diversity: The signal transmission over broad-band wireless channels always suffers from attenuation due to the detrimental effect of multipath fading, and this can severely degrade the reception performance. In MIMO systems, the same information can be transmitted from multiple transmit antennas and received at multiple receive antennas simultaneously. Since the fading for each link between a pair of transmit and receive antennas can usually be considered to be independent, the probability that the information is detected accurately is increased.

3. Diversity-Multiplexing Trade off: Earlier research on MIMO systems has focused either on extracting the maximal diversity gain or the maximal spatial multiplexing gain of a channel. This has led to either a diversity-oriented or multiplexing-oriented design approach. First, all transmit antennas are partitioned into G groups, and data is encoded over these G blocks, each of which fades independently. Within the g th ($g = 1, \dots, G$) group, the signals to be sent are associated with a data rate R_g . Then, at the receiver group detection should be used and two approaches were proposed, namely, group zero forcing (GZF) and group successive interference cancellation (GSIC). In the first approach, a ZF decorrelator is used to separate the various groups of data and then maximum likelihood (ML) detection is applied to detect each group of data. In the GSIC approach, each group is detected using ML after canceling the interference of the already detected groups in previous stages. In a framework for constructing optimal coding/decoding schemes, which was referred to as lattice Space-Time (LAST) coding/decoding, was also proposed for achieving the optimal diversity-multiplexing trade-off.

Fig. 2. A simplified block diagram of MIMO-OFDM system, where $\mathbf{S} = [s_1, s_2, \dots, s_{N_s}]$ denotes a block of N_s data symbols.

III. MIMO-OFDM SYSTEM MODEL

Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM) is essentially a discrete implementation of multicarrier modulation, which divides the transmitted bit stream into many different sub-streams and sends them over many different sub-channels. Thus, inter symbol interference (ISI) on each sub channel is very small. For this reason, OFDM is widely used in many high data rate wireless systems. Figure 1a shows a simplified block diagram of an N -tone OFDM system. First, the incoming bits are mapped to data symbols according to some modulation scheme such as QPSK or QAM. Then the serial data stream is converted into a number of parallel blocks, and each of them has length- N . Then, each block of symbols (including pilot symbols, which are used for channel estimation or synchronization) will be forwarded to the IFFT and transformed into an OFDM signal. After that, the OFDM signal will be appended with a cyclic prefix by copying the last N_{cp} samples to the top of the current OFDM block. By choosing the length of the cyclic prefix larger than the maximum path delay of the channel, ISI can be eliminated. Afterward, the OFDM blocks will be converted to serial signals and sent out.

At the receiver, assuming a perfect timing and carrier frequency synchronization, the received signals will be first converted to parallel signals and then the cyclic prefix will be removed. MIMOs can potentially be combined with any modulation or multiple access technique, recent research suggests that the implementation of MIMO aided OFDM is more efficient, as a benefit of the straightforward matrix algebra invoked for processing the MIMO OFDM signals. The combination of MIMO and OFDM has the potential of meeting this stringent requirement since MIMO can boost the capacity and the diversity and OFDM can mitigate the detrimental effects due to multipath fading. A general MIMO-OFDM system is shown in Fig. 1b, where M_t transmit antennas, M_r receive antennas, and N -tone OFDM are used. First, the incoming bit stream is mapped into a number of data symbols via some modulation type such as QAM.

Then a block of N_s data symbols $\mathbf{S} = [s_1, s_2, \dots,$

$s_{N_s}]$ are encoded into a codeword matrix \mathbf{C} of size NT
 $\square M_r$, which will then be sent through M_t antennas in T OFDM blocks, each block consisting of N sub

channels. Specifically, $\mathbf{c}_j^1, \mathbf{c}_j^2, \dots, \mathbf{c}_j^T$ will be

transmitted from the j th transmit antenna in OFDM blocks $1, 2, \dots, T$, respectively, where \mathbf{c}_j^n denotes a vector of length- N , for all $j=1, 2, \dots, M_t$ and $n=1, 2, \dots, T$. After appending the cyclic prefix on each OFDM block, \mathbf{c}_j^n will be transmitted from the j th transmit antenna in the n th OFDM block.

IV. MIMO-OFDM DESIGN CONSTRAINTS

The key channel characteristics that influence the broadband wireless system design such as channel dispersion, K -factor, Doppler shift, cross-polarization discrimination, antenna correlation, and condition number.

1. Channel Dispersion — An important channel characteristic that influences a system performance is channel dispersion due to reflections from close in and far away objects. The dispersion is often quantified by the rms delay spread, which increases with distance, and changes with environment, antenna beam width, and antenna height typical values are in the 0.1–5 μ s range.

2. K -Factor — The fading signal magnitude follows a Rice distribution, which can be characterized by two parameters: the power P_c of constant channel components and the power P_s from scatter channel components. The ratio of these two (P_c/P_s) is called the Ricean K -factor. The worst case fading occurs when $P_c = 0$ and the distribution is regarded as Rayleigh distribution ($K = 0$). The K -factor is an important parameter in system design since it relates to the probability of a fade of certain depth. Both fixed and mobile communications systems have to be designed for the most severe fading conditions for reliable operation.

3. Doppler Shift — Spread in the frequency domain relative to a variation in the time domain is often related to movement of the transmitter or the receiver. Variation in the time domain of the received signal caused by the motion of the transmitter or receiver is called the *Doppler shift*. Based on the mobility of the transmitter, the received signal undergoes fast or slow fading. In fast fading, where the transmitter or receiver is mobile, the coherence time is smaller than the symbol period.

4. Cross-Polarization Discrimination — The cross-polarization discrimination (XPD) is defined as the ratio of the co-polarized average received power $P_{||}$ to

the cross-polarized average received power, P_{\perp} . XPD

quantifies the separation between two transmission channels that use different polarization orientations. The larger the XPD, the less energy is coupled

between the cross-polarized channels. The XPD values were found to decrease with increasing distance.

5. Antenna Correlation — Antenna correlation plays a very important role in single-input multi-output (SIMO), multi-input single-output (MISO), and MIMO systems. If the complex correlation coefficient is high (e.g., greater than 0.7), diversity and multiplexing gains can be significantly reduced (or completely diminished in the case of correlation of 1). Generally, it was found that the complex correlation coefficients are low, in the 0.1–0.5 range for properly selected base station and receiver antenna configurations.

V. MIMO-OFDM ARCHITECTURE

The combined application of multi-antenna technology and OFDM modulation (MIMO-OFDM) yields a unique physical layer capable of meeting the requirements of a second-generation non-LOS system.

1. Transmit Diversity — Many transmit diversity schemes have been proposed in the literature offering different complexity vs. performance trade-offs. We chose delay diversity for downlink transmission due to its simple implementation, good performance, and no feedback requirement. In this scheme, the signal sent from the second antenna is a delayed copy of the signal at the first antenna. The delay introduced at the transmitter results in frequency selectivity in the received channel response. With proper coding and interleaving, space-frequency diversity gain is achieved without requiring any channel knowledge at the transmitter.

2. Spatial Multiplexing — It is possible to transmit two separately encoded data streams from the two base station antennas. A high-rate signal is multiplexed into a set of lower-rate streams, each of which is encoded, modulated, and transmitted at a different antenna, while using the same time and frequency slot. Each of the three receiving antennas receives a linear combination of the two transmitted messages that have been filtered by different channel impulse responses. The receiver separates the two signals using a spatial equalizer, and demodulates, decodes, and demultiplexes them to yield the original signal.

3. Receive Diversity and Interference Cancellation — There is some natural interference suppression with MRC since it matches the spatial signature of the desired signal, not that of the interferer, which therefore gets attenuated. In this case, it is desirable to use the minimum mean square error (MMSE) algorithm that minimizes the mean square error between each desired signal and its estimate, thereby maximizing signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio

(SINR). If the interferer is friendly (e.g., a spatial multiplexing user), the interferer's spatial signature is available to be used in the MMSE weights. For unfriendly interference from neighboring cells, second-order statistics (covariance matrices) are used to capture the spatial structure of interference.

4. Soft Decoding — Both MRC and MMSE algorithms yield soft signal estimates that are input to a soft decoder. The soft decisions are weighted by the estimated SINR on a tone-by-tone basis to give more weight to good tones and less weight to bad tones. Soft-decision decoding combined with SINR weighting provides significant performance gains (3–4 dB) in frequency selective channels.

5. Channel Estimation — The purpose of channel estimation is to identify the channel between each pair of transmit and receive antennas. The training tones transmitted from each antenna are orthogonal with respect to each other so that the channel from each transmit antenna can be identified uniquely. The training tones are spaced in frequency, with spacing less than the channel's frequency coherence so that the channel can be interpolated between training tones.

6. Synchronization — Both uplink and downlink transmission are preceded by a synchronization (*sync*) slot for timing phase, timing frequency, and frequency offset estimation. The slot is structured such that data and training are transmitted over even numbered tones, and odd tones are set to zero. This introduces a repetitive pattern in the time-domain signal, which allows estimation of the above parameters. Once synchronization is obtained, fine timing estimates can be computed from the training tones.

7. Adaptive Modulation and Coding — The Airburst system maximizes system capacity by optimizing the link parameters available to each user. The QAM levels vary from 4 to 64, and the coding consists of a punctured convolutional code combined with a Reed-Solomon code. There are six combinations of QAM and coding levels, referred to as coding modes. The coding modes 1–6 correspond to data rates of 1.1–6.8 Mb/s obtained over a 2 MHz channel. For the downlink, the above rates are doubled when spatial multiplexing is used. Each coding mode has a different set point, which is defined to be the average SINR required to obtain a specified pre-ARQ packet error rate, typically in the 0.1–5 percent range.

Fig. 3. Sample BER vs. SNR for several SUI models

Figure 3 shows a BER comparison of results for a subset of channel models and transmission modes:

1. SUI-3 channel: uplink coding mode 2
2. SUI-4 channel: downlink transmit Diversity coding mode 3
3. SUI-6 channel: downlink spatial multiplexing coding mode 3

VI. CONCLUSION

In this article the results show dramatic increase in capacity, coverage, and reliability over SISO, MISO, or SIMO communication systems. It was shown that orthogonal ST-coded OFDM has a simple implementation that can provide a minimal decoding complexity, but cannot achieve multipath diversity nor high rate. On the other hand, it was shown that SF-coded OFDM with signal space diversity technique can achieve the maximum diversity and full rate over multipath fading channels, at the expense of a high decoding complexity. For block-fading channels, we have demonstrated that STF-coded OFDM can achieve full rate along with full diversity in space, time, and frequency. However and similar to SF coding, a joint detection is needed in STF-coded OFDM, and this results in high decoding complexity. As one of the promising multiple.

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Gas Leakage Detection through XBEE Technology Based On Low Power PIC Microcontroller

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Abstract—The reliable detection of a gas leakage is important to ensure safety. The main purpose of this system is to avoid accidents due to gas leakage. If gas leakage exists, sensors such as MQ-2 or MQ-3 are activated and the information is stored. The information can be used to activate buzzer to alert people. Xbee transmitter and receiver modules are used for transferring and receiving information respectively. Microcontroller (PIC16F877A) is a heart of the whole system and is connected with the other devices for the detection of gas leakage. The primary object of this project is to provide safety by detecting any malfunction or to prevent accumulation of combustible gases.

Keywords—Micro controller, Xbee module, sensors, Wireless communication, PIC16F877A

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the wireless technology has become popular and rapidly developed. These technologies are being used in smart applications in a homes, green house, healthcare centers. The system is flexible and scalable and allows additional home applications designed by multiple vendors. In general, pipeline defects can occur in the manufacture, construction and operation process. As the power supply is on, the microcontroller checks the devices, connections. Once microcontroller is active, the sensors sense the leakage of the gas and location information will be sent to display on LCD [1]. In this system the MQ-2 and MQ-3 gas sensors are used to sense the natural LPG and alcoholic gases respectively. In order to resolve the issues related to wired systems, the inexpensive wireless sensor devices [2] which are located in the territory operate autonomously on a CO. In highly risky industries like petroleum industries [3], the accidents due to leakage will occur with in few seconds. This should be avoided [4]. The different types of developed monitoring systems provide advantage to users. The systems can monitor leakage that may happen. At safe distance, the monitoring system activates the alarm after detection of the presence of gas in zigbee receiver and locates the places of leakage. Then, the gas leakage can be controlled through real time

monitoring [5]. The Gas sensor gives the analog output voltage based on the intensity of the gas. This sensor is connected in circuit board to give the analog input to PIC microcontroller (PIC16F877A). The controller has on chip 10-bit ADC. It converts the voltage from gas sensor and stores in the flash memory of the microcontroller.

A) HARDWARE

a) ZIG-BEE TECHNOLOGY

A ZigBee PAN is formed by nodes joining to a coordinator or to a previously joined Router. Once the coordinator defines the operating channel, it can allow Routers and end devices to join to it. When a node joins a network, it receives a 16-bit Network Address. Once a Router has joined the network, it can also allow other nodes to join to it. It establishes a parent/child relationship between two nodes. The node that allowed the join is the parent and the node that joined is the child. The parent/child relationship is not necessary for routing [6]. However, it is necessary for network formation and Network Address assignment. If a Coordinator does not exist, a network cannot be formed. A node cannot transmit or receive data until it has joined a PAN. ZIG-BEE is a specification for a suite of high level communication protocols using small, low-power digital radios based on IEEE 802.15.4, 2003 and 2004 standard for wireless personal area networks (WPANs)[7]. Zigbee is targeted at radio-frequency (RF) applications that require a low data rate, secure and long battery life, networking. Zigbee has a defined rate of 250 kbps best suited for periodic or intermittent data or a dual mode signal transmission from a sensor or input/output devices [8].

b) Max 232

The MAX232 device is a dual driver/receiver that includes a capacitive voltage generator to supply EIA-232 voltage levels from a single 5-V supply. Each receiver converts EIA-232 inputs to 5-V TTL/CMOS levels. These receivers have a typical threshold of 1.3 V and a typical hysteresis of 0.5 V and they accept ± 30 -V inputs. Each driver converts TTL/CMOS input levels into EIA-232 levels. The

driver, receiver, and voltage-generator functions are available as cells in the Texas Instruments LinASICE library. The MAX232 is characterized for operation from 0°C to 70°C. The MAX232I is characterized for operation from -40°C to 85°C.

c) DB9-USB-RS232 CONNECTOR

The DB9-USB-RS232 connectors can be used to upgrade an RS232 port to an active USB port without the need to redesign the PCB. These active connectors contain all the USB to RS232 (and vice-versa) conversion and are designed to fit directly into the same PCB footprint as a PC compatible RS232DB9connector. The FTDI DB9-USB-RS232 connectors come in two types DB9-USB-RS232-M and DB9-USB-RS232-F. A DB9-USB-RS232-M can be used to replace a male DB9 connector that is wired in a PC compatible RS232manner. A DB9-USB-RS232-F can be used to replace a female DB9 connector that is wired in a PC compatible RS232manner.The DB9-USB-RS232 is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: DB9-USB-RS232

The purposes of the modules is to provide a simple method of adapting legacy serial devices with RS232 interfaces to modern USB ports by replacing the DB9 connector with this miniaturized module which closely resembles a DB9 connector. This is accomplished by incorporating the industry standard FTDI FT232R USB-Serial Bridge IC plus the required level shifters inside the module.

d) GAS SENSORS

The MQ-2 and MQ-3(alcoholic) sensors can be easily connected to an alarm unit to sound an alarm or give a indication of the Combustible Gas / LPG concentration. The sensors have sensitivity combined with a quickly response time [3]. This LPG Gas Sensor can be used to make wireless Gas leak detector in home security system. The MQ-2 and MQ-3 gas sensors are shown in Figures 2(a) and 2 (b) respectively. MQ-2 is natural gas sensor that is LPG sensor and MQ-3 is alcoholic gas sensor.

Figure 2: a) MQ-2Gas sensor b) MQ-3 Gas sensor

II. WORKING PROCEDURE

Transmitter & receiver sections are used for the developed model. They have range of 100to400 meters. Zigbee is used as RF module which transmits data at 250 kbps and same module is used at receiver to receive the data sent from to microcontroller. LCD is used to display location of gas leakage. Number of utilities can be controlled by using PIC microcontroller section. The sensors will give analog output. To interface sensors with microcontroller, the external Analog to Digital Converter (ADC) IC is used.

At the transmitter section, the sensors are activated when gas leakage occurs. The sensors give the information to the microcontroller. The data is transmitted to the receiver section wirelessly using zigbee technology [7]. Then the information is received by the receiver and the information is sent to controller in the receiver section. The location of leakage of gas is displayed on LCD and buzzer is activated to alert people. The advantage of PIC microcontroller is that it contains inbuilt ADC. The PIC micro controller can be easily interfaced with sensors. The transmitter and receiver block diagrams are shown in Figures 3 and 5 respectively. The Photographs of Transmission and receiver are shown in Figures4 and 6 respectively .MPLAB integrated development environment software is used and programming is done in embedded C language. The programmes are dumped to controller.

Figure 3: Functional Block Diagram of transmitter

Figure 4: Photograph of Transmission section

A PIC16F877A microcontroller is used to transfer information to alert the people by using buzzer and location of the gas leakage is displayed on LCD.

Figure 5: Functional Block Diagram of Receiver

Figure 6: Photograph of receiver section

III. SOFTWARE DETAILS

The MPLAB IDE software brings an ease of software development previously unseen in the 8/16-bit microcontroller market. MPLAB IDE supports multiple debugging tools in a single development paradigm. It is the cost effective simulator and has low cost in-circuit de buggers and full-featured emulators. It can be upgraded to tools with increased flexibility. The MPLAB IDE is used in Micro IDE development, rf LabTM development software and also in high power IR drivers, delta sigma ADC's, and flow rate sensors. Programs are written in embedded C language and they are placed in MPLAB integrated development environment.

IV. CONCLUSION

The presented work is useful to identify the exact location of gas leakage in working atmosphere and the intimation is given through a text on LCD via Xbee. The gas leakage is detected with the help of MQ-2 and MQ-3 gas sensors. Sensor sends a signal to microcontroller. The microcontroller sends active signals to other externally connected devices. Alert is also given by activation of buzzer when gas leakage occurs. Thus system is easy to maintain and has low power consumption, low cost. The implemented hardware is used to protect environment by detection of gas leakage.

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A New BNR and SNR caluculations for MIMO-OFDM System

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Abstract— Multiple Antenna Communication has become one of the major focuses in wireless communication research. MIMO Technology is used to enhance the system capacity. The effect of Fading and Interference can be combated to increase the capacity of a link. MIMO system uses Multiple Transmit and Multiple Receive antennas which exploit the multipath propagation in rich scattering environment. The matrix channel plays a pivotal role in the throughput of a MIMO link since the modulation, data rate, power allocation and antenna weights are dependent on the channel gain. Alternative in order to reduce the complexity of MIMO system, detection techniques are proposed but the complexity of algorithmic schemes are in higher than that of equalizer based techniques such as Zero Forcing (ZF), Minimum mean square Error Methods (MMSE) and Maximal Ratio Combining (MRC). In this paper BER analysis is presented using different equalizers and then optimum equalization method is suggested.

Keywords— Minimum mean square Error Methods (MMSE), Multiple Input Multiple Output Systems (MIMO), Rayleigh Channels, Bit Error Rate (BER), Zero Forcing (ZF), Maximal Ratio Combining (MRC), Successive Interference Cancellation (SIC), Binary Phase Shift Keying (BPSK), Fast Fading, Adaptive Equalization.

I. INTRODUCTION

Wireless communications can be regarded as the most significant and important development in a modern society. Wireless communication systems need tremendously high data rates and high transmission reliability in order to meet the hastily increasing demand for multimedia applications such as high quality audio and video. Existing wireless technologies cannot efficiently support high data rates, because of these technologies are very sensitive to fading. In present day's communication, OFDM [1] is a widespread and one of the most promising modulation techniques. It is beneficial in many areas such as high spectral efficiency, robustness, low computational complexity, frequency selective fading, and ease of implementation using IFFT/FFT and equalization schemes. Recently, there have been a lot of interest to use OFDM in combination with a MIMO [2] transceiver system, named MIMO OFDM [3] [6] system; which is used to increase the diversity gain and system capacity. MIMO as the name indicates; used multiple inputs at the transmitter and

multiple outputs at the receiver end which is advantageous rather than a single transceiver (SISO- Single input Single output) systems. MIMO wireless systems are Motivated by two vital goals: high-data-rate and high performance. This combination of MIMOOFDM is a very promising feature since OFDM able to sustain of more antennas since it simplify equalization in MIMO systems. Usually in OFDM, fading is considered as a problem in wireless network but MIMO channels uses the fading to increase the capacity of the entire communication network. MIMO is a frequency-selective technique. OFDM can be used to convert such a frequency-selective channel into a set of parallel frequency-flat sub channels. MIMO-OFDM technology has been investigated as the infrastructure for the next generation wireless/ multimedia networks

II. CHANNEL DESCRIPTION

We choose three most widely used channels in our paper: AWGN, Rayleigh and Rician fading channels.

AWGN Channel: Additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) channel is a basic or commonly used channel model for analyzing modulation schemes. In this model, the AWGN channel adds a white Gaussian noise to the signal that passes through it. This implies that the channel's amplitude frequency response is flat (thus with unlimited or infinite bandwidth) and phase frequency response is linear for all frequencies so that modulated signals go through it without any amplitude loss and phase distortion. Fading does not exist for this channel. The transmitted signal gets distorted .AWGN channel is a standard channel used for analysis purpose only. The mathematical expression in receiving signal is:

$$r(t) = s(t) + n(t) \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

that passes through the AWGN channel where $s(t)$ is transmitted signal and $n(t)$ is background noise or additive white Gaussian noise

Rayleigh Channel: The effects of multipath embrace constructive and destructive interference, and phase shifting of the signal. This causes Rayleigh fading. There is no line of sight (NLOS) path means

no direct path between transmitter and receiver in Rayleigh fading channel. The received signal can be simplified to:

$$R(n) = h(n) S(n - m) + w(n) \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Where $w(n)$ is AWGN noise with zero mean and unit variance, $h(n)$ is channel impulse response i.e

$$h(n) = \alpha(n) e^{-j\theta(n)} \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

Where $\alpha(n)$ and $\theta(n)$ are attenuation and phase shift for n th path. If the coherence bandwidth of the channel is larger than signal bandwidth, the channel is called flat; otherwise it is frequency-selective fading channel. In this paper, MIMO OFDM is simulated under frequency-selective fading channel. The Rayleigh distribution is basically the magnitude of the sum of two equal independent orthogonal Gaussian random variables and the probability density function (pdf) given by:

$$p(z) = \frac{z}{\delta^2} e^{-z/\delta^2} \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

where δ^2 is the time-average power of the received signal is called a **Rayleigh random variable**.

Rician Channel: In environments where there is a dominant Line-of-Sight (LOS) path between the transmitter and the receiver, the complex Gaussian distributed fading coefficient should be modeled with a non-zero mean, giving rise to the Rician fading. Or also say that, Rayleigh fading with a strong line of sight (LOS) content is said to have a Rician distribution, or to be Rician fading. The Rician distribution is usually characterized by the Rice factor κ ,

$$\kappa = \frac{m}{2\delta^2} \dots\dots\dots(5)$$

shows the relative strength of the direct LOS path component of the fading coefficient. When $\kappa = 0$ this model reduces to Rayleigh fading.

III. SIGNAL DETECTION OF MIMO-OFDM SYSTEM

MIMO-OFDM detection methods consist of linear and nonlinear detection methods. We are using only linear detection methods in this paper. **Zero Forcing Equalizer:** This is a linear equalization algorithm used in communication systems, which inverts the frequency response of the channel at the receiver to restore the signal before the channel. ZF algorithm considers as the signal of each transmitting antenna output as the desired signal, and consider the remaining part as a disturbance, so the mutual interference between the different transmitting antennas can be completely neglected. ZF equalizers ignore the additive noise and may considerably

amplify noise for channels with spectral nulls. Mathematical expression of sub-channel in the MIMO-OFDM system is as follows:

$$R(k) = H(k) X(k) + n(k)$$

Where, $R(k)$, $X(k)$, and $n(k)$ respectively expresses output signal, the input signal and noise vector of The k sub-channels in MIMO-OFDM system. The relation between input (k) and output signal $R(k)$ as in exploits that this is a linear equalizer. A ZF detection algorithm for MIMO OFDM is the most simple and basic algorithm, and the basic idea of ZF algorithm is kept of MIMO-channel interference by multiplying received signal and the inverse matrix of channel matrix. Zero- Forcing solution of MIMO-OFDM system is as follows:

$$XZF = H^{-1}R = x + H^{-1}n \dots\dots\dots(6)$$

in which H^{-1} is the channel matrix for the generalized inverse matrix.

Minimum mean square error (MMSE) equalizer:

A MMSE estimator is a method in which it minimizes the mean square error (MSE), which is a universal measure of estimator quality. The most important characteristic of MMSE equalizer is that it does not usually eliminate ISI totally but instead of minimizes the total power of the noise and ISI components in the output. Let us assume that x be an unknown random variable and R be a known random variable, then

$$R = HX + n \dots\dots\dots(7)$$

An estimator $x(R)$ is any function of the measurement y , and its mean square error is given by

$$MSE = \{E\{X - x(R)\}^2\} \dots\dots\dots(8)$$

where the expectation is taken over both X and R . The MMSE always performs better than the ZF equalizer and is of the same complications of implementation.

IV. BIT ERROR RATE (BER)

In digital transmission, the no. of bit errors is the number of receiving bits of a signal data over a communication channel that has been changed because of noise, noise, distortion, interference or bit synchronization redundancy. The bit error rate or bit error ratio (BER) is defined as the rate at which errors occur in a transmission system during a studied time interval. BER is a unit less quantity, often expressed as a percentage or 10 to the negative power. The definition of BER can be translated into a simple formula:

$$BER = \text{number of errors} / \text{total number of bits sent} \dots\dots\dots(9)$$

Noise is the main enemy of BER performance. Quantization errors also reduce BER performance, through reconstruction of the digital waveform. The precision of the analog modulation/ demodulation process and the effects of filtering on signal and noise bandwidth also influence quantization errors.

V. SIGNAL TO NOISE RATIO (SNR)

The SNR is the ratio of the received signal power over the noise power in the frequency range of the process. SNR is inversely related to BER, that is high BER causes low SNR. High BER causes an increase in packet loss, enhance in delay and decrease throughput. SNR is an indicator usually measures the clarity of the signal in a circuit or a wired/wireless transmission channel and measure in decibel (dB). The SNR is the ratio between the wanted signal and the unwanted background noise.

$$SNR = \frac{P_{signal}}{P_{noise}} \dots\dots\dots(10)$$

SNR formula in terms of diversity:

$$BER \propto \frac{1}{SNR^d} \dots\dots\dots(11)$$

VI. PROPOSED ALGORITHM

VII. SIMULATION RESULTS

Fig 1: Performance analysis of equalization techniques in a Rayleigh channel

Fig2: Performance analysis of equalization techniques in a Rayleigh channel

VIII. CONCLUSION

The simulations were carried out at signal processing lab. Now let us consider the simulation analysis of MMSE equalizer for 2 x n antenna configurations which means keeping the transmitter antenna as two and vary the number of antennas in the receiver side. From the figure window shown in figure no. 6, it's evident that the BER decreases as the receiver antenna increases for all of the equalizers. This can be done by comparing BER of three techniques for 2 x 2 equalizers as shown in figure no. 4. Comparative Bar graph of BER for three 2 x 2 equalizer is given in figure no. 5. Eb/No BER Values for MMSE, ZF and MRC Equalizer in (2x4) MIMO system No of Receivers SimBer MMSE Theory Ber ZF TheoryBer MRC Column 1 0.0193 0.1464 0.0581

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VLSI Implementation of Adaptive LMS Equalizer with Pipelined Architecture

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Abstract: In Communication channels due to various non-idealities like Inter Symbol Interference (ISI), Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN), Non-linear effects etc the input signal suffers from different distortions. In order to neutralize the effect of these distortions introduced by the channel and to be able to recover the original signal as best as possible, we need Channel Equalizer which acts as a Compensator for the Channel distortion, time-varying and can adapt itself to the changes in channel characteristics. This paper is about the implementation of five tap adaptive filter based on least mean square (LMS) algorithm with pipelined architecture and this implementation can work with higher data rates with less clock speed requirements and so with less power consumption. It uses fixed point arithmetic blocks for filtering.

Keywords: Inter Symbol Interference, Channel Equalizer, Filtering

I. INTRODUCTION

In digital communication, multi-path distortion channel results in Intersymbol interference (ISI). ISI also brings on higher Bit Error Rate (BER). Accordingly, it is necessary to design a filter to compensate distortion of channel. So to circumvent the channel impairment caused by multi-path fading, more and more receivers resort to adaptive equalizers. An adaptive equalizer is essentially a linear adaptive filter used to model the inverse transfer function of the channel.

The algorithm is used to process a speech signal to enhance its signal to noise ratio (SNR). The adaptive algorithms are classified as Stochastic gradient algorithms and Exact least Square algorithms. Stochastic gradient algorithms include self orthogonalizing algorithms as a subclass. The conventional least mean square (LMS) algorithm (with sample update), normalized LMS algorithm and block LMS algorithm (with block update) are all stochastic gradient algorithms. Recursive Least Squares (RLS) algorithm is least squares algorithm.

RLS algorithm has better convergence speed than LMS. But the complexity for hardware implementation is very high LMS algorithm is widely adopted in hardware implementation because of its simplicity and robustness.

Based on this adaptive equalization technique has been widely studied and applied in the field of wireless communication. It is an important means of compensating the distorted channel. Using this technique, an alterable or adjustable system that improves the performance of signal processing via contacting with the outside can be designed and is adaptive. Nowadays, with the ability to operate at high switching frequencies FPGAs (Field Programmable Gate Arrays) have provided an ideal solution for implementing large amounts of high speed signal processing circuitry, allowing the designer to reduce the size and cost of a product. In this project, we describe a pipelined implementation of the LMS adaptive FIR filter.

II. LEAST MEAN SQUARE ALGORITHM

The least-mean-square (LMS) algorithm is similar to the method of Steepest-descent in that it adapts the weights by iteratively approaching the MSE minimum. The LMS algorithm was developed by Windrow and Hoff in 1959. The algorithm uses a gradient descent to estimate a time varying signal. The gradient descent method finds a minimum, if it exists, by taking steps in the direction negative of the gradient. It does so by adjusting the filter coefficients so as to minimize the error. The gradient is the del operator (partial derivative) and is applied to find the divergence of a function, which is the error with respect to the nth coefficient in this case. The LMS algorithm approaches the minimum of a function to minimize error by taking the negative gradient of the function.

A LMS algorithm can be implemented as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. LMS Implementation Using FIR Filter

The desired signal $d(n)$ is tracked by adjusting the filter coefficients $c(n)$. The input reference signal $x(n)$ is a known signal that is fed to the FIR filter. The difference between $d(n)$ and $y(n)$ is the error $e(n)$. The error $e(n)$ is then fed to the LMS algorithm to compute the filter coefficients $c(n+1)$ to iteratively minimize the error.

The following is the LMS equation to compute the FIR coefficients:

$$e(n) = d(n) - y(n) \quad c(n+1) = c(n) + \mu * e(n) * x(n)$$

The convergence time of the LMS algorithm depends on the step size μ . If μ is small, then it may take a long convergence time and this may defeat the purpose of using an LMS filter. However if μ is too large, the algorithm may never converge. The value of μ should be scientifically computed based on the effects the environment will have on $d(n)$. As with the steepest-descent algorithm, it can be shown to converge for values of μ less than the reciprocal of λ_{max} , but λ_{max} may be time-varying, and to avoid computing it another criterion can be used. This is

$$0 < \mu < \frac{2}{MS_{max}}$$

where M is the number of filter taps and S_{max} is the maximum value of the power spectral density of the tap inputs u .

Functional Implementation

The LMS reference design has the following two main functional blocks:

1. FIR Filter
2. LMS Algorithm

a. FIR Filter

The FIR filter is implemented serially using a multiplier and an adder with a feedback as shown in the high level schematic in Figure 2. The FIR result is normalized to minimize saturation.

Figure 2. FIR Implementation

The LMS algorithm iteratively updates the coefficient and feeds it to the FIR filter. The FIR filter then uses this coefficient $c(n)$ along with the input reference signal $x(n)$ to generate the output $y(n)$. The output $y(n)$ is then subtracted from the desired signal $d(n)$ to generate an error, which is used

by the LMS algorithm to compute the next set of coefficients.

b. LMS Algorithm

The LMS algorithm is implemented as shown in Figure 3. The coefficients are calculated according to equation (1). The delay is necessary in the design to separate the current coefficients from the next set of coefficients.

Figure 3. LMS Algorithm Implementation

III. IMPLEMENTATION OF ADAPTIVE LMS EQUALIZER

c. Equalization

One of the fundamental components of a Communication System is the Transmission Channel. Ideally, the transmission channel should not introduce distortions in the signal that is transmitted, but this seldom the case. Instead it introduces a distortion and its Frequency Response may be characterized as $H_c(f)$. Thus in order to reverse the effect of this distortion, we introduce an Equalizer in the Receiver section, just after the channel. For distortion less output, we require

$$H_{eq}(f) = \frac{Ke^{-j\omega t_d}}{H_c(f)}$$

Figure 4. Block Diagram of Adaptive Equalization Process

IV. FPGA-BASED FINE-GRAINED PIPELINED LMS FILTER ARCHITECTURE

Two different adaptive LMS predictor architectures based on the fine-grain pipelined DLMS algorithm were selected. The TF fine-grained pipelined DLMS (TF-FPDLMS) is designed for ease of expansion while still maintaining the system sampling rate. The direct-

form fine-grained pipelined DLMS (DF-FPDLMS) architecture is well optimized for filtering and speed/cost performance. The advantage of using the direct-form over the TF approach is that the output latency is not linearly dependent on the filter order. In this structure, the pipelining effect on a single tap PM does not carry forward to other taps.

A brief description of the components used to implement the FPDLMs filters is given below:

Reg (1-AoS): A register to store the signal value.

Mult (7-AoS): An 8x 8-b pipelined adder-tree multiplier with a 16-b output format—pipelined at partial product generator and at the first and second adders in the tree.

Adder (1-AoS): An 8-b or 16-b input adder with registered output (As a smaller value of step size μ is used for pipelined design, the internal wordlength is increased to 16-b to accommodate the small coefficient values).

μ scaling circuit (0-AoS): A 6-b arithmetic shift right (ASR) operation.

Figure 5. Complete circuit of a single tap processing element.

Truncation circuit (0-AoS): Rounding the result has the smallest truncation error, but it needs additional hardware for its implementation. Truncation is used here.

Saturation circuit (2-AoS): The system noise generated by truncation can be amplified through the recursive loop. As the coefficient $w(n)$ in the LMS algorithm equation must be 1 or less for stable operation, a saturation circuit which is shown in figure 6 is employed to prevent overflow. As the number range is between +15 and -16, a 4-input LUT (1-AoS) and a 4-input multiplexer (1-AoS) are used with the 4 most-significant bits to determine the path selection for the output. The saturation circuit was also used for fixed-point simulation in Matlab to determine the wordlength. An alternative to the saturation circuit is the incorporation of a leakage term (0-AoS) in the LMS algorithm but this brings undesirable filtering performance.

Figure 6. Saturation Circuit.

VHDL Simulation

In this project the input signal $x(n)$ and desired signal $d(n)$ have taken and five tap LMS adaptive equalizer is simulated using VHDL. The three parts of LMS algorithm is designed with the architecture shown in the Figure 12. The following equations are designed with this architecture.

$$Y(n) = W_0(n-1)X(n) + W_1(n-1)X(n-1). \quad (1)$$

$$e(n) = d(n) - Y(n). \quad (2)$$

$$W_0(n) = W_0(n-1) + \mu e(n).X(n). \quad (3)$$

$$W_1(n) = W_1(n-1) + \mu e(n).X(n-1). \quad (4)$$

In the below architecture, each tap requires two multipliers for computing filter output and updating the filter weight. And one more common multiplier for μ multiplication.

Figure 7. Structure of the FIR-LMS filter—possible pipelining paths.

First we started our design with simulating each tap in VHDL and then by cascading all taps to form a 5 tap filter as shown in the above figure where each tap consists of adder, multiplier, truncation and saturation circuit which are implemented using VHDL. Then we implemented adaptive equalizer routine which produces error depending on the output produced by the filter and the desired response. We have then integrated this equalizer with

display MSE unit to show the squared error which includes a 4x1 mux and a binary to 7segment display.

V. RESULTS

1. VHDL Simulation results for Equalizer

2. RTL Schematic of Adaptive LMS Equalizer

VI. CONCLUSION

we have described a pipelined implementation of the LMS adaptive filter. VHDL simulation of five tap adaptive equalizer is tested for LMS algorithm. The Least Mean-Square algorithm was found to be the most efficient training algorithm for FPGA based adaptive filters. The issue of whether to train in hardware or software is based on bandwidth needed and power specifications, and is dependent on the complete system being designed. The future scope is that to reduce the hardware complexity and feedback latency still more, sign-sign LMS algorithm can be used for VHDL simulation of adaptive channel equalizer which results in area and power savings.

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Retinal Blood Vessel Region Exploration by Hybrid Method Segmentation

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Abstract—Accurate segmentation and evaluation of the anatomical and pathological features of retinal vessels are critical for the diagnosis and study of many ocular diseases. These include retinopathy of prematurity (ROP). ROP is a disorder of the retinal blood vessels that is a major cause of vision loss in premature neonates. It is proposed a methodology for extracting the vascular network in the human retina using Hybrid automatic vessel segmentation method by using shortest path algorithm. In this method by preserving vessel thickness, without manual intervention, vessel branching is achieved naturally and efficiently. A single-frame image enhancement step can be optionally replaced by a multi-frame image mosaicking technique. This technique recently developed to combine several low Quality Video Indirect Ophthalmoscopes (VIO) frames into a high-quality, large field-of-view (FOV) composite [9]. As results this approach provides a superior segmentation results on both types of –raw and composite– VIO images compared to current state-of-the-art segmentation methods.

Keywords—Image processing, Image analysis, Ophthalmology, Retinopathy

I. INTRODUCTION

Segmentation of anatomical and pathological structures in ophthalmic images is crucial for the diagnosis and study of ocular diseases. However, manual segmentation is often a time-consuming and subjective process. Retinopathy of prematurity (ROP) or Terry syndrome,[1] previously known as retrolental fibroplasias (RLF), is a disease of the eye affecting prematurely-born babies generally having received intensive neonatal care, in which oxygen therapy is often used and advantageous. ROP is a disorder of the retinal blood vessels that is a major cause of vision loss in premature neonates [1]. It is thought to be caused by disorganized growth of retinal blood vessels which may result in scarring and retinal detachment. ROP can be mild and may resolve spontaneously, but it may lead to blindness in serious cases. As such, all preterm babies are at risk for ROP, and very low birth weight is an additional risk factor. Both oxygen toxicity and relative hypoxia can contribute to the development of ROP. Important features of the disease include increased diameter (dilation) as well as increased tortuosity (wiggleness) of the retinal blood vessels in the portion of the retina centered on the optic nerve (the posterior pole). Increased dilation and tortuosity of the blood vessels

in the posterior pole (called pre-plus in intermediate, and plus in severe circumstances) is an important indicator of ROP severity[2]. Plus disease: This term refers to other ocular findings indicative of vascular activity. The most widely recognized feature of plus disease is posterior pole retinal venous dilation and arteriolar tortuosity. Subjective assessment of plus and pre-plus disease leads to poor agreement between examiners [3]. Manual segmentation of retinal images is not only demanding for experts and excessively time-consuming for clinical use, but is also inherently subjective, and different annotators often yield different results [4]. To address these difficulties, different approaches for automated segmentation of retinal vessels have been tried, with varying levels of success. Segmentation methods vary depending on the imaging modality, application domain, method being automatic or semi-automatic, and other specific factors. There is no single segmentation method that can extract vasculature from every medical image modality. While some methods employ pure intensity based pattern recognition techniques such as thresholding followed by connected component analysis [1], [2], some other methods apply explicit vessel models to extract the vessel contours [3], and [5]. Depending on the image quality and the general image artifacts such as noise, some segmentation methods may Require image pre-processing prior to the segmentation algorithm [6], [7].

On the other hand, some methods apply post-processing to overcome the problems arising from over segmentation we divide vessel segmentation algorithms and techniques into six main categories: (1) Parallel Multi scale Feature Extraction and Region Growing, (2) a hybrid filtering, (3) Ridge-Based Vessel Segmentation, (4)artificial intelligence based approaches, (5)neural network based approaches, and (6) miscellaneous tube like object detection approaches. Pattern recognition techniques are further divided into seven categories: (1) multi scale approaches ,(2) skeleton based approaches, (3) region growing approaches, (4) ridge- based approaches, (5) differential geometry-based approaches, (6) matching filters approaches, and (7) mathematical morphology schemes. Model-based approaches are also further divided into four categories: (1) deformable models, (2) parametric models, (3) template matching approaches, and (4) generalized cylinders approaches. Sometimes multiple techniques are used together to solve

different segmentation problems. However, the usual method for diagnosing ROP is the indirect ophthalmoscope (IO). More recently, Video Indirect Ophthalmoscopy (VIO), in which the physician wears a head-mounted video camera during IO evaluations, has emerged as an economical and convenient method for capturing digital retinal images during ROP examinations. In contrast to Ret Cam, however, VIO data is often of low quality, fraught with reflections from the IO lens, motion blur, low resolution, and sensor noise. A previous study reported that only 24% of randomly selected video sequences can be utilized for semi-automated evaluation of retinal vessel morphology in ROP [4].

II. PROPOSED WORK

In this paper, a hybrid method is proposed that extends the path-based methodology into a region-based segmentation scheme for detecting retinal vessels. This complete approach works in two stages. The first stage pre-processes the input image to remove both lens and motion artifacts, and to construct a high-contrast vessel map as explained in flow chart. The second stage builds a forest of tree-like vessel regions through a sequence of exploration waves on the vessel map: the most vessel-like pixel s_0 in the image is used as the starting point for an exploration wave that searches for the best tree-like vessel region in the image around s_0 by means of the single-source, multi-destination version of Dijkstra's shortest path algorithm [8]. This exploration returns an entire tree region for part of the vessel system, that is, it handles branching naturally and efficiently, and preserves vessel thickness. When this exploration ends, a new exploration begins at the best remaining starting point s_1 in the unexplored part of the image, which yields a new vessel tree region. This method stops constructing new regions when the best unexplored starting point is no longer likely to be part of the vessel system. Unlike existing single-source, single-destination vessel analysis methods [1, 2, 3], our single-source, multiple-destinations approach automatically explores the complete vasculature in a retinal image, and requires no user intervention whatsoever.

Furthermore, the initial single-frame image enhancement step can be optionally replaced by a multi-frame image mosaicing technique. Recently such a technique was developed to combine several low-quality VIO frames into a high-quality, large field-of-view (FOV) composite [9]. As the results in Section 3 show, this approach obtains superior segmentation results on both types of raw and composite VIO images compared to current state-of-the-art segmentation methods.

III. METHODS

Region-based methods [5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13] classify image pixels directly into vessel and non-vessel pixels. Classification relies on local appearance, as measured by the responses of suitable filter banks at various scales and orientations. In

unsupervised region-based approaches, these filter responses are combined into a new image, which is then appropriately thresholded to yield the final classification. Methods in this category employ matched filters [5], piecewise thresholding, local entropy, and quadrature filters [12]. Supervised region-based methods, on the other hand, assemble the filter responses into feature vectors that are fed to a classifier, which is trained on hand-labeled data. Techniques used within this framework include ridge detection [10], Gabor wavelet filtering, line operators and moment invariants.

Figure 1. Flow chart showing Vessel Segmentation Algorithm

Other region-based approaches have used region growing, mathematical morphology [12], and multiconcavity modeling [11]. The goal of path-based methods [13, 14], on the other hand, is primarily to trace the centerline of individual vessels, rather than classifying every pixel in the image. Many path-based approaches also estimate vessel thickness as they track each branch, generally by determining the width of the cross-section perpendicular to the current path. Prior work on two dimensional branch extraction has addressed this topological ambiguity semi-automatically by relying on user-supplied points, requiring either a single seed point [4] or a pair of start and end-points [2]. User-supplied one-point methods generally employ ridge detection based on differential geometry [6], while two-point methods find a path between the points that minimizes a cost measure designed to penalize paths that stray from the middle of a vessel.

Several of these methods rely on front propagation algorithms, such as the fast marching method [7]. In contrast our tracking methodology forgoes the need for external seed points by being robust to a particular tracker's initial position.

IV. ALGORITHM S

Input: Graph G , source vertex s , threshold t .

Output: Dijkstra region R .

$Q = \text{initialize priority queue}();$

$\text{push}(Q, s, 0);$

while not empty(Q) **do**

$[vc, g^0, c] = \text{pop}(Q);$

if not visited(vc) **then**

set visited(G, vc);

$Vc = \text{neighbors}(G, vc);$

foreach $v \in Vc$ **do**

$h = c(g^0(s, vc)) + c(vc, v);$

if $h < t$ **then**

$\text{push}(Q, v, h);$

end

end

end

end

$R = \text{visited}(G);$

Algorithm 1. Exploratory Dijkstra vessel segmentation: starting from a single pixel, the algorithm progressively explores the rest of the image such that every unvisited pixel has a higher minimum

path cost than every visited pixel. The algorithm keeps adding pixels until a cost boundary is reached.

Input: Graph G over image domain V , inverted Laplace Gabor responses F ,

exploratory threshold t , filtering threshold y .

Output: Dijkstra forest \mathbf{R} .

$\mathbf{R} = \emptyset;$

while $s < y$ **do**

$s = \text{argmin}_V(F);$

$R = \text{exploratory dijkstra}(G, s, t);$

$\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{R} \cup R;$

$V = V \setminus \mathbf{R};$

end

Algorithm 2. Dijkstra forest vessel segmentation: The algorithm adds disjoint Dijkstra regions until the minimum inverted Laplace-Gabor response at the source pixel exceeds y . The operation $V \setminus \mathbf{R}$ represents $\{x \in V \mid x \notin \mathbf{R}\}$.

V. EXPLORATORY DIJKSTRA SEGMENTATION

Dijkstra minimum cost algorithm for any graph with non-negative arc costs [8]. More generally, it finds a minimum cost path $\gamma^*(s, v)$ between a single source vertex s and (potentially) every other vertex v in the graph. As discussed earlier, instead of simply connecting user-defined points, we employ an exploratory strategy by using the single-source, many-destinations version of Dijkstra's method. Starting from a single position s on a major vessel, this strategy enables us to segment this major vessel and all the less prominent vessels that branch out of it, without any need for setting any destination point. Instead, we set an exploration threshold τ on the cost of any path, and find all the minimum-cost paths γ^* from s in G such that $c(\gamma^*) < \tau$. Algorithm 1 outlines our exploratory Dijkstra vessel segmentation method.

The exploratory Dijkstra method outlined in efficiently segments a Dijkstra region $R_\tau(s)$ given a single source vertex s . However, the vasculature in the retina extends from more than one primary vessel. Furthermore, the low quality and blur of VIO frames can obscure large sections of the vascular network, and break up the vasculature into several disconnected regions. Therefore, in order to segment all visible vessels better, we extend the single source method to multiple sources.

To this end, first generate the initial region $R_0 = R_\tau(s_0)$ from a first source point s_0 as described above. Then select a new source vertex s_1 from those vertices in V that are not part of R_0 , and generate a new region R_1 from it, such that $R_0 \cap R_1 = \emptyset$. By repeating, we thus form a *Dijkstra forest*:

$R = \{R_0, R_1, \dots, R_K\}$, where $F(s_0) \leq \dots \leq F(s_K) \leq \psi$.

Here, ψ is a threshold on the highest allowable inverted Laplace-Gabor response. We stop adding new regions to the forest when the highest response outside R is higher than ψ . Algorithm 2 outlines the complete Dijkstra forest computation. As with τ , we determine ψ in our experiments using the training set of images in our database. In our experiments, each image requires around 10 source vertices.

VI EXPERIMENT RESULTS

a.) Input image

b.) Pre-processed image

c.) Filtered image

d.) Segmented image by using Dijkstra forest vessel Segmentation

VI. CONCLUSION

DLCF pre-processing has a sizable impact on the segmentation results of existing methods. All state-of-the-art methods performed significantly better on pre-processed frames than raw frames. In the future, we wish to expand our VEVIO database with more images from more patients. The presented experimental results highlight the challenges that VIO data present for vessel segmentation methods.

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Delay Modeling and Power Analysis for MTCMOS Using Trimode Technique

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Abstract— Multi-threshold CMOS (MTCMOS), which is also known as power/ground gating is the most commonly used leakage power suppression technique in state-of-the-art integrated circuits. Significant power and ground distribution network noise is produced when an MTCMOS circuit blocks transitions from sleep mode to active mode. Mode transition noise is the most important reliability issue in MTCMOS circuits. Sleep signal slew rate modulation is an alternative technique that is effective for suppressing the reactivation noise in MTCMOS circuits. A tri-mode MTCMOS technique is proposed in this dissertation. With the new digital tri-mode MTCMOS techniques, fast and energy efficient mode transitions are achieved with negligible reactivation noise in MTCMOS circuits.

Keywords— MTCMOS circuit technique, ground bounce noise, tri-mode MTCMOS technique.

I. INTRODUCTION

MTCMOS [1],[8]-[13],[16]-[18] logic is effective standby leakage control technique, but difficult to implement since sleep transistor sizing is highly dependent on discharge pattern within the circuit block. They showed dual Vt domino logic avoids the sizing difficulties and inherent performance associated with MTCMOS. High Vt cells are used where leakage has to be prevented whereas low Vt cells are employed where speed is of concern. Both cells are effectively used in MTCMOS technique.

Fig.1. Basic Power Gating Circuit

In active mode of operation the high Vt transistors are turned on and the logic gates consisting of low Vt transistors can operate with low switching power dissipation and smaller propagation delay. In standby mode the high Vt transistors are turned on thereby cutting off the internal low Vt circuitry. Multiple

threshold voltage techniques use both Low Vt and High Vt cells. Use lower threshold gates on critical path while higher threshold gates off the critical path. This methodology improves performance without an increase in power. Flip side of this technique is that Multi Vt cells increase fabrication complexity. It also lengthens the design time. Improper optimization of the design may utilize more Low Vt cells and hence could end up with increased power. All have discussed the design issues related with multiple supply voltages and multiple threshold voltages in the optimization of dynamic and static power. They noted several advantages of Multi Vt optimization. Multi Vt optimization is placement non disturbing transformation. Footprint and area of low Vt and high Vt cells are same as that of nominal Vt cells. This enables time critical paths to be swapped by low Vt cells easily. Frank Sill et al. have proposed a new method for assignment of devices with different Vth in a double Vth process. They developed mixed Vth gates. They showed leakage reduction of 25%. They created a library of LVT, mixed Vt, HVT and Multi Vt. They compared simulation results with a LVT version of each design. Leakage power dissipation decreased by average 65% with mixed Vth technique compared to the LVT implementation.

An integrated circuit is typically divided into multiple autonomous power/ground gating domains for effective reduction of leakage power consumption [4]-[7]. When an idle circuit is awoken, high currents flow through the sleep transistors. Significant voltage fluctuations occur on the power and ground distribution networks (power and ground bouncing noise). Mode transition noise produced by an awakening circuit block propagates to the already active circuit blocks in the neighboring domains through the shared power and ground distribution networks. Logic states of internal nodes in surrounding active circuits are disturbed due to significant noise. Increasing numbers of (finer-grain) independently power/ground-gated logic and memory domains are employed for enhanced energy efficiency in modern integrated circuits [4]. With more frequent transitions between the ACTIVE and SLEEP modes of operation to achieve more effective leakage power savings, reactivation noise has become

an important reliability concern in modern integrated circuits. Sleep signal slew rate modulation techniques and Tri-mode techniques are presented in this paper. This paper is organized as follows. Triple phase sleep signal slew rate modulation technique is described in section II. An alternate Trimode MTCMOS technique is presented in section III.

II. TRIPLE PHASE SLEEP SIGNAL SLEW RATE MODULATION

An alternative triple-phase sleep signal slew rate modulation (TPS) technique is presented in [2][3] to suppress the reactivation noise while accelerating the reactivation process in MTCMOS circuits. The concept of TPS is illustrated in Fig. 2. The sleep transistor produce negligible noise in the weak inversion region of operation (when $V_{gs} < V_{th_sleep}$). The sleep signal is preferred to rise faster from 0 V to the threshold voltage of sleep transistor in order to reduce the overall reactivation time without producing significant noise. Reactivation noise is primarily produced after the sleep transistor is turned on. The sleep signal should be therefore subsequently decelerated as the gate voltage level reaches the threshold voltage of sleep transistor. Deceleration of sleep signal suppresses the peak mode transition noise that is produced after the sleep transistor is fully activated. After the VGND voltage is reduced to a very low level close to 0 V (time point T_B as shown in Fig. 2), the mode transition noise diminishes to a negligibly low level. The rise of sleep signal should therefore be again accelerated to shorten the remaining duration of reactivation process. Due to the shorter periods of Phase_1 and Phase_3, the reactivation time and energy consumption of MTCMOS circuits are reduced with the TPS technique as compared with the single-phase sleep signal slew rate modulation technique.

Fig.2. Illustration of TPS technique

A new superior fully digital triple-phase sleep signal slew rate modulator is proposed in this paper. The circuit is shown in Fig. 3. Sleep_Global is the input signal of the new sleep signal modulator. Sleep_Global triggers the activation and deactivation procedures of an MTCMOS circuit block. Sleep_Local is produced by the signal modulator and

applied to the gate terminal of the sleep transistor that controls the ground connection of a local circuit block. $P1$, $P2$, and $P3$ are used for tuning the slew rate of Sleep_Local during reactivation events that occur in three phases.

The new triple-phase sleep signal slew rate modulator (in Fig. 3) operates as follows. In SLEEP mode, Sleep_Global is "0." $P1$, $P2$, and $P3$ are cut off. $N_{discharge}$ is turned on. Sleep_Local is maintained at ~ 0 V. The sleep transistor is cut off. EN1 is maintained at V_{DD} by Preset1 that is turned on in SLEEP mode.

Sleep_Global transitions from "0" to V_{DD} to initiate a reactivation event. PH1 transitions to low. $P1$ is turned on to start the first phase (Phase_1) of reactivation. Sleep_Local starts to rise. When Sleep_Local reaches the threshold voltage of N_{sense_L} (low- $|V_{th}|$), N_{sense_L} is turned on. EN1 is discharged through N_{reset1} and N_{sense_L} . PH1 transitions to high. $P1$ is cut off. PH2 transitions to low. $P2$ is thereby turned on to start the second phase (Phase_2) of reactivation, where the sleep signal slew rate is reduced. The VGND is discharged primarily during Phase_2. Highest switching currents are produced in this phase as the internal nodes in the awakening low- $|V_{th}|$ circuit block transition to correct logic states. The rise of Sleep_Local is intentionally decelerated by turning on $P2$ while cutting off $P1$ in Phase_2. $P2$ is designed (sized) to be significantly weaker as compared to $P1$. The peak reactivation noise produced by an awakening MTCMOS circuit is thereby mitigated.

When the VGND is discharged to a relatively low voltage level, the voltage difference between Sleep_Local and VGND becomes higher than the threshold voltage of N_{sense_H} (high- $|V_{th}|$). N_{sense_H} is turned on. EN2 (maintained at V_{DD} in SLEEP mode) is discharged. P_{charge} is activated. After the delay of "Delay_Chain" and $G5$, PH3 transitions to low. $P3$ is turned on to start the third phase (Phase_3) of reactivation where the rate of change of Sleep_Local is increased again. Weak $P2$ is maintained on to assist the significantly stronger $P3$ as Sleep_Local is raised faster toward V_{DD} in Phase_3.

During a deactivation event, Sleep_Global transitions from V_{DD} to "0." PH1, PH2, and PH3 transition to high after the delay of $G0$, $G1$, and $G5$, respectively. $P1$, $P2$, and $P3$ are cut off. Alternatively, $N_{discharge}$ is turned on after the delay of $G4$. Sleep_Local is discharged to ~ 0 V by $N_{discharge}$, thereby deactivating the MTCMOS circuit. Since $P1$, $P2$, and $P3$ are disabled before $N_{discharge}$ is turned on, no short-circuit current is produced by $P1$, $P2$, and $P3$ in this new digital sleep

signal modulator. Alternatively, with the digital sleep signal modulator that is presented in [6], $P3$ is cut off after the delay of a chain of inverters while $N_{discharge}$ is activated after the delay of only a single inverter during a deactivation event. A significant amount of energy is consumed due to the short circuit current produced by $P3$ and $N_{discharge}$.

With the sleep signal modulator that is shown in Fig. 3, an MTCMOS circuit can transition to SLEEP mode more frequently due to the reduced deactivation short-circuit currents, thereby achieving more significant savings in energy consumption as compared to the sleep signal modulator that is presented in [6].

Fig.3 . Schematic of the new fully digital triple-phase sleep signal slew rate modulator. “Sleep_Global” is the input signal coming from the on-chip power management unit. “Sleep_Local” is the sleep signal applied to the local ground-gated MTCMOS circuit block. VGND: virtual ground line of the ground-gated MTCMOS circuit. High- $|V_{th}|$ transistors and CMOS logic gates are represented with thick lines in the transistor and gate symbols, respectively

With the triple-phase sleep signal slew rate modulator that is shown in Fig. 3, the rising speed of sleep signal is adjusted by monitoring the voltage level of Sleep_Local and VGND. The transitions between the three phases of reactivation occur automatically. No additional control signals or voltage bias sources are required by the new sleep signal slew rate modulator. Furthermore, the proposed sleep signal modulator is a digital circuit with lower power consumption, smaller area, and enhanced immunity to process variations as compared to the mixed-signal sleep signal modulator circuit that is presented in [3].

Although the triple-phase sleep signal slew rate modulation idea is discussed in [3], the effectiveness of the TPS technique for suppressing mode transition noise and reducing reactivation delay is not quantitatively evaluated in [3].

A. Operation For Triple phase inverter and 8-bit adder

Fig.4. Triple Phase Circuit Diagram for Inverter

When the sleep signal generated by sleep signal modulator shown in fig 3 is applied to sleep transistor in the inverter circuit in fig.4 the inverter starts functioning. When the input applied to inverter is high the output goes to low and when the input applied is low the output goes to high as shown in Fig.7. when the inverter circuit goes to hold state then the

Fig.5 . Triple Phase Circuit Diagram for 8-bit Adder

sleep signal is disabled from the sleep transistor in order to reduce the leakage currents. In the same way for 8-bit adder also when the adder is in active mode the sleep signal generated by sleep signal modulator in fig.3. is applied to sleep transistor of adder circuit shown in fig.5 and simulation results of 8-bit adder is shown in fig.9. when the adder circuit is in hold state the signal is disabled from the sleep transistor in order to reduce the leakage currents. The layouts for inverter and 8-bit adder is shown in fig.6 and fig.8. The power consumption, PDP factor and layout area of inverter and 8-bit adder is shown in Table I.

B. Simulation results for triple phase inverter and 8-bit adder

Fig.6 . Layout For Triple Phase Inverter Circuit Diagram

Fig.7 . Power Estimation For Triple Phase Inverter

Fig.8 .Layout for Triple Phase 8-bit Adder

Fig.9 . Power Estimation For Triple Phase 8-bit Adder

TABLE I

PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS FOR TRIPLE PHASE CIRCUITS

	Triple phase	
	Inverter	8-bit adder
Power	2.181 μ w	0.311 mw
PDP factor	0.03707* 10^{-3} PJ	29.234* 10^{-3} PJ
Layout Area	540 μ m ²	7686 μ m ²

III. TRI-MODE MTCMOS TECHNIQUE

The tri-mode MTCMOS technique is reviewed in this section. An Additional intermediate PARK mode is introduced between SLEEP and ACTIVE modes to lower the mode transition noise that is produced during reactivation events. A high-|V_{th}| PMOS transistor (Parker) is connected in parallel with the sleep transistor (N1) as illustrated In Fig. 10 .

Fig.10 .Tri Mode Circuit Diagram

Both N1 and the Parker are turned off to reduce the subthreshold leakage currents of an idle circuit. The voltage of virtual ground line is maintained at $\sim V_{DD}$ during SLEEP mode. Prior to the activation of the circuit, the Parker is turned on while N1 is maintained cut-off. The circuit transitions to the intermediate PARK mode. The virtual ground line is discharged to the threshold voltage of Parker ($|V_{tp}|$). The reactivation noise is suppressed due to the lower range of voltage swings on the virtual ground line with the two-step transition from SLEEP mode to ACTIVE mode through the intermediate PARK mode as illustrated in Fig. 10. To complete the reactivation process, the sleep transistor N1 is subsequently turned on. The virtual ground line is discharged to $\sim V_{gnd}$, thereby fully activating the circuit.

C. Operation of Trimode Inverter and 8-bit adder

Fig.11 . Tri mode Inverter

Fig.12 . Tri mode 8-bit Adder

When a tri-mode MTCMOS circuit is idle, the sleep transistors (footer and parker) are cut off to

place the circuit into low-leakage SLEEP mode. The virtual ground line is raised to approximately the power supply voltage VDD during SLEEP mode. The effective supply voltage that is experienced by the MTCMOS circuit is completely crushed to approximately 0V. The subthreshold leakage currents that are produced by the low- $|V_{th}|$ circuit block are thereby suppressed in SLEEP mode.

When an activation command is issued by the on chip power management unit at the end of an idle period, the parker is turned on while the footer is maintained cut-off. Prior to the activation of the circuit, the circuit transitions to the intermediate PARK mode. The virtual ground line is discharged to the threshold voltage of parker ($|V_{tp}|$). The first wave of activation noise is produced during the transition from SLEEP mode to PARK mode. Subsequently, the circuit transitions from PARK mode to ACTIVE mode in order to complete the activation process. Footer is turned on to discharge the virtual ground line to $\sim 0V$. The second wave of activation noise is produced during this transition from PARK mode to ACTIVE mode. The effective supply voltage of low- $|V_{th}|$ circuit block is approximately equal to the power supply voltage VDD in the ACTIVE mode. The tri-mode MTCMOS circuit thereby resumes normal high performance ACTIVE mode of operation.

The activation noise is reduced by lowering the voltage swing on the virtual ground line and restricting the current surge through the sleep transistors with a two step transition from SLEEP mode to ACTIVE mode through PARK mode in a tri mode MTCMOS circuit. The activation noise can be minimized by adjusting (optimizing) the size of parker in a tri-mode MTCMOS circuit.

Fig.11 shows trimode inverter circuit. when the inverter circuit is in sleep mode the footer and parker in fig.11 are off and the virtual ground raise to Vdd. Before the circuit makes a transition to ACTIVE mode the parker will be turned on and then the parker is discharged upto to the threshold voltage V_{tp} . Thus the first wave of activation noise is produced during the transition from sleep mode to park mode. Subsequently, the circuit transitions from park mode to active mode in order to complete the reactivation event and then the remaining voltage at virtual ground is discharged upto 0V. The second wave of activation noise is produced during this transition from park mode to active mode. Fig.12 shows trimode 8-bit adder. The operation of 8-bit adder also involves two step transition that is from sleep mode to park mode and from park mode to active mode as that of in trimode inverter. The simulation results of trimode inverter and 8-bit adder is shown fig.14,15 and 17,18 respectively. The layouts for trimode inverter and 8-bit adder is shown in fig. 13 and 16. The power consumption, PDP factor and layout area of trimode inverter and 8-bit adder is shown in Table II.

D. Simulation results for trimode inverter and 8-bit adder

Fig.13 . Layout for Tri mode Inverter

Fig. 14 . Tri Mode Operation of inverter When Sleep Is OFF And Park Is ON.

Fig.15 . Tri Mode Operation of inverter When Sleep Is ON And Park Is OFF

Fig.16 .Layout for Tri mode 8 – bit Adder

Fig 17 : Tri Mode Operation for 8-bit adder when sleep is OFF and park is ON

18 : Tri Mode Operation for 8-bit adder When Sleep Is ON And Park Is OFF.

TABLE II
 PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS FOR TRI-MODE CIRCUITS

	TRI-MODE	
	INVERTER	8-BIT ADDER
POWER	0.572 μw (SleepOn) 0.483μw (Park On)	0.128 mw (SleepOn) 15.599μw (ParkOn)
PDP FACTOR	0.00629*10 ⁻³ PJ 0.00627*10 ⁻³ PJ	16.896*10 ⁻³ PJ 2.0434*10 ⁻³ PJ
LAYOUT AREA	121μm ²	7634μm ²

TABLE III

COMPARISON OF TRIPLE PHASE AND TRI-MODE MTCMOS TECHNIQUES

	Triple phase		Tri-mode	
	Inverter	8 bit Adder	Inverter	8 bit Adder
Power	2.181 μw	0.311 mw	0.572μw (SleepOn) 0.483μw (ParkOn)	0.128mw (SleepOn) 15.599 w (ParkOn)
PDP Factor	0.037*10 ⁻³ PJ	29.23*10 ⁻³ PJ	0.00629*10 ⁻³ PJ 0.00627*10 ⁻³ PJ	16.8*10 ⁻³ PJ 2.04*10 ⁻³ PJ
Layout Area	540 μm ²	7686μm ²	121 μm ²	7634μm ²

In this paper final result the power is reduced to $0.572\mu\text{w}$ when SLEEP ON and PARK OFF and $0.483\mu\text{w}$ when PARK ON and SLEEP OFF for inverter circuit and 0.128mw when SLEEP ON and PARK OFF and $15.599\mu\text{w}$ when PARK ON and SLEEP OFF for 8-bit adder circuit. The layout area is reduced to $121\mu\text{m}^2$ for inverter and $7634\mu\text{m}^2$ for 8-bit adder. The PDP factor is also reduced from triple phase to trimode technique as shown in Table III.

IV. CONCLUSION

Sleep signal slew rate modulation techniques are explored in this paper for reducing mode transition noise in MTCMOS circuits with low power and delay. A triple phase sleep signal slew rate modulation technique with a novel digital sleep signal generator is presented and tri mode technique is proposed. Comparing both the techniques triple phase and tri mode ,trimode circuit shows the less power,PDPfactor and layout area when compared to triple phase.

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Aggregation of Data in Wireless Sensor Networks using Singular Value Decomposition (SVD)

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Abstract: The Wireless Sensor Networks (WSN), consists of thousand small and inexpensive sensing devices (Sensors) with a limited energy resources, memory, computational capability, and communication [1]. In WSN, most of the limited energy will be spent during the communication process, both reception and transmissions [2]. Thus, reducing the amount of energy consumption during the transmission process can increase the WSN lifetime and overall efficiency. One of the most effective methods of the energy reduction in WSN is to reduce the amount of transmitted data between the sensor nodes and Cluster Heads (CH) as well as the transmitted data from cluster heads to the Base Station (BS) [3, 4]. These data reduction criteria can be accomplished by using data aggregation algorithms in which the data redundancy will be eliminated to reduce the amount of transmission data as well as to improve the energy consumption required for the transmission in WSN. During the data aggregation process, the collected data from the various sensor nodes and cluster heads will be combined to be processed by an efficient algorithm to reduce the possible data redundancy. The elimination of data redundancy will minimize the amount of useful data to be transmitted and reduce the overall energy consumption which improves the efficiency and increase the life time of the WSN. The process of data reduction by eliminating the possible data redundancy to obtain the useful data with the minimum volume would be more effective when the data types are images. The proposed algorithm will use Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) to extract the important features of the images needed to build the feature vectors. These feature vectors can be used to find the similar images, reduce the redundancy, and create useful images with least volume before they are transmitted to the cluster heads or from cluster heads to the base station. The proposed algorithm will apply SVD on all images that are transmitted from sensor nodes to the CH and use the feature factors which are obtained from SVD analysis to eliminate the number of similar images in each cluster group and save the energy consumption due to reduction of the transmitted images from CH to the BS. This algorithm is appropriate for

both type of heterogeneous and homogeneous WSN regardless the type of algorithm that is used for the clustering process. The results of implementation show that the number of transferring images from CH to the BS is reduced about 50 percent in the proposed algorithm. In addition, the comparison of our proposed method with the LEACH algorithm, Figure 4, clearly indicated that, this method has a better life time.

Keywords: WSN, SVD, Lifetime, Sensor, Redundancy, Energy, clustering, Image reduction

I. INTRODUCTION

Wireless Sensor Networks consist of a large number of sensor nodes, which are distributed in the environment and each of them autonomously, follow a particular purpose by the cooperation of other nodes [5, 6]. Nodes are close together, and each node can communicate with another node and share its information with others. The sensing devices in WSN can be used to collect the environmental information from the sensors and then transmit them to the cluster heads. The collected information received by each CH will be processed and transmitted to the sink or base station to control the environmental conditions, such as moisture, humidity, chemical gas leakage, or dangerous gas distribution in the coal mines [7]. To control the behavior of the wild habitants in the forest, or even monitor the enemy movements in a battle field, we need to have an unlimited energy resource for long life WSN. But due to the limitation of energy resource for each node some measures should be taken to reduce the energy consumption of each sensor node for the information collection and data transmission. There are many techniques that can be used to apply in order to reduce the energy consumption of the WSN [8-10].

Clustering architectures are the most effective in energy consumption [11]. Clustering is an efficient energy saving approach that can be used to put a group of adjacent sensor nodes under one cluster group and assign a cluster head for the group. All nodes at the same cluster will transmit their data to the cluster head and collected information will be transmitted to the base station.

Cluster head which is selected is responsible for the data aggregation from other nodes of the cluster group in the network. The collected data at each cluster head will be transmitted to the sink node or BS[12]. In each cluster most of the aggregated data from the neighboring nodes are usually repetitive, redundant and highly correlated [13]. According to the classification techniques presented in [14] all methods of energy consumption reduction in wireless sensor networks are divided into three general categories:

- Duty-Cycling
- Data-Driven
- Mobility-Based

Unlike other methods, in Data-Driven plans, the collected data by the sensors are considered and processed to obtain the energy reduction during the transmission time from the CH to the BS by one of these two methods [14]:

- Data reduction
- Energy-Efficient data acquisition

It should be considered that the purpose of all these methods is to reduce the energy consumption and consequently to increase the life time of WSN. One of the best solutions to reduce the amount of the transmitted data in WSN is the use of data aggregation techniques. Since the collected data by the sensor are highly correlated, there would be not necessary to transmit the redundant (duplicate) information to the BS [13] because the transmission of the duplicated data to BS leads to the energy lost. The problem of the data redundancy can be considered with special cares when the sensing devices are collecting images rather than other type of data.

In the proposed algorithm, the network is divided into few clusters and in each cluster the data sensed by the sensing devices will be transmitted to their cluster heads. Cluster heads aggregate or receive the data by using proposed algorithm and do not send the duplicate data.

By applying the SVD algorithm in each cluster head and creating the feature vectors to be compared to remove the redundancy, duplicated and similar images would be removed and only those images that contain vital information will be transmitted to BS.

II. SINGULAR VALUE DECOMPOSITION (SVD)

Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) is one forms of matrix analysis which leads to a low-dimensional representation of a high dimensional matrix. It can be applied to any matrices of real or complex. Let us have a real matrix P with m rows and n columns but with rank R , where $R \leq n \leq m$. Then the matrix P can be decomposed into three matrices of U , Σ , and V [15]:

$$P = U \Sigma V^T = \sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_i u_i v_i^T \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where matrix U is an $m \times m$ orthogonal matrix, V is an $n \times n$ orthogonal matrix, and Σ is an $m \times n$ rectangular matrix with non-negative real numbers on the diagonal elements, and called the transpose of V . The diagonal entries $\Sigma_{i,i}$ of Σ are known as the singular values of P as following:

$$\Sigma_{i,i} = \text{diag}(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \dots, \sigma_{r+1}, \dots, \sigma_n) \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where $\Sigma_{i,i}$ is the $n \times n$ elements of the matrix Σ and the rest of its elements are zeroes.

III. PROPOSED ALGORITHM

The Proposed algorithms can be applied for the cluster-based wireless sensor networks to remove the data redundancy and to prevent the unnecessary data transmission to prolong the lifetime of the sensor networks.

The method is designed to identify the similar images in one cluster and to remove the image redundancy before images are transmitted from CH to the BS. To achieve the objective and to obtain an efficient algorithm we have performed the data aggregation locally in CH as well as applied the SVD to the Cluster Heads for the data aggregating. By applying SVD on each cluster, it can reduce the number of the sensed images by removing the repetitive images as well as the similar images. Thus those images that are transmitted from CH to BS by using the proposed algorithm will have the vital information about the environment. It also has the best characteristic of the images located inside the cluster group and suitable for the transmission from CH to BS.

In this proposed algorithm the SVD is applied on each image inside the cluster group and the singular values of each image are stored into a vector called feature vector. The Frobenius Norm can be applied on each feature vector to obtain an efficient algorithm for the comparison. Once, the norms of the feature vectors are calculated and then compared with the Norm of other feature vectors, the redundant elements are detected and then removed, using the best norm approximation. Once the norm of Singular values of two images is the same, or very close to each other as compared with a threshold, one of the images can be removed. By using SVD we have eliminated the similar images and reduced the number images to be transmitted from CH to BS.

For applying proposed algorithm, the following assumptions are made for the WSN.

- The sensors are considered to be fixed sensors.
- The base station has infinite processing energy.
- Sensors are uniformly and randomly distributed in the environment.
- In each round, all nodes send data to the base station.
- All nodes are equipped with the cameras for monitoring a network environment.
- Data of all nodes are image type.
- The structure of the network is clustered structure
- Steps in Proposed Algorithm
- This algorithm has the following steps in each round:
- Clustering
- In this step, the nodes are divided into groups called clusters. Each cluster consists of a selected node called cluster head.

Figure 1: Flowchart of Proposed Algorithm

Clustering can be done by any methods of clustering such as, LEACH, HIT, PEGASIS, etc. after choosing cluster heads, nodes become a member of the cluster heads.

- Data collection
 In second step, data or sensed images will be transferred unprocessed from normal nodes to the cluster head. It means that images which received from the sensors will be sent to the cluster heads without any processing.
- Apply SVD in cluster head and get Singular Value of all images in the Cluster Head
- Remove the repetitive image by using the Singular Values of the images in each cluster.
 To compare images in the cluster head and to delete the duplicate and similar images we calculate the Frobenius Norm of the Singular values and find the similarity between images in one cluster. In addition, we have used mean and variance to make the feature vector more versatile and strong.
- Send selected images to BS.

Cluster head adds selected images to the sending data queue in order to send it to the base station.

a- Finding Similarities in Gray Scale Images

For gray scale images we do the following stages are to be followed:

- Applying SVD on images at cluster heads and get the Singular Values of all of them.
- Calculate the Norm of the Singular Values of the cluster.
- Calculate the mean of the norm of the Singular Values of each image.
- For choosing similar images a threshold would be considered and if the norm difference from the previous stage is less than the considered threshold, two images will be considered similar.

b- Finding Similarities Color Scale Images

For color images different comparison method will be used. The colored image consists of three components of red, green and blue. So for finding similarities in images, the below stages are to be followed.

- Obtained the Red, Green and Blue components of images.
- Applying SVD on Red, Green and Blue components of images to calculate the Singular Values of Them
- Apply the Frobenius Norm on Singular Values of each color space, Red, Green, and Blue.

IV. SIMULATION

Two scenarios are considered in Table 1. to show the performance of this proposed algorithm over the existing methods. The simulation conditions for the implementation of both methods were intended to be the same. In the first scenario no manner has been applied for ata aggregation in CHs and all images that received from clustered nodes will transfer to BS in fact, in this scenario the simulated LEACH algorithm (Low Energy Adaptive Clustering Hierarchy) that has simple algorithm for data aggregation, whereas in implementation of second scenario which means, proposed algorithm, SVD was used to eliminate the similar images and Implemented as data aggregation

For simulating the proposed algorithm and demonstrate its performance, we have used the MATLAB software. In this assumed simulation, 100 nodes in an area of 100 square meters are randomly distributed. The central node location is at the point (50, 50)

Table 1: Network Life Time for two scenarios

	Scenario 2 (Proposed Algorithm)	Scenario 1 (LEACH Algorithm)
First Round Node Dies (FND)	188	99
Last Round Node Dies (LND)	776	659

Figure 2: Distributed randomly 100 Sensor Nodes in a 100×100 meters area

The offered algorithm can be used in both heterogeneous and homogeneous sensor networks. All parameters used for the simulation are provided in Table 2.

Table 2: Parameters for Simulation

Parameter	Value
Simulation Area	100 × 100 m ²
Number of Nodes	100
Node Deployment	Randomly
Normal Node Initial	200 j
Advanced Node	400 j
threshold	10
Eelec	5×10 ⁻⁸ j
Eamp	1.3×10 ⁻¹⁵ j

Allocation of Images to Sensors in the Network According to positional coordinate of each node, to stimulate the node imaging, an image will be randomly allocated to that node in each round. To do this, the same sensing environment like Figure 3 is considered.

Figure 3 : Sensing Area for Simulation

For allocating appropriate images to the nodes which are distributed in the sensor area, we divide the sensor area to 16 virtual areas like Figure3 Each of the 16 areas will be imaged from various directions and put them in 16 separate groups which are correspondents to the areas. According to the area where a node is placed a corresponding group will be selected and an image will be randomly selected from related groups and allocated to the node.

V. ANALYSIS OF ENERGY CONSUMPTION

In table 1 the results of simulation of two defined scenarios are compared by using standard network lifetime metrics. First Node Died (FND) and Last Node Died (LND) metrics are used to measure the network lifetime. According to FND standard, the network lifetime is equal to the time or round the first node dies and gets out of the network and according to the LND standard, the network life time is equal to the rounds that the last node dies in the network [16]. As can be seen in Table 1, the proposed algorithm in comparison with LEACH algorithm which is simulated in first scenario, the network lifetime is increased about 50 percent. Due to elimination of redundant images via SVD and reduction of energy consumption subsequently, the network lifetime would be increased in proposed algorithm. In Figure 4, dying of nodes and increase trend of them in different rounds are outlined in both two scenarios

Figure 4: Dead Node in Each Round

As indicated in Figure 5, in each round on average 55 to 60 percent of images are removed and only 35 to 40 percent of images are sent.

Fig5. Comparison of Number of Transmitted Image in Each Round

VI. CONCLUSION

Due to the importance of increase lifetime and decrease energy consumption in sensor network, in this paper a method is proposed in order to aggregate data in cluster head. This method uses SVD to avoid sending similar images. Network longevity is compared to LEACH through this algorithm, and the simulation results show the use of this algorithm for aggregating data increase network lifetime about 50 percent.

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Efficient Bandwidth and Improved Throughput OFDM Based Wireless Communication Networks

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Abstract--This work considers to advance the use of radio resources in a wireless network, for two ways communications based on multiple relays by using a maximum weighted bipartite technique in OFDM depended network. The main idea is to make best use of the system by advancing the total throughput of the system. By pairing the best relay and sub carrier between the several pairs of users and improve the throughput of the system. Simulation results are done to estimate the system throughput.

Used tool: RMATLAB 2009b

Keywords--Throughput, maximum weighted bipartite matching, Two-way relaying, AF (amplify and forward).

I. INTRODUCTION

Recently many people had shown interest in resource allocation in relay under OFDM network (e.g., [1]– [7]). For instance the best possible relay and subcarrier allotment in an OFDMA relay network with several sources, several destinations are discussed in [1]. In [2] a structure is made for the relay selection by joint optimization of subcarrier allocation and power, using dual decomposition method. The whole work is done in two parts i.e. source /destination to relay and relay to destination/ source. By these methods system can overcome the problems, but the main problem still lies uncovered i.e. utilization of channel dynamically. If the pairing of subcarriers in first to the subcarrier of second phase is done carefully as the considered channel conditions, then we can get a better performance (as given in [3][4]). In [5] an OFDM system was studied for pairing subcarrier and assignment of subcarrier in the system. Here by doing joint optimizations between relay selection and power allocations, subcarrier pairing is done and at the same time subcarrier assignment is done for various relay and single user. Similarly [6] tells how two way relay and power allocation is done during the subcarrier pairing, their it uses heuristic method and water filling methods respectively.

For bidirectional OFDMA cellular network a three time slot time division transmission protocol was proposed by doing the joint optimization for

subcarrier pairing base two way communication, selection of relay and assignment of subcarrier were studied in [7]. Here an OFDM system is assumed for communication with the help of multi relay and multi pairs of users. The main focus of this paper is to get better throughput by synchronizing the subcarrier assignment & relay and to estimate the loss of packet in data during the communication between sources to destinations [1]–[7]. By considering the previous work in this field, we will come to know that there are mainly two different type challenges here which we need to come over. The initial one is assigned of subcarrier and pairing. And the second one is that at the same time selecting of the relay. The challenge of the assignment of subcarrier and pairing was done single side relay contact [3-5]. Only heuristic pairing techniques are present for bidirectional relay contacts [6-7]. As it's known that the trouble is more when there are more customers as subcarriers need to be watchful balanced for bidirectional communications at the same time it's also necessary to allocate for various customers. are more customers as subcarriers need to be watchful balanced for bidirectional communications at the same time it's also necessary to allocate for various customers. Similarly the challenges of selecting of the relay are very important work here. Every relay choices will take to special assignment of subcarrier and pairing.

In proposing work the relays and subcarrier were distributed by which throughput of system was not so good and so here relays are fixed.[8] By using a graph technique system throughput is increased. The rest of the paper is prepared as follows Section I working Section III Proposed Technique. Section IV simulation results and Section V is telling conclusion of the paper.

II. WORKING

For getting a better idea about the system lets denotes relay users and subcarriers with R, U, and S respectively. i.e. as shown in Fig. 1.

$S=\{1,2,\dots,S\}$ will be placed for subcarriers, $R=\{1,2,\dots,R\}$ will be placed for Relays and similarly $U=\{1,2,\dots,U\}$ will be placed for the users in the system.

For the simplification of understanding of running concept here whole process is divided into two periods SR (Source To Relay), RD (Relay To Destination)

Fig 1. System model (showing different users and relay along with subcarriers)

The main goal of this work is to get system total throughput by pairing the subcarriers of SR and RD period to the best relays for every user of the system. Before going into the working let's get the clear idea about the notation of the system variables. Following are the main notations which will be used in this work.

- s = subcarrier from source to relay
- s' = subcarrier from relay to destination
- r = relays
- u = users

Here it's important to remember that to avoid interference every subcarrier will be allotted to only one relay and one user pair only. At the same time every user pair or relay can be allotted more the one pair of subcarrier (depended upon the length of the signal). Let suppose in SR period user u is paired with the subcarrier s and transfer the signal/data to the relay r, then these relays will amplify the signal and forward it to subcarrier s' of the RD period. Then by the above considerations, we can get the sum rate of user's pair u over the subcarrier pair (s,s') with the help of relay r, it can begenas follows:

$$M_{u,r}^{s,s'} = \frac{1}{2} C \left(\frac{Y_{s,r}^{u,u} Y_{r,s'}^{u,u}}{1 + Y_{r,u}^{u,u} + Y_{u,r}^{u,u} + Y_{u,r}^{u,r}} \right) + \frac{1}{2} C \left(\frac{Y_{r,s'}^{u,u} Y_{s,r}^{u,u}}{1 + Y_{r,u}^{u,u} + Y_{u,r}^{u,u} + Y_{u,r}^{u,r}} \right) \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Where M = sum rate of user pair u over subcarriers pair (s,s') $Y_{i,j}^k$ = signal to noise ratio from node i to node j over subcarriers $C(x) = \log_2(1 + x)$

Lets now consider a set of binary variables $A_{u,r}^{s,s'} \in \{0,1\}$ for all u, r, s, s', where $A_{u,r}^{s,s'} = 1$ when the subcarrier s in the SR period is connected with subcarrier s' in the RD period with the help of relay r for user pair u and $A_{u,r}^{s,s'} = 0$ for elsewhere. According to the pervious considerations about the pairing of subcarrier with relay for removing the interference.

For that every subcarrier will be connected to one user pair and one relay, in the SR period and in RD period respectively. To prove that $\{A_{u,r}^{s,s'}\}$ have satisfy the below conditions:

$$\sum_{u \in U} \sum_{r \in R} \sum_{s \in S} A_{u,r}^{s,s'} \leq 1 \quad \forall s \in S \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

$$\sum_{u \in U} \sum_{r \in R} \sum_{s \in S} A_{u,r}^{s,s'} \leq 1 \quad \forall s' \in S \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

From the above two equations we can form an equation(T1):

$$C1: \max \sum_{u \in U} \sum_{r \in R} \sum_{s \in S} \sum_{s' \in S} M_{u,r}^{s,s'} A_{u,r}^{s,s'} \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

By this here modification of objective function in T1 to the weighted sum of every user rates will become easy without affecting the system model if quality in signal is considered.

Fig 2: Bipartite graphs (a) An example of matching. (b) An example of a perfect matching (c) the proposed graph approach

III PROPOSED TECHNIQUE

Here by doing an exhaustive search we can overcome the challenge C1 where optimization problem and best solved are achieved. The main challenge here is when the user, relay and subcarriers are in large number the complexity of the system will increase. So to solve that challenge, here are going with this method where it can be solved in many times in many ways. By observing the C1 it can be observed that most of the non zero elements are given to subcarrier pair (s, s') because of above equations it can be defined as for every possible subcarrier pair(s, s').

$$M(s, s') = \max \sum_{u \in U} \sum_{r \in R} M_{u,r}^{s,s'} \dots\dots\dots(5)$$

Connected users and relay which consume maximum in (v) for every subcarrier pair will be termed as u* and r* respectively. Therefore challenge C1 can be simplified as challenge C2 to see that system works without the loss of optimality: i.e.

$$C2: \max \sum_{s \in S} \sum_{s' \in S} M(s, s') A_{u,r}^{s,s'} \dots\dots\dots(6)$$

Substituting

$$\sum_{s \in S} A_{u,r}^{s,s'} \leq 1 \quad \forall s' \in S$$

$$\sum_{s' \in S} A_{u,r}^{s,s'} \leq 1 \quad \forall s \in S$$

After this here it will be illustrated that simplified C2 is similar to maximum weighted bipartite matching problem . A bipartite graph is a technique where total vertices are divided into two disjoint parts

so that each point of one part connects to the one of the part of the second disjoint part. From Fig 2 it can be observed that, if both parts of the graph have same cardinality the graph is said to be balanced. Fig 2(a) how matching is done between two sets Fig 2(b) a perfect matching is that each node of set is matched to the node of another set. Fig 2(c) a balanced bipartite graph is constructed $B = (V_{SR} * V_{RD}, \epsilon, w)$ where V_{SR} and V_{RD} will be having a group of subcarriers S in the SR period and RD period respectively. ϵ is collection edge which connects the possible pairs of vertices in the two sets of vertices. As we know that S will be shared in each period, therefore $|V_{SR}| = |S| = S$ and $|V_{RD}| = S_2$, where $| \cdot |$ is used for the cardinality of two sets. And is weighting function of every edge allocated a weight in the system, represents the maximum.

$$W(s,s') = M(s,s') \dots \dots \dots (7)$$

From equation (5) To find the weighting of the system we need to work across all the edges of the two vertices. Therefore the total complexity is $T(U R S_2)$ which is done in polynomial times.

Steps for construction of working system:

- 1) Firstly a pair is matched from the two set of vertices of SR and RD period.
- 2) Then for each pair separate subcarrier is assigned for both SR and RD period (from eq (2) and (3)).
- 3) Then the weighted process is done for every edge in the two vertices to find a best user pair and relay for every subcarrier pair.
- 4) After that for finding a perfect matching is equivalent to system throughput maximization joint optimization challenge of the assignment of subcarrier and pairing and the same time

selecting of the relay. $\mathcal{F}^* \subseteq \mathcal{E}$ in B in order that

the sum weight of \mathcal{F}^* is maximum (MWBM

should be perfect matching not vice versa). this is showing the challenge3(C3) which is called as MWBM challenge:

$$C3: \max_{\mathcal{F} \subseteq \mathcal{E}} \sum_{(s,s') \in \mathcal{F}} W(s,s') \dots \dots \dots (8)$$

The main concept of using proposed algorithm is that it will connect original challenge C1 to the simplified challenge C2 and then to the MWBM challenge C3 without any loss in the optimality. After the mapping is done, here Hungarian algorithm is used for solving the challenge C3 optimally with complex calculation of $T(S_3)$. By combining the complexity which is given above to the total complexity of proposed algorithm will be

$$T(KMM2 + M3) \dots \dots \dots (9)$$

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

Here two dimensional planes is considered which is having node locations in it Fig 3. Where the source and relay nodes are uniformly distributed in the considered region. Where path loss exponent is set to 4 and the standard deviation is normal shadowing is set to 5.8db. By multi path Rayleigh fading process, small scale fading is modeled. Where the power delay profile is exponentially decaying with maximum

delay spread of $5 \mu s$ and maximum Doppler spread of 5Hz.

Fig 3: Two dimensional planes

A test for 2000 channel was generated, every channel related to different node locations. Where subcarrier $S=32$, each source has same power

constraints, so that all relays satisfy $P_r = P_u1 + 3dB =$

$P_u2 + 3dB$ (per subcarrier) for each relay r and user u .

For a standard performance the fixed subcarrier pairing is considered and pervious work [1, 2, and 3]. Now the signal is transmitted by user pair to subcarrier in the SR period is forwarded on the same

subcarrier by a relay in RD period, i.e. $\pi(s) = s$,

besides searching for optimal subcarrier pairing. Because of this problem gets reduced to selecting the best user pair and relay for every subcarrier to maximize the throughput, which can be solved in many ways by using a greedy algorithm. Specifically, every subcarrier s will be assigned to user and relay

which satisfy the $(u^*, r^*) = \arg \max_{u \in U, r \in R}$

therefore the complexity of the fixed subcarrier pairing is $O(U R S)$. Since eq (10) tells the complexity of the graph based method is $O(URS^2+S^3)$ which is better than the standard method.

Fig 4: performance comparison between the fixed and proposed method

In the fig 4, where user $U=5$ and relay $R=4$ are present in the network. After simulation, it is observed that the system throughput is increased by 8-10% compare to the proposed /pervious work i.e. (fixed subcarrier pairing is showing 8-10% improvement compare to the proposed works).

In Fig5, throughput performance is shown with respect to number of relay where $u=5$ and $P_k1=10\text{dB}$ are present. It is known that having multi relays in the system can provide relay selection diversity. Yet the gain caused by the increasing the numbers of relay is withdrawn when the R is very large because of its scaling capacity $0.5\log \log R$.

Fig 5: effect of number of relays, where $S=32$, $U=5$ and $P_k1=10\text{dB}$.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, bipartite matching approach, AF are used to solve the problems of throughput, utilization of the channel. By considering new techniques in future we can still improve the above mentioned parameter in a much more effective manner.

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Analytical study on scheduling algorithms for real time static system

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Abstract—Scheduling algorithms are a backbone of any operating system. This paper analyzes and concludes the types of different scheduling algorithms used in real time. As you all know that scheduling algorithms are basically divided into two main streams: first approach is the uni-processor and another one is multiprocessor. This paper describes the uni-processor system which are based on static rate monotonic (SRM) and static deadline monotonic (SDM). Here in this paper you studied and analyzed different SRM and SDM algorithms to conclude that which algorithm or which policy is best for real time scheduling. This paper is also defined that which static algorithm take less time for the completion of different tasks whether it is SRM or SDM. This paper also has given a short detail about the dynamic approach of scheduling. Under this paper you should also get explanation of Earlier deadline first(EDF) and Least laxity first(LLF) in brief.

Keywords—Static Rate Monotonic(SRM), Static Deadline monotonic(SDM), Real Time Operating system(RTOS), Earlier deadline first(EDF),Least laxity first(LLF) ;

I. INTRODUCTION

The scheduling of real-time tasks is very different from general scheduling. Ordinary scheduling algorithms attempt to ensure fairness among tasks, minimum progress for any individual task, and prevention of starvation and deadlock. Within computer science real-time systems are an important while often less known branch. You use Real-time systems in so many ways today more than PCs in our real life, still you are not so familiar about it when you use the devices in which they reside. Some of the devices in which real time system resides are cars, planes and entertainment system which govern the working of those devices which you do not consider that such system exist within the chosen device. Basically you can say that a real-time-system is a computer based system in which the major aspect of the system is to perform tasks on time, not finishing too early nor too late. A classic example is that of the opening of para suit; it is of great importance that the para suit must be pulled in time not too soon not too late in order to land safely while skydiving. One more example is of the air-bag in a car; it is of great importance that the bag inflates neither too soon nor too late in order to be of aid and not be potentially harmful.

In this paper you survey several algorithms developed over the last few years that are designed to schedule real-time tasks in distributed systems. The choice of algorithm can influence the behavior of a real-time system and for this reason there are many available algorithms. For the different categories of real-time systems there are specialized algorithms developed. With the help of this paper you will attempt to provide an overview of many of the different available real-time algorithms.[1]

Before examining the actual algorithms, it is helpful to establish the exact meanings of the terms real-time task and distributed system. This paper provides a basic definition of what a real-time task is and identifies the different dimensions along which this definition may vary. Other overviews of real-time scheduling algorithms have been presented by Burns[1], Burns and Audsley[2] and by Mohammadi and Akl[3]. Those are somewhat more in depth on some topics than this overview.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: - In section 2 basic concepts of real-time system and scheduling are explained. Section 3 deals with the different scheduling algorithms being the main section of this paper. Here in this paper you will come to know about Uni-processor algorithm under which static and dynamic scheduling algorithms are covered. The final section, 4, covers summary and conclusions.

II. REAL TIME SYSTEM

Real-time applications usually are executed on top of a Real-time Operating System (RTOS). Scheduling algorithms are the rule set that defines that how you manage the real-time system in the scheduler, that is, how processor-time is allotted to the task present in any queue. The choice of algorithm depends on whether your system base is uni-processor, multiprocessor or distributed.

A *uni-processor* system executes only one process at a time and is capable of switching between processes, due to this reason context switching add some more time to the overall execution time when you preempt the process.

Multiprocessing is the use of two or more central processing units (CPUs) within a single computer system. A *multiprocessor* system will range from multi-core, essentially several uni-processors in one processor, to several separate uni-processors controlling the same system.

A *distributed* system will range from a geographically dispersed system to several processors on the same board. In a distributed system the nodes are autonomous while in a

In *real-time systems* processes are referred to as tasks and these have certain temporal qualities and restrictions. First of all a real-time task is a task like any other. However, there is essential difference to other computation: the notion of time maintaining the Integrity of the Specifications.

Each of the tasks will have a deadline, an execution time and a release time. In addition there are other temporal attributes that may be assigned to a task. The three mentioned are the basic ones. The *release time*, or *ready time* is when the task is made ready for execution. The *deadline* is when a given task must be done executing and the *execution time* is how long time it takes to run the given task. In addition most tasks are recurring and have a period in which it executes. Such a task is referred to as *periodic*. The period is the time from when a task may start until when the next instance of the same task may start and the length of the period of a task is static.

An example, shown in Figure 1, of scheduling can be made using three tasks T1, T2 and T3 with execution time and deadline of (1, 3), (4, 9) and (2, 9) respectively and periods equal to their deadlines. These tasks can be scheduled so that all tasks get to execute before the deadlines.

Figure 1: Scheduling of T1, T2 and T3.

The example is very simple as it does not show priorities or use preemption. There are also other properties of interest when looking at scheduling. Properties a task may use briefly explained:

- *Release/ready time*: The time a task is ready to run and just waits for the scheduler to activate it.
- *Deadline*: The time when a task must be finished executing.

- *Execution/run time*: The active computation time a tasks need to complete.
- *Worst Case Execution Time (WCET)*: The longest possible execution time for a task on a particular type of system.
- *Response time*: The time it takes a task to finish execution. Measured from release time to execution completes, including preemptions.
- *Priority/weight*: The importance given a task in context of the schedule at hand.

III. SCHEDULING ALGORITHMS

A. STATIC SCHEDULING

Scheduling algorithms themselves can be categorized as being static or dynamic[4]. The static scheduling algorithms are those algorithms which come under uni-processors. The tasks present here have enough execution time and are ensured to fulfill the condition of deadline if possible. It calculates (or pre-determines) schedules for the system. Static approach requires prior knowledge of the process characteristics in order to process it in particular time. Certainly in safety critical systems it is reasonable to argue that no event should be unpredicted and that schedulability should be guaranteed before execution. This implies the use of a static scheduling algorithm. When all the scheduling decisions are made prior to the running of the system then it is static and offline. A table is generated which carry the scheduling decisions which are to be used during run-time.

Rate monotonic (RM) is a scheduling algorithm [5,6] used in real time operating systems with static priority preemptive scheme. It is static-priority in the sense that all priorities are determined for all instances of tasks before run time. The length of the period of respective tasks determines the priority of a task. Tasks with short period times are assigned higher priority. Periodic tasks are scheduled using RM. The following are preconditions for the rate monotonic algorithm formalized by Liu and Layland[8].

1. Periodic tasks have constant known execution times and are ready for execution at the beginning of each period(T).
2. Deadlines(D) for tasks are at the end of each period:

$$(D = T)$$

3. The tasks are independent, that is, there is no precedence between tasks and they do not block each other.

4. Scheduling overhead due to context switches and swapping etc. are assumed to be zero.

The *rate monotonic* priority assignment is *optimal* meaning that if any *static priority* scheduling algorithm can meet all the deadlines, then the *rate monotonic* algorithm can too. The Utilization For the given process is obtained by the given formula which was proposed by Liu&Layland(1973)[8] which is as:

$$U = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{C_i}{T_i} \leq n(2^{\frac{1}{n}} - 1) \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Where C_i =Computation Time, T_i =Release Time Period, N =No. of processes to be Scheduled. An Example for rate monotonic is explained as follows:

TABLE 1: Process Timing

Process	Execution Time	Period
P1	3	7
P2	4	9
P3	6	10

The table contains three processes P1, P2, P3 whose execution time and period are mentioned in their respective columns. With the help of given data utilization time for the rate monotonic scheduling is obtained.

The utilization for the given processes present in table 2 will be solved by the given formula:

The Utilization will be: $3/7 + 4/9 + 6/10 = 0.6492$.
 With the help of this utilization time we conclude the feasibility of the algorithm.

Figure 2: Scheduling example of Rate-Monotonic.

See Figure 2: One more example for RM is shown above which shows the two different tasks T1 and T2 with their execution times and periods (1,4) & (2,6). T1 with a shorter period & therefore higher priority runs before T2. They then run as they are release.

Deadline Monotonic[7] is a scheduling algorithm is an algorithm that uses fixed priority preemptive scheduling. The tasks in this algorithms assigned according to the deadline of the given processes are

assigned according to the given deadline. The task having the shortest deadline is assigned with the highest priority. Each task is assigned a priority inversely proportional to its relative Deadline. Deadline monotonic priority assignment is **not** optimal for fixed priority non-preemptive scheduling.

An Example that shows the feasibility for deadline can be shown by the example below:

Figure 3: Scheduling example for deadline monotonic.

Can we derive utilization based tests with the Given Formula:

$$U = \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{C_i}{D_i} \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Here D_i =Deadline of the task, C_i =Computation Time, N =no. of process to schedule.

B. DYNAMIC SCHEDULING:

Dynamic Scheduling algorithms are those algorithms in which the priorities to the processes are given to them at the time of execution of the task. The main moto behind this is to adapt to dynamically changing progress of processes and form an optimal configuration for tasks in a self-sustained manner.

Earlier Deadline First(EDF)[5,10] is a dynamic priority driven scheduling algorithm in which the priorities of tasks is based on the given deadline uses the simple system model given earlier. Like the RM algorithm, a preemptive priority-based scheduling scheme is assumed. The algorithm used for scheduling is: the process with the (current) closest deadline is assigned the highest priority in the system and therefore executes. The schedule ability constant is given by:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{C_i}{P_i} \leq 1 \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

For example let us Consider 3 periodic processes scheduled on a preemptive uni-processor. The execution times and periods are as shown in the following table:

TABLE 2: Process Timing.

Process	Execution Time	Period
P1	1	8
P2	2	5
P3	4	10

This table illustrate about the no. of processes in a dynamic scheduling. The table has 3 processes namely P1,P2 and P3 whose execution time and period are given. The earliest deadline utilization time is obtained through the above table.

Least laxity first (LLF)[9] a process is defined as the deadline minus remaining computation time. With the least laxity approach the schedulability constraint is again given by equation above (figure 3). It assigns priority based on the laxity. The smaller the laxity value of a task is, the sooner it needs to be executed. Its most common use is in embedded system. When two or more tasks have same or approximate laxity values, LLF scheduling algorithm leads to frequent switches among tasks, causes extra overhead in a system, and therefore, restricts its application.

This scheduling algorithm first selects those processes that have the smallest "slack time". Slack time is defined as the temporal difference between the deadline, the ready time and the run time.

More formally, the *slack time* for a process is defined as:

$$(d-t)-c'$$

where d is the process deadline, t is the real time since the cycle start, and c' is the remaining computation time. Multiprocessor systems are the future as we see it now, but finding algorithms that takes full advantage of these systems is an arduous task in which much effort has been and is being made by researchers. Future work could be to focus on these new algorithms being produced as well as dynamic based server algorithms.

IV CONCLUSION

This paper studied and analyzed the various algorithms based on static scheduling and discusses that rate monotonic and deadline monotonic scheduling are two algorithms which are used for real time task system which are periodic. This paper discuss the feasibility decision for the given real time tasks when the system is scheduled using rate monotonic and deadline monotonic scheduling. The

complexity of both the algorithms depends on the number of tasks and the maximum periods given or on the deadlines of the given processes. The time complexity for the particular algorithm depends on the number of task. This paper come to a conclusion that the rate monotonic is more feasible as compared to the deadline monotonic algorithm as the priorities for rate monotonic are based on the process timing and for the deadline monotonic it is based on the deadline of each process which is preempted if higher priority task comes in between.

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Congestion Aware and Control routing in Mobile Ad-hoc Networks: Current State of the Art

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Abstract—With the increase of multimedia traffic over the past few years and traffic differentiation introduced by IEEE 802.11e, nodes with packet loss, delay-sensitive multimedia traffic tend to be busy for long periods, thus exacerbating the congestion problem in mobile ad hoc networks (MANETs). In this paper, we first expose that the performance of MANETs routing protocols is highly dependent on the type of traffic generated or routed by intermediate nodes and also recent inventions and updates in congestion aware and control routing in mobile ad hoc networks.

Keywords— Mobile ad hoc network, congestion, QoS

I. INTRODUCTION

With the fast moving and increasing population the developments in the communications has also increased, and this demanded for the mobility in communications led to mobile Ad Hoc Networks [MANETS] and I would like to present their implementation with the routing protocols along with the new methods for saving power consumption, cost and also increasing the efficiency of transmission. MANETS is rather a group of nodes which form a wireless network where transmission of data takes place between 2 nodes. In these two, one sends the message where as the other receives MANETS are infrastructure free and they create their own connected network of nodes at that particular instant of time. So, these are self adaptive and self organized networks particularly for WLANS and WLLS etc. Factors like transmitted power, receiver sensitivity and propagation loss the effect the transmission range where as this is handled dynamically by constructing a network which forwards the packets of data through multihop paths where nodes and routers are free to move randomly.

Apart from these advantages there are some hurdles which are needed to be focused on like:

Restricted Bandwidth: The network capacity is relatively less than the total application demand when compared with that of the wired communications.

Lapse in physical security: Here, transfer of data takes place blindly by mutual trust relationship between nodes. So, wireless network provides fast and free access to many applications like distributed mobile computing to disaster recovery, law reinforcement and military communications.

Non-period link capacity: This effect is observed during high bit transmission rate and there is also high error rate in WLAN compared to Wired.

Fixed energy resources: MANETS get their power from time limited batteries so power consumption mechanisms involving algorithms and protocols must efficiently designed by Making the nodes to hibernate when not in use, Selection of routing path for minimal consumption, Reduction in networking overhead, Selection of nodes depending on energy status.

II. ASSORTMENT OF ROUTING PROTOCOLS FOR AD-HOC MOBILE NETWORKS

An ad hoc routing protocol [12] is a convention, or standard, that controls how nodes decide which way to route packet between computing devices in a mobile ad hoc network. Here nodes do not start out familiar with the topology of their networks; instead, they have to discover it. The basic idea is that a new node may announce its presence and should listen for announcements broadcast by its neighbors. Each node learns about nodes nearby and how to reach them, and may announce that it, too, can reach them. The factors of consideration for designing are: Minimum route acquisition delay, Quick route reconfiguration in the case of path breaks, Loop-free routing, Distributed routing protocol, Low control overhead, Scalability with network size, QoS support as demanded by the application, Support of time-sensitive traffic, Security and privacy.

The following is a list of some ad hoc network routing protocols like table driven (proactive), on demand (reactive) and hybrid routing protocol.

A. Table Driven Routing Protocols: In Table-driven routing protocols [3] each node maintains one or more tables containing routing information to every other node in the network. All nodes update these tables so as to maintain a consistent and up-to-date view of the network. When the network topology changes the nodes propagate update messages throughout the network in order to maintain consistent and up-to-date routing information about the whole network. These routing protocols differ in the method by which the topology change information is distributed across the network and the number of necessary routing-related tables. The following sections discuss some of the existing table-driven ad hoc routing protocols.

The Destination-Sequenced Distance-Vector (DSDV) [9] Routing Algorithm: It is based on the idea of the classical Bellman-Ford Routing Algorithm with certain improvements. Every mobile station maintains a routing table that lists all available destinations, the number of hops to reach the destination and the sequence number assigned by the destination node. The sequence number is used to distinguish stale routes from new ones and thus avoid the formation of loops. The stations periodically transmit their routing tables to their immediate neighbors. A station also transmits its routing table if a significant change has occurred in its table from the last update sent. So, the update is both time-driven and event-driven. The routing table updates can be sent in two ways: - a "full dump" or an incremental update. A full dump sends the full routing table to the neighbors and could span many packets whereas in an incremental update only those entries from the routing table are sent that has a metric change since the last update and it must fit in a packet.

Wireless Routing Protocol (WRP): The Message Retransmission list (MRL) contains information to let a node know which of its neighbor has not acknowledged its update message and to retransmit update message to that neighbor. The nodes present on the response list of update message (formed using MRL) are required to Acknowledge the receipt of update message. If there is no change in routing table since last update, the node is required to send an idle Hello message to ensure connectivity. On receiving an update message, the node modifies its distance table and looks for better paths using new information. Any new path so found is relayed back to the original nodes so that they can update their tables. The node also updates its routing table if the new path is better than the existing path. On receiving an ACK, the node updates its MRL. A unique feature of this algorithm is that it checks the consistency of all its neighbors every time it detects a change in link

of any of its neighbors. Consistency check in this manner helps eliminate looping. Situations in a better way and also have fast convergence.

Global State Routing (GSR)[12]: It takes the idea of link state routing but improves it by avoiding flooding of routing messages. The routing messages are generated on a link change as in link state protocols. On receiving a routing message, the node updates its Topology table if the sequence number of the message is newer than the sequence number stored in the table. After this the node reconstructs its routing table and broadcasts the information to its neighbors.

Landmark Ad Hoc Routing (LANMAR): LANMAR reduces the control overhead largely through the truncation (i.e., scoping) of local routing tables and the "summarization" of routing information to remote groups of nodes. The above features reduce line and processing O/H and thus greatly improve routing scalability to large, mobile ad hoc networks. As a final note, we must stress that the LANMAR addressing and routing scheme has significance only within the ad hoc network (e.g., battlefield). Each node has also an IP address, which is distinct from the LANMAR address.

Fisheye State Routing: Fisheye State Routing (FSR) is an improvement of GSR. The large size of update messages in GSR wastes a considerable amount of network bandwidth. In FSR, each update message does not contain information about all nodes. Instead, it exchanges information about closer nodes more frequently than it does about farther nodes thus reducing the update message size. So each node gets accurate information about neighbors and the detail and accuracy of information decreases as the distance from node increases.

Optimized Link State Routing Protocol: OLSR protocol, at each node discovers 2-hop neighbor information and performs a distributed election of a set of multipoint relays (MPRs). Nodes select MPRs such that there will be a path to each of its 2-hop neighbors via a node selected as an MPR. These MPR nodes then source and forward TC messages that contain the MPR selectors. This functioning of MPRs makes OLSR unique from other link state routing protocols in a few different ways: The forwarding path for TC messages is not shared among all nodes but varies depending on the source, only a subset of nodes source link state information, not all links of a node are advertised but only those that represent MPR selections.

Hierarchical State Routing: The characteristic feature of Hierarchical State Routing (HSR) is multilevel clustering and logical partitioning of

mobile nodes. The network is partitioned into clusters and a cluster-head elected as In a cluster-based algorithm. In HSR, the cluster-heads again organize themselves into clusters and so on. The nodes of a physical cluster broadcast their link information to each other.

Zone-based Hierarchical Link State Routing Protocol: In ZHLS, the network is divided into non-overlapping zones. Unlike other hierarchical protocols, there is no zone-head. ZHLS defines two levels of topologies - node level and zone level. A node level topology tells how nodes of a zone are connected to each other physically. A virtual link between two zones exists if at least one node of a zone is physically connected to some node of the other zone. Zone level topology tells how zones are connected together.

Cluster head Gateway Switch Routing Protocol: CGSR uses as basis the DSDV Routing algorithm .The mobile nodes are aggregated into clusters and a cluster-head is elected. All nodes that are in the communication range of the cluster-head belong to its cluster. A gateway node is a node that is in the communication range of two or more cluster-heads. In a dynamic network cluster head scheme can cause performance degradation due to frequent cluster-head elections, so CGSR uses a Least Cluster Change (LCC) algorithm. In LCC, cluster-head change occurs only if a change in network causes two cluster-heads to come into one cluster or one of the nodes moves out of the range of all the cluster-heads.

B. On-Demand Routing Protocols: These protocols take a lazy approach to routing [12]. In contrast to table-driven routing protocols all up-to-date routes are not maintained at every node, instead the routes are created as and when required. When a source wants to send to a destination, it invokes the route discovery mechanisms to find the path to the destination. The route remains valid till the destination is reachable or until the route is no longer needed. The following are a few on-demand routing protocols:

Cluster based Routing Protocol: In Cluster Based Routing protocol (CBRP) the nodes are divided into clusters. To form the cluster the following algorithm is used. When a node comes up, it enters the "undecided" state, starts a timer and broadcasts a Hello message. When a cluster-head gets this hello message it responds with a triggered hello message immediately. When the undecided node gets this message it sets its state to "member". If the undecided node times out, then it makes itself the cluster-head if it has bi-directional link to some neighbor otherwise it remains in undecided state and repeats the

procedure again. Cluster heads are changed as infrequently as possible.

Ad hoc On-demand Distance Vector Routing: Ad hoc On-demand Distance Vector Routing (AODV) is an improvement on the DSDV algorithm. AODV minimizes the number of broadcasts by creating routes On-demand as opposed to DSDV that maintains the list of all the routes. To find a path to the destination, the source broadcasts a route request packet. The neighbors in turn broadcast the packet to their neighbors till it reaches an intermediate node that has recent route information about the destination or till it reaches the destination. A node discards a route request packet that it has already seen. The route request packet uses sequence numbers to ensure that the routes are loop free and to make sure that if the intermediate nodes reply to route requests, they reply with the latest information only.

Dynamic Source Routing Protocol: The Dynamic Source Routing Protocol [23] is a source-routed on-demand routing protocol. A node maintains route caches containing the source routes that it is aware of. The node updates entries in the route cache as and when it learns about new routes. The two major phases of the protocol are: route discovery and route maintenance. When the source node wants to send a packet to a destination, it looks up its route cache to determine if it already contains a route to the destination. If it finds that an unexpired route to the destination exists, then it uses this route to send the packet. But if the node does not have such a route, then it initiates the route discovery process by broadcasting a route request packet.

Temporally Ordered Routing Algorithm: The Temporally Ordered Routing Algorithm (TORA) is a highly adaptive, efficient and scalable distributed routing algorithm based on the concept of link reversal. TORA is proposed for highly dynamic mobile, multihop wireless networks. It is a source-initiated on-demand routing protocol. It finds multiple routes from a source node to a destination node. The main feature of TORA is that the control messages are localized to a very small set of nodes near the occurrence of a topological change. To achieve this, the nodes maintain routing information about adjacent nodes. The protocol has three basic functions: Route creation, Route maintenance, and Route erasure.

Associatively Based Routing: ABR defines a new metric for routing known as the degree of association stability. It is free from loops, deadlock, and packet duplicates. In ABR, a route is selected based on associatively states of nodes. The routes thus selected are liked to be long-lived. All node generate periodic beacons to Signify its existence. When a neighbor

node receives a beacon, it updates its associatively tables. For every beacon received, a node increments its associatively tick with respect to the node from which it received the beacon.

Signal Stability Routing: Signal Stability-Based Adaptive Routing protocol (SSR) presented is an on-demand routing protocol that selects routes based on the signal strength between nodes and a node's location stability. This route selection criterion has the effect of choosing routes that have "stronger" connectivity. SSR comprises of two cooperative protocols: the Dynamic Routing Protocol (DRP) and the Static Routing Protocol (SRP). The DRP maintains the Signal Stability Table (SST) and Routing Table (RT). The SST stores the signal strength of neighboring nodes obtained by periodic beacons from the link layer of each neighboring node. Signal strength is either recorded as a strong or weak channel. All transmissions are received by DRP and processed. After updating the appropriate table entries, the DRP passes the packet to the SRP.

III. UNDERSTANDING CONGESTION IN WIRELESS NETWORKS

The occurrence of a high density of nodes within a single collision domain of a wireless network can result in congestion, thereby causing a significant performance bottleneck. Effects of congestion include drastic drops in network throughput, unacceptable packet delays, and session disruptions. In contrast, the back-haul wire line portion of a wireless network is typically well provisioned to handle the network load. Therefore, there arises a compelling need to understand the behavior of the wireless portion of heavily utilized and congested wireless networks. [6]

Acknowledgments for data sent, or lack of acknowledgments, are used by senders to infer network conditions between the TCP sender and receiver. Coupled with timers, TCP senders and receivers can alter the behavior of the flow of data. This is more generally referred to as congestion control and/or network congestion avoidance.

In addition, senders employ a retransmission timeout (RTO) that is based on the estimated round-trip time (or RTT) between the sender and receiver, as well as the variance in this round trip time. There are subtleties in the estimation of RTT. For example, senders must be careful when calculating RTT samples for retransmitted packets; typically they use Karn's Algorithm or TCP timestamps. These individual RTT samples are then averaged over time to create a Smoothed Round Trip Time (SRTT) using Jacobson's algorithm. This SRTT value is what is finally used as the round-trip time estimate.

IV. CHALLENGES FOR TCP IN MANETS

TCP assumes that network congestion has happened whenever a packet is lost. It then invokes appropriate congestion control actions including window size reduction. Although this assumption is reasonable for wired networks; it is questionable for wireless networks especially MANETs. The main causes of errors in wireless channels are the following

Signal attenuation: This is due to a decrease in the intensity of the electromagnetic energy at the receiver (e.g. due to long distance), which leads to low signal-to-noise ratio (SNR).

Doppler shift: This is due to the relative velocities of the transmitter and the receiver. Doppler shift causes frequency shifts in the arriving signal, thereby complicating the successful reception of the signal receiver.

Path asymmetry: Path asymmetry in ad hoc networks may appear in several forms as bandwidth asymmetry, loss rate asymmetry, and route asymmetry.

Route failures: In MANETs route failures are frequent events. The main cause of route failures is node mobility. Another factor that can lead to route failures is the link failures caused by the contention on the wireless channel, which is the main cause of TCP performance degradation.

Energy efficiency: As power is limited at mobile nodes, any successful scheme must be designed to be energy efficient. In some scenarios where battery recharge is not allowed, energy efficiency is critical for prolonging network lifetime. Because batteries carried by each mobile node have limited power supply, processing power is limited.

V. CURRENT STATE OF THE ART

Duc A. Tran et al[10] published a research paper on Congestion Adaptive Routing in Mobile Ad Hoc Networks. In this context they argued that Mobility, channel error, and congestion are the main causes for packet loss in mobile ad hoc networks. Reducing packet loss typically involves congestion control operating on top of a mobility and failure adaptive routing protocol at the network layer. In the current designs, routing is not congestion-adaptive. Routing may let a congestion happen which is detected by congestion control, but dealing with congestion in this reactive manner results in longer delay and unnecessary packet loss and requires significant overhead if a new route is needed. This problem becomes more visible especially in large-scale transmission of heavy traffic such as multimedia data,

where congestion is more probable and the negative impact of packet loss on the service quality is of more significance. We argue that routing should not only be aware of, but also be adaptive to, network congestion. Based on this argument Duc A. Tran et al [10] proposed a routing protocol (CRP) with such properties.

CRP Overview: Congestion Adaptive Routing protocol (CRP) is a unicast routing protocol for MANETs. The preliminary concepts of the CRP explored in their earlier work. In proposed CRP, every node appearing on a route warns its previous node when prone to be congested. The previous node uses a “bypass” route for bypassing the potential congestion area to the first non-congested node on the primary route. Traffic is split probabilistically over these two routes, primary and bypass, thus effectively lessening the chance of congestion occurrence. CRP is on-demand and consists of the following components: Congestion monitoring, primary route discovery, Bypass discovery, Traffic splitting and adaptive congestion, Multipath minimization, and Failure recovery.

A bypass is a sub-path connecting a node and the next non-congested node. If a node is aware of a potential congestion ahead, it finds a bypass that will be used in case the congestion actually occurs or is about to. Part of the incoming traffic will be sent on the bypass, making the traffic coming to the potentially congested node less. The congestion may be avoided as a result. Because a bypass is removed when the congestion is totally resolved, CRP does not incur heavy overhead due to maintaining bypass paths. The bypass maintenance cost is further reduced because a bypass is typically short and a primary node can only create at most one bypass.

Observation: Since CRP attempted to prevent congestion from occurring in the first place, rather than dealing with it reactively, it experienced fewer packet losses than routing protocols that are not adaptive to congestion. A key in CRP design is the bypass concept. A short end-to-end delay is also provided by CRP. Indeed, since CRP makes the network less congested, the queuing delay is less. Furthermore, since recovery of a link breakage is realized gracefully and quickly by making use of the existing bypass paths, the delay due to new-route establishment is also low. The simulation results indicated the advantages of CRP over AODV and DSR in routing and energy efficiency.

Santhosh Baboo et al [7] argued that congestion with limited resources occurs in heterogeneous mobile ad hoc networks (MANETs). Packet transmissions suffer from interference and fading because of the shared wireless channel and dynamic

topology. In heterogeneous ad hoc networks, throughput via a given route depends upon the minimum data rate of its entire links. In a route of links with various data rates, there is a chance of congestion if a high data rate node passes more traffic to a low data rate node and this leads to long queuing delays in such routes. The conventional hop count routing metric does not adapt well to mobile nodes. The transmission capability, reliability and congestion around a link are included in a congestion-aware routing metric for MANETs. In the context of this argument Santhosh Baboo et al[7] proposed an energy efficient congestion aware routing protocol which uses a combined weight values as a routing metric. This proposed protocol is based on the data rate, queuing delay, link quality, residual energy and MAC overhead. The energy efficiency is justified since the route with minimum cost index is selected among the discovered routes, which is based on the node weight of all the in-network nodes.

Overview of the protocol [7]:A congestion-aware routing metric for MANETs should incorporate transmission capability, reliability, and congestion around a link. The proposed energy efficient congestion aware routing protocol (EECARP) employed the following routing metrics: Data-rate, Buffer queuing delay, Link Quality, Residual Energy, MAC Overhead. These metrics were used to find and prefer less congested high throughput links to improve channel utilization. After estimating the above metrics, a combined weight value will be calculated for each node. A multi path on-demand routing protocol, which discovers multiple disjoint routes from a source to destination is used as underlying protocol. Among the discovered routes, the route with minimum cost index will be selected, which is based on the node weight of all the in-network nodes for each packet successfully delivered from the source node to the destination node. The node's cost index will be calculated in a backward propagating way. The cost indices of a node's possible downstream neighbors are obtained by the feedbacks of its downstream neighbors.

Observation: The proposed energy efficient congestion aware routing protocol employs a combined weight value as a routing metric, based on the data rate, queuing delay, link quality, residual energy and MAC overhead. A multipath on demand routing protocol used as underlying routing protocol that discovers multiple disjoint routes from a source to destination. Among the discovered routes, the route with minimum cost index is selected, which is based on the node weight of all the in-network nodes from the source node to the destination node. By simulation results explored, indicating that the proposed routing protocol attains high throughput and

packet delivery ratio, by reducing the energy consumption, packet drop and delay.

Yuvaraju, B.N et al[4] proposed a protocol independent congestion control method in short can refered as PICCO, which uses mobile relays. In the context of the proposed method, they argued that the limited lifetime of batteries and the bandwidth limitation of channels are the major issues in Ad-hoc networks. The term Congestion is usually associated with the bandwidth issues. The bandwidth keeps varying and when there is insufficient bandwidth to satisfy the demand, hence there is congestion problem. Congestion control methods are partially implemented in the network elements (e.g.: routers) inside the network and partially in the transport protocols running on the end hosts. All congestion control methods were developed depending on the underlying transport protocol TCP and hence cannot be used when the underlying transport protocol changes to UDP. In real time applications, where UDP is mostly used with Real time Transport Protocol (RTP), lost data packets cannot be resent. So it becomes all the more critical to have a proper congestion control method which can be used by UDP as well. Hence the PICCO method to solve the congestion problem can be implemented only in the network elements and is independent of the underlying transport protocols and can be used for TCP as well as UDP. This method aimed to reduce the number of packets being dropped in the network, thus improving the overall performance of the network.

Overview of Picco [4]: The proposed idea is based on Ad-hoc networks where the nodes themselves act as the routers (network elements). As and when the node becomes congested (starts dropping the packet due to queue overflow), it calls for the service of a mobile relay [9]. The mobile relay shares the load of the congested node. As and when the load on the congested node reduces to efficient level, the mobile relay is released so that it can provide service to other congested nodes in the network. This method reduces the number of packets being dropped in the network, thus improving the overall performance [14] of the network. The two assumptions in this method are that every node in the network is capable of calling the service of a mobile relay and that mobile relay has sufficient queue size to provide service to the congested nodes in the network.

Observation: The PICCO is based on Ad-hoc networks where the nodes themselves act as the routers (network elements). This method to solve the congestion problem can be implemented only in the network elements (e.g.: routers, etc) and is independent of the underlying transport protocols.

Hence this congestion control method can be used for Transmission Control Protocol (TCP) as well as User Datagram Protocol (UDP). This method aimed to reduce the number of packets being dropped in the network, thus improving the overall performance of the network. The lack of an Ad-hoc Networks capacity theory has stunted the development and commercialization of many types of wireless networks including emergency, military, sensor and community mesh networks. Information theory, which has been vital for links and centralized networks, has not been successfully applied to decentralized wireless networks [4]. PICCO acts as a probe to analyze the performance of these decentralized wireless networks.

Raza.I et al[5] proposed a model called Congestion Aware Nodes based scheme, which is using cross layered design to exchange congestion statistics between Media Access Control (MAC) layer and routing layer. The parameters used by CAN based scheme for congestion detection at MAC layer are MAC overhead, packet retransmission, back off interval and queuing delay. This scheme is based on CAN and implemented at MAC Layer for Dynamic Source Routing (DSR) protocol. Raza.I et al[41] argued that TCP congestion detection and avoidance mechanism in ad hoc networks is vulnerable to spurious congestion attacks and acclaimed following two reasons for implementing CAN based scheme at MAC layer.

- 1) The channel conditions can be monitored effectively by continuously observing contention window, queuing delay and overhead at MAC layer.
- 2) The TCP congestion detection and avoidance mechanism will not be triggered as congestion will be handled at MAC layer, resulting in better end-to-end throughput.

Observation: CAN is implemented at MAC layer and it monitors different MAC layer parameters such as MAC overhead, packet retransmissions, back off intervals and queuing delay to detect congestion. Each node after detecting congestion passes the congestion information to routing layer which selects alternate paths and removes congested links from the route cache. CAN is implemented on each node to handle congestion locally. This property seems to be avoiding transmission of control overhead messages. The explored simulation results indicating that DSR with proposed CAN based scheme capability in presence of congestion has high throughput gain, low access delay, less data drop rate, less packet retransmissions and less number of back off intervals. But on contradict side this model is not considering the energy efficiency, which is critical issue in ad hoc network infrastructure.

T. Senthil kumaran et al[2] proposed an early congestion detection and optimal control routing in MANET called as EDOCR. The proposed EDOCR initially segregates network in to sparse and dense region by using mean of neighbors. After segregation of networks, it initiates an optimal route discovery process to find a route to destination. This optimal route discovery is reducing the RREQ overhead during the route discovery operation. All the primary path nodes periodically calculate its queue status at node level. While using early congestion detection technique, node detects congestion that is likely to happen and sends warning message to Neighbors. Then EDOCR utilizes the non-congested predecessor node of a congested node and initiates optimal route discovery process to find an alternate non-congested path for a destination. In the context of EDOCR proposal T. Senthil kumaran et al[2] argued that in ad hoc networks, broadcast storm and congestion are major issues listed below.

First During route discovery, conventional on demand route discovery methods in mobile ad hoc networks (MANET) employ simple flooding method, where a mobile node blindly rebroadcasts received route request (RREQ) packets until a route to a particular destination is established, it is usually costly and results in serious redundancy, contention and collisions in the network. These problems are widely referred to as the broadcast storm problem.

Second, Congestion occurs in any intermediate node when data packets travel from source to destination and they incur high packet loss and long delay, which cause the performance degradations of a network.

The performance of EDOCR was compared with EDAODV, EDCSCAODV and AODV using the Ns-2 simulator. Based on the simulation results the authors justified the significant improvement of EDOCR over EDAODV, EDCSCAODV and AODV routing schemes.

Overview of the EDOCR [2]: Early congestion detection and optimal control routing protocol (EDOCR) is a uni-cast routing protocol for MANET. In EDOCR, every node appearing on a route warns its neighbor nodes when prone to be congested. The congested nodes' neighbors when aware of this situation, try to find an alternate path with limited number of control packets by using optimal control routing. EDOCR consists of the following components: Network Classification, Optimal Route discovery, Early congestion detection, Alternate path Discovery. In EDOCR, a node every second checks the occupancy of its link-layer queue by using an early congestion detection technique to detect the congestion well in advance. An early congestion

detection technique is a queue management algorithm with an optimization of random early detection (RED) model that makes use of direct measurement congestion status well in advance in a network.

Observation: The proposed EDOCR to accomplish congestion control in wireless multihop networks attempted to detect congestion in advance from occurring in the first place, rather than dealing with it reactively. The ancestor node is aware of a potential congestion ahead. Its efforts to find a non-congested route between source and destination helps to control the congestion as a result. The efforts of EDOCR design to avoid the brute force attitude of simple flooding which causes very high overhead can be observable at large dense networks. EDOCR design boosted with optimal route discovery method for reducing the RREQ overhead during the route discovery operation, which helps not to incur heavy overhead to find non-congested paths. The simulation results explored indicated that this technique substantially reduces the overhead as compared to the existing flooding mechanism and also provided a short end-to-end delay compared to other techniques.

Chen, R.R et al [6] proposed A "Markovian Jump Congestion Control Strategy for Mobile Ad-Hoc Networks with Differentiated Services Traffic" to model the changes in the number of neighboring nodes and subsequently a Markovian Jump Congestion Control (MJCC) strategy is proposed for mobile ad hoc networks. The MJCC strategy does take into account the associated physical network resource limitations and is shown to be robust to the existing unknown and time-varying network delays. Furthermore, the MJCC controller is developed on the basis of Differentiated Services (Diff-Serv) architecture by utilizing a robust adaptive technique. A Linear Matrix Inequality (LMI) condition is obtained to guarantee the stochastic stability of the closed-loop system.

Overview of the MJCC [6]: The ordinary traffic controller needs to simultaneously regulate the incoming flow rate and allocate its capacity by also using an adaptive controller. Finally, for the best effort traffic no explicit active control is designed since this traffic does not have any QoS requirements. Suppose each node of an ad hoc network with N nodes has three queues corresponding to the premium, the ordinary and the best-effort traffics [15]. The congestion controller is implemented at the output port of each node. The control objective for the premium traffic is to allocate the output capacity by incorporating an adaptive estimator to cope with the incoming traffic uncertainties.

Observation: A novel Markovian jump queuing model corresponding to the premium and the ordinary

traffics are obtained by using a fluid flow model and conservation principles. LMI conditions are derived to facilitate the design of the controller parameters as well as the network traffic compression/transmission gains. These conditions are shown formally to guarantee stochastic stability properties for the closed-loop system. The simulation results presented demonstrate that the resulting steady state and the transient behavior of our proposed congestion control strategies are satisfactory. The main limits observed in MJCC are lack of energy efficient system in congestion discovery and no congestion control strategy in hop level and neighbor level.

Dhurandher S.K et al[3] proposed a mechanism for reducing congestion while routing bulky data in mobile ad hoc networks that aimed to provide a solution to the problem of network congestion that arises when huge amount of data such as multimedia data is transferred in mobile ad hoc networks. This issue has been addressed by designing a protocol that performs routing intelligently and minimizes the delay in data transmission. The objective of this work is to move the traffic away from the shortest path that is obtained by a suitable shortest path calculation algorithm to a less congested path so as to minimize the number of packet drops during data transmission and to avoid unnecessary delay. In this context Dhurandher S.K et al[44] proposed a protocol named as Congestion Aware Selection of Path with Efficient Routing (CASPER). In CASPER a router play a key role that runs the shortest path algorithm after pruning those links that violate a given set of constraints.

CASPER[3] overview: CASPER is a circle based routing technique for forwarding data. Instead of calculating and storing the path from the source node to all the nodes in the topology, it calculates and store path between the source node, destination node and the intermediate nodes that lie in a restricted circular topology. Also the shortest path is calculated such that it satisfies the minimum bandwidth requirement of the data to be sent so as to minimize the chances of congestion in the network. Thus, instead of complete topology graph for shortest path calculation, it considers a portion of the graph extracted using constrained circular routing technique. This technique seems to help in reduction in the number of control packets as lesser number of nodes are involved in the shortest path calculation and which is so in the routing process as well. This attempts to reduce the probability of congestion in the network, which is due to the fact that, this is done in order to satisfy the minimum bandwidth criteria taking into consideration the bandwidth requirement of the message that needs to be transmitted. This further would help in better routing table space since only those routes that are obtained through the constrained circular routing are stored in the routing table.

Observation: The CASPER protocol design attempted to decrease the average drop in packets and evident to improvement in terms of eradication of traffic congestion by taking care of the bandwidth requirements of the data to be transmitted. CASPER significantly proved itself as better design to avoid the unnecessary calculations and processing of each node, thereby saving time. It involves less storage consumption in routing tables as only the constrained shortest paths from a source to the destination node and intermediate nodes are stored at a time instead of paths between all possible nodes in topology, which are not even involved in routing.

Liu Ban-teng et al[1] put forward the importance of node degree theory to achieve congestion control routing for Mobile Ad Hoc Networks. The proposed Node degree theory based congestion control model select nodes with low degree to forward data packets in the process of routing searching.

Overview of node degree routing algorithm [1]: The routing algorithm based on node degree thought can be divided into the following several process steps:

1. Initialization: Using GPS to determine the location of each node in the network, then determine the adjacency matrix A and each node's degree values, turns to Step5.
2. Judgment: Through the adjacency matrix, local node determines whether exist a goal node within a jump communication range, if a goal node is in a jump communication range, then show that we have successfully built a routing.
3. Calculation: If the adjacent nodes assembly of local node doesn't include goal nodes, then calculate whether the number of hops exceeds the limit. If it exceeds the limit, then you show that we have failed to build a routing, turns to Step5.
4. Update: Compare this node degree value with the previous nodes, and fill the smaller in routing degrees values in routing establish request form.
5. End: record hops required to successfully find routes, when destination node received multiple route setup requests, will choose the lesser degrees value data sent routing. Above is the first search process.

Observation: The principle of the node degree algorithm considered that selects nodes with high probability to forward data, thus reducing network congestion. The proposed model is mainly concentrating on to identify the path with low congestion possibilities. Due to ad hoc infrastructure and node mobility it is obvious to identify the

dynamic changes in congestion state; hence the adaptive congestion control is crucial requirement in mobile ad hoc networks, which is not a part of this proposed model.

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the mobile ad hoc networks continue to move forward in the areas of implementing and testing routing protocol draft proposals. Varied participants are beginning to report both simulation and "live" network testing results. Also, additional mobile ad hoc networks protocol enhancements areas (e.g., security, multicast, and quality of service) continue to be discussed and presented within the group. Also two approaches one is to maintain compatibility with wide spread protocols mainly with TCP and other is to gain freedom in protocol design and hence better fit the specific needs of mobile ad hoc networks. The solutions discussed in this paper represent the solutions for a subset of the identified problems, which can serve as building blocks for application specific protocol stacks. There is still a lot of scope for the development of new congestion prevention models in mobile ad hoc network protocols. Particularly current experiments can be done to derive a generic cross layer congestion control stack for mobile ad hoc network. The further investigations in this context can consider two remarkable issues: The support hops can be expected to equip with significant memory and computational power in relation to the available network bandwidth and a certain homogeneity of the nodes in different application scenarios. These two considerations offer many opportunities for a protocol design to exploit both cross-layer information and sophisticated support by the intermediate hops. Therefore in this field the experiments can be inevitable that leads to develop a generic cross layer congestion control stacks, which can easily adopt by various mobile ad hoc network protocols.

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Improving of Visual Quality of Digital Image Using a Wavelet Based Dynamic Range Compression Algorithm

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Abstract— In today's technology wavelet based dynamic range compression algorithm is used to improve the quality of digital image, which has been captured in the scene of lightening conditions where enhances the local contrast and tonal rendition for defense and security task. This is the one type of logical algorithm which is used for aviation safety and which has direct human observation is utilized for aerial images for showing strong robustness and high image quality and result will be obtained by applying the algorithm to numerous aerial images.

Introduction

The introduction of this paper is to improve the image structure which is captured from satellites, air crafts or space crafts which does not have clarity due to the bad conditions of atmosphere such as clouds,rains,or fogs. Due to this condition the images drastically decrease and some time it may not visible to human noise that is the images which are taken form the bad atmosphere conditions may lead to near zero visibility even for the human eyes.

For this to maintain the clarity we can seek the system named as human visual system which has High dynamic range of scenes by compressing the dynamic range and adopting for each part of the scene.

To overcome these type of problems ,related to imaging devices by limited dynamic range, there are different ways of algorithm to which wavelet based compression algorithm have been developed.

The algorithms which have been developed in the image processing will also provide and contrast enhancement to some extent. To improve the visual quality of images i.e. digital images of high dynamic range scenes with the non uniform lightening conditions wavelet-based dynamic range compression (WDRC) algorithm was developed which is modified by introducing the term an histogram adjustment and color restoration of non linear image to process in single band the scenes which are having a very strong spectral characteristic in a single band called as (pathological) and here we can introduce the fast

image enhancement algorithm. The image enhancement algorithm is used to provide a very good local contrast and local rendition for preserving the dynamic range compression in aerial imagery applications such as security task and image interpretation for defense. This algorithm can also be applied for aviation safety in video streaming. .The main application of wavelet based dynamic range compression is aerial imagery is presented in this paper. All the result obtained from the large variety of aerial images by showing high image quality strong robustness and indicating promises for an aerial image during pure visibility of flight conditions.

I. IMAGE PROCESSING

Here we will introduce the Image processing which will be used in electrical engineering and computer science engineering , The **image processing** is one type of signal processing in which an image is the input such as video frame or photo grapy or a set of characteristics or parameters related to the image and output of the image processing may be either image or parameters the most image processing techniques nowadays involve a two dimensional signal in the image i.e treating the image as a two dimensional signal and standard signal processing techniques applied to it.

The image processing can also be possible in optical image processing and analog image processing were also be applicable for digital image processing this paper about one type of technique which is applicable for all .Producing the input image in the first place of acquisition images is refer to as image.

The physical process which is used to convert image signal to physical signal is image processing, image signal can be either digital or analog .The actual output can be physical image or characteristics of a image

Photography is common type of image processing. In this camera has to be used for capturing both digital or analog image to produce the physical picture the image is processed using some technology based on input.

The image is stored as a computer file in digital photo grapy and translated by using some software to generate the actual file. While photo grapy is taken shading , Color and many features are captured, these are translated by software in to the image.

- Brightness and contrast adjustment, color balancing, color translation, color mapping , quantization all are color corrections to a different color space.
- Combination of two or more images is called as optical compositing or Digital compositing .These are used in, “matte” to make a film-making.
- Recovery of full image, denouncing, ,Interpolation, from a raw image format by using a Bayer filter pattern
- Image morphing and differencing
- Alignment of two or more image and image registration.
- Image recognition, for example, extracting the text form the image using check box and bubble values and optical character recognition using optical mark recongnisation
- Image segmentation
- Combination of multiple images with the high dynamic range imaging.
- 2-D object recognition in geometric hashing with affine invariance.

II. INFORMATION EXTRACTION

It is the last step toward the final output of the image analysis. After pre-processing and image enhancement the remotely sensed data is subjected to quantitative analysis to assign individual pixels to specific classes. Classification of the image is based on the known and unknown identity to classify the remainder of the image consisting of those pixels of unknown identity. After classification is complete, it is necessary to evaluate its accuracy by comparing the categories on the classified images with the areas of known identity on the ground. The final result of the analysis consists of maps (or images), data and a report. These three components of the result provide the user with full information concerning the source data, the method of analysis and the outcome and its reliability.

When remotely sensed data is received from the imaging sensors on the satellite platforms it contains flaws and deficiencies. Pre-processing refers to those operations that are preliminary to the main analysis. Preprocessing includes a wide range of operations from the very simple to extremes of abstractness and complexity.

A. Equations

The below equation defined as continuous wavelet transform ,

$$CWT_x^\psi(\tau, s) = \Psi_x^\psi(\tau, s) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{|s|}} \int x(t) \psi^* \left(\frac{t - \tau}{s} \right) dt$$

$$x[n] * h[n] = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} x[k] \cdot h[n - k]$$

$$y[n] = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} h[k] \cdot x[2n - k]$$

$$y_{high}[k] = \sum_n x[n] \cdot g[2k - n]$$

$$y_{low}[k] = \sum_n x[n] \cdot h[2k - n]$$

III. PROPOSED CODING ALGORITHM

Her we will proposed one algorithm called as sub band coding algorithm. It can be repeated for decomposition further. At every filtering level and sub sampling will result in half of the time resolution and half of the frequency (frequency resolution)and half of the no of samples to be band spanned (double the frequency resolution).The below figure shows procedure for decomposition. Where x(n) is the original signal for decomposing and h(n) and g(n) are high pass and low pass filters respectively. F is the bandwidth of signal at every level.

IV. EXPERIMENT AND RESULT

ORIGINAL.IMAGE

ORIGINAL-IMAGE-HISTOGRAM

HISTOGRAM-ADJUSTED-IMAGE

ADJUSTED HISTOGRAM IMAGE

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper the WDRC algorithm in aerial imagery is presented. The results obtained from large variety of aerial images show strong robustness, high image quality, and improved visibility indicating promise for aerial imagery during poor visibility flight conditions. This algorithm can further be applied to real time video streaming and the enhanced video can be

projected to the pilot's heads-up display for aviation safety.

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A Novel Algorithm for Image Enhancement using Biomedical Images Based on Histogram Equalization

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Abstract---This paper presents a novel technique to increase the quality of medical images based on Histogram Equalization. In the proposed method first we have applied a noise reduction method and then we apply some suitable preprocessing on histogram of the medical images and after that histogram equalization has been applied on the new histogram. Our proposed method in despite of its simplicity has better results in compare to other usual methods based on histogram equalization. The quality of resulted images after applying our proposed methods has been tested on a database (medical images) with a confirmed criterion by viewer. Also we have considered a mathematical criterion for comparing our proposed algorithm with other available methods for contrast enhancement. Results show the better efficiency of the proposed method.

Key words ---biomedical images, histogram equalization

I. INTRODUCTION

Medical imaging is one of the best techniques for monitoring the person's health condition which is used widely nowadays. Also some of diseases can be detected using medical imaging methods. One of the problems that physicians encounter with it using medical images is low quality of the medical images. This low quality is caused to difficulty in diagnosis. So it is necessary to improve the quality of the medical images. There are so many methods for medical image enhancement to make a better perception from medical images. Various methods have been suggested for increasing medical image's quality in recently years. Histogram processing is one of the most important digital image processing techniques and it is widely used for increasing medical image's quality. Because the simplicity and better efficiency of the histogram based algorithms, these algorithms are widely used for contrast enhancement of images. Also it should be

mentioned that histogram based techniques are much less expensive in compare to the other methods [1].Histogram Equalization (HE) based algorithms are also used in other applications for example speech recognition and other areas [2] [3] [4] [5].

Histogram based techniques for image enhancement is mostly based on equalizing the histogram of the image and increasing the dynamic range corresponding to the image. Histogram Equalization (HE) method has two main disadvantages which affect efficiency of this method. These two main disadvantages are followed:

- Histogram Equalization (HE) assigns one gray level into two different neighbor gray levels with different intensities.
- If most of an image includes a gray level, Histogram Equalization (HE) assign a gray level with higher intensity to that gray level and it causes a phenomenon as we called it washed out. Figure1.shows this effect.

Figure 1. Effect of washed out after histogram equalization

There are so many ways for decreasing the effect of the mentioned problems. Bi Histogram Equalization (BHE) is one of these ways for obtaining better results using histogram equalization. Bi-Histogram Equalization (BHE) first divides histogram

of the input image to two segments based on the average of the histogram and then applies Histogram Equalization (HE) algorithm on each segment separately .

One of the improved histogram based methods is **Dualistic Sub Image Histogram Equalization(DSIHE)**. In this method, first histogram is divided to segments based on entropy and then histogram equalization method is applied on each segment separately . Despite the mentioned methods can often increase contrast of the image but they make undesirable effects in the image. In this paper we have proposed an efficient method for increasing contrast of the medical images based on histogram equalization without any undesirable effect.

At the follow, basics of Histogram Equalization (HE) and Bi Histogram Equalization (BHE) are stated in detail and then our proposed algorithm is considered.

II. Histogram Equalization (HE) and Bi Histogram Equalization (BHE)

Histogram Equalization (HE) and Bi Histogram Equalization (BHE) methods are considered as methods for contrast enhancement of the images in this section of the paper.

A. Histogram Equalization (HE)

Consider a digital image with gray levels in the range $[0, L-1]$, Probability Distribution Function of the image can be computed as equation (1):

$$P(r_k) = \frac{n_k}{N} \quad k=0, \dots, L-1 \quad (1)$$

Where r_k is the k th gray level and n_k is the number of pixels in the image having gray level r_k . Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) can also be computed as followed:

$$C(r_k) = \sum_{i=0}^{i=k} P(r_i) \quad (2)$$

$$k=0, \dots, L-1, 0 \leq C(r_k) \leq 1$$

Histogram Equalization (HE) appropriates gray level S_k to gray level r_k of the input image using equation (2). So we have:

$$S_k = (L-1) \times C(r_k) \quad (3)$$

Gray level S_k 's changes can be computed in usual histogram equalization method:

$$S_k = (L-1) \times P(r_k) \quad (4)$$

Equation (4) means that distance between S_c and S_{k+1} has direct relation with PDF of the input image at gray level r_k . Undesirable effects of the usual histogram equalization method (HE) are resulted from equation(2) because of the quantization operation and summarizing properties of this equation.

B. Bi Histogram Equalization (BHE)

Bi Histogram Equalization is considered as an improved histogram equalization (HE) method for contrast enhancement in this section. BHE first finds average point in histogram of the image and then divides histogram to two segments based on this point. After that histogram equalization operation is applied on each segment. There are two cumulative distribution functions for two segments. Gray level (r_k) under the average point are pointed to the new gray level (S_k) as it can be seen in equation (5)

$$S_k = (L_1) \times C_1(r_k) \quad (5)$$

$$C_1(r_k) = \left(\sum_{i=0}^k n_i \right) / \left(\sum_{j=0}^{L_1} n_j \right);$$

$$k=0, 1, \dots, L_1$$

Where L_1 is the average of gray levels of the histogram and it can be computed as in equation (6).

$$L_1 = \sum_{k=0}^{L-1} P(r_k) * r_k \quad (6)$$

Gray level (r_k) above the average point are pointed to the new gray level (S_k) as it can be seen in equation (7).

$$S_k = (L-1-L_1) \times C_2(r_k) + L_1 \quad (7)$$

$$C_2(r_k) = \left(\sum_{i=L_1+1}^k n_i \right) / \left(\sum_{j=L_1+1}^{L-1} n_j \right);$$

$$k=L_1+1, \dots, L-1$$

Results of applying BHE method comparing to HE and our proposed method are depicted in results section.

III. Proposed Algorithm

Our new method is considered for decreasing the mentioned undesirable effects in this section. Our proposed method first applies a few preprocessing on histogram of the image and equalizes the resulted PDF and then the new image is constructed based on the new PDF.

Our proposal method first finds a gray level with maximum number of pixels in an image's histogram. Now we make a new histogram which in it number of pixels corresponding to each gray level is equal to the average of the number of pixels of gray levels around that point. Then we normalized the values in new histogram such that adding of the new values is equaled to 1. After that we have applied histogram equalization on the new histogram and the new image is constructed based on this new histogram. We should mention some important points about using the proposed method:

1. Making new histogram starts at a gray level with maximum number of pixels and then expands into the right side or left side or into the both sides around this gray level.
2. The gray level corresponding to maximum number of pixels may represents background of the image. In this situation gray levels after and before the background gray level don't contain any important information for us. So expanding histogram in this situation can be resulted inversely and can be caused in undesirable effects. For overcoming on this problem, we should apply proposed algorithm once on the left side of the average gray level and once on the other side and also on both sides once time. After reconstructing three images from above, the best one is selected.
3. We have considered a quantitative criterion for comparing the methods and selecting the best image.

$$PixDis = \frac{1}{N_{pix}(N_{pix}-1)} \sum_{i=0}^{L-2} \sum_{j=i+1}^{L-1} H(i)H(j)(j-i) \quad (8)$$

$For, i, j \in [0, L-1]$

Where $H(i)$ represents the number of pixels in the image which their gray levels is i and N_{pix} is the total number of pixels in the image. Larger amount of this criterion exhibits better contrast enhancement in the image. Using the proposed method the mentioned undesirable effects do not occur and a better improvement is resulted comparing to HE and BHE. The pixels of every gray level is the average of the number of pixels corresponding to gray levels around this gray level, so there won't be quick changes in the number of pixels corresponding to gray levels. Figure 2 shows a histogram before and after applying proposed algorithm.

Figure 2. Result of applying proposed algorithm. Above histogram: before applying, down histogram: after applying.

IV. Experiments and Results

We applied our proposed algorithm on a database which includes 220 medical images. Also we should mention that we have subtracted background manually where the number of background pixels is more than other pixels. Figure 3 shows an example of applying the proposed algorithm and also the results of applying HE and BHE algorithm.

Figure 3. Comparing HE, BHE and our method

BHE is an improved version of HE and for comparing BHE method with our proposed method we have defined a parameter known as improvement measure:

$$\frac{Pixdist(\text{method}) - Pixdist_{HE}}{Pixdist(\text{method})} \times 100 \quad (9)$$

Table 1 shows results of applying BHE and our proposed method on database and comparing these two methods based on improvement measure parameter.

Table 1: comparing BHE method and our method for better improvement in contrast of medical images

Method	Minimum Improvement	Maximum Improvement	Average
BHE	-18.7 %	93.91 %	7.41 %
Proposed method	-2.86 %	95.32%	18.2 %

As it can be seen our proposed method has better results comparing to BHE method. Also we have compared the efficiency of BHE and our proposed method in noisy images by adding Gaussian noise with mean 0 and variance 0.001 to the images. Table 2 shows the results after adding noise.

Table 2: comparing BHE method and our method for better improvement in contrast of noisy medical images

Method	Minimum Improvement	Maximum Improvement	Average
BHE	-9.7 %	90.91 %	5.41 %
Proposed method	-0.86 %	92.32%	15.2 %

As it can be seen our proposed method has better results comparing to BHE method even after adding noise to the images.

V. Conclusion

This paper presents a new method for contrast enhancement in medical images for better perception. The proposed method is based on histogram processing before histogram equalization. The results were promising better efficiency of the proposed method comparing to other usual methods for contrast enhancement. Automatic subtraction of background before applying proposed method can increase the efficiency of the method in future.

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Novel Algorithm for Image Enhancement

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Abstract — In this paper, a generalized novel algorithm for image enhancement. Based on our analysis on the relationships between image histogram and contrast enhancement/white balancing, we first establish a generalized equalization model integrating contrast enhancement and white balancing into a unified framework of convex programming of image histogram. We show that many image enhancement tasks can be accomplished by the proposed model using different configurations of parameters. With two defining properties of histogram transform, namely contrast gain and nonlinearity, the model parameters for different enhancement applications can be optimized. We then derive an optimal image enhancement algorithm that theoretically achieves the best joint contrast enhancement and white balancing result with trading-off between contrast enhancement and tonal distortion. Subjective and objective experimental results show favorable performances of the proposed algorithm in applications of image enhancement, white balancing and tone correction. Computational complexity of the proposed method is also analyzed.

Key words

Contrast enhancement, contrast gain, generalized equalization, nonlinearity of transform, tone mapping, white balancing.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the fast advance of technologies and the prevalence of imaging devices, billions of digital images are being created every day. Due to undesirable light source, unfavourable weather or failure of the imaging device itself, the contrast and tone of the captured image may not always be satisfactory. Therefore, image enhancement is often required for both the aesthetic and pragmatic purposes. In fact, image enhancement algorithms have already been widely applied in imaging devices for tone mapping. For example, in a typical digital camera, the CCD or CMOS array receives the photons pass through lens and then the charge levels are transformed to the original image. Usually, the original image is stored in RAW format, with a bit-length too big for normal displays. So tone mapping techniques, e.g. the widely known gamma correction, are used to transfer the image into a suitable dynamic range. More sophisticated tone mapping algorithms were developed through the years, see [2], just to name a few. Generally, tone mapping algorithms can be classified into two categories by their functionalities during the imaging process.

1) *White Balancing*: Because of the undesirable illumination or the physical limitations of inexpensive imaging sensors, the captured image may carry obvious color bias. To calibrate the

color bias of image, we need to estimate the value of light source, the problem of which called color constancy.

Using a suitable physical imaging model, one can get an approximated illuminance, and then the linear transform can be applied to map the original image into an ideal one.

2) *Contrast Enhancement*: Contrast enhancement algorithms are widely used for the restoration of degraded media, among which global histogram equalization is the most popular choice. Other variants include local histogram equalization and the spatial filtering type of methods. For example, in the fractional filter is used to promote the variance of textures so as to enhance the image. In a texture synthesis based algorithm is proposed for degraded media, such as old pictures or films. On the other hand, transform based methods also exist, e.g. curvelet based algorithm. In an adaptive steering regression kernel is proposed to combine image sharpening with denoising. Despite of the abundant literature on image enhancement, including those representative listed above, two challenging problems for image enhancement are still not solved. First, *how to achieve contrast enhancement while preserving a good tone*. The contrast and tone of an image have mutual influence. Because of the complicated interaction, those algorithms merely aiming towards contrast enhancement or white balancing cannot provide optimal visual effect. Most, if not all, of current image enhancement systems divide white balancing and contrast enhancement into two separate and independent phases, as Fig. 1 (a) shows. This strategy has an obvious drawback: although tone has adjusted in the white balancing phase, contrast enhancement may undesirably bias it again. This trouble has been observed in many applications, e.g. the denoising algorithms; achieve contrast enhancement by increasing saturation of the image, but cause tonal distortion in some cases. It is easy to imagine that joint white balancing and contrast enhancement, as Fig. 1 (b) shows, is a more efficient solution towards overall quality enhancement.

Second, *how to theoretically relate different types of enhancement algorithms to each other*. In this aspect, the work in unified spatial filtering based enhancement methods, including bi-lateral filter, non-local means filter, steering regression and so on, which has potential applications in image enhancement. However, the computational complexity of filtering based method is much higher than traditional histogram based method in most situations. In many cases, such as real-

time video surveillance, the histogram based methods are still being widely used. Taking its significance in practical situations into consideration, finding a unified framework of histogram based methods is a meaningful work that may bring more inspiration to the image enhancement problem and facilitate future research. Although being originated from different applications, both of contrast enhancement and white balancing are essentially tone manipulation processes. In fact, it is noticed that almost all global algorithms of contrast enhancement and white balancing are based on histogram transform. Recently, a unified model for color constancy is proposed in [40] based on the concept of low-level visual information. However, this unified model does not take contrast into consideration, so it is limited to the application of white balancing. We introduce a strict definition of expected contrast-free contrast and devised a method called Optimal Contrast-Tone Mapping (OCTM) to solve contrast enhancement problem by maximizing the expected contrast gains subject to an upper limit on tone distortion. OCTM is a promising solution for the intensity channel, but it does not elucidate the relationship between contrast and tone on the color channels.

Fig.1

II. GENERALIZED EQUALIZATION MODEL

Consider an image $f = (f_r, f_g, f_b)^T$. The available dynamic range of f_c is $[0, L_c]$, $c=r, g, b$. The histogram of image is denoted as $\{h_c, p_c\}_{c=r, g, b}$. Here, $h_c \in \mathbb{R}^k$ represents the total K intensity levels, which corresponds to probability vector $p_c \in \mathbb{R}^k$. K is the number of intensity level whose probability value is non-zero. Given the histogram of original image, denoted as $\{h_c, p_c\}_{c=r, g, b}$, we achieve image enhancement by manipulating the histogram to be $\{\hat{h}_c, \hat{p}_c\}_{c=r, g, b}$. The distance between adjacent intensity levels is denoted as $s_{ck} = h_{ck} - h_{c,k-1}$, $k=2, \dots, k$, $s_{c1} = h_{c1}$. According to this denotation, we have $\hat{s}_c = \nabla \hat{h}_c$, $\hat{s}_c = \nabla \hat{h}_c$, represents derivation operator.

A. Histogram-Based Analysis on White Balancing

White balancing is a popular image enhancement method, with a critical step of color constancy. Being different from the learning based methods we focus on a low-level

approach to color constancy and establish the relationship between color constancy and the histogram of an image. In the Lambertian surface model, the image is expressed as

$$f_c = \int r(\lambda) l(\lambda) m_c(\lambda) d\lambda \quad (1)$$

Here, λ is the wavelength of visible light. $r(\lambda)$ is the surface reflectance, $l(\lambda)$ is the light source, and $m_c(\lambda)$ is the sensitivity of camera in the channel c . The goal of color constancy is to estimate the projection of light source on the RGB space. To achieve this goal, many assumptions have been made. For example, the max-rgb is proposed, which estimates the light source from the maximum responses of the three channels. Another widely used assumption is gray-world hypothesis [4], which assumes that the average reflectance in the scene is achromatic. Recently, these assumptions are unified in [10], as follows

$$\left(\frac{\int |f(x)|^\alpha dx}{\int dx} \right) = C e \quad (2)$$

Here, x is the coordinate of pixel. C is an arbitrary positive constant and α is a parameter. $e = [e_r, e_g, e_b]^T$ is the normalized estimation of light source. When $\alpha=1$ (2) is equivalent to Gray-world assumption while when $\alpha=\infty$ (2) is equivalent to max-rgb. White balancing is achieved by multiplying the element of e to the corresponding channel.

Because is

$[1/\sqrt{3}, 1/\sqrt{3}, 1/\sqrt{3}]$ is the normalized form of white light, the multiplication factor of channel C is $1/e_c \sqrt{3}$ from the viewpoint of image histogram, the left side of (2) can be rewritten as

$$\left(\frac{\int |f(x)|^\alpha dx}{\int dx} \right) \frac{1}{\alpha} = \begin{pmatrix} (p r^T h r^\alpha)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} \\ (p g^T h g^\alpha)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} \\ (p b^T h b^\alpha)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Where $h_c^\alpha = [h_{c1}^\alpha, \dots, h_{cK}^\alpha]^T$. Eq (3) reveals the interconnection among white balancing and histogram. Given an image, e is calculated as

$$e_c(\alpha) = \frac{(p c^T h c^\alpha)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}}}{\sqrt{\sum_{c=r, g, b} (p c^T h c^\alpha)^{\frac{2}{\alpha}}}} \quad (4)$$

As a result, the histogram of white balancing result, denoted as \hat{h} , is computed as follows

$$\hat{h} = 1/(e_c(\alpha) \sqrt{3}) \hat{h} \quad (5)$$

It is obvious that this process is linear. The linearity of the

trans-form is the most significant feature of histogram-based white balancing algorithm. In the next subsection, we will show that this linearity is also an important difference between white balancing and contrast enhancement

B. *Histogram-Based Analysis on Contrast Enhancement in the expected context-free contrast of image is defined by*

$$C = Pc^T Sc. \quad (6)$$

By the definition, the maximum contrast L_c , which is achieved by a binary black-and-white image; the minimum contrast is zero when the image is a constant. So, the contrast enhancement is achieved by maximizing (6) in [9], as follows.

$$\hat{S}c = \operatorname{argmax} Pc^T Sc, \quad (7)$$

Where the first constraint makes sure that the output image still has a suitable dynamic range and the second constraint denotes the minimum distance between adjacent gray levels as d . However, although the definition in (6) has obvious statistical meaning, it is not optimal to be used as an objective function directly. Eq. (7) is a linear programming problem whose solution is sparse—to the maximum probability p_{ci} , the corresponding $\hat{S}c_i = L_c - d$ (K-1) and other $\hat{S}c_k = d$. Realizing this problem, another two constraints are added to suppress artifacts, which make the model complicated and sensitive to some predefined parameters. Before the work, histogram-based algorithm has been widely used in contrast enhancement. The most commonly used approach is histogram equalization, which makes the probability density function of enhanced image close to that of uniform distribution. After equalization, the intensity level of new image, \hat{h}_{ci} , is

$$\hat{h}_{ci} = C \sum_{j=0}^i P_{cj}. \quad (8)$$

here is a constant. Eq. (8) also gives a relationship between histogram and the distance between adjacent intensity level, as following shows.

$$\hat{S}c_i = \hat{h}_{ci} - \hat{h}_{c,i-1} = Cp_{ci}. \quad (9)$$

According to (8), (9), histogram equalization is equivalent to solving the following optimization problem

$$\hat{S}c = \operatorname{argmax} \frac{1}{\|Pc^{-1} Sc\|_\infty}, \quad (10)$$

$$s. t. \sum_{i=1}^K S_{ci} = L_{ci}, S_{ci} \geq d,$$

Here $Pc = \operatorname{diag}(p_{c1}, \dots, p_{ck})$

The performance of histogram equalization is not optimal in most situations. The essential reason for its limited performance is the questionable assumption that the histogram of ideal image obeys uniform distribution. To get a better equalization result, we need to find a better distribution which is a big challenge. Recently, some adaptive histogram equalization methods are proposed in [1], [5], but gave neither a clear definition of contrast nor an explicit objective function of contrast enhancement.

A common feature of all the enhancement methods mentioned above is that the transform of histogram is non-linear, which is different from white balancing.

III. The Proposed Model

The aims of establishing the generalized equalization model include: 1) giving a unified explanation to white balancing problem and contrast enhancement problem; 2) providing an explicit objective function for these two problems and proposing a joint algorithm for them; 3) controlling the performance of the algorithm by as few parameters as possible. The proposed model is inspired by (7), (10). Although (7), (10) seem to be very different, if we regard the order of Pc and the norm of the objective function as two parameters, β and n , (7), (10) are rewritten in a generalized form

$$\hat{S}c = \operatorname{argmax} \frac{1}{\|Pc^{-\beta} Sc\|_n}, \quad (11)$$

$$s. t. \sum_{i=1}^K S_{ci} = L_{ci}, S_{ci} \geq d,$$

Both (10) and (7) have interesting relationships with (11). When $n=2$ and $\beta=0.5$ (or $n=\infty$ and $\beta=1$), maximum is reached when $S_{ci}/(p_{ci})^\beta = C$, which is equivalent to (10). When $n=2$ and $0 \leq \beta \leq 0.5$, (or $n=\infty$ and $0 \leq \beta \leq 1$), the solution would be smoother than that of (10). When $n=1$ or $\beta \rightarrow \infty$, the solution is equivalent to that of (7). Compared with traditional histogram equalization, (11) is more flexible, because the target histogram does not have to obey uniform distribution. Considering the fact that traditional histogram equalization often leads to over-enhanced results, relaxing the constraints of uniform distribution can suppress over-enhancement effectively.

$$\hat{S}c = \underset{c=r,g,b}{\operatorname{argmax}} \sum \|Pc^{-\beta} Sc\|_n,$$

$$s. t \sum_{i=1}^K S_{ci} = \frac{1}{sc(\alpha)\sqrt{3}} \sum_{i=1}^K \hat{S}_{ci}, \hat{S}_{ci} \geq d \quad (12)$$

Here, S is the original distance between adjacent intensity level of the channel c . In generalized model, we set the upper bound L as the result of white balancing. On the top of (12), we introduce two measures into generalized equalization model: the gain of expected context-free contrast and the nonlinearity of the transform from \hat{h} to \hat{h}_c , which are defined as

$$G = \frac{Pc^T \hat{S}c}{Pc^T S} , NL = \|\nabla (\hat{S}c - S)\|_2 \quad (13)$$

If $\hat{S}c$ is homogeneous enough, $NL \approx \|\nabla \hat{S}c\|_2$. The larger NL , the stronger non-linearity of the transform. The nonlinearity of white balancing methods is close to 0. On the other hand, the contrast enhancement methods often have strong nonlinearity, which achieve visible enhancement of contrast. However, separate nonlinear transform of histograms of three channels may cause tone distortion. In the next section, we will theoretically prove that the proposed method, with a suitable configuration of parameters, can achieve a best trade-off between contrast enhancement and tone adjustment.

Fig.2

Fig. 2. In each sub-figure, the thick black line represents the feasible domain of Eq. (12); the red and blue wireframes show the boundaries of the objective function of Eq. (12) which correspond to the $\beta=0$ and $\beta>0$ situations respectively; the red and blue points are the optimal solutions corresponding to the $\beta=0$ and $\beta>0$ situations respectively. The parameter n in (a), (b), (c) is 1, 2 and ∞ respectively.

Fig.3. Figure (a) gives the curves of contrast gain with the increase of β . Figure (b) gives the curves of nonlinearity of transform with the increase of β . Figure (c) gives the curves of the ratio of NL to G , $n=1, 2, \infty$. The red, green and blue curves correspond to $n=1, 2, \infty$, respectively.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Optimal Contrast Enhancement

As a basic application of the proposed algorithm, image contrast enhancement is used in the experiments. The configuration of parameters is: $d=0$, $\alpha=\infty$, $n=2$. β is chosen according to the optimal image enhancement algorithm introduced in the former section. To demonstrate the validity of the proposed algorithm, we design a subjective experiment. In the experiment, 6 images are given simultaneously in a screen, including the original image from Berkeley Segmentation Dataset (BSDS300), the result corresponding to β and 4 results with randomly selected $\beta \in [0, 0.64]$. The 6 images are presented randomly. Each viewer selects the image that they think has the best visual effect. The experiment is stopped when the viewer does not want to continue. 50 volunteers joined in our subjective viewing experiment. In our experiment, the probability that a volunteer selects the image corresponding to the optimal is 65.8%. The average error between β and β selected subjectively is 0.0621. The experimental results show that in most situations, the enhancement results of the proposed method match well with our subjective preference. Fig. 2 shows the errors between subjective β s and the β s from the proposed algorithm for 300 images in the dataset. Compared with β , the error is small in most cases. Fig. 2 gives the comparison results of the proposed algorithm and some existing methods. We can find that the proposed method achieves the best overall visual effect: it not only enhances the contrast, but also prevents serious nonlinear tone distortion. Another database we use is the old pictures in the network resource of Nagasaki University library. We also randomly choose some other images from the Internet. These pictures suffer not only from low contrast but also from serious tone distortion. Using the algorithm based on the generalized equalization model, we can achieve contrast enhancement and white balancing jointly, as illustrated in Fig. 3. We also tested the proposed method on underexposed images, as shown in Fig. 4. With the help of the proposed method, the details in the dark

region become clearer.

B. Joint White Balancing and Enhancement

When β is close to 0, the behavior of the proposed method is close to white balancing. To demonstrate performance of the proposed method in white balancing, test the proposed method on three color constancy datasets. The angular error between the estimated light source and the ground truth is calculated as $\arccos(\hat{e} \cdot e)$. The median angular error on three datasets [3], for various color constancy methods. Compared with gray-edge method, under suitable configuration, our method provides comparable color constancy results. As a major contribution, the generalized equalization model provides a joint strategy for image enhancement. If we relax β to a small positive number, we can combine white balancing and enhancement into an integrated algorithm. In Fig. 3 and 4, we compare the proposed method with some existing white balancing algorithms, where we can see that the proposed method not only corrects the tone bias in original images but also enhances the contrast.

C. Global Tone Mapping for HDR Image

Tone mapping for HDR image is another natural application for the proposed model. Many tone mapping algorithms have been proposed through the years, e.g. those in [1], although the methods based on local adaptive filtering achieve encouraging results, the global method, such as gamma correction, is still the most popular choice because of its robustness and lower complexity. We test our method on the HDR images captured by Nikon D700⁵ and map them into 8-bit and compare the results with those from the default tone mapping process in MATLAB and gamma correction.

Although the default tone mapping in MATLAB can reveal some image details, it cannot recover the color of image correctly. In other words, the contrast is enhanced but the tone bias is raised. On the other hand, gamma correction avoids obvious tone bias and protects the color of image but suffers from

Fig.4

is an inappropriate choice of γ : if γ is close to 1, the details in the dark region of image will not be visible, as Fig. 1(a),(b) shows; if γ is close to 0, the contrast of image will be reduced, as shown in Fig. 4. Compared with the MATLAB tone mapping and gamma correction, the proposed model clearly gives more visually pleasant results, as shown in Fig. 4.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we analyzed the relationships between image histogram and contrast/tone. We established a generalized equalization model for global image tone mapping. Extensive experimental results suggest that the proposed method has good performance in many typical applications including image contrast enhancement, tone correction, white balancing and post-processing of de-hazed images. In the future, besides global image enhancement, we expect to unify more local image enhancement methods into the model through local image feature analysis.

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A 32nm SRAM Using Sense Amplifier with Non-Strobe Signal

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Abstract—Normally, the high solidity Static Random Access Memory (SRAM) devices use very small bit cell which may cause severe changes, by reducing their read static noise margin (SNM) and read current. In addition to this, the array performance is limited and unstable strobed signal found the necessity of the device named sense amplifier. This paper, Designs a sense amplifier which is unified with 64Kbyte array which is the collection of $0.15\mu\text{m}^2$ 6T bit cell to achieve good performance. The sense amplifier achieve various performance degradation especially it reduces the sensitivity of device which cause great change with the small changes in load on high speed nodes; to avoid tracking mismatch in an external circuit path by internal reference stable voltage by sense amplifier ;the actual small signal detects the small read currents so that the bit cell parameters can be enhanced ;the single ended sensing is appropriate to asymmetric bit cells which improves the operating margin. It finally shows the excellent improvement in access time like four times of conventional amplifiers and at least 40% in worst case

Index Terms—Auto-zeroing, device variation, offset compensation, sense-amplifier, SRAM.

I. INTRODUCTION

HIGH-DENSITY SRAMs are a critical means for digital systems to benefit from technology scaling. Further, more and more, these systems target highly mobile applications, where low power consumption is paramount. As a result, their constituent SRAMs, whose power is becoming increasingly dominant, must utilize low-power (LP) CMOS technologies.

At the 45 nm node, bit-cells as small as a $0.25\mu\text{m}^2$ are manufacturable. Fig. 1, however, summarizes the associated challenges. First, such aggressive scaling requires the use of tiny devices, aggravating variability. As a result, the cell read current and read static noise margin (SNM) [1], [2], are greatly degraded, subjecting the 6T design to a highly constrained density–stability–performance trade-off. This is, however, alleviated somewhat in 8T topologies at the cost of density and sensing complexity. Similarly, sense-amplifiers are also primarily limited by variation, as their input offset sets the required bit-line discharge, and as a result, in many cases, their

Fig. 2. Degradation in bit-line discharge time for high-density SRAMs caused by (a) reduced cell read-current and (b) increased bit-line capacitance.

Fig. 1. Critical limitations faced by low-power high-density SRAMs at the 45 nm node. area has stopped scaling [3]. Accordingly, even though their density constraints are not nearly as severe as the bit-cell's, sense-amplifiers are becoming a limiting feature in high-density arrays. Finally, another source of variation emerging as a major limitation is the timing of the sense-

amplifier strobe signal, which does not track well with the array read-path over all of the operating corners. As a result, excessive margin must be introduced into the critical read-path. Although these limitations span the entire array, they can be greatly alleviated by means of the sense-amplifier. The following sections start by elaborating on the challenges faced by low-power high-density SRAMs and how they are related to the sense-amplifier.

II. HIGH-DENSITY SRAM DESIGN CHALLENGES

The most urgent challenges in high-density SRAMs arise from severe variation in the bit-cell and the trade-offs inherent in its structure. The following subsections describe how these are related to the sense-amplifier.

A. Read-Current Degradation

Low-power SRAMs must incur the reduced I_{READ} that comes with technology optimizations to manage leakage-currents. Fig. 2(a) shows how read-current scales further with cell size. The reduction in mean read-current is a direct consequence of reducing the size of the driver devices. However, the increased variation in the smaller devices also results in severer degradation to the weak-cell read-current in proportion to this already reduced mean read-current. For instance, the 5σ read-current for the $0.25\mu\text{m}^2$ cell is easily degraded by an additional factor of two.

Furthermore, in high-density arrays, the integration of many cells per bit-line, in order to maximize array efficiency, leads to very large bit-line capacitance. As shown in Fig. 2(b), the resulting ratio of I_{READ}/C_{BL} , which is critical to the array's performance, suffers even further.

B. Sense-Amplifier Strobing Uncertainty

The sense-amplifier strobe signal must ensure that enough time is allocated for bit-line discharge to overcome the sense-amplifier offset. However, as shown in Fig. 4(a), the bit-line discharge time depends on the delay through the array read-path, which is limited by the weakest bit-cell. Such a cell, whose statistical characteristics might be beyond the 5σ level, is impossible to replicate in the strobe control path. Consequently, as shown in Fig. 4(b) the timing of the two paths diverges greatly over process, voltage, and temperature corners [6] even if carefully laid out SRAM devices are employed in the strobe path, as in [7]. Since the strobe path must be designed such that it is

Fig. 3. Read SNM trade-off in high-density SRAMs limited by (a) cell size and (b) inverse correlation with cell read-current, caused by opposing access-device requirements.

the power-supply and on the bit-lines. As a result, an inherent trade-off is introduced between sensitivity, which ultimately affects the array's performance, and robustness to noise. Since no distinction can be made between noise on the bit-line and read-data droop, it becomes critical to ensure a desired level of bit-line noise margin, and relatedly, the sensitivity (or, correspondingly, speed) must be characterized with respect to this noise margin.

III. NON-STROBED REGENERATIVE SENSE-AMPLIFIER

The Non-Strobed Regenerative Sense-Amplifier (NSR-SA) shown in Fig. 5 addresses the limitations described in Section II. Two cascaded inverters ($M1-M2$ and $M3-M4$) form an amplification path that is self-biased for high-gain by the feedback switches, S_{AZ} . As described in Section IV-B, these also perform offset compensation of the inverter amplifiers via input auto-zeroing [13]. Importantly, however, to support small-signal sensing, which greatly improves the density-performance trade-off of the array, the large gain required is achieved most efficiently through regeneration [14]. Accordingly, the regenerative device, $M5$, provides very large positive-feedback gain. A critical feature, however, is that regeneration requires no external enable or strobe signal, thereby overcoming the severe tracking uncertainty described in Section II-C. Instead, the ideal DC transfer function, shown in Fig. 5, is implemented in continuous time, and the precise point at which regeneration is enabled depends only on the input bit-

longer than the array path in all cases, this implies, as shown in Fig. 4(b), that in many cases, it will be much longer than it needs to be, thereby excessively limiting the overall performance. In fact, the overall worst case delay, for the array configuration considered, need only be 820 ps based on the read-path delay; however, the actual worst case delay is 80 ps, limited by the strobe-path, imposing an excess overhead of nearly 20%

A. Noise Sensitivity

An important drawback to any single-ended sensing scheme is the loss of common-mode noise rejection capability both on

Fig. 4. Array read-path and sense-amplifier strobe-path (a) limited by matching to 5 bit-cell and (b) exhibiting severe delay divergence over process-voltage-temperature conditions, leading to excess overall delay.

line voltage (with respect to the internal reference, V_{TRIP}). Further, V_{TRIP} is very stable despite variation since it is generated implicitly by the original auto-zeroing, and, additionally, its precise value can be selected by design. Accordingly, this sense-amplifier, which is single-ended and compatible with asymmetric bit-cells, can enforce a desired balance between sensitivity and noise rejection.

A. Basic Operation

The NSR-SA operates over two phases: reset and detection. The reset phase occurs during SRAM bit-line pre-charge, during which the sense-amplifier does not need to detect bit-line droop. Hence, this time is used to perform self-correction of offsets via auto-zeroing. The detection phase corresponds with bit-line discharge, where the actual read-data must be quickly resolved.

1) *Reset Phase*: The purpose of the reset phase is to charge the internal nodes so that the inverters formed by $M1_2$ and

Fig. 5. Non-strobed regenerative sense-amplifier (NSR-SA) schematic and ideal transfer function.

Fig. 6. NSR-SA circuit and waveforms during reset phase.

ingly, when the S_{REG} switches are closed to enable $M5$ and $M6$, the V_{GS} of these devices remains very small, and in fact, as discussed in Section IV-C, even negative, thanks to charge-injection errors originating from the specific choice of the devices used to implement the S_{AZ} switches. As a result, the output logic level of $QB=0$ is sustained. Of course, bit-line leakage, arising from the unaccessed cells sharing BL , can compromise the logic “1” value, leading to detection errors. Although, the NSR-SA’s BL noise margin can be designed to reject these (as discussed in section Section IV-D), maximum-leakage simula-tions in the target LP process indicate that, for the 256 cells/ BL configuration considered, the nominal NSR-SA rejects bit-line leakage for access times up to 35 ns, which is much longer than the target delays.

Alternatively, in the logic “0” case, also shown in Fig. 7, an intentional bit-line droop is detected. Here, the voltage of node X rises rapidly, as a result of the inverter gain, and the voltage of node Y decreases even more rapidly, as a result of the cascaded inverter gains. Correspondingly, at some point, the regenerative

device’s (i.e., $M5$ ’s) V_{GS} , which is the difference between the voltage of nodes X and Y , becomes large enough that the device turns on, triggering positive feedback. Subsequently, the input of the first inverter is actively pulled low, and the entire NSR-SA quickly latches. The precise point where regeneration is enabled can be seen at the annotated inflection in the waveform of node Y . Shortly after this, the output, QB , quickly changes its state.

3) *Output Clocking Margin:* As mentioned, an important feature of the NSR-SA is that regeneration is triggered by the input bit-line droop itself, rather than an explicit strobe signal. Nonetheless, the read data must ultimately be clocked at the array output. However, as shown in Fig. 8(a), the timing problem described in Section II-C has actually been overcome and not just propagated to the subsequent output clock, $OCLK$.

By comparison, for instance, the strobe signal of a conventional sense-amplifier must arrive during the bit-line discharge phase, before the next pre-charge phase can begin. As a result, the timing of the strobe signal limits the critical read-path inside the array. However, as shown in Fig. 8(b), the NSR-SA latcFig. 7. NSR-SA circuit and waveforms during detection phase (for both bit-line logic

cases) are biased in their high-gain regions very close to their ideal trip-points. Simultaneously, this initializes the regenerative device, $M5$, such that its positive feedback gain is very low. As mentioned, the reset phase occurs during bit-line pre-charge; however, it is actually meant to occupy only a small portion of this period. For instance, as shown in Fig. 6, a short RST pulse is asserted (even its duration as shown is much longer than required). During this time, the input node and output stage ($M6$) are pre-charged, while, simultaneously, the negative feedback switches, S_{AZ} , are closed, and the regeneration switches, S_{REG} , are opened. Consequently, as shown in Fig. 6, nodes X and Y get biased to mid-rail voltages at the inverter trip-points, which are nominally designed to be equal. Offsets can lead to differences in their precise value, but the analysis in Section IV-B describes how this biasing greatly attenuates the errors.

It can be seen that nodes X and Y settle to their required reset values in less than 100 ps, implying that only a very small RST pulse is required. It should be noted, however, that while nodes X and Y remain at these mid-rail voltages, a static current path exists through $M1-2$ and $M3-4$. As discussed in Section V-B, however, the total power overhead introduced as a result is small.

2) *Detection Phase:* Following reset, bit-line discharge must be detected. First, the case where the bit-line remains high at its pre-charge value (i.e. logic “1”) will be considered. Here, the bit-line voltage, BL , remains unchanged, so all internal volt-ages remain essentially at their reset bias values. For instance, as shown in Fig. 7, after the negative feedback switches, S_{AZ} , are opened, nodes X and Y remain unchanged aside from small perturbations arising from charge-injection errors from the S_{AZ} switches (which will be addressed in Section IV-C). Accord the output without a strobe signal, and the output state remains valid until the reset pulse is asserted. Since the reset pulse can be a small fraction of the pre-charge phase, the output data can be clocked well after the pre-charge phase begins, until the data is cleared by the reset pulse. As a result, its timing is decoupled from the critical read-path inside the array.

B. Offset Compensation

In Fig. 9(a), the inverters are abstracted by their logic symbol, and each of them is modeled as being ideal and offset-free.

Fig. 10. 10 k point Monte Carlo simulation showing improved sigma of NSR-SA access time compared to conventional sense-amplifier access time.

The offsets are modeled as the series voltage sources, V_{OS1-3} , each of which is associated with an inverter and the regenerative device.

During the reset phase, the S_{AZ} switches are closed, forcing the inverters into negative feedback. Analytically, this implies that the input and output values of the voltage transfer characteristic (VTC) must be equal, as shown by the diagonal line.

Accordingly, if the inverter is offset-free, as in the case of the solid VTC, its input would settle to the voltage V_M , which is the ideal trip-point. However, offset shifts the VTC to the left by an amount equal to V_{OS} . Now, as shown by the dotted VTC, the input instead settles to a value approximately equal to $V_M - V_{OS}$. In particular, this requires that the VTC is nearly vertical near these trip-points, which corresponds to a large inverter gain. If this is the case, the resulting voltage of $V_M - V_{OS}$ gets stored on the preceding coupling capacitor. As a result, $-V_{OS}$ appears in series with the actual V_{OS} , canceling the offset-voltage and biasing each inverter to its ideal trip-point.

Complete offset cancellation in this manner, however, requires that the gains of the inverters be infinite. Practically, the offset is only reduced by a factor equal to the finite inverter gain [13], which is approximately given by $g_m r_o$, where g_m

sufficient bit-line discharge in all operating conditions. Nonetheless, as shown, it achieves good mean performance thanks to its differential operation, as, nominally, it must wait long enough for only a very minute differential to develop on the bit-lines. However, because it is more sensitive to variation, its sigma is much worse at 37 ps, compared to 18 ps for the NSR-SA, and, therefore, it achieves far slower worst case performance. The greatly improved stability achieved by the NSR-SA points to the benefit of offset compensation. However, the next

primary limitation to its sigma comes from variation in the charge-injection errors introduced by the S_{AZ} switches.

C. False Regeneration Immunity

An even more urgent failure mode arising from charge-injection errors than residual delay sigma, however, is that, in an amplifier with high gain and regeneration, these can potentially result in resolution to the wrong output state, from which re-covery might not even be possible. For instance, in the NSR-SA, if charge-injection errors were to cause the input of the first inverter to decrease and the input of the second inverter to increase, the gain through the inverters would cause a large positive V_{GS} on the regenerative device, $M5$, causing the output to transition and latch, regardless of the input bit-line voltage.

The NSR-SA, however exploits the fact that it only needs to respond to bit-line discharge, not up-charge. As a result, regeneration only needs to occur in one direction, and, as shown in Fig. 11 the charge-injection error sources can be designed to oppose that direction. Specifically, the main device used for the first S_{AZ} switch is a PMOS, whose charge-injection errors tend to increase the input of the first inverter, and the main device used for the second S_{AZ} switch is an NMOS, whose charge-injection errors tend to decrease the input of the second inverter. As a result, nodes X and Y decrease and increase respectively,

is the transconductance and r_o is the output resistance of the inverter devices. As shown in Fig. 9(b), however, the residual offset of the second inverter stage is reduced by an additional factor of $g_m r_o$ when input referred, which requires dividing by the preceding inverter's gain. Finally, nothing explicit is done to manage the offset of the regenerative device, but, once again, its contribution to the overall offset is very small when input referred, since the gain from the input to its V_{GS} is given by $g_m r_o + (g_m r_o)^2$ through the inverter path. Accordingly, after all of the attenuation factors in Fig. 9(b), the offset of the first inverter dominates, but it is significantly reduced thanks to the offset compensation.

A Monte Carlo simulation of the access-time distributions for the NSR-SA and a conventional strobed sense-amplifier is shown in Fig. 10. In this context, access time includes the delay of the word-line driver, bit-line discharge, and sense-amplifier, and it is measured from the word-line enable signal to the sense-amplifier output valid. A 256-by-256 array configuration is considered with a mean bit-cell, so that the variation in the sense-amplifiers can be isolated. The conventional sense-amplifier has been sized for minimum offset while occupying a layout area of $12 \mu m^2$, and it also includes the strobe timing margin required to ensure

giving a negative V_{GS} on $M5$, pushing it away from false

re-generation.

D. Regeneration Trip Point

Although offset compensation improves the stability of the NSR-SA in the presence of variation, it is also important to set its nominal trip-point, V_{TRIP} , based on speed and noise re-jection considerations. One way to achieve this control is

Fig. 12. NSR-SA technique to set regeneration trip-point V_{TRIP} for noise re-jection and sensitivity considerations.

Fig. 13. IC die photo of prototype implemented in low-power 45 nm CMOS to compare performance of NSR-SA with conventional sense-amp adjusting the reset voltages of nodes X and Y , which change the V_{GS} of $M5$ and trim the amount of additional bit-line dis-charge required to actually trigger regeneration. This can be im-plemented, for instance, with the addition of an appropriately sized device at the inverter outputs, as shown in Fig. 12. This device can be either an NMOS or PMOS (NMOS is shown), de-pending on the trimming required, and, with its gate connected to an appropriate rail voltage, even a very small device (less than $0.2 \mu\text{m} \times 0.2 \mu\text{m}$) results in a wide range of output reset voltages (covering almost 0.3 V, in this case)

V. TEST-CHIP

A photograph of the prototype test-chip, which is imple-mented in LP 45 nm CMOS is shown in Fig. 13. A block diagram of its architecture is shown in Fig. 14. Here, two 64-kb (256 by 256) arrays of high-density $0.25 \mu\text{m}^2$ 6T SRAM bit-cells are integrated. The first drives a set of conventional strobed sense-amplifiers, of the structure shown in Fig. 10, and the second drives a set of NSR-SAs, so that the relative performances can be accurately compared.

To measure the access time with the NSR-SA, the word-line enable signal, WLE , must be asserted, and the $CLKIN$ signal must be swept inward, as shown in Fig. 14, until bit-failures ap-pear. To measure the access time with the conventional sense-amplifier, however, first the $STRB$ signal must be swept in-ward, with the $CLKIN$ signal held at a much larger delay, and then the $CLKIN$ signal must be swept in to measure the final access time. This two sweep procedure is also shown in Fig. 14. The final WLE_CLKIN access times can then be suitably compared, since the WLE and $CLKIN$ paths for the two ar-rays are carefully matched on-chip.

A. Noise Characterization

As mentioned in Section III-A, with any single-ended sensing scheme, it is important to characterize the noise re-jection versus sensitivity performance. In the case of bit-line noise, this re-quires dedicated additional circuitry, which is shown in Fig. 15, to inject a controllable noise amplitude on one set of bit-lines. In particular, the coupling capacitors, C_{NOISE} can be pulsed from off-chip, and the bit-line noise can be estimated from the ampli-tude of the off-chip pulse (set by the potentiometer), and the nominal ratio of the capacitor divider formed by C_{NOISE} and the actual parasitic bit-line capacitance, C_{BL} . Simultaneously, the regeneration trip-point of the NSR-SA can be adjusted by injecting a controllable current at the inverter outputs using $M7$

Fig. 15. Dedicated circuitry to inject a controllable noise amplitude on one set of bit-lines and independently adjust the sensitivity/noise re-jection of the NSR-SAND $M8$, whose gates are biased off-chip. As a result, this allows both the bit-line noise and NSR-SA sensitivity to be varied, al-lowing noise re-jection to be characterized versus access-speed.

B. Measurement Results

Measurements were taken from 53 chips in order to cap-ture some statistical behavior. The access-time distributions for the NSR-SA and the conventional sense-amplifier are shown in Fig. 16. Additionally, a distribution of the difference between the access times on each chip is also plotted to de-embed the absolute delays through board traces and chip packaging. As shown, the NSR-SA achieves superior sigma, as expected from Monte Carlo simulations. Unlike Fig. 10, however, the measure-ment results include the effect of variation in the bit-cells, and as a result the absolute delays here are larger. Nonetheless, es-pecially in the presence of this extra variation, which implies lower worst case bit-cell read-current, the NSR-SA performs very well, achieving a factor of four reduction in access-time sigma. Accordingly, the overall worst case delay improves from 2.46 ns to 1.63 ns, representing a speed-up of 34%.

With regards to transient supply noise, no severe effects in functionality were observed with large negative pulses on V_{DD} . However, long positive pulses larger than 55 mV that occur after the reset phase must be managed with proper system timing in order to avoid incorrect data latching. A performance summary of the NSR-SA and conventional sense-amplifier is provided in Table I. Each conventional sense- Fig. 16. Access-time measurements from 53 chips showing a factor of four improvement in the NSR-SA distribution sigma compared to the conventional sense-amplifier sigma. amplifier occupies a layout area of $12 \mu\text{m}^2$ while each NSR-SA occupies $19 \mu\text{m}^2$, though this includes all of the testability fea- tures that have been integrated for characterizations purposes

TABLE I
 TEST-CHIP PERFORMANCE SUMMARY

	Conventional SA	NSR-SA
Technology	45nm low-power CMOS	
Cell size	0.25 μ m ²	
Array configuration	256 x 256	
Capacity	64kb	
Area	12 μ m ²	19 μ m ² *
Power in reset	-	23 μ W
% of array power (at 100MHz)	2%	7%
Mean access-time	1.59ns	1.27ns
Max. access-time	2.46ns	1.67ns
Access-time sigma	401ps	103ps

* Includes testability features

only. Additionally, during the reset phase, each NSR-SA draws static power of 20 μ W while its inverters are at their trip-points, and, in total, this contributes 5% to the overall array power when the array is running at 100 MHz

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Low-power, high-density SRAMs are critical to technology scaling in a broad range of applications and devices. Their reliability, however, is threatened by extreme variability, and excessive margining to cell stability, sense-amplifier offset, and array timing is required. As a result, severe performance compromises must be incurred. To recover these, however, an offset compensating self-regenerating sense-amplifier is integrated into a 64-kb array of high-density 0.15 μ m² bit-cells in low-power 32 nm CMOS. By performing simple auto-zeroing to detect and correct its own offsets, the sense ampilfer achieves high-stability in the presence of variation. Further, the stable internal voltage references are exploited as a means to self-trigger regeneration without relying on an external strobe-path, thereby precluding the associated timing uncertainty. The ability to stably detect small-signal bit-line discharge implies that smaller read-currents can be Acoma-dated for a given performance requirement, and the bit-cells can thus be optimized for stability, facilitating increased density

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